

Critical Social Theory and the Politics of Muslim Subjectivity

Eleftheria Rosa Vasilaki

A dissertation submitted to the University of Bristol in accordance with the requirements for award of the degree of PhD in the Faculty of Social Sciences and Law.

School of Sociology, Politics and International Relations

September 2012

81242 words

Abstract

The thesis looks at the ways 'Islam' is constructed as a subject of analysis within critical social theory and as an effect of poststructuralist analytics. An important change in the accounts of 'Islam' has been taking place since the postmodern turn. This change is three-fold: methodologically, there is a considerable shift in the analytical categories deployed, from the modernist and largely materialist accounts of Islam to the more recent postmodern focus on subjectivities. Politically, there is a significant turn towards more positive accounts of the politicisation of religion as 'politically progressive' or even as radically Left (anti-hegemonic, anti-imperialist, anticolonialist and so on). Epistemologically, these changes sustain a more general claim for the provincialisation of secular social science and for the equal consideration of postsecular (religious) modalities of knowledge.

These accounts of Islam enable the emergence of a discourse of Muslim subjectivity with special focus on its oppression by the dominant ideology of secularism and its need of recognition as a legitimate, public cum political identity. The thesis engages primarily with the manifestations of this discourse and its significance for critical social theory, and secondly with the way it has shaped political sensibilities in relation to religious, in general, and Muslim subjectivities in particular. To do so, the thesis looks at the way the politics of Muslim subjectivity are debated within the rationale of the new 'reflexive' disciplines and fields, i.e. feminism, postcolonialism and multiculturalism, engages with the theoretical contradictions and political implications of such approaches and questions their tendency to see Muslim political subjectivity as 'critical', 'resisting' or 'progressive'.

To my parents, Christos and Panayiota, who taught me the importance of political struggles.

Acknowledgments

I have accumulated substantial debts in writing this thesis which would not have been possible without the support of many people. First and foremost I would like to thank my thesis supervisor, Professor Gregor McLennan, without whom I would have not learned to face the complexities of theoretical thinking, to stay with a question and reflect on its uncomfortable contradictions and multiple ramifications and to come to terms with the necessary shortcomings embedded in comprehension. There are perhaps no adequate words to express my gratitude for such precious gifts. Many students have the fortune to have caring and demanding supervisors, few, however, have the good luck to have a mentor exemplary of rigorous scholarship and an interlocutor fearless of bold questions who made this project a tremendous pleasure and a tremendous challenge.

I would also like to thank my second supervisor Professor Tariq Modood who offered me valuable insights and intriguing counterarguments to my views and positions.

I also wish to thank Professor Thomas Osborne for the enthusiastic encouragement he has given me and for his willingness to give his time so generously in numerous occasions to discuss aspects of this project.

There are intellectual debts and defining influences that run deep in one's scholarly development. Early in my career I had the fortune to meet Dr Nikos Rotzokos and Dr Eleni Andriakaina who introduced me to the fascinating world of conceptual work. Their unique regard to social reality, their intellectual generosity, distinctive sense of humanity and philosophy of life has marked me and still guides me in my own trajectory to knowledge.

I complete this work with a sense of gratitude also to friends and family members, whose constant support led me out of impasses and helped me going through my journey. I would like to thank first, some of my colleagues and friends whom I met in the University of Bristol and with whom I have shared discussions, disagreements, agreements, cups of coffee and glasses of wine. Filip Vostal, Laura Morosanu, Maria Balen, Thomas Hayes and above all Lorenzo Silvaggi have been central figures in my thinking and life in the PhD years, and I hope for many years to come too.

I would also like to thank my brother George Vassilakes for his never failing support to all matters and his faith in my project and choices in moments of great doubt; Christina Karayianni who has been the most reliable and affectionate friend one could ever hope for; Angeliki Kotoula, Mania Vasilaki and Zacca Vasilaki for being such a consistent presence and infinite source of power during the various stages of this project. Finally, I would like to thank my partner David Armstrong who endured my endless business, flow of deadlines and late nights on the computer with a smile.

Author's declaration

I declare that the work in this dissertation was carried out in accordance with the requirements of the University's Regulations and Code of Practice for Research Degree Programmes and that it has not been submitted for any other academic award. Except where indicated by specific reference in the text, the work is the candidate's own work. Work done in collaboration with, or with the assistance of, others, is indicated as such. Any views expressed in the dissertation are those of the author.

SIGNED:

DATE: 28/09/2012

Table of contents

Introduction: The Emergence of anti-Orientalism

1. The problem to be addressed	7
2. The theoretical stance and the discursive space of the thesis	15
3. The scope and limits of the thesis	21
4. The structure of the thesis	21

Chapter One: Islamic Feminism: Tensions, Paradoxes, Limits

1.1 Introduction: the case and the problematic	28
1.2 Islamic feminism as pragmatism: the contours of a compromise	33
1.3 Islamic feminism as radicalism: a new revolutionary paradigm?	43

Chapter Two: From Resistance to Docility: Feminism and the Dilemmatics of Islamic Agency

2.1 Introduction: religion as a category of political agency	55
2.2 From victimisation to resistance: conceptual shifts in the semantics of the veil	59
2.3 Feminism and its 'Others': postsecular feminism and the end of oppositional consciousness	66
2.4 The politics of piety and the docile female subject	72

Chapter Three: Towards a New Teleology: from Historicism to the Singularity of Cultures

3.1 Introduction: Eurocentrism as a problem	81
3.2 From postcolonialism to posthistoricism: history in the perspective of the subaltern	84
3.3 Radical historicism: poststructuralist analytics at cross roads or at a cul-de sac?	96

Chapter Four: Postcolonialism versus Islam/ism: Disentangling the Conundrum of a Contested Relationship

4.1 Introduction: Islam/ism in the perspective of subjugated knowldges	107
4.2 The historical grounds of the relationship between postcolonialism and Islam/ism	109
4.3 The political potential of postcolonial theory	114
4.4 Postcolonialism meets Islam/ism	118
4.5 The discourse of resistance and the contemporary Left academic and political culture	126

Chapter Five: Religious Multiculturalism and the Politics of Muslim Assertiveness

5.1. Introduction: Islam and multiculturalism	135
5.2 The politics of Muslim assertiveness and the logic of multiculturalism	136
5.3. Postsecular multiculturalism: the coming of age or the end of the road?	155

Chapter Six: Shaping Political Reasoning: Muslim Subjectivity and the Culturalisation of Politics

6.1 Introduction: Muslim subjectivity between competing political frameworks	165
6.2 Debating Islamophobia: from concept to discourse	167
6.3 Political assertion as ethical battle: oppression, offense and injury	173
6.4 Culturalism and its discontents	187

Conclusion: Towards a New Universalism?	196
--	-----

Bibliography	202
---------------------	-----

Introduction

Introduction: The Emergence of anti-Orientalism

1. The problem to be addressed
 - The history of Islam as an object of study
 - The political climate
 - The theoretical context
2. The theoretical stance and the discursive space of the thesis
 - Critical theory and immanent critique
 - The discursive space of the thesis
3. The scope and limits of the thesis
4. The structure of the thesis

1.1 The problem to be addressed

Islam has been the object of extraordinary interest across academic fields and political debates in recent years. Two intertwined phenomena can be probably identified as the main sources for sustaining this interest: the first is the resurrection and strong appeal of Islamist politics, that is the reinstatement of Islam as political ideology, as political identity or as political activism. This revivification of Islam is not only observable in the Muslim-majority countries where it has made a significant come-back. It is also present in the Western countries, in which lively discussions about Islam have been conducted over the past two decades with regards to its accommodation in the public sphere of Western democracies, and in relation to the claims of those who think that the very core of their (Islamic) identity has been misrecognised or even oppressed by the dominant Western secular cultures. Together with this social development – i.e. the revival of Islam as the primary instance of social existence - a parallel and interlinked intellectual development emerged, that is a renewed academic interest in Islam. This second cultural development, its ideological descent and theoretical preconditions, the specific understanding of Islam and the kind of Muslim subjectivity it enables, and the epistemological and political implications generated by such approaches constitute the object of research of the work in hand.

The thesis looks at the ways ‘Islam’ is constructed as a subject of analysis within critical social theory and as an effect of poststructuralist analytics. An important change in the accounts of ‘Islam’, has been taking place since the postmodern turn. This change is three-fold: methodologically, there is a considerable shift in the analytical categories deployed, from the modernist and largely materialist accounts of Islam, to the more recent postmodern focus on subjectivities. Politically, there is a significant turn towards more positive accounts of the

politicisation of religion as ‘politically progressive’ or even as radically Left (anti-hegemonic, anti-imperialist, anticolonialist and so on). Epistemologically, these changes sustain a more general claim for the provincialisation of secular social science and for the equal consideration of postsecular (religious) modalities of knowledge. The thesis looks at the way the rise of political Muslim subjectivity has been conceived within the rationale of the new ‘reflexive’ disciplines and fields, i.e. postmodern and postsecular feminism, postcolonialism and multiculturalism, engages with the theoretical contradictions and political implications of such approaches and questions their tendency to see Muslim political subjectivity as ‘critical’, ‘resisting’ or ‘progressive’. Oscillating between Islam as a system of belief and Islamism as an ideology which produces and politicises the kind of public Muslim identity which has been at the epicentre of main controversies of our times, these discourses are often a mix of both elements, of religious doctrine and political commitment, which – intentionally or incidentally – become inseparable. The term ‘Islam/ism’ to which I often have recourse in this thesis aims to acknowledge the merging of religious doctrine and political ideology which occurs in articulations of Islam in recent years, and to account for the cluster of theoretical cum political positions which represent Islam/ism as a new critical or resisting force against Western hegemony, neo-colonialism, neo-imperialism, and the power relations they entail.

The focus of the thesis, as well as its unity, is theoretical and thematic: it focuses on those notable developments in critical social theory (poststructuralist/postmodern turn) which enabled the configuration of discourses which see Islam, its recent significant revival, as well as the emergence of Muslim subjectivity, not just as a social phenomenon to be explained but as the repository of an ethical and political shift that has something to say beyond its own natural audience (the Muslims) and beyond its natural realm (the one of religious belief). In this perspective, Islam is perceived as a narrative which can contribute to the role of social theory and can also transform the understanding of politics, the meaning of core values, such as equality, agency and emancipation, or the way we make sense of the history of modernity or the tradition of Enlightenment. As such the object of enquiry is not Islam *per se* but specific core problems in social theory, especially their reconfiguration after the poststructuralist/postmodern turn, such as the nature of knowledge or of historical change, the processes of subjectivation, the purpose of critical social theory, the meaning of political agency, and the possibility (and desirability) of emancipation. Islam and Muslim subjectivity are used as a vehicle for this exploration.

The history of Islam as an object of study

The interest in Islam has a long history in the realm of scholarly preoccupations: Islam, as an object of investigation, as Edward Said's (2003 [1978]) influential work on Orientalism has demonstrated, is an old theme, one that has been central in the very possibility of articulation of the political entity 'Europe', and the main organising category in opposition to which the 'West' is constructed. Said's seminal work emerged in the context of established approaches to Islam and effectively challenged their monopoly over the interpretation of Islam. These approaches fall broadly under two categories, namely a philological and a sociological one, which can be distinguished by their methodologies and the kind of explanations they offer about the 'difference' of Islam. The textual and philological approach – the one that is known as 'Orientalism' – is coeval with both the development of scientific disciplines in Europe and the colonialist expansion. It derives from the assumption that 'Islam' can be used as a category of explanation for the history of societies whose inhabitants are Muslims, from an increasing interest of what Muslims believe and what they have done in history, but also from changing ideas in Europe about religion and history. As is the case with every discipline, when this philological approach emerged as a separate field, it was given shape by certain ideas which were prominent at the time, i.e. ideas about cultural history, the nature and development of religions and ideas about the relationship between languages. The sociological approach, on the other hand, is defined in terms drawn from social sciences and its categories of analysis derive from the concept of 'modernization', such as the extension of bureaucratic authority over society, the expansion of urban control in the countryside, the commercialisation of agriculture, the beginnings of large-scale industry, the emergence within the cities of social classes similar to the ones in western industrial societies, or the formation of an elite educated in a specific way. This sociological take on Islam is mainly a postwar approach which developed in the centres of 'area studies' from the 1950s onwards and it is often thought as a form of contemporary 'Orientalism'.

Said's *Orientalism* takes issue with both these approaches. A short summary of Said's view and analysis of 'Orientalism' cannot naturally do justice to the calibre of his undertaking, nonetheless it is necessary here, as the sum total of works and positions examined by this thesis falls under the paradigm of 'anti-Orientalism' which Said's work inspired. Said studied 'Orientalism' an intellectual phenomenon which he defined in three different senses: a. as an academic discipline, i.e. 'the study of the Orient' meant as a set of institutions, disciplines and activities usually

confined to Western universities which have been concerned with the study of Oriental societies and cultures; b. as a style of thought based on the ontological and epistemological distinction between the 'Orient' and the 'Occident'; and c. as a corporate institution primarily concerned with the Orient with the purpose of describing as well as controlling it. Said had argued that Orientalism as a discourse arose initially in Christianity as part of the missionary interest in the control of the Muslim Other by knowledge. What Said had found both surprising and outrageous is that this discourse has been particularly resistant to change despite its antiquity and that it was a self-perpetuating closed system with little substantial relationship with the reality it purported to be describing, and a mode of engagement which had ultimately less to do with the Orient and more with the West itself. Said's study was concerned with the analysis – deconstruction and demystification to be more precise – of this discourse, i.e. 'Orientalism', which is the outcome produced by the interplay between legitimate institutions of knowledge, political institutions, academic modes of thought, aesthetic approaches and popular mentalities. In this perspective of deconstruction, the basis of what the West thinks about the 'Orient' lies in the reality of power, in the reality of domination, or in the reality of cultural imperialism which perpetuates the distinction between 'them' and 'us', between the Western Self and the Oriental Other. As a result the world is divided between Occident and Orient and typologies are created within which antithetical characteristics can be distributed: the decisive and energetic Westerner versus the passive and idle Oriental; the rational versus the superstitious; the civilised versus the barbaric; the masculine versus the feminine. By deconstructing the ostensible 'objectivity' or 'neutrality' of such academic methods, Said's work marked the erosion of belief in the disinterested representation of the Muslim Other.

What makes Said's project so distinctive though is not only the application of social theory for the explanation of history and culture - the sociological approach to Islam mentioned above has been relying on theoretical models and insights since its inception. The innovative move of Said's work is the application of Foucault's insights about the inextricable relationship between power and knowledge to the examination of the Western production of the cultural order outside the West, namely the cultural order of the Orient. As it is often the case with influential and controversial works such as Said's, the strength of criticism against *Orientalism* is comparable to its enthusiastic reception. Few books in the recent intellectual history of the West had such a tremendous impact in the re-organisation of knowledge as Said's *Orientalism* and this despite the fierce critique that

followed the publication of the book.¹ Its impact can be felt, first, in the strong devaluation and virtual disappearance of the entire field of 'Orientalism' - as the discipline which studied Islam based on methods elaborated by philologists - but also as a subject that can be unproblematically studied through the lenses of (Western) social sciences; and, second, in the creation of new academic fields of expertise, such as postcolonialism which emerges largely as an effect of Said's analysis. But also, Said's work enabled the emergence of a new paradigm in the approach of Islam, a kind of new 'orthodoxy', namely 'anti-Orientalism'. The political stance of this new paradigm - i.e. the critique of the relationship between power, knowledge and culture in the production of what counts as 'truth' for the Muslim Other, as well as the deconstruction of the negative stereotyping of Islam in academic and popular culture - and its epistemological emphasis on methods inspired by the postmodern turn are central to the particular recovery of the study of Islam as a matter of subjectivity.

The political climate

Except the intellectual history of the study of Islam and the significance of anti-Orientalism as a paradigm, what also underlies the body of work addressed by the thesis is the political climate in which such academic debates are conducted. This political climate has a particular temporality as well as geography: the post 09/11 attacks and their impact in reconfiguring the international relations agenda and domestic policies in the US and Europe. The increasing eminence of 'terrorism' as a signifier, the declaration of 'war on terror', the human rights abuse scandals in Abu Ghraib and Guantanamo Bay, the signing of the Patriot Act and the creeping effect of the ideology of securitisation on civil liberties are the background against which the discourse of Muslim subjectivity established itself as a concrete, counter-hegemonic alternative to xenophobic discourses - albeit by instituting its own orthodoxy in the field of social critical theory. The

¹ As expected a variety of criticisms have been addressed against Said's argument. To mention but a few, critics focused on the loose, or even inconsistent, use and conceptualisation of the term 'Orientalism' which becomes a substitute of imperialism, racism, positivism, evolutionism, stereotyping and so on and on Said's recurrent recourse to tautologies and metaphors that function as substitutes for each other (Mussallam 1979; Clifford 1980; Winder 1981). But also on his retrospective attitude towards history which allows for the conceptualisation of 'Orientalism' as an over-historical enterprise, or an 'expressive totality', an almost metaphysical all-pervasive power transcending history and genres of expression (Halliday 1993); and on the anticipation of 'Orientalism' as the key factor which prepared for imperialism (Mussallam 1979). Methodological choices and delimitations as well as generalizations have been naturally the target of 'Orientalist' scholars (Beckingham 1980; Dawn 1979; Irwin 2006; Kerr 1990) who felt that they have been 'Orientalised' themselves (Winder 1981). More recently others, albeit recognising the importance of Said's paradigm, argued that the hypothesis of the Orient versus Occident divide and their independent cultural regimes have become redundant in the age of globalisation (Turner 1994; Ahmed and Donnan 1994).

emergence of a critical discourse which sees Islam as enabling, resisting, liberating, progressive or on the Left, must be understood partially as a reaction to this climate of rampant demonisation of Muslims. Legitimate and necessary as it may be to counter these phobic manifestations in the political arena, however, the effects of such moves are ridden with ambiguity, if not contradiction. One of the most acute political dilemmas of our modern times which Islam/ism brings to the fore is what to do - from a theoretically critical or politically Left perspective - with conservative, often regressive movements whose agenda includes progressive ends. For example, as we shall see in the thesis, anti-imperialism comes often with the price of gender inequality, or with the re-establishment of traditional forms of (arbitrary) authority rather than the generation of radical democratic transformation. But also, by situating itself at the opposite end of the spectrum of Orientalism, the discourse of Islam as resistance or critique becomes part of a dominant polarisation (e.g. Islam as terror vs. Islam as resistance). It becomes a constitutive part of the process of 'othering' of Muslims and their alleged anti-Westernism - a dangerous development for the Right, an admirable stance for the Left - which, in the perspective of such polarization, appears as inescapable.

The theoretical context

The political and theoretical topography of the discourse of Muslim subjectivity is also conditioned by the conceptual and more generally intellectual context within which it arises. The conceptual roots of this discourse, despite their stated anti-Westernism, are located within the intellectual history of the West and in the potential of reflexivity embedded in the nature of modern knowledge. The emergence of the analytical category of difference is perhaps the most notable categorical shift in the social and human sciences and underpins the very possibility for the articulation of discourse of Muslim subjectivity. What I mean to emphasise by the reference to the postmodern/poststructuralist turn is the importance of historicising the context of production of the new discourse of Muslim subjectivity. The point is not to prove that each of the authors engaged by the thesis meticulously follows the poststructuralist or postmodern theoretical norms, but that these positions enable the articulation of a field and the constitution of a discourse which is aligned with the kind of intellectual concerns brought about by the postmodern/poststructuralist turn. The emphasis on the analytical category of difference, the shift to suppressed knowledges, the prominence of subjective experience, the demise of realist epistemologies and materialist explanations, the opening to alternative systems of thought and

knowledge such as religions and traditions, constitute the intellectual climate within which the new critical discourses about Islam, i.e. the discourse about Muslim subjectivity, emerges. From the point of view of history of ideas, the trajectory of the study of Islam – i.e. the different modes of engagement, that is philological, sociological, postmodern, and their rise and fall within academia – tells the story of the intellectual shifts that marked the historical time of production of these specific approaches. It also tells the story of the way Islam is continuously reconstituted in relation to the assumptions that each approach makes in relation to core breakthroughs in epistemological thinking (essentialism, materialism, subjectivity).

Therefore, the analysis of the recent subjectivity-driven approach of Islam is particularly instructive of the way postmodernism and the rise of standpoint epistemologies defined the theoretical issues and political questions of our times: ‘Western’ feminism, its unitary subject and the possibility to articulate a culturally sensitive approach open to religion and to allegiances that sit uncomfortably with the established tenets of feminism, patriarchy most notably; the critique of Eurocentrism and its anthropocentric view of modern history, the ideals of progress and the linear, stagist development of history; citizenship, the managing of difference and the re-signification of the political agency as an ethical battle as well as the place and meaning of secularism and religion in the era of globalised late capitalism. The possibility of thinking about Islam outside the structural categories of ‘Western’ human and social science and the articulation of the critique of Western categories of knowledge as confluent to the possibility of enabling a new epistemic discourse and rationale, inspired by religion in general and by the tradition of Islam in particular, are the effects of an intellectual climate in which difference is analytically and politically prioritised.

The same goes with the emphasis on authenticity of self-representation and the empowerment of the Muslim subject so as to speak about herself. The stress on subjectivity is also an effect of the intellectual condition enabled by the postmodern turn. Subjectivity refers to the subject and his or her perspective, feelings, beliefs and desires and has been an increasingly important concept for academic research since the 1970s. The idea of subjectivity had a catalytic effect in changing the terms of the debate across social sciences and humanities which goes beyond disciplinary boundaries: it has become an established category of social, cultural, psychological, historical and political analysis, along with being analysed as a site of social change and as a means of political

intervention. Subjectivity with its focus on experiences, affects, sensibilities and modes of knowing and reasoning that are thought as not universal or universalizable, has become one of the most authoritative conceptual loci of anti-Eurocentric critique and its epistemological premise of separation of subject and object in social research.

Another aspect that must be taken into account in order to contextualise the conceptual and intellectual background against which the politics of Muslim subjectivity emerge is the growing eminence of a new 'post' term, namely postsecularism. In the last decade the debate about Otherness seems to have marked a categorical shift, since arguments are not evolving around identity in general or ethnicity in particular, but around religion. It is important to note that the kind of postsecularism I refer to here belongs to the realm of social theory and philosophical possibility and not to the one of sociological reality. In the debates I engage with postsecularism can be seen more as a kind of 'reading strategy' analogous to postcolonialism or postmodernism, rather than as an indicator of social realities, like in the germane, yet different in focus, debates about the so-called breakdown of the secularisation thesis. This kind of postsecularism is often used as a metaphor for ideas and ideologies arguing that Western secularism may have come to an end and it has been increasingly prominent in academic debates. The meaning of religious belief in processes of subjectivation, and in particular the recent alignment of political agency with religious subjectivity, is one of the key themes within the postsecular perspective. Acclaimed as a new force in critical theory, postsecularism appears to have taken as its main opponent not only secularism as an ideology advocating the formal separation between public and private, or secular epistemology advocating the separation between faith and reason, but also the signature institution of Western modernity, the secular State. Secularism in these accounts is understood not only as the doctrinal separation of Church from State but also as the reconfiguring of religion itself in a way that becomes compatible with modern sensibilities and modern governmentality. Postsecularism in that sense aims to account for a specific cluster of sensibilities that are believed suppressed by the dominant secular ideology (which is more often than not collapsed into the ideology of the modern State), and must be understood partly as an attack on what are thought as self-privileging versions of Western modernity and of the moral superiority it assumes against the illiberal cultural practices of the non-West.

1.2 The theoretical stance and the discursive space of the thesis

In many ways this thesis can be seen as an internal dialogue about the role, purpose and nature of critical social theory. The body of works and positions addressed here share the same political commitment in the subversion of the current power relations, as well as the same theoretical interest in questioning the existing regimes of truths and in deconstructing their assumed naturalness or self-evidence. There is remarkable strength in the arguments expressed under the umbrella of ‘posts’ and a kind of political legitimacy that cannot be denied. However, the thesis argues that the subversion of relations of dominations targeted by the body of anti-Orientalist critique addressed here is ultimately hindered by the embedded postsecular orientation of its epistemology and its particular philosophy of history, as well as by the way subaltern subjectivities are reduced to their religious beliefs. What I will try to articulate in the chapters that follow is a sympathetic, albeit sceptical, critique of someone who shares the anti-hegemonic politics, critical thrust and intellectual challenge of anti-Eurocentrism and anti-Orientalism as expressed by the strands of postmodern feminism, postcolonialism or multiculturalism examined by the thesis, but who does not agree on the epistemological means.

Critical social theory and immanent critique

Critical social theory, and more precisely its most essential element, i.e. critique, has been the object of intense debate over the past few years, especially in relation to the rejection of its ‘necessary secularism’ and its assumed ‘negativity’ and in favour of its opening to religious sensibilities and to the possibility of ‘positive critique’ (e.g. Braidotti 2008; Asad et al. 2009; Blencowe 2012). Naturally, the meaning of areas of engagement like ‘critical social theory’ is the object of ever-open contestation and interpretation. Nevertheless we can perhaps identify two routes in which critical social theory has developed: a strand which is firmly rooted in the tradition of Western Marxism from which critical theory originally emanates, and a strand which developed in opposition to Marxism and its fundamental aims and methods (especially against the long-standing relationship between critical theory and Marxist political economy) which is situated within the postmodern tradition. The theoretical stance I adopt here sympathises with the Marxist stance, broadly construed as a commitment to universal values such as equality and autonomy, an endorsement of a realist epistemology, a need to recover some form of the concept of ideology if critique hopes to remain critical against the entire spectrum of social inequalities and injustices, and, finally, a belief in the infinite possibility of better knowledge. Hence, my

engagement with the postmodern strand of critical social theory which takes as its object the meaning and political purpose of the discourse of Muslim subjectivity needs to be seen also as a constructive exchange about the development of critical social theory *per se*. I would like to briefly mention three main characteristics of the kind of critical social theory which is assumed as a framework here, based on Harvey's (1990: 3-4) preliminary discussion on the practice of critical theory in a social scientific context, in order to theoretically anchor the arguments made in the following chapters. First, critical theory is reflexive and self-consciously historical in its orientations. That means that its truths are neither unconditioned, universal laws nor idealist presuppositions. On the contrary critical theory is self-reflexive and seeks to understand the social and material processes by which theory is formed. Most importantly critical theory aims to preserve the autonomy of theoretical reflection and strives to keep a clear distance from the practical, historical processes in which it is entangled. It also means that society and our knowledge of it are historically produced, but also that the subjective reproduction of the world is ultimately grounded in material need and the processes of social reproduction. Second, critical social theory is epistemologically anti-irrationalist and committed to clarity and reason in a way that makes subjectivism and mysticism questionable and suspect rather than welcome. Third, critical social theory maintains the possibility of an epistemologically and ontologically open world. That involves the idea of an 'unfinished quality', an openness to the world which would always stand outside of and remain opposed to the rationalising and totalitarian tendencies inherent in capitalist culture.

It must be obvious now that according to the theoretical tradition described above, critical social theory assumes an acknowledged political stance. In this I follow Fraser (1985: 1997) who, referencing Marx's 1843 initial definition of critical theory as '*the self-clarification of the struggles and wishes of the age*', points out that the appeal of this phrase lies in its straightforward political character: 'It makes no claim to any special epistemological status but, rather, supposes that with respect to justification there is no philosophically interesting difference between a critical theory of society and an uncritical one. But there is, according to this definition, an important political difference'. Naturally, one can question the extent to which the philosophical and the political can be separated as starkly as Fraser seems to assume, nonetheless this definition makes obvious the inherent and unambiguous politicality of critical social theory. It goes without saying that for critical theory to be 'critical' it must be 'for' something and 'against' something else, hence critical

social theory is not and cannot be neutral. It is associated with a broader project and the normative assumptions it entails. Following Arnason (1989) we can perhaps identify this project as creating an autonomous democratic society. Arnason points to capitalism as a major source of heteronomy, but one could add here patriarchy, racism, and other ideologies of inequality and exclusion - such as the ambiguous case of religion examined by this thesis - because for the creation of a genuinely autonomous, democratic society, critical social theory must task itself with the radical questioning of all forms of heteronomy.

The thesis enters these debates about the nature and the role of critical social theory via the exploration of the politics of Muslim subjectivity by practising the method of immanent critique. Immanent critique - the central mode of critical theoretical analysis and the corollary of the ontological openness of critical theory - aims to contextualise not only the object of its investigation, but also the ideological basis of that object. By detecting societal contradictions it aims to demonstrate that both the object and the category to which it belongs are products of a historical process. To do so, immanent critique questions social reality from its own standpoint, but at the same time criticises the standpoint from the perspective of its historical context and it seeks, by revealing the contradictions of claim and context, to transform legitimations into emancipatory weapons (Antonio 1989: 338). Harvey (1990: 5) explains that by standing over and against orthodoxy and its view of the world, critical theory begins as a formal 'negativity' which selects some tradition, ideological premise, or institutionalised orthodoxy for analysis. Immanent critique tests the postulates of orthodoxy by the latter's own standards of proof and adequacy and provisionally accepts the methodological presuppositions, substantive premises and truth-claims of orthodoxy as its own. Once the orthodoxy's premises and assertions are identified and certain strategic contradictions located, these contradictions are developed according to their own logic, and during this process of internal expansion the proclamations of orthodoxy collapse. Following the methodological process described above, the thesis engages with the discourse of Muslim subjectivity, as articulated within the tradition of anti-Orientalism, and debated within the disciplines and fields that have been the mostly responsive to the postmodern theoretical and political sensitivities. This particular understanding of Islam and its social, sociological and political significance as well as its emphasis on subaltern subjectivity, self-representation, affects and subjugated modes of knowledge has acquired - no doubt because of the political weight of questions of colonialism, imperialism and emancipation - an intellectual authority which often

goes unchallenged. The thesis investigates the logic and theoretical cogency of such positions, but also aims to assess to what extent they can fulfil the progressive and emancipatory political goals of critical social theory.

The discursive space of the thesis

Obviously questions about power and knowledge and their relationship are central to a project which takes critical social theory as its object. Bringing culture into this relationship, however, is of crucial importance here. By examining the nexus between knowledge, power *and* culture, I am aiming to look at the ways the interplay between these three registers enables a new discourse about Muslim subjectivity. The meaning of culture has been defined by the relationship of power and knowledge and this is particularly obvious when one enters the debates about Islam: a series of hierarchical binaries, like the backwardness of the non-Western societies assumed to be grounded in their tradition or the supposedly timeless or unchanging nature of their cultures as opposed to the rapid change of Western societies, were founded on historical - and to a large extent colonialist - definitions of culture. But 'culture' is of particular relevance here also because it relates to the 'cultural turn', itself a product of the postmodern theoretical focus on difference, and the shift from economy or class and even gender to a certain extent, to cultural identity, mostly understood as ethnicity or religion. The very term 'culture' - as opposed to the term 'society' - denotes the shift from the monopoly of social science as the utterly legitimate way of explaining the social world to the (re)turn to antagonistic ways of knowing, mainly emanating from tradition or religion.

Western science, and together with it Western social theory – so the line of argument of anti-Eurocentric critique goes – has emerged as the authoritative locus of knowledge about both modernity and tradition. It also produced hierarchies of knowledge (science over religion), hierarchies of culture (the Western over the Oriental) or of historical eras (civilisation over 'barbarity' or 'backwardness) and in that sense, it also produced inequalities. Partly because of the postmodern turn, partly because of a more generalised cultural phenomenon of disenchantment with modernity, and partly because of the deconstruction of Western colonial power in the second half of the twentieth century, the recent years experienced a significant realignment of positions in the relationship between power, knowledge and culture. One important change to

which our topic here (the emergence of a new discourse about Muslim subjectivity) unquestionably relates to is the radical questioning of scientific-based knowledge, the redefinition of what constitutes or counts as knowledge and the way this impacts on current questions of social relations. More specifically, scientific knowledge, and as a result social science, has faced important challenges from the postmodern philosophical tradition which enabled the intellectual conditions for other ways of knowing to contest the authority and legitimacy of 'Western' science by relating this knowledge with the history and politics of colonialism. This perspective relies on the well-known Foucault's insights that science is itself a social construction deeply embedded in those power relations that helps itself to create and maintain. The deconstruction of the authority of science - and in our case social science - is what allows and underlies the renewed attention of critical social theory to critiques and challenges coming from religion, and more specifically Islam, and from local cultures. The turn to tradition and the constantly shifting constellations of new hybrid identities which desire to fit traditional allegiances to modern lifestyles are exemplary instances of the way the battle for authority between knowledges and subjectivities is conducted. This is particularly true in the case of Islam whose challenge to Western science in the name of Islamic authenticity is thought as an act of resisting and of overcoming the colonial legacy and the neocolonial hegemony. As domains of knowledge undergo reorganization, a key underlying aim of the thesis is to understand how religion attempts to negotiate its place in the new arrangements of power-knowledge relations within the conditions enabled by the postmodern turn. And in this perspective to look at how a specific body of knowledge - that is Islam - is represented by intellectuals located mostly within Western academic institutions, how these representations are used to create new meanings and if, how, and with what purpose these representations disrupt the dominant-subordinated relationship, and in what kind of political antagonisms they get entangled.

With this in mind, the thesis develops within a critical and meta-theoretical discursive space which seeks to formulate questions from a different perspective, one that escapes the dilemmatics in which we are compelled by the polarisation of the recent debates about Islam. As such the thesis is not so much concerned about picking the 'right' side, but seeks to understand the theoretical significance and political meaning of the opposition between 'Orientalism' and 'anti-Orientalism', or between 'Islamophobia' and 'Islamophilia' and to historicise the process through which Muslim political subjectivity and more broadly religious subjectivity, as one specific site of

knowledge and experience, reconfigures the content of concepts such as agency, choice, emancipation, autonomy, or equality. In this perspective, the thesis examines the implications of analysing and understanding Muslim political subjectivity, or Islam/ism within the theoretical framework of 'anti-Eurocentrism'. It asks to what extent any critical consideration of Muslim political subjectivity has been compromised by the question of Eurocentrism and by relativist epistemologies which argue that critical social theory does not even have the right categories to understand the challenge posed by religion in general, and Islam in particular. It goes without saying that looking at Muslim subjectivity as a theoretical problem and reflecting on its political ramifications does not mean denying that anti-Muslim discrimination and indeed 'Islamophobia' is a very serious political and social problem, or to reject the demands for some form of accommodation of religious subjectivity and difference out of hand. Nonetheless, it involves asking to what extent the need to critique Western stereotyping may foreclose other possibilities of critique, such as the critique of gender inequalities, or the political dissent against orthodoxies, even when these orthodoxies emerge in the name of the marginalised and the excluded. It also involves asking whether these conceptualizations which favour the religious subjectivity silence questions about modes of sociality that are not religious, questions about class and social status, about gender and modes of traditional authority – of men over women, of the old over the young, of the exploiters over the exploited – which, by way of emphasising religion, are left unexplored. And, lastly, it involves evaluating whether the opening to religiosity and spirituality comes with the closure of sociological categories of analysis, and whether the 'politics of piety' or the 'politics of Muslim assertiveness' come with the price of emptying the subversive content of progressive politics itself.

Therefore, the intellectual and cultural developments which enabled the emergence of the 'empowering' discourses of Islam are not something to be celebrated or endorsed *a priori* despite their political legitimacy, but a phenomenon to be construed, especially as the 'anti-Orientalist' representations of Islam, despite their anti-essentialist aspirations, are often the mirror-image of the Orientalist ones. The same critical attitude and rigorous examination of arguments must be applied and that means that the political weight associated with the phenomena of colonialism or imperialism should be used as tools of contextualisation or historicization and not as hindrances to thorough questioning. If critical social theory wishes to maintain its critical thrust, then all

orthodoxies, even the ones rooted in anti-hegemonic politics, must be open for examination. This is why, in some ways, the project in hand begins where anti-Orientalism concludes.

1.3 The scope and the limits of the thesis

As mentioned above, the thesis tasks itself with the examination of central problems in critical social theory and their redeployment after the poststructuralist turn via the exploration of recent debates about Muslim political subjectivity. In this perspective, the interesting work of Muslim intellectuals who are working within the framework of their religious faith and debate for its interpretation or reform on the basis of theological arguments (e.g. Al-Azmeh 1993; An-Na'im 2008; Arkoun 2007; El Fadl 2001; Esack 1997; Filali-Ansary 2003; Noor 2002; Rahman 2000; Ramadan 2003, 2004a, 2004b, 2009; Safi 2003; Soroush 2000), or the history of Islam qua civilisation, with its distinct governance and legal system and its own cultural mentalities (e.g. Hodgson 1974), are out of the scope of this thesis. The same goes with debates about the correct interpretation of Islamic founding sources; the legitimacy of modernist, reformist, conservative or fundamentalist approaches of Islam; the range of reactions enabled by the encounter of Islam with Western modernity; the quandaries in relation to the modernisation of Islam or the Islamicisation of modernity and the attempts to disentangle the nexus of tradition and modernity within the specific location of the Orient; the constitution of the Islamic intellectual field and the role of Muslim intellectuals (Abaza 2002; Anderson 1979; Benzine 2004; Boroujerdi 1996; Burgat 2005; Cooper 2000; Eickelman Anderson 1999; Esposito 1999; Halliday 2003; Halpern 1963; Hourani 1983 [1962], 2001 [1991]; Kepel 2002, 2004; Khosrokhavar 2004; Lapidus 1997; Laroui 1976; Lerner 1958; Mandaville 2001; Rodinson 2007 [1973]; Roy 1994, 1999, 2002; Sharabi 1970; Turner 1974b, 1978, 1994; Zeghal, 2008). These topics have received great attention and have been the object of systematic work by the both Muslim and Western scholars, however, despite their importance, they are peripheral to the focal concerns of the thesis and they are touched upon, if at all, only in a tangential manner by the work in hand.

1.4 The structure of the thesis

The thesis is composed of six chapters which develop around three areas of engagement, i.e. feminism, postcolonialism and multiculturalism. These particular fields were selected because they have been amongst the most responsive to the general turn of critical scholarship to

questions of reflexivity and Otherness and significantly influenced by the issues raised after the postmodern turn, as mentioned above. Feminism is, by its inception, an area of scholarly engagement which has been particularly preoccupied with the question of the Other and with the way social and political theory conceptualise those subjects – women mainly, but not only – which are excluded by the narratives of history, politics and legitimised (academic) knowledges. As such the question of subjectivity - and consequently political agency – is central in feminist theory, especially since the retreat of ideology critique and the shift of debates towards Foucauldian and poststructuralist paradigms. In recent years, the debates about the status of historical and cultural specificity in feminist accounts of the subject and the opening of feminism to new understandings of the constitution of feminine self and feminist consciousness have shifted towards a new kind of Other, the ‘religious’ Other. The constitution of Muslim subjectivity has received great attention, as attested for example, by the rise of a specialised subfield, i.e. Islamic feminism. As such, feminism constitutes one of the main components of the debate about subjectivation in general, and one of the main avenues of debates about the nature of Muslim subjectivity in particular.

If feminism is a privileged theoretical terrain to explore questions related to the constitution of the female and non-Western self, postcolonialism is the field where the Muslim subject is discussed by reference to claims for the decolonization of history and subjugated knowledges and for the emergence of anti-Eurocentric epistemologies. Postcolonialism is the theoretical terrain which has established the link between the critique of reason and progress and the question of the ‘non-West’ on the one hand, and the poststructuralist insights exposing the inextricable relationship between knowledge/science and hegemony/power on the other. Religious subjectivity in general and Muslim political agency in particular have been increasingly analysed in relation to questions of political resistance to Western hegemony and the possibility of articulation of decentralised, non-Eurocentric ways of producing knowledge about the world within the field of postcolonialism. With this in mind, an engagement with postcolonial theory emerges as the most appropriate vehicle for this venture.

Last but not least, multiculturalism is one of the fields of theoretical and political analysis that have been mostly associated with the discourse of Muslim subjectivity. Significant political controversies of our times have been tied up with Islamic political agency and the challenges it

poses to the way the Western public spheres are structured, whereas the relationship between Islam and politics has become a metonymy for what is often thought as the most important crisis of secularism in the West. These political controversies, as well as the specific demands articulated by the Muslim communities and the response to them by both sides of the political spectrum, have been, more often than not, expressed and explained by reference to multiculturalism. Like feminism and postcolonialism, multiculturalism challenges Western secularism on a philosophical, epistemological level, but also on the level of applied political choices and decisions, of which the accommodation and politics of Muslim communities in Europe is a prime example.

Hence, the choice of these three areas of focus - based on their preoccupation with questions of reflexivity and Otherness but also on their increasing interest with the emerging Muslim subjectivity - is also reflected on the chapter sequence. The starting point for this investigation is the question of the subject itself: therefore, the thesis starts with the way the Muslim subject is imagined and contested within contemporary debates in critical social theory. This is addressed via an engagement with postmodern/poststructuralist feminist literature for the reasons explained above. The specific Muslim subject emerging from the examination of this field gives rise to two kinds of further inquiry: first, the question of philosophy of history and epistemology of social science that underpins Muslim subjectivity, as well as the implications that these philosophies and epistemologies have for the practice of critical social theory itself; and second, the political effects of this particular conceptualisation of the Muslim subject. The first question is addressed via an examination of postcolonial theory and in particular by focusing on the literature which perceives Islam and Muslim subjectivity as an exemplary instance of non-Eurocentric, non-secular mode of knowledge. The second question is addressed via an investigation of the field of multiculturalism, and more precisely with the analysis of the emergence of a religious-oriented theory of multiculturalism and the kind of political sensibilities and forms of political reasoning it enables.

Following this logic, the thesis is structured around six chapters. More precisely, chapters one and two focus on the way recent discussions about Muslim subjectivity attempt to reconfigure the relationship between feminism and religion. The first chapter engages with the field of Islamic feminism and its contribution to the discussion of Muslim Other by way of focusing on the uneasy relationship between gender and religion in feminist theory. It explores the problems,

paradoxes and challenges that the Islamic understanding of subjectivity poses to secular feminism as a political position and theoretical project. By dividing the field between pragmatist and radical positions, the chapter examines those authors who seek to reconcile Islam as a system of belief with feminism, as a movement advocating the subversion of the current patriarchal distribution of power between sexes. The chapter looks at the insights such positions can offer to feminism, especially in relation to the reception of abstract, universal political projects within the existing cultural experiences and material constraints under which women think and act, while it asks to what extent, feminism, whose conceptual pillars oppose the translation of biological difference to social difference, can develop as an Islamic offshoot without compromising its basic premises.

Continuing this discussion, chapter two focuses on how ideas about resistance, empowerment and political subjectivity or agency have been reconceptualised based on women's 'Islamic' or 'nonsecular' experience, by looking at the shift of discursive frameworks in which women's political subjectivity is debated, i.e. the shifts from Orientalism to anti-Orientalism, from victimisation to resistance, or from submission to empowerment. It focuses, firstly, on the re-signification of veiling, as the most emblematic symbol of Islamic religiosity. Secondly, it looks at the way the conceptualisation of religiosity as agentic, enabling and nonsecular leads to further depreciation of the grand narratives of emancipation – or even negative dialectics – and gives rise to postsecularism as the new politics of the Left and the 'end of oppositional consciousness'. Finally, the chapter addresses the implications stemming from the conceptualisation of agency in Islamic terms and the radical dissociation of humanist-cum-secular tradition from the social politics of equality, via an emphasis on Saba Mahmood's ethnography of women's piety movement in Egypt.

Chapters three and four engage with the field of postcolonialism and some of its main theoretical preoccupations, such as the Eurocentricity of knowledge and of the way academic disciplines are organised, the relationship between modernity and its modes of subjectivation, and the legacies of colonialism and postcoloniality. These issues are discussed via a focus on understandings which see Islam and Muslim subjectivity as an example of non-modern, non-Eurocentric, non-secular instance of politicality and mode of knowledge. Chapter three engages with the philosophies of history undergirding the poststructuralist representation of the Muslim political subject, since the

poststructuralist, anti-foundationalist and anti-progressist variant of anti-Eurocentric critique is the one that underlies the positions addressed by the thesis. The chapter proceeds, firstly, by examining the most elaborate and influential theoretical effort to expose the Eurocentric bias of 'history' itself, i.e. the project of *Provincializing Europe* as articulated by Dipesh Chakrabarty. By doing so, it locates the structural overlaps and tensions between the postcolonial philosophy of history and the radical – poststructuralist – historicism represented by Talal Asad, whose 'anthropology of the secular' is pivotal in the development of religious pietism and revivalism as a site of critique, or as a locus of agency.

Chapter four challenges the established assumptions that put postcolonialism and Islam/ism in an explanatory relationship by looking at their divergent theoretical and political agendas and at the contrasting worldviews conveyed by these two projects. The chapter aims to make the antinomy between the two terms tangible but also to suggest an explanation about the cultural, political and intellectual conditions which allow for the establishment of the relationship between them. It starts by questioning both the historical and theoretical grounds which sustain the explanatory relationship between postcolonialism and Islam/ism. Subsequently, it moves on to discuss in detail the most significant effort to draw a theoretical, postcolonial project based on Islam/ism, i.e. Bobby Sayyid's *A Fundamental Fear*, whilst also canvassing other significant works which attempt to bring together postcolonialism and Islam/ism by reference to the idea of resistance.

Chapters five and six look at the way Muslim subjectivity has been debated within one of the most emblematic fields of engagement with religious otherness, namely multiculturalism, but also expands the insights of this analysis to the realm of political reasoning. Chapter five shows how multiculturalism, when coupled with the politics of Muslim subjectivity, acquires a specifically postsecular edge. It looks at the way the logic of the politics of Muslim assertiveness is articulated by addressing its main positions and shortcomings, in order to show how they undergird but also diverge from more mainstream or established forms of theoretical multiculturalism. By engaging with one of the main figures in the debate, Tariq Modood, the chapter makes tangible the theoretical underpinning of the shift of multiculturalism towards religious identity, the tensions in relation to the established 'multiculturalist canon' and the political implications of the postsecular leanings of the discourse of 'Muslim assertiveness'. The 'politics of Muslim assertiveness' has been advocated as an example of a more mature, consistent and inclusive

multiculturalism, however, as the chapter demonstrates, this postsecular turn of multiculturalism can also be seen as symptomatic of the closure of the possibility of a 'secular multiculturalism'.

Chapter six looks at the way public and political sensibilities have been formed in relation to religious, and more precisely Muslim subjectivity, and analyses their significance. The chapter focuses, firstly, on the concept of Islamophobia, a term in which some of the most significant and recognisable controversies of our times have been framed, and traces its transformation from a diagnostic of discrimination to a discourse of victimhood. Secondly, it looks at the uses of central rhetorical tropes and analytical categories of the politics of Muslim subjectivity and shows how political and moral sensibilities about religious identities have been enabled in academic and public debates about Islam. The chapter concludes by arguing that the prominence of culture brought to the fore by the logic of culturalism is a problematical move on two levels: on the conceptual level, because it has recourse to the *same* Orientalist rationality that it aims to deconstruct; on the political level, because it offers to the racist far-right new differentialist categories constructed around the idea of culture and as a consequence new insidious ways of demarcating and excluding the Other in the name of culture.

The thesis concludes by arguing that the (mainly poststructuralist) positions employed to build the case of Muslim subjectivity as an exemplary instance of articulation of anti-Eurocentric, postsecular sensibilities, knowledges and modes of political resistance are not conducive either to a relational consideration of alterity or to subversive anti-hegemonic politics, which can be better served by a genuine universalism, dissociated from Westernism and reclaimed in terms of shared commonalities and shared futures.

Chapter One

Chapter One

Islamic Feminism: Tensions, Paradoxes, Limits

- 1.1 Introduction: the case and the problematic
- 1.2 Islamic feminism as pragmatism: the contours of a compromise
- 1.3 Islamic feminism as radicalism: a new revolutionary paradigm?

1.1 Introduction: the case and the problematic

Gender has been the core constituent in some of the most significant controversies concerning Islam, Islamism, as well as the politicisation and accommodation of the religious self in recent years. The veil and the burqa have not only been discussed for their own sake but they have also acquired the status of 'public affairs'. As such they have become vehicles to debate secularism, the role of the State, the constitution of Europe, immigration, postcoloniality, racism and Islamophobia among other things. The relationship between gender, Islam and Islamism has been, albeit not without a hypocritical aspect, a central issue in international politics as the war in Afghanistan in the name of women's rights bears witness, but also in international activism as the more recent campaign to save Sakineh Mohhamadi Ashtiani from being stoned to death demonstrates. Therefore, the nexus formed by women, Islam/ism and the politicisation - and necessarily - instrumentalisation of gender, seem to be a central avenue through which the entity of 'Islam' and the variety of its contemporary connotations are approached academically, politically and publicly. Naturally then, anyone who seeks to address the antagonism between secular and religious - Islamic in our case - ideologies, as well as contemporary conceptions of critique and critical social theory, needs to consider gender as one of the main components of the discussion. No other field illustrates better than gender the difficult and contested relationship between modern concepts of autonomy, freedom, equality and rights on the one hand, and religious conceptions of values, dignity and meaningful life on the other. Even more, no other strand of post-Foucauldian social theory than feminism engages more with the nature of political subjectivity or agency, with the way it is conditioned and with the technologies through which consciousness and bodies are subjectified.

Two clarifications are important for the analysis attempted here: firstly, the focus of the chapter is not *gender* in the sense of the ways gender identities are experienced in different cultural settings, a rather anthropological task, but *feminism* and the political and epistemological issues that arise with its encounter with Islam both as religious practice and as political ideology. The chapter looks at the ways the question of gender relations has been debated and problematised within the Islamic feminist literature and the challenges that this poses for secular feminism and points to the political implications of this position. Secondly, in line with the general orientation of the thesis, the other focus of this chapter is not Islam as religious practice and spiritual orientation (a guide for good life), but its political instrumentalisation, i.e. Islam/ism as the application of Islamic precepts for political (a guide for good community) and epistemic (a guide for good social science) purposes. In this perspective, I will attempt to examine the tensions, paradoxes and limits in the relationship between Islam/ism and feminism through the examination of their hybridisation which claims to have brought into being a new avenue of thinking and practice, i.e. Islamic feminism.

The academic interest as well as the very possibility of articulation of Islamic feminism relies on the broadening of the category of the 'political' as a field of practice so as to address the relationship between women and politics in general and the relationship between non-Western women and politics in particular. Originating in the intention to break the divide between the public and private - the bedrock assumption of the ostensibly neutral character of the individual in liberal theory sustaining the division between men and women - feminists sought to give new meaning to the definition of the political and to broaden the field of analysis (Pateman 1989; Waylen 1996). Not only the traditionally dominated discipline of political theory but also an earlier phase of feminism have been accused for their monolithic perception of 'Third World woman as victim of her culture' and for being insensitive to Third World women's choices and to forms of political activism or forms of feminine activity that are located in indigenous ideologies, religious discourses or ideologies of motherhood (Mohanty's *Under Western Eyes* 1984, is the most seminal example and the founding text of Third World feminism, examined in section two of this chapter). This particular opening of feminism to the female 'Other' together with the prevalence of poststructuralist/postmodern analytics of power underlie the shift to the possibilities of new ways of 'doing politics'. The motto 'the personal is political' questioned the rigid allocation of spaces dictating that the political is exercised in the public only and shifted the

interest to 'the politics of everyday life'. As far as the relationship between Islam/ism and feminism is concerned, it has been suggested that Islamism and feminism are the most significant movements in terms of blurring and redesigning the borders between private and public spheres (Gole 2003: 811). In that sense questioning the extension of the principle of equality into new social relations and the associated expansion of secularisation into new realms of life together with a certain understanding of Islamism as 'politics of recognition' (Gole 1996: 22), led to the emergence of Islamic feminism and to the consideration of the adoption of Islamic fundamentalism by women as 'a means for political struggles' (Afshar 1996b: 120).

Arguably an alternative strand of feminism, Islamic feminism – whose postmodern allegiances are openly acknowledged by its most prominent representatives (Afshar 1996:124; Ahmadi 2006: 47-48) - emerged in the Middle East and found supporters among feminists in the West, most remarkable among the stands of postmodern feminism.² Islamic feminism approaches the question of gender on the basis of Islamic values and principles deploying methods and techniques that derive from Islamic sources (Badran 1995, 2002, 2005, 2006; Barlas 2002; Shaikh 1997; Wadud 1999). It can be broadly situated within a larger postsecular current of thought that proposes to construct ideal society and new social science inspired by religious rather than secular premises, in our case, from a particular, 'progressive' or 'radical' reading of Islamic texts and traditions (Barlas 2002; Hassan 1999; Wadud 2004). Its methods and objectives then, have for us two implications: the cultural relativist orientation, a position implying that Islam – meant here as the culture and society of Muslims – should be understood by reference to its own cultural logic. The second issue arising from this position points to the relationship between values and social science. The acknowledged ideological commitment of Islamic feminism - or what in different words could be described as its value-oriented approach which acknowledges the analytical primacy of Islamic values over the sociological study of those Islamic values (Tapper 1995) - points to the possible categorisation of this particular strand of feminism as *Islamist* rather than Islamic,³ i.e. as another 'ideological feminism' such as Marxist, secular, liberal and so on. The shift

² The term itself had caused controversy since its inception (Moghadam 2001) to the point that one of its main proponents and key voices of the debate, Mir-Hosseini, argued recently that 'the composite term "Islamic feminism" has become so loaded with disputed meanings and implications, so enmeshed in local and global political struggles, that it is no longer useful in any kind of descriptive or analytical sense' (Mir-Hosseini 2011: 67).

³ By referring to Islamist rather than Islamic feminism here I aim to bring into attention the thin line between the theological and the political when Islamic analytics are given primacy over sociological ones, rather than alluding to the typology used by Halverson and Way (2001) who focus their analysis on the gender politics of female Islamist leading figures, such as Zaynab al-Ghazali and Nadia Yassine.

from Islamic to Islamist feminism as examined by the chapter raises questions about the room allowed for a compromise between this particular strong determinist methodology based on Islamic sources (and their core of essential and unchangeable truths) on the one hand, and feminist precepts on the other hand.

Is then Islamic feminism a subfield of feminism that aims to produce categories and concepts alternative to the western ones in order to engage in a productive dialogue with 'Western' feminism and 'Western' social science? Is it an Islamic approach to questions of gender rather than a feminist approach to Islamic practices with regards to gender? The articulation of Islamic feminism is not only challenging for feminism as a radical political theory and project of social change but it also exemplifies central problems in critical social theory itself today. If the hegemonic Eurocentric or Western views need deconstruction, the anti-hegemonic postmodern/poststructuralist understanding of the particular, local or indigenous in general, and Islamic in particular, needs to be questioned as well. The possibility of articulation of Islamic feminism illustrates uneasy quandaries for feminist theory: for instance, is feminism a 'Western ideology' only? Are those who practically promote the improvement of women's position *de facto* feminists? Can a more inclusive feminism be developed from the contributions from other parts of the world? And would this entail a more general turn from 'universal' principles to consideration of local particularities?

The questions asked above suggest that Islamic feminism is not self-explanatory and the arguments and questions raised by the intellectuals working within this paradigm should be carefully discussed, not only because they involve the lives of many, but mainly – for the kind of questions that this work seeks to address - because they invite a critical dialogue over the very premises of social science. Using Islamic feminism as its vehicle the chapter explores the challenges that this new Islamic (and postmodern) understanding of subjectivity poses to secular feminism as a political position and theoretical project. My focus on Islamic feminism here has two interlocked aims: in the first place it aims to examine those authors and positions who self-identify as Islamic feminists and more broadly those who seek to reconcile Islam as a system of belief, with feminism, i.e. a movement and theory advocating not only the improvement of women's position in society but the subversion of the current patriarchal distribution of power between sexes. In the second, since Islamic feminists and those who sympathise with them in

Western academia (Badran 1995, 2001, 2002, 2005, 2006; Cooke 2001; Fernea 1998; Roald 1998; Simmons 2003) see their alternative feminisms not only as alternative visions of female subjectivity but as antagonistic to the Western ones, as 'critical' against secular ('Western') feminism, the chapter aims to offer the background against which ideas about resistance, empowerment, political subjectivity and agency have been reconceptualised based on women's 'Islamic' or 'nonsecular' experience discussed in the following chapter.

In the relevant literature two positions prevail regarding the meaning of the politics of Islamic feminist. For analytical purposes I distinguish between a 'pragmatic' and a 'radical' position: a. the pragmatic position seeks to improve women's condition through the re-interpretation of Islamic sources and focuses also on the specific action to be taken in order to improve mainly their legal status (Ahmed 1992; Afshar 1996a, 1996b, 1998, 2007; Badran 1995, 2001, 2002, 2005, 2006; El Guidi 1999, Hassan 1996, 1999; Mernissi 1991, 1992, 1993; Mir-Hosseini 1996a, 1996b, 2000, 2002, 2006; Wadud 1999, 2004; see also Abu-Odeh 1993, Ahmadi 2006, Al-Hassan Golley 2004, Hashim 1991, Moghadam 2001, 2002 for a sympathetic evaluation of the movement as well as Mojab 2001, Moghissi 2002, Yuval-Davis 1997 for a critique from a secular perspective); b. the radical position essentially sees Islamic feminism as part of a larger radical ('revolutionary') political project articulated around Islam (Majid 1998a, 1998b). These projects naturally converge on three fronts: firstly, in terms of their political motivation, that is the rejection of 'Eurocentric' or 'Western' modes of social and political thinking and the improvement of women's status by reference to Islam. Secondly, in terms of their political intention, i.e. in the sense of seeking to reform Islam, or in different terms of 'liberating' Islam from its 'cultural' distortions by turning to the most fundamental sources of Islamic religion. And thirdly, in terms of situating their argumentation at the intersection of two frameworks: the apologetic and the pluralist one. By 'apologetic' framework⁴ I refer to the clichéd stance that Islam at its inception allocates women a special, higher status and therefore women do not need to struggle for liberation or seek for equality in un-Islamic ideologies such as 'Western' feminism (e.g. Afshar 1996b:124; Afshar 2007: 425). The apologetic logic occasionally acquires more political overtones by actually attributing the loss of rights that women allegedly enjoyed within the Islamic tradition to the colonial pressures and the effect of secularising and consumerist trends (El Guidi 1999: 177). By 'pluralist'

⁴ The idea of a 'degeneration of an ideal' is central in the apologetic logic which claims equality between sexes as an achievement of the Golden Ages of Islam (Gole 1996: 107) and which sees the current unequal distribution of power between sexes as the outcome of misinterpretations and mispractices of Islam (ibid: 104).

framework I refer to the set of reformist attitudes which are broadly inspired by the anti-essentialist epistemological stance as well as by the multiculturalist emphasis on culture and seek to promote a 'progressive' interpretation of Islamic holy sources. However, despite their commonalities, these two positions the 'pragmatic' and the 'radical' differ in terms of the nature of social change they envision (pragmatic and practical for the ones, ideological for the others) and in terms of their respective topology of reference (the currently existing and experienced Islamic societies on the one hand and the revolutionary imagined topos on the other). But most importantly, as the chapter will demonstrate, they differ in terms of hierarchisation of the two opposing paradigms they engage with, i.e. Islam and feminism.

1.2 Islamic feminism as pragmatism: the contours of a compromise

Islamic feminism - a distinct strand of the broader reformist trend within Islam which claims to be both a renewed and authentic approach – can be seen as an *a priori* paradox since it attempts to reconcile a radical political theory and project of social change i.e. feminism, and a system of religious belief which unavoidably contains elements of immutability, a core of unchangeable, eternal 'truth', i.e. Islam. Islamic feminism can be described both as the practice or method of a women-centred rereading of Islamic texts and traditions within the Islamic countries and as part of those strands of postmodern feminist thought seeking to counter the dominant Eurocentric universalist categories of analysis. Often questioned about the cogency of its positions, the efficacy of its practices and the possibility to represent women's interests, Islamic feminism has been defined by its leading figures as a 'feminist discourse and practice articulated within an Islamic paradigm' (Badran 2002) and as 'a brand of feminism which takes Islam, not the West, as its source of legitimacy' (Mir Hosseini 1996b: 316). Or as a possibility 'to construct a dialogue and initiate a process of interpretation and development which places Islam in the framework of what could be called a feminist discourse' (Afshar 2007: 419) which is 'feminist because it seeks to liberate womanhood; it is Islamic because its premises are embedded in Islamic principles and values' (El Guidi 1999: 184). Its methodology consists in the engagement into feminist *ijtihad* (independent investigation of religious sources) and *tafsir* (interpretation of the Quran) by emphasising the egalitarian ethics of Islam and by deconstructing Sharia-related rules in a women-friendly, egalitarian fashion. Although it emerged as an 'indigenous' feminism in Iran,

rejecting the state-sponsored and Western-oriented 'feminism' of the Pahlavi as well as the liberal-left feminism of 1970s, yet assimilating elements of both (Mir-Hosseini 1996: 163), Islamic feminism is thought by its adherents today as a 'global' phenomenon, produced in diverse locations and transcending the divide between East and West (Badran 2006). It is described as a trend which has demonstrated in practice that 'feminism and cultural authenticity are not necessarily exclusive, and that women can reconcile their cultural and feminist selves' (Ahmadi 2006: 45).

For the Islamic feminists of pragmatic orientation arguments for women's equality within Islam - or in different words religion as a narrative of emancipation - hold a lot of potential for women in cultural settings 'where the Quran virtually functions as the constitution' as 'this refiguring of Islam has direct implications for the practice of citizenship' (Badran 2001: 50). In this line of argument, Islamic feminism practically proves that 'there is no inherent and logical link between patriarchy and Islamic ideals' and that it is possible to 'break the old and tired dichotomy between Islam and feminism' whilst ensuring that these positions 'cannot be dismissed by the Islamists merely as "corrupt and Western"' (Mir-Hosseini 1996a: 158-159). It is therefore thought that any attempt to change the position of women through total rejection of Islam is bound to result in accusations of cultural imperialism since 'highly educated and articulate Muslim women regard Western feminism as a poor example they do not wish to follow' (Afshar 1996b: 123). Even more, 'not only do they [women] dismiss Western feminism for being one of the many instruments of colonialism, but also they despise the kind of freedom that is offered to women under the Western patriarchy', since liberation in the Islamic world tends to be associated with the liberation from the political and ideological presuppositions of the West (ibid).

As Islamic feminist scholars observe unanimously (Abu Odeh 1993; Al-Hassan Golley 2004; Hashim 1999; Mir-Hosseini 2000), feminism in the Islamic countries is constantly entangled in a double struggle, against the old religious and social order, which is perceived as restraining yet authentic, and against Western colonisation which is seen as liberating yet corrupt. This is even more problematic since women often do not tend to see religion - a paramount element of women's everyday experience in Muslim societies - as the source of the constraints placed upon them and because in the absence of other alternatives, women are unlikely to reject the foundations of their social position (Hashim 1999; Shaheed 1995; Yuval-Davis 1997).

Furthermore, since those women who defend their rights or ask for social justice are often accused of importing a 'foreign' ideology, Islamic feminists try to demonstrate their true allegiance to their Islamic culture and to distinguish themselves from 'Western' and 'Third World' feminists alike (Ahmadi 2006: 44), even if Islamic feminism has also occasionally inscribed itself in the broader project of Third World politics (Afshar 1996).

For those who look at Islamic feminism with sympathy, this reformist women-centred interpretation of Islam should be understood not only as an alternative to secular and democratic demands but as a component of a more general social change (Moghadam 1993a, 1993b, 2001, 2002). The extent to which liberation is appropriate or desirable for the Muslim context is seen as a question that should be considered from within as well from outside of tradition in a way that is consistent with the Quran and generally with what the Muslims see as the divinely-ordained principles of Islam (Smith 1979). Therefore, the efforts of believing women to subject their religious texts to a feminist re-reading should be supported (Moghadam 2002: 1162), even if it is acknowledged that their discursive strategy can only have limited impact as long as they remain focused on theological questions rather than socioeconomic and political ones (Moghadam 2002: 1158; 2006: 44-45). On the basis of this compromise and re-synthesis, Islamic women may appear as sharing the same concerns with left-wing women about their legal status and social positions (Moghadam 2002: 1143), or as not being substantially different from liberal feminists who work within the discursive framework of liberalism to improve women's position (Moghadam 2002: 1159). Indeed, with the aide of postmodern hermeneutics the Islamic feminist enterprise is viewed as an attempt to decentre the clergy's monopoly from the domain of interpretation and to place women as interpreters of the faith. For this, however, one would need to separate the 'authentic' message of Islam - hence the recourse to the re-interpretation of the Quran - from its cultural 'contamination' from traditional, local practices.⁵ It goes without saying though that it is impossible in many cases to separate what is cultural from what is Islamic *per se*, as theology, the 'theory' of religion, is always inscribed in practices within specific cultural contexts.

The important interpretative move that Islamic feminists attempt when looking at the condition of women and gender relations within Islam, is to shift the focus from question of inferiority to

⁵ The female circumcision is, for instance, a very controversial and debated example, see Boddy (1982) for an anthropological analysis of the meaning of this practice.

questions of subjugation (Smith 1979: 527). Central to this kind of approach Smith (1979: 528-529) suggests, is the conviction that subjugation 'is divinely-ordained and therefore a natural circumstance', hence 'asking the question about rights is essentially asking the wrong question', i.e. 'the female against male approach being alien in a culture where the priority is put on the complementary of roles of women and men'. Framing the issue this way it makes it 'easy to see that women use concepts (...) such as "complementarity" rather than "equality" to pursue particular goals' Afshar (1996a: 1) argues. From a feminist-historical point of view this approach is, of course, rather questionable: the argument of complementarity of sexes has been the main ideological strategy employed from strands of conservative feminism as well as from state fascist ideologies to counter more radical feminist demands about equality on suffrage, employment and education opportunities and reforms of family law prior to the Second World War in Europe (Vasilaki 2003, 2008). Its merit, however, lies in the insight that it offers for the explanation of effects ('empowering and seductive' Abu Odeh 1993: 26) of Islamic restraining practices such as veiling, and the way their reinforcement on the public sphere has legitimised the presence of women into it, as discussed in the next chapter.

What is striking in the efforts of Islamic feminism is its ambivalence vis-à-vis 'Western' feminism, as it oscillates between the rejection of what is seen as a 'Western ideology' and the desire to inscribe this 'Western paradigm' and its language of rights within the Islamic experience. Take for instance El Guidi (1999: 182), who asserts that Muslim women's rights cannot be approached through liberal feminist agendas as these are based on Western experience and therefore are irrelevant to them. Hence, the only effective way to deal with these matters is to address them within the context that created them as 'feminism within the context of Islam can provide the only path to empowerment and liberation available without challenging the culture as a whole' (ibid). Promoting women's (Islamic) knowledge of their rights is seen as the best strategy against the various fundamentalist approaches of Islamic laws for 'it is only from a position of knowledge that women can challenge the patriarchal distortions of the essentially egalitarian message of Islam' (Hashim 1999: 12).

Nevertheless, those who pronounce themselves in favour of 'uncovering' the egalitarian message of Islam as evidence of the equal status granted to women within Islam on the basis of sacred texts and traditions, fail to see that women are not conceptualised as human beings in the same way

that men are (Moghissi 1999), as we have seen above with the case of ‘complementarity of sexes’. Equality of all human beings does not include women who are thought as *different* and hence entitled to – and more often deprived of – different rights and that is not only the case of traditionally patriarchal societies such as the Islamic ones – and for that matter monotheistic cultures in general - but also often the case of modern cultures as the initial understanding of universal suffrage as male only suffrage in most early European liberal democracies demonstrates. To be sure, this innovative reading of the Quran – an initiative inspired by the emancipatory message and influence of ‘Western’ feminism in the first place - holds considerable potential within societies where the political field is entirely Islamicised (Hashim 1999; Moghadam 2002; Shaheed 1995). But it also has considerable limitations, if not impasses, like any strategy founded on divinely-ordained principles which can be easily manipulated within authoritarian religious environments, where religious authorities can decry hard-won achievements based on religious law (Yuval Davis 1997).

There are several paradoxes related both to the argumentation of Islamic feminism *per se* as well as to the way it has been supported in Western academia. Despite its self-declared anti-essentialism which urges the opening of ‘Western’, secular feminism to the multiplicity of women’s experience and needs, it seem that Islamic feminism builds its approach on a rather essentialist conception of Islam as a superior, totalised and, in the last instance, the most authentic and meaningful way of life (Afshar 1996a, 1996b, 2007; El Guidi 1999; Mir-Hosseini 1996a, 1996b, 2000). By this I mean that the return to the ‘basics’ of Islam, to its ‘true’ message, which has been distorted by patriarchal interpretations, presupposes an ‘essence’ of Islam. Insisting on the specificity of the ‘Muslim woman’ and her special status in society and arguing that Islam, ‘correctly’ interpreted, grants women equal rights (Barlas 2002; Hassan 1996, 1999; Shaikh 1997; Wadud 1999), presupposes an essentialised (and probably monolithic) category of ‘Muslim woman’ and follows an romanticised, apologetic logic which, in short, purports that Islam made things better from women, but the fundamentalists or traditionalists misinterpret it (Mernissi 1991, 1992, 1993). What is of course omitted here is the fact that the discussion about rights and women’s rights in particular, are ‘Western’, secular products inseparable of questions of citizenship, democratic state and civil society, and therefore it would be perhaps more appropriate to examine the whole Islamic feminist project under the light of the western experience, as Mojab suggests (2001:137), despite claims about the authentic or indigenous character of the project.

Needless to say, from an Islamic feminist point of view, Mojab's (ibid) suggestion could only be rejected as it would be seen as carrying an underlying expectation from 'non-Western' women to abandon their native cultures. However, such rejection overlooks the fact that the very idea of turning to the native culture for the legitimation of rights, citizenship, feminism and so on, implies that the native culture is already viewed with 'Western eyes'. The articulation of Islamic feminism as a project, despite seeking its source of legitimacy in Islam, embodies a 'Western', secular, modern view of women reflected in the very categories it employs and in its mode of rationalisation. Even if Islamic feminists, Islamists and cultural relativists share the belief that allegiance to the community or native culture overrides notions of individual rights and liberties, Western conceptions of autonomy and so on, their discourse seeks to appropriate and/or redefine the content of these same notions.

The issue of the abandonment of the 'native', 'local' or 'traditional' in favour of the Western first made its appearance, according to Ahmed (1992) in what she calls the 'discourse of colonial feminism'. The association of colonialism with feminism or with other Western political ideas – socialism, equality, emancipation and so on – is a well-known strategy in both sides of the fence: by the colonisers in the past who sought to create hierarchies of superior and inferior cultures and by their neoconservative successors today who seek to obscure the truly universalist content of such notions and to promote them as something 'Western' to be protected or imposed. But also by Islamism or certain forms of Thirdworldism or xenophobic localist ideologies who seek to legitimize their political agendas by denouncing such ideas as 'Western', alien and alienating. Women then easily find themselves trapped between 'betrayal and betrayal' (Kandiyoti 1991b: 7), a condition of double-bind that Islamic feminism is supposed to overcome by merging the local with the universal, the traditional with the modern, the dogma with the multiplicity of its interpretations. One of the arguments put forward is that 'Western' feminism is undergirded by the idea that whilst Western women may pursue feminist goals by engaging critically with and challenging their cultural heritage, Muslim women cannot pursue such goals without rejecting their traditions in favour of the ways of the West. Furthermore, the argument goes, the underlying position is that Islamic cultures and religion are inimical to change and reinterpretation, in a way that the cultures and religions of the West are (Ahmed 1992: 244-245). Except the fact that this position has already integrated a Western view about the status of women specifically, and about social change and historical teleology more generally by employing

the conceptual polarities of 'West' versus 'Islam', it also seems to imply that the only way for non-Western women to be 'true' or 'authentic' is to remain within the boundaries of their local, indigenous, ethnic or religious cultures. The way the critique of western hegemony has evolved suggests that premodern formations were necessarily better for the women; and down this road, Islam appears as the only acceptable and workable solution for the Muslim parts of the world and for their diasporic communities in the West. Arguing against 'Western' feminism on the grounds of defence of native cultures from Western cultural imperialism and calling for the rediscovery of 'culturally authentic, home-grown ideologies' (Moghissi 1999: 9) has further implications as, if we follow Moghissi (*ibid*), this implies that 'feminism is and must remain the privileged domain of women in the West'. Naturally, this makes the idea of deciding for whom individual liberties, rights to autonomy and self-determination are deemed appropriate and desirable, problematical on both political and ethical fronts.

Much of the confusion about the content and goals of Islamic feminism stems from the conflation between feminine identity or a certain gender awareness on the one hand, and feminist consciousness, which implies an understanding of feminism as a political project that seeks the redistribution of gender power on the one hand, and the democratisation of the patriarchal social and economic system on the other. Those who support Islamic feminism, like many feminists historians who seek the origins of a kind of 'proto-feminism', tend to see any expression of feminine identity as a form of indigenous feminism, and feminine activism within the Islamic world falls under this case. In this perspective the universality of patriarchy is dismissed as an ahistorical, Western construct which levels out the multiplicity of women's experience. However, as Winter (2001: 17) remarks 'the identification of patterns of male domination neither renders women passive, denying them agency, not, conversely, does it – in the name of agency within a situation of oppression – render women unaccountable for their actions'. Once the universality of patriarchy is dismissed, those who endorse Islamic feminism as an authentic and indigenous emancipatory alternative to secular feminism can afford to disregard the fact that the Islamicisation of gender relations legitimizes further oppressive patriarchies which cannot be countered efficiently through limited legal reforms. For secular feminists (Mojab 2001; Moghissi 1999) the suspicion against the universality of patriarchy advocated by Islamic feminists and cultural relativists alike, overlooks oppressive gender relations in non-Western societies. Even more, the rejection of the unified feminine subject as Eurocentric tends to fragment women into

religious, ethnic, racial and cultural entities with particularist agendas, as well as to undermine the collective object and objective that all feminisms minimally and nominally share (Schor 1995). As Mojab (2001: 135) argues, all interventions in gender relations, religious and secular are political as they are dealing with the question of power, and gender is a prime site of exercise of this power which is unequally distributed and hierarchically organised. Since the main struggle is over the control of women in public and private spheres of life and the institution of religion plays a significant role in it, the conflict cannot be reduced to individual, cultural or religious identities. Ebert (1991: 898) notices that the prevailing discourses that endorse the concrete, specific, and local while rejecting theory and abstraction, reduce poststructuralism to anti-structuralism and confuse 'totality' with 'totalitarianism'. In that sense, if we follow Ebert's line of thought (ibid: 901), Islamic feminism, as an offspring of postmodern feminism, also fails to operate the distinction between the universality of patriarchy as a system on the one hand, and its specific articulations of oppression which produce the same effects, that is the exclusion of women who are subjugated in the same position differently, on the other hand. This is why the main problem with this kind of postmodern feminist rationale⁶ is not only, or primarily, of academic or contextual but of political nature: the kind of epistemological pluralism they adopt tends to neutralize the possibility to question structural relations of power and this has paralysing implications for a (necessarily) prescriptive project of social change, such as feminism.

The issue that the convergence of cultural relativists and Islamists raises for feminism is that of recognition: the recognition of the 'particular', the 'local', the 'communal', whose primacy within postmodern feminism is grounded on the claimed authenticity of such perspectives. In different words, the tension between liberal/secular and postmodern/postsecular feminism - of which Islamic feminism is a telling example - could be phrased as the one between the social politics of equality and the cultural politics of difference. The challenge for feminism is what kind of recognition is due, if any, to allegiances - cultural, religious, ethnic - that collide with the feminist ones. Among the attempts that have been made to reconcile feminism with the politics of difference, Baum (2004) sketches a 'feminist critical theory of recognition' that seems to balance well between these opposing commitments: in epistemological terms, it takes into consideration the religious and cultural identities for the local knowledge that they carry without disregarding

⁶ Ebert (1991) labels this trend 'ludic' postmodernism which she opposes to 'resistance postmodernism' that rewrites difference not as a matter of identity, neither as a matter of tropic slippage, but as political, materialised difference.

the asymmetrical relations of power, whereas in ethical terms, it seeks cross-culturally respectful ways to understand agency while pursuing feminist critique of gendered norms and practices (2004: 1086-1087). Baum is not the only one who stresses the importance of focusing on the asymmetrical relations of power and the pursuit of feminist critique. What can be discerned in this attempt of accommodation between the epistemological and ethical collision of secular and postmodern feminism is the (re)turn of certain postmodern-oriented authors to more general perspectives, as a result of the political implications emanating from the subscription to the postmodern theoretical frameworks. In other words, it is acknowledged that it is impossible to work out any theory or pursuit of feminist goals on a global level without maintaining some notion of universality if not of the subject, at least of power relations (patriarchal power above all in the feminist perspective).

Mohanty's reframing of her own secular feminist commitment is the most significant. In 'Under Western Eyes' (1984), one of the founding texts of postcolonial feminism, Mohanty had provided a sustained, fierce critique of the production of a singular monolithic subject, the 'Third World woman'. She saw this construct as a product of discursive colonisation that focused on a specific mode of appropriation and codification of 'scholarship' and 'knowledge' about women in the Third World that took as their referent feminist interests in the way they had been articulated in the West (1984: 333). Mohanty had argued that the feminist orthodoxy of those days discursively colonised the material and historical heterogeneities of the lives of women in the Third World and produced an arbitrary singular Third World woman (ibid: 334). She criticised the monopoly of 'woman' as a universal, cross-cultural category, beyond class, ethnic or racial locations (ibid: 336-337) and the presumption that 'women' as a coherent category builds on gender over and above everything else and prior to their entry into the arena of social relations where the meaning of categories is acquired (ibid: 340). And she maintained that it is only through the understanding of contradictions inherent in women's locations within various structures that effective political action could be taken (ibid: 346).⁷

⁷ However, this de-essentialisation of feminism's central category was also met with accusations of residual essentialism. For instance, Narayan (2000: 1083) notices that 'seemingly universal essentialist generalisations about "all women" are replaced by culture-specific essentialist generalisations that depend on totalizing categories such as "Western culture", "non-Western cultures", "Indian women", and "Muslim women"', and that the picture of cultures sustaining such categorisations remains fundamentally essentialist as it is oblivious of 'heterogeneous peoples whose values, ways of life, and political commitments are internally divergent'.

In 2002, however, in 'Under Western Eyes Revisited', Mohanty seems to re-engage with the question of the relationship between the universal and the particular in feminist theory and to examine the political implications of the postmodern analytical strategies and principles. She explains that she had not argued against all forms of generalisation and that she had not privileged the local over the systemic, the difference over commonalities, or the discursive over the material, but that the point she was trying to make was the consideration of the importance of the particular in relation to the universal (2002: 502). She proposes a framework that would re-emphasize the connections between the local and the universal as a basis for a cross-border feminist community where 'common differences' can form the basis of solidarity across differences and unequal power relations (2002: 504). However, if these 'common differences' do mean something, then it seems that the postmodern perspective reaches the limits of its own epistemological break: 'common differences' sound as another way to re-insert the unified 'feminist subject' which is subordinated in the same position differently.

No doubt, the emergence of Islamic feminism demonstrates that people respond to theories of social change in relation to their existing cultural experience and therefore the understanding of desires ('what women want') and agency ('how women act') needs to be contextualised in relation to the cultural and material constraints under which women think and act. In that sense feminists have to come to terms with the fact that feminism is not a natural destination for all women, even if this does not mean that it is not endorsed by many women across cultures. The experience of the postcolonial condition, local cultures and the practical knowledge they carry together with the local understandings of constraints and possibilities of autonomy are issues that definitely challenge the premises, perspectives and strategies of feminism. However, one of the conceptual pillars of feminism is that biological difference between men and women should not entail differences on the legal status and should not be translated to an unequal social status. Islam, however – operates in the opposite way as it translates biological difference into social difference. How far then both feminism and Islam can go in terms of compromising their basic premises, and at whose expense the compromise should be made? For, either Islam/ism should abandon certain aspirations of regulating public life, acknowledge the primacy of individual self-fulfilment over the allegiance to the religious community and restraint itself largely to the realm of spiritual choice; but then Islamism would have to abandon essentially its political aspirations and leave the 'anti-imperialist' or 'dehegemonizing' agenda to political agents of different nature. Either

feminism would have to accept that the pursuit of the subversion of existing patriarchal system and the unequal relations of power it sustains is not always a priority, and that equality of sexes could sometimes be understood as both deliberate and 'liberating' subordination. The next section focuses on this quandary and examines the implications of the shift from Islamic to Islamist feminism.

1.3 Islamic feminism as radicalism: a new revolutionary paradigm?

In parallel to the more pragmatic and therefore necessarily compromising effort of the Islamic feminists described above, another political project, which sees Islamic feminism as part of a broader Islamist project of radical social transformation and as an 'indigenous path' to women's emancipation has been advocated by Anouar Majid (1998a, 1998b) in his article and rejoinder in the prestigious feminist revue *Signs*. His intervention had provoked a lively reaction from 'Western' feminists which is crucial to examine as it illustrates the shift from Islamic to what could be described as *Islamist* feminism. This shift is manifested in two ways: first, in the more radical transformation of consciousness required by Majid's project. Whereas for Islamic feminists the question lies in the practical application of Islam in a manner that benefits women, for Majid's Islamist feminism what is requested is an ideological conversion, a radical and holistic transformation of the self, the rise of a new revolutionary subject capable of liberating herself. Second, the move from 'Islamic' to 'Islamist' shifts the emphasis from the equal negotiation between feminism and Islam to the clear prioritisation of the latter. The negotiation between the two opposing authoritative discourses, which is the crux of the matter in the pragmatic version of Islamic feminism, turns into the clear prioritisation of Islam at the expense of feminism in Majid's version. Despite the common terrain between them (in terms of their political motivation, intention and discursive strategies as explained in the introduction of this chapter), Islamic feminists focus on the reconciliation between the two opposing paradigms, whereas Majid's position puts the emphasis on rupture, even if this rupture is engineered in a rather theoretically inconsistent manner, as discussed below. The shift from Islamic to Islamist feminism suggests that when religion becomes the guiding principle around which the political is imagined and organised, then Islam is never too far from Islamism: naturally, this is not a tendency inherent in Islam *per se*, but a disposition which resides in the politicisation of *any* religion, regardless of its often progressive aspirations. The examination of the superimposition of Islam as a critical tool on

political imaginaries, such as feminism, which operate within secular and/or humanist premises, makes manifest both the theoretical paradoxicality of such projects and the political hazards they generate, such as the devaluation of women's rights rebranded as 'Islamic liberation', as discussed below.

Let us then, in the first place, reconstruct a brief outline of Majid's proposition of Islam as a 'dehegemonizing' force and as a revolutionary paradigm within which his ideas about the relationship between women, feminism and Islam develop. Majid departs from the position that 'the critical redefinition and reassessment of Islamic traditions, including contesting several 'Islamically questionable assumptions about women, are the proper framework in order to engage into dialogues and movements of liberation in the Islamic world today' (Majid 1998a: 322). Majid, as other Islamic reformist intellectuals from the West, sees Islamic feminism as part of a 'dehegemonizing', anti-imperialist project assigned with the task to contest both orthodoxies of global capitalism and male domination. It is part of a broader 'Islamically progressive agenda - democratic, anti-patriarchal and anti-imperialist' (1998a: 324) which can provide, in his view, a new revolutionary paradigm. As such, the non-negotiable rejection of 'certain Western secular models' is a matter of survival for 'Muslim people' (1998a: 343). Majid's progressive Islam is 'empowered by the equal status and contributions of women, the attribution of full rights to minorities' and aims to 'break away from Eurocentric structures and promote progressive non-Western traditions and redynamize progressive non-Western traditions in a genuinely multicultural world' (1998a: 325). He sees the current Islamist project as a 'third way' between socialism and capitalist democracy that is both indigenous and progressive and he suggests that the best way to combat 'Islamic obscurantism' (by this he means the fundamentalist currents within Islam) is not through an 'equally irrational recourse to secularism' but through reforms that would make Islam a 'viable modern ideology' (1998: 352). In line with other (non-Muslim) scholars who work within the paradigm of the so-called ethical dimension of Marxism like Cornell West (1991) Majid wants to re-inscribe the 'individual' within the spiritual and socio-economic welfare of the 'community' and therefore concludes that 'secularism cannot be superimposed on a culture in which human agency is constantly negotiating its boundaries with those of Revelation' (1998a: 340).

Majid advocates for a 'new Islamic consciousness',⁸ expressed in 'indigenous vocabularies', rooted in 'usable' traditions and 'uncompromisingly universal' in scope which can redefine the meaning of Islam without abandoning the parameters of the faith. Majid's Islam is 'a cosmopolitan culture since its inception' even if it has failed to the present day to eradicate 'certain social and political inequalities in terms of class, gender and religion' (Majid 1998a: 342), an alternative social imaginary and the most authentic voice of the South against the Western hegemonic aspirations of the transnational capital (1998a: 341). The renewed approach concerning women's position and as a result gender relations in Islam proposed by Majid is inscribed in the perspective of rectifying the social inequalities left unaddressed by Islamic theology and/or practice to the present day. Majid (1998a: 338-40) sees the turn of the oppressed poor classes to obscurantist practices like gender-related discrimination as a reaction to the colonialist attack to their cultural identities but also as a reaction to the Westernised elites who surrendered to cultural imperialism.

In that sense it does not come as a surprise that Majid, in line with the Islamic feminists examined above, dismisses 'Western' (i.e. secular) feminism as a 'transcultural ideology' which addresses an assumed, in his view, universal patriarchy and disregards the complexities and specificities of different cultures. For Majid, 'Western feminism, largely shaped by gender relations in Christian capitalist cultures and by the exhausted paradigms of Western social thought' (1998a: 322) is neither a viable nor a desirable model for Muslim women who want to promote their rights.⁹ He accuses 'Western feminism' as employing largely a 'victimisation' framework which 'erases the complexities, pluralities, and historical specificities of different cultures' and whose 'monolithic assumptions are (...) akin to those of capitalism' (1998a: 354). The strain that feminists in Islamic societies face between the 'opposing loyalties' of gender and culture and the impossible choice between 'betrayal and betrayal' (Kandiyoti 1991b: 7) seems to be resolved by Majid who is

⁸ Gole (1996: 109-110) distinguishes Islamism between an explicitly militant, 'political' strand which gives priority to seizing state power and a 'cultural' one which seeks to protect Islam from the loss of its sacredness. This does not mean that cultural Islam lacks in political dimension but that transformation concerns in the first place the individual rather than the state; in that sense the conflict between Islam and the West is relocated on a new intellectual axis. It is this second, sophisticated and intellectualised strand of Islamism, a 'conveyor of a new value system' which seems to square with Majid's call for the transformation of consciousness as the basis of his broader revolutionary project.

⁹ By pointing to the relationship between Christianity and feminism here though, Majid not only reiterates the Orientalist, essentialist divide between Christianity and Islam, but he also seems oblivious of the fact that Islam and the Islamic Middle East share much with the Western World in terms of grounding in the Greco-Roman philosophy and Semitic-monotheistic theology (Tapper 1995: 187). If we take this into account, not only these two cultural 'blocks' – Islam and the West – may not be as radically opposed as Majid is trying to suggest but also, if we follow Tapper further, 'the Muslim world as such, which inevitably shares many of its traditions with the West, cannot produce a truly radical critique of it' (ibid).

adamant that 'Western feminism' is not useful to Muslim women who seek to liberate themselves from male domination (1998b: 387). For Majid, any feminist approach emanating from secular premises, including those authors who seek to demonstrate the distortions that allowed for an obscurantist use of Islam in matters of gender relations, is essentially misguided, if not straightforward hegemonic. Secular Muslim feminists, like the sociologist Mernissi (1991, 1992, 1993), who attempt to deconstruct misogynist ideas and practices allegedly founded on Islam by historicising their context of production and development are falling short of the 'dehegemonizing' task Majid has in mind for feminism, as Mernissi's approach 'desacralizes the Qu'ran, reducing it into a mere historical document' (1998a: 330). The demystification of the transcendental process of Revelation is undesirable and that is indicative of the limits in the approach, method, scope and objective between feminist students of Islam, like Mernissi, and Islamist feminists like Majid.

Instead then of the insidious 'Western' feminism Majid suggests an understanding of feminism as a mode of intervention into particular hegemonic discourses, as a series of critical interventions into localised patterns of patriarchal privilege (Majid 1998a: 354; 1998b: 379). Relying, as he claims, on the significant interventions against the monolithical 'Western' feminism by Mohanty (1984) and Lazreg (1998), he advocates the pluralisation of feminism and he concludes that there is no reason to believe that secularism is a prerequisite for the emancipation of women of a male-dominated Islam (Majid 1998a: 350). The kind of feminism sketched by Majid has two main characteristics: first, it is endowed with a distinctive source of aspiration, that is the 'usable' traditions of Islam that can be raised against 'obscurantist Islam'; and second, it is assigned with a distinctive mission, that is the opposition to the capitalist, imperialist, Western hegemony.

Intriguing and subversive as it may sound at first sight, there are two noticeable problems with Majid's conceptualisation of feminism, of which the first relates to sources whilst the second relates to objectives. In terms of sources, there is little information about what the 'usable' traditions may be or how they could be adapted to the contemporary Muslim societies except one phrase suggesting that 'the Prophet's wives could stand as a new model of womanhood in Islam, for it is well known that several of his wives challenged male supremacy and, as widows, took an active interest in public and political affairs' (1998a: 354). Even so, there are several questionable assumptions embedded in this suggestion from a feminist point of view: for instance, the *a priori*

assignment of the social role of wife, or widow, from which women are only allowed to challenge - but never eventually subvert - male supremacy; or the historical-social context of polygamy within which these role-models suggested by Majid operate. These problematical aspects are left in the dark as for Majid the holiness of Islamic figures seems to be a sufficient condition to combat male domination in Muslim societies. In terms of objectives, Majid's Islamist feminism seem to be more committed to the anti-imperialist, anti-capitalist, anti-secular and anti-Western agenda than in the struggle of women for equality *per se*. This is obvious in Majid's suspicion of international human rights, the terrain *par excellence* where debates about the thorny relationship between women and Islam in modernity are conducted. Women's struggles to limit the arbitrariness of male domination and attain a more equal status are hierarchised as a minor, if not undesirable achievement, since 'given the current definition of human rights in the West (...) women would emerge as beneficiaries, while entire peoples do not have the right to determine their own cultural and economic agendas' (1998a: 349). The issue at the core of this rather puzzling statement which assumes a certain rivalry between women's rights and peoples' cultural and economic rights, is Majid's conceptualisation of women's mission, or in different terms, women's political agency within the new Islamist revolutionary paradigm he puts forward. If we disregard the fact that 'historically women have been the victims *par excellence* of such sanctification of cultures' as Joseph (1998: 365) notifies in her comment of Majid's proposition, the 'protection' or better 'self-defence' of cultures sounds indeed as a critical and 'dehegemonizing' project. However, one which comes together with the price of women's subordination to a competing authoritative discourse: that of Islamic culture, tradition or faith and the revolutionary program against 'the West'.

From a similar critical perspective, Mayer's (1998) response to Majid's feminism notifies us of the dangerous implications of Majid's rhetoric which operates no distinction among the different discourses in the West and labels all supporters of human and women's rights as representatives of the hegemonic cultural project of the West and as servants of the imperialist/capitalist agenda. Mayer suggests caution about the enthusiastic adoption of 'Islamic' rights as an alternative to the 'hegemonic' international human rights. The issue of 'Islamic' versus 'human' rights has triggered

important discussions amongst Muslim intellectuals.¹⁰ However, here I want to further Meyer's critique not in relation to the question of rights but in relation to the nature of Majid's rhetoric and its 'resulting inconsistencies' (Mayer 1998: 373), not the least because his critique as well as his alternative operates in the discursive rather than the realist realm, and as such, utterances and their epistemological premises are of particular significance.

Majid's position and rhetoric are representative of a wider range of critical Islamist thinkers and popular discourses which see Islam as an alternative political imaginary and as a critical project in the vein of 'decolonisation' of social and human sciences. Majid's project sets off on the basis of the imperative need (a matter of 'survival') to reject '*certain* Western secular models' (1998a: 343). 'Certain' is a word of particular importance here as it allows Majid to, selectively albeit questionably, divide between 'good' and 'bad' Western secular models and to adamantly reject feminism and secularism ('secularisation [...] cannot be the basis of any emancipatory social movement in the Arab and Islamic worlds', 1998a: 340) among these. It is the word 'certain', vague as it is, which allows Majid to mix-and-match between opposing paradigms. Majid's rhetoric is full of puzzling and unapologetic paradoxes: on the one hand, he dismisses 'the exhausted paradigms of Western social thought' whilst on the other he appropriates them, disjointed from their context of production and web of their connotations and usages, and inscribes them in his own 'revolutionary', 'multicultural' and anti-Western Islam. For instance, whilst he joins the postcolonial, postmodern denunciation of 'universalizing Eurocentric discourses' as 'inevitable by-product of imperialism' (Majid 1998b: 379-380), his own new Islamic consciousness is 'uncompromisingly universal'. If 'the world in its natural state is a series of particularisms' (ibid), 'genuinely multicultural' and 'polycentric', one naturally wonders how this pluralistic logic is consistent with the universalist aspirations of Majid's new revolutionary paradigm.

In the same vein, the appropriation of Marxist tropes – liberation, anti-imperialism, anti-capitalism – interwoven with anti-secularism omits a serious discussion (limited in a footnote, Majid 1998b: 382, footnote 2) of a central tension: i.e. that Marxism is an unambiguously *secular* project, one which conceives emancipation as a break from both the constraints of capitalism and

¹⁰ See amongst the extensive literature on the subject the interesting exchange between Muslim intellectuals of secular convictions, such as An'Naim and critics of secular political values and institutions such as Asad ('Religion, Law and the Politics of Human Rights. Talal Asad and Abdullahi An'Naim' 2009).

tradition, and in particular religion. Politically speaking, historical experience of the practical application of such 'hybrid' ideologies which combine Thirdworldist and Islamist elements and which employed similar rhetoric strategies had ruinous outcomes, as the recent political histories of Iran and Sudan bear witness. The enthusiasm about local narratives of liberation tends to disregard the fact that behind the radical, 'revolutionary' vocabulary, social conservatism remains intact and that as Islamic metaphors and symbols become forms of political expression, Muslims across the world are told that conformity to Islamic practices is a liberating move and in a sense the *only* meaningful project of social and/or personal change. Theoretically speaking suffice to mention here¹¹ that Majid's 'dehegemonizing', 'critical' Islam appears as not only inconsistent but also un-reflexive vis-à-vis the genealogy of its own categories of articulation: the concepts of rights, resistance, liberation, emancipation, resistance, self-determination of cultures, cultural imperialism have a secular, 'Western' in different terms, descent. They are core constituents of 'the exhausted paradigms of Western social thought' (Majid 1998a: 322) that are deemed necessary to be dismissed in order to create the premises of critical Islamist thinking.

Majid's elaboration on feminism is an instructive example of the shift from Islamic to Islamist feminism, from a feminist approach to questions of gender in Islam to an Islamist critique of feminism. As mentioned above this is an inbuilt possibility in the very conceptualisation of Islamic feminism and in the cultural relativism that sustains its approach and explanatory framework. Afshar's (1996b: 121) suggestion to 'move away from the usual condemnatory approach to Islamic fundamentalism and consider it in the light of the views and activities of its adherents' and to see 'how, if at all, it could be used as a means for political struggles' or Mir-Hosseini's (1996a: 143) observation that 'the impact of revolution on women has been emancipatory, in the sense that it has paved the way for the emergence of a popular feminist consciousness' becomes a full-fledged paradigm in Majid's work. The contradictory premises (Marxism, anti-secularism, anti-Eurocentric rejection of universalism along with Islamist universalism) that define the meaning of these political struggles allow room for the subordination of women to a political cause which expresses itself in the vocabulary of anti-domination. Feminist literature has often made the point about the instrumentalisation of women as repositories of cultural identity and about the transformation of their lives and bodies into a

¹¹ See chapter four for a detailed discussion of the tensions between postcolonial theory and the postcolonial rhetoric of academic Islamism.

battlefield of antagonisms of moral and cultural authorities in anticolonialist projects and movements of national liberation. The public image of women as symbol of cultural purity, or cultural authenticity, Kandiyoti explains (1991: 14 and chapter 6) has dreadful consequences as it practically shifts the control over women from the private – the traditional authority exercised by particular men, i.e. the family – to *all* men, even if this instrumentalisation does not exclude women from being actively involved in challenging or even manipulating the meanings and usages of gender and national identities, as for instance in Egypt (Ahmed 1992) or Algeria (Moruzzi 1993). The radical vocabulary used by academic Islamists like Majid, together with the appropriation of these larger emancipatory projects of social change, like anti-colonialism, national liberation or anti-imperialism, mask the centrality of women's subordination to Islamist projects. The 'postcolonial politicisation of culture', as Winter (2006: 33-4) puts it, mistakes a problem of political domination for one of identity: 'it is particularly a matter of concern that women, in being identified as primary targets of Islamism, are generally perceived as "symbols" or "instruments" in what is perceived first and foremost as a battle to impose a particular cultural-religious identity'.

The radical vocabulary and the moral legitimacy it guarantees explain why Islam/ism finds important support across the Western Left. The 'Western fear to a decentring telos' (Kipnis 1989: 163) is certainly part of the logic that sustains the demonisation of Islam and the current anti-terrorist political panic, as well as the naive and manipulative Western claims about women from Islamic traditions which should 'be free like me'¹² as Eisenstein (2002: 82) points out. However, the opposition to this imperialist logic should not be necessarily conducing to the endorsement of Islam/ism as a blanket resisting force. Winter (2006: 25) observes that 'the mobilisation of Islam in the name of national liberation or "multiculturalism" (...) has been accepted by the Western antiracist left' and that this 'acceptance of "left-wing" mobilisation of religion' has hindered the identification of Islamism as an extreme right movement but also contributed to the legitimisation of women's oppression in the name of cultural and political liberation. Questioning the positive reception of the 'liberating' or 'feminist' potential of Islamism by the progressive Western intelligentsia, Winter points out that 'one would be hard pressed to find a feminist advocating

¹² Scott makes a similar point when she argues that in the case of the French feminist critics of the veil, what was sought by the feminists who got entangled in the controversy was not equality with men or the issue of individual political rights; rather, Scott argues, the removal of the veil was seen as making Muslim women the equals of French women, 'free to experience what is taken to be the superior French way of conducting gendered relationships' (Scott 2005: 122).

that we seek to determine whether French FN ideology could be used to support feminist political struggles' (2006: 16) and wonders why 'should we rush to embrace the extreme Right when it is dressed up in an "ethnic" cloak?' (ibid: 295). Provocative as it may sound in the first place given a certain tendency within Left milieus to represent Islam/ism as a progressive force in the European public sphere, Winter's questioning of the uncritical Left endorsement of the political uses of Islam points to larger questions about the identification and definition of 'progressive causes' pursued by 'regressive movements'.

Majid's 'dehegemonizing' critique is aimed not only against Western cultural imperialism but also against 'false Islamic orthodoxy'. Nonetheless, battling against this front also comes with implications because questions about orthodoxy and reform cannot be isolated as theological problems *per se*, since they always come tied up with issues about intellectual authority and political power. The first problem that can be identified, is the separation of 'real' Islam from the 'false orthodoxy' and the 'obscurantist practices', as noted above, or in different words the purification of Islamic faith from certain of its cultural manifestations. Such separation, however, cannot take place under the same banner of self-defence of 'indigenous' culture. One wonders if Islam has any meaning, any life at all, outside the cultural context in which it is experienced specifically by these 'indigenous' cultures which must on the one hand be defended and on the other accused of misunderstanding the true message of Islam. The second problem, which cuts across all efforts of reform, or interpretation, of Islamic traditions is one of authority. As Joseph (1998: 37) asks pertinently 'Who gets to say what the 'true Islam' is? Who gets to decide what is the "usable" past?'. The 'recovery of a long obfuscated egalitarian Islam together with an effort to reconceptualise a progressive Islam for the future' as proposed by Majid (1998a: 323) alludes this fundamental clash about the correct interpretation of the sacred texts or traditions and their true meaning or message, which is, in the last instance, an antagonism about the ideological control of society and about the legitimation of power. The clash then between conservatives and the preservation of tradition as it stands, fundamentalists and their literal approach on religious texts and practices, and reformers and their opening to the multiplicity of meanings and experiences, as exemplified here by the questions of women's status and gender relations, is not a socially-independent theological matter but a condition enabled by the de-traditionalisation of Islam. The very emergence of Islamic and Islamist feminism is an effect of this process of de-traditionalisation.

Moaddel (1998: 127) notices in his account of the ideological context of the rise of modernist and fundamentalist positions on gender relations in Islam, that whilst the elemental values and principles of any religion formulate its views on gender relations, the religious commands in terms of practices (e.g. the veil) are formed within the context of specific discursive fields in a particular historical period. Moaddel's observation is of great importance with regards to the attempt of those who seek to reform Islam and those who engage in the analyses of these reforming efforts: whether the issue is women's position, the liberation from postcolonial capitalism or the opposition to Western cultural domination, this cannot be conceptualised or explained by reference to theological debates. In a more radical vein, Cliteur (2011) questions even the very possibility of reform based on 'interpretation' of holy texts. He argues that those Islamic reformers who perceive the problems arising from the holy texts as essentially problems of interpretation, fail to demystify the idea of scriptural authority itself, since 'the problem is not that people give a conservative interpretation of religion that is "per se" pristine and incorruptible, but that people think that they can defer their modern consciousness to ancient texts' (2011: 165). Therefore, it is the reference to the context – intellectual and political – which gives meaning and shape to those theological debates, or in different words, enables their specific articulations. These issues need also to be seen as a result of a particular historical period, of a specific political occurrence, that of the long *durée* of modernity which is marked by the end of colonial rule, the disappointment about the failed promises of 'liberation' of postcolonial regimes, and above all, the dissemination of ideas such as equality, freedom, liberation and so on. In different words, the need to reform, radicalize or reconceptualise Islam – as the debate about women's status exemplifies – is the product of the processes of modern subjectivation: it is the modern ideas about the subject, its individual and collective rights to autonomy, liberation or emancipation which motivate Muslim men and women to look for those ideals or concepts, or at least their potential, in Islam. The question of subjectivation, the kind of subjectivity enabled by different discursive traditions – secular/liberal or Islamic – has been the object of another important debate concerning the relationship between women and Islam. In opposition to Islamic feminism and Majid's radicalism, which despite the general postmodern political sensitivities they endorse (cultural difference, pluralism, multiculturalism, polycentricity etc.) are conceptualised on the basis of modern, secular categories such as those of resistance and autonomy, there is a parallel, more sceptical, more radical and more consistently poststructuralist theoretical attempt

addressing the relationship between women, feminism and Islam. The shift operated by this sceptical trend from the category of resistance to that of docility and the subsequent reconceptualisation of Islamic agency it proposes are the object of analysis of the next chapter.

Chapter Two

Chapter Two

From Resistance to Docility: Feminism and the Dilemmatics of Islamic Agency

- 2.1 Introduction: religion as a category of political agency
- 2.2 From victimisation to resistance: conceptual shifts in the semantics of the veil
- 2.3 Feminism and its 'Others': postsecular feminism and the end of oppositional consciousness
- 2.4 The politics of piety and the docile female subject

2.1 Introduction: religion as a category of political agency

The production of subjectivity – or political agency – is symptomatic of the debate about feminism, its role, its history and its future. The kind of subject – unified, multiple, 'Western', 'Third World', 'Islamic', 'postcolonial', 'subaltern' and so on - determines the kind of political questions we can ask: i.e. questions regarding the political stance towards power (submission, resistance, docility, emancipation), the constitution of consciousness (oppositional or affirmative), or the subscription to specific political projects (secular, postsecular or religious). As we have seen in the previous chapter, Islamic and Islamist feminist, despite their important differences, share a common idea about women's agency: the Muslim woman of their writings is an empowered political being resisting the hegemony of intellectual or political authorities, whether this is cultural imperialism, Western feminism, or the conservative ulamas and their followers. Seen as reformers or new interpreters of Islamic faith, as guardians of national, traditional, cultural and religious identity, or as opponents of Western cultural imperialism, women are constructed as dynamic, empowered, resisting agents. Agency or subjectivity then, and in particular that of women, emerges as the main battlefield where the Muslim political subject is contested, deconstructed and reconstructed, orientalised and de-orientalised, or in one word politicised, in contemporary critical social theory.

This chapter identifies and examines the discursive frameworks within which agency is conceptualised by those who study the nexus of relationship between gender, feminism and Islam. It looks at the interaction between the discursive frameworks employed on the one hand, by those who see the practice of Islam as a constraint placed upon women's life and emancipation,

thus risking to reproduce stereotypical images of Muslim women as necessarily passive and deprived of ability of action; and on the other, by those who see the practice of Islam and the acceptance of certain gender discriminatory practices it entails as potential forms of subversive actions, as well as by those who see piety as a distinct, Islamic-specific form of agency.

Conceptually, the possibility of thinking women's political agency in terms of adherence to gender discriminatory practices and ideas emanating from a religious discursive tradition as well as the shift of theoretical interest from secular to postsecular or straight forward religious forms of subjectivation, relies on the detachment of political agency from its secular lineage, but also from the politics of grand narratives of emancipation and its subsequent re-orientation to forms of micro-politics where religious expression holds a prominent place. This development within feminist theory, i.e. the turn to the 'politics of everyday life' as mentioned in the previous chapter, reconsidered the content and orientation of politics. From the moment the unified feminist subject comes into question and the subscription to the idea of universal patriarchy and the necessity to overthrow the unequal relations of power it sustains and enables no longer enjoys unanimity, political action as well as political agency, or subjectivity, is re-opened to definition. Therefore a new space opens up, a new hermeneutics, within which questions of consciousness and will (i.e. what women want), agency (i.e. how women act) and content (what counts as a political act) become a new stake in which religion, and in our case Islam, takes a significant role. The shift towards agency in feminism was hailed as 'one of the most important areas of work for feminist sociologists' (Roseneil 1995: 200). Bracke goes as far as to term this shift as a 'turn to agency' (2008: 62) and she identifies three main forms in which interest in agency has been pursued: first, the focus on agency as a reaction to scholarship looking at structural power relations, which can be questioned for its tendency to produce a limited understanding of agency void of structural constraints and conditions. Second, the focus on agency as a mode of integration into modernity, which can be criticised for making agency essential in the recognition of other people's humanity and for turning agency into a certain modern form, or epistemic structure employed to integrate categories of people into modern, liberal, secular subjectivity. Third, the focus on agency by questioning the necessary link between resistance and agency, which is often assumed rather than examined. The 'turn to agency' is not unrelated to another germane shift in sociological and anthropological scholarship, especially of feminist orientation, namely to what has been labelled as the 'affective turn' (Halley and Ticineto Clough 2007). Within this approach

affects – with religious affects holding an important place - are thought as co-constitutive of social and cultural phenomena and a main concern is ‘to understand how (individual and collective) emotions are generated, regulated and structured in particular contexts, and how these in turn are linked with the sustenance, reproduction and/or contestation of a particular order’ (Fadil 2009: 441).

Politically, what enabled this new shift in reconceptualising agency in religious terms and in re-interpreting abidance by religious practices as not necessarily politically restraining, but on the contrary as politically enabling, was the reaction to the hegemonic discursive framework of Muslim woman as victim of her culture: stereotyped as covered, subservient and docile in a culture in which women are often thought to be secondary, passive and manipulated agents, the Muslim woman has been the ideal example of powerlessness and victimisation. It is in reaction to this monolithical and monosemantic image that the studies focusing on resistance emerged. The new discursive framework of ‘resistance’ or ‘empowerment’ develops as a reaction to this stereotype. The use of concepts such as ‘resistance’ and ‘agency’ was a political strategy which provided both Muslim women discussing the signification of their own acts and the researchers studying Muslim women as social agents, with a new powerful image capable of countering the discourse of Muslim’s women victimisation. Since E. Said many authors engaged in the analysis of the intersection of gender and Orientalism which engendered both the stereotypical image of Muslim women as the embodiment of an oppressive religion (Kabbani 1986; Lutz 1991) as well as in the analysis of the way colonialism established its ‘superiority’ in contrast to the ‘inferiority’ of non-Western cultures by special reference to their patriarchal practices from which women needed to be rescued by the ‘modernising’ enterprise of the colonial rule (Abu-Lughod 2002; Ahmed 1992; Lazreg 1994; Mohanty 1984; Spivak 1987). Since the colonial times civilisational discourses rely on gender assumptions turning women into a barometer of civilisation and barbarity, into the living content of signifiers such as progress, modernisation or backwardness and of the binaries in which they are entangled (Abu-Lughod 1998; Deeb 2010; Moallem 2005; Saliba 2002). But more recently as well, women were used as a signifier of these same categories: complemented with neo-Orientalist overtones of national or civilisational threat, the stereotype which sees the Muslim woman ‘as alien, subversive and unpatriotic even when she embodies nineteenth - and early twentieth-century European ideals of modesty and self-control’ (Bruck 2008: 64) and undoubtedly ‘believed to be forced to veil by their community and husbands’

(Lorasdagi 2009a: 455) was re-enacted to animate and legitimate conservative political theses such as the infamous 'clash of civilizations' and military interventions in the form of 'war on terror'. The image of the Muslim women as victims in immediate need of 'liberation' or 'modernisation' from the West was resurrected with great success, especially after 09/11 in the USA. This specific view was also quite unproblematically embraced by certain feminist milieus (Hirschkind and Mahmood 2002), but also met with considerable opposition which denounced the equally 'masculinist-militarist mentality' of both the 09/11 attack and the 'war on terror' response (e.g. Agathangelou and Ling 2004; Eisenstein 2002, MacKinnon 2006).

Nonetheless, as the two contrasting paradigms, i.e. Orientalism and anti-Orientalism have recourse to the same categories to define the meaning of agency, that is the binaries of activity and passivity, destabilisation and consolidation of social norms and so on, and as both paradigms are driven by equally, albeit opposing, ideological-political motives, it is questionable to what extent the anti-Orientalist logic can overcome or bypass the profoundly modernist presuppositions of contemporary political thinking. However, if the difference in the definition of agency in the two opposing discursive frameworks is ambiguous, what on the contrary seems clearly unambiguous is the centrality of gender in the contemporary discussion about Muslim subjectivity. Gender is the primary field within which the difference of Islam is claimed by essentialists, e.g. total war against an incommensurable entity, and anti-essentialists alike, e.g. total inability of understanding Islam in terms of any 'universal' social science and therefore necessity of accounting for Islam in terms of its own discursive logic.

In a nutshell then, what the chapter aims to do is to look at the shift in narratives, or discursive frameworks, in which women's political subjectivity is discussed: from Orientalism to anti-Orientalism, from victimisation to resistance, or from submission to empowerment and further to the emergence of piety as a form of political agency. To do so, the chapter focuses, firstly, at the resignification of veiling in the recent years since the veil stands throughout modernity as the most emblematic symbol of Islamic religiosity and Islamic distribution of gender roles and power relations. Secondly, the chapter moves to assess how this alteration in the way religiosity is conceptualised prompted debates about agency conceived in nonsecular terms and how the further depreciation of the grand narratives of emancipation – or even negative dialectics – gave rise to postsecularism as the new politics of the Left and the 'end of oppositional consciousness'.

Finally, the chapter addresses the implications of the conceptualisation of agency, or political subjectivity, in Islamic terms and of the full detachment of the humanist-cum-secular tradition of the social politics of equality, as exemplified by Saba Mahmood's ethnography of women's piety movement in Egypt.

2.2 From victimisation to resistance: conceptual shifts in the semantics of the veil

No other symbol¹³ of Islamic religiosity has been more emblematic in recent debates regarding Islamic revivalism and the emergence of a new public Muslim subjectivity than the veil.¹⁴ Both symbol of feminine oppression and liberation, of passivity and resistance, the veil has become a synecdoche for the politicisation of Islam by its adherents and by those who seek to question the political boundaries and allocation of spaces in the contemporary secular world. Much has been written on the question of the veil whilst its meaning and political significance have been the object of intense debates across disciplines. It goes without saying that the aim of this section is not to discuss the veil in detail, or to offer a summary of its history, multiplicity and manifestations related to ethnic and sectarian allegiances connoted by the different head covers in Islam. My aim is to illustrate an intellectual trend within feminist literature analysing Islam: the redefinition of political agency or subjectivity and the transformation of discursive frameworks and strategies which condition the meaning of how, when and why women act in ways that seem conducive to their subordination in sex discriminatory practices.

The veil, 'as the dominant signifier for Islam' (Dwyer 1997: 7) and its array of meanings is a privileged vehicle if one wishes to trace the shift in the semantics of religious allegiance and the redefinition of Muslim political subjectivity. It is the shift of attention from the monosemantic understanding of the veil as a symbol of submission *only* to the consideration of its polysemy,

¹³ This is not to suggest that I take the interpretation of the veil as symbol for granted, but rather that I engage with these debates which themselves focus on the veil as a sign. Mahmood (2006: 343 and note 50) criticises a dominant trend in the current literature in which veiling is explained either with reference to instrumental reasons (e.g. as a 'passport' to the public sphere, as for example in the case of Islamic feminism in the previous chapter) or as a sign (e.g. resistance to the hegemony of Western cultural values, or as a sign of women's oppression or of the backwardness of Islam). What seems to be missed out in such debates, according to Mahmood, is the centrality of veiling in Islamic doctrine or the form of ethical practice it represents.

¹⁴ Here I alternate between the terms 'veil' and 'headscarf' on purely stylistic grounds. Therefore, in this case, the use of the word veil does not seek to convey 'fantasies of invisibility and visibility, darkness and light, blindness and full sightedness' as suggested by Scott (2005: 118) in her discussion about the substitution of the term veil for the term headscarf in the French 'affaire du foulard'.

whether as an ‘unstable’ (Scott 2005: 117) or ‘overdetermined’ (Dwyer 1997: 8) signifier that undergirds the logic which sees the veil as a tool of empowerment or as a vehicle of resistance, and which relates it to the rise of the new hermeneutics of female agency within the Islamic discursive tradition. Invested in the meaning of the veil are political (e.g. ‘what counts as a political act?’, ‘is emancipation and/or autonomy a universal desire?’, ‘is patriarchy a cross-cultural phenomenon?’), epistemological (e.g. ‘is religion a valid modality of knowledge?’, ‘is critique only secular?’, ‘does the divide between reason and faith need to be revised?’) and pedagogical (e.g. ‘how to decolonise or de-patriarchalise knowledge, history or modes of appreciation?’) questions which are symptomatic of the general intellectual shift in academic and political cultures in the West in the postcolonial and postmodern era.

The empowering *side* effects of the enforcement of sex-discriminatory practices, for instance the use of the veil as an instrument to ensure access to the public sphere, i.e. the ‘distortion’ of the use and meaning of such practices or their resisting potential, has been an venue of analysis systematically explored by feminist scholars. Their approaches threw new light to the blanket monosemantic consideration of such practices and moved the discussion towards the understanding of strategies at play when women seem to act against their feminist interests. Certainly, a specific use of the veil by the agents meets the ascription of veiling as a strategy and as a coping mechanism employed by women to ‘bargain with patriarchy’ (Kandiyoti 1988) whether this is resisting, adapting or accommodating possibilities and expectations, coming to terms with paradoxes and overwhelming dilemmas (MacLeod 1993),¹⁵ or consciously ‘converting’ the tools of oppression into tools of emancipation. Resistance to specific configurations of power across the Islamic cultures and societies has been a line of analysis systematically explored by anthropologists – whether this resistance takes a ‘passive’ form, like the cases of Bedouin women who resist against the domination of the elder (Abu-Lughod 1990), or like the Iranian women who ‘construct’ the discourse of morality in relation to the listener of their narratives (Bauer 1985); or whether it takes an ‘active’ or even ‘militant’ form, like the Tadjik women who adopt a ‘popular’, ‘private’ version of Islam against the imposition of Soviet culture (Tadjbakhsh 1998), the recruitment of Egyptian women to the Islamist movements (Duval 1998), or through the demands

¹⁵ MacLeod (1993) sees in the adoption of the veil by working women in Egypt a strategy to overcome the ‘double-bind’ created by the conflicting demands of economic need and gender ideology which opposes work. Veiling in this case reflects on the one hand the dilemma created by this conflict, and on the other legitimises women who need to work since they can still claim traditional respect.

for social rights in Saudi Arabia (Doumato 1992). It is important to point out though that from these practices or attitudes of resistance, it is the 'active', 'militant' one that seems more problematic as it is more susceptible to the entrapment of women to the new dilemmas formed by the nexus of religion, state, nationalism, postcoloniality or globalisation (Yuval Davis 1997), as the shift from Islamic to Islamist feminism discussed in the previous chapter shows. Common line in these approaches is the analysis of resistance not only as a new way to approach Islamic societies, but as an entirely new field that emerges from the reversal of perspective from the study of power to the study of resistance. In this block of studies the focus is shifted from the question of the nature of power to the forms of resistance and what they can reveal about power itself, in other words, the concept of resistance is seen as a tool for the diagnosis of power.

The recognition of precisely this ambiguity, i.e. that the veil can be both restricting and emancipating, within the anthropological studies focusing on strategies of resistance, is a central element that tends to be understated in more contemporary accounts. The polysemous character of the veil as a vehicle for the exploration of the complexity surrounding gender relations of domination and subordination is reduced again to a reversed monosemantic image: from the unambiguously submissive Muslim woman of Orientalism we move to the unambiguously liberated through her veil Muslim woman of anti-Orientalism. Lorasdigi's account is a characteristic example of the abundant literature which followed the discussion about the veil, especially after 'l' affaire du foulard' in France. Under the indicative titles 'The Headscarf and "Resistance Identity-Building": A Case Study on Headscarf-Wearing in Amsterdam' (2009a) and 'The Headscarf and Emancipation in the Netherlands' (2009b), Lorasdigi explains that the overwhelming majority of the participants in her study felt emancipated by wearing their headscarves, that 'expectedly, all of the interviewees rejected the idea that the headscarf is a symbol of oppression of women' (2009a, 458) and that 'the headscarf is used as a tool for self-definition and self-empowerment in public, which, they [the interviewees] believed, brings their liberation' (2009b: 331). The recognition of modern veiling as a liberating practice is also certified via its break with the traditional Islam represented by the 'passive mothers' of the young veiled participants (2009a: 460). Even if Lorasdigi attempts to balance her account of the social significance of veiling in her conclusion, by stating that her study 'aimed to show that the headscarf is a multifaceted and complicated issue that cannot be solely reduced to Muslim women's emancipation' and that it is hard to decide when the donning of the veil is a matter of

choice due to religious education and family socialisation (ibid), the presentation and analysis of the findings does not point to the polysemy of the veil, but on the contrary heavily privileges its interpretation as an ‘instrument of resistance-identity building’ and tool of liberation.

It is natural then to ask why and under what circumstances the recovered polysemy of the veil – as an example for exploring the dynamics of gender relations of power – retreats to the monosemantic, albeit politically powerful, representation of liberation. Or how the rhetoric ‘which posits Islam as the only context in which women can truly be free from oppression’ (Deeb 2010: 97) achieves its eminence in contemporary accounts of gender relations. Looking at the adoption of the veil as a political statement and the ways in which the engagement in the rhetoric of political resistance articulates the lives of women and the relationship with their bodies can perhaps illuminate this development. Invested in the meaning of the veil is the symbolism of the West versus Islam division of the world by Islamists and Islamophobes alike. As feminist authors of different theoretical and ethical convictions observe unanimously, veiling is instrumental in conveying political meanings: ‘it is the female face of a politicized Islam’ (Winter 2006: 289); ‘it underscores the insurmountability of boundaries between Islamic and Western civilization’ (Gole 1996: 1) and ‘the existing asymmetry between Islamic and Western societies and their distinct organization of spaces and lifestyles’ (ibid: 52); ‘it stands for everything that is thought to be wrong with Islam: porous boundaries between public and private and between politics and religion (Scott 2005: 110); or even ‘it continues to assert the kind of religiosity that is incommensurable with, and inimical to, those forms of public sociability that a secular-liberal polity seeks to make normative’ (Mahmood 2005: 75). As the analysts of the political semantics of the veil observe, both wearing it and discarding it in different situations can be seen as symbolising political struggle and its enforcement can be as empowering as its ban (Al-Hassan Golley 2004; El Guidi 1999; Mir Hosseini 1996a). In the same perspective, it has also been recognised that empowerment can be achieved through secular and Islamic avenues likewise (Holt 1996).

However, what attributes to the veil its overdetermined contemporary identity of ‘resistance’, ‘emancipation’ or ‘liberation’, which tends to obfuscate the more obvious side of coercion and subordination, is the association of the veil with the politics of postcoloniality and the rejection of the ‘West’. Even erudite and astute approaches of the semantics of the veil seem to prioritise the

aspect of resistance and liberation over the one of submissiveness and coercion. El Guidi, for instance, recognises that the signification of the veil is entirely dependent on the socio-historical context, that 'it does not represent a return to any traditional dress form and has not tangible precedent' (1999: 148) and that the modern donning of the veil 'is neither a return to an early veil nor a return to any early Islamic community' (1999: 168). El Guidi rightly upholds that dress embodies a sociomoral code and serves as a central vehicle for this message (ibid), but she opts for the analysis of only *one* sociomoral code, the one of anti-Western ideology and postcolonial rhetoric. This prioritisation though, comes with a price: even if it is true that 'the veil is now a symbol of resistance against the legacy of foreign occupation, against the contemporary occupation of Palestinian land, and against the local unelected regimes' (El Guidi p. 173),¹⁶ it is also true that this focus misses the complexity generated by the intersection of the political ideology of anti-Westernism and gender power relations. As Gole observes, 'with the act of veiling women perform a political statement against Western modernism,¹⁷ yet at the same time they seem to accept the male domination that rests their own invisibility and their confinement to the private sphere' (Gole 1996 p. 136). Just like the case of Majid's Islamist feminism in the previous chapter, women's emancipation or autonomy seems to get engulfed by the 'larger' political causes – national liberation, anti-imperialism, anti-colonialism, anti-Westernism – and to be secondary to superior entities, such as the nation, the community, Ummah and so on.

The same problem, the obliteration of the issue of coercion or submission, emerges with approaches of female religiosity which put the emphasis instead of the category of resistance to the increasingly prominent category of empowerment.¹⁸ It is therefore no surprise that the Islamicisation of gender relations is viewed almost as an opportunity by Mir-Hosseini, who maintains that 'we need to shift from the ways in which Sharia-based ideology is oppressive to women and to the ways in which its embedded contradictions are empowering to women' (1996a:

¹⁶ Yet, more recent accounts suggest that the veil lost its counter-hegemonic potential in the last three decades, at least in Turkey. Cindoglu and Zenciri (2008) argue that: 'On the one hand, the headscarf question lost its democratic discourse by losing its agents, i.e. individual women, through the transformation of the assumed agency from individual citizens to the wives of the political elite' and on the other because women's issues 'are always discussed within the parameters of the national imaginary' (ibid: 804) and therefore as subjugated to the assumed 'greater' causes.

¹⁷ Even if, according to Kaya (2000), this rejection of modernity is essentially a formalist one.

¹⁸ It is important to note though that thinking through the category of empowerment does not necessarily lead to relativist or 'positive' accounts of Islamicisation of gender power relations. For instance, working through the category of empowerment enables Gole to interpret the voluntary adoption of Islamic stigmata, such as the veil, as an identitarian process which turns 'an attribute of potential public discredit, into a subaltern advantage' (2003: 817) and a symbol 'of submissiveness to one of assertiveness' (ibid: 810) and which serves as a vehicle of personal and collective radical transformation of consciousness from Muslimness into Islamism (Gole 2004: 113-4).

147) or that ‘many Muslim women have chosen the veil as the symbol of Islamification and have accepted it as the public face of their revivalist position’, and that ‘for them the veil is a liberating, and not an oppressive force’, as Afshar (1996b: 124) suggests. The Muslim woman that emerges as a result of this specific feminist scholarship privileging the ‘resistance identity-building’ and emancipatory choice of donning the veil is an empowered gender-conscious human being, capable of challenging Western and Islamic, political and discursive authorities alike. However, these analyses which see the veil as a tool of empowerment and praise its empowering effects fail to recognise in veiling a practice that is a means of social control in the first place. Naturally, context matters before one can judge on passivity and agency or oppression and resistance. Nevertheless, the understanding of the adoption or enforcement of sex-discriminatory practices as ‘creative alternatives’ tends to overstate the element of choice and agency and to completely disregard the element of coercion, whether overt and formal as in the case of illiberal regimes, or covert under the banner of ‘choice’.¹⁹ As Sahgal and Yuval-Davis (1992: 9) note ‘being active in a religious movement allows women a legitimate space in a public sphere which otherwise might be blocked to them and which in certain circumstances they may be able to subvert for their purposes’ whilst for women of racial and ethnic minorities it can provide a language to counter hegemonic racist culture. Overall, however, the effect of such practices ‘has been very detrimental to women, limiting and defining their roles and activities and actively opposing them when they step out of the preordained limits of their designated roles’ (ibid). Even more, what is left unquestioned in the rhetoric of Islamic gender emancipation is a core issue in relation to the preconditions governing the access to the public sphere: i.e. if public life was equally accessible to both sexes or if individual life was more autonomous – that is, if women were less constrained to make informed decisions about the pursuit of meaningful lives with religious allegiance being only one option among others – in one word, if public life, was more *secular*, the veil would not be a prerequisite for women to access it.

¹⁹ See for instance Moghadam’s (2006: 275) caustic uptake of the overemphasis on seeing gender-based restraining practices as a ‘matter of choice’:

Paris, and Geneva, one frequently finds the following scene, especially in the summer: an Arab couple is strolling, he in jeans or shorts and a T-shirt, sometimes even wearing a baseball cap; she fully enveloped in a black veil, her vision so obscured that when crossing the street she holds on to the man for dear life. On a visit to the Tunisian resort city of Hammamet, I was mesmerized by the sight of a heavily veiled woman (not Tunisian) standing on the beach, filming her husband as he swam happily in the cool waters of the sea. (...) thus, she chooses to dress in a heavy black veil in the summer heat and refrain from swimming, while he chooses to dress reasonably and enjoy a swim.

As explained above, the discursive framework of resistance/empowerment is partially a reaction to the hegemony of the stereotype of Muslim woman as victim of her culture and partially an effect of internal developments within feminist literature, i.e. the impact of postmodernism in feminism itself and the questioning of universal categories such as 'woman'. Having said this, it is important to note that both positions, i.e. the one that seeks to liberate Muslim women from their subordination to male patriarchy and focuses on strategies of resistance, and the one that seeks to identify instances of female agency in the adoption of gender discriminatory practices, are the effects of feminist concerns on political theory and on the study of Islam in the first place. The split between these two positions, is evident in the - subtle nonetheless important - divergence in the way that the discursive framework of resistance/empowerment developed. Although these are considerably overlapping terms, the position which prioritises resistance emanates from the tradition of critical theory's normative critique, whilst the one that revolves around the concept of empowerment stems from the antifoundationalism of poststructuralism. Even if in the literature which engages with the relationship between gender and Islam the terms 'resistance' and 'empowerment' are used interchangeably, it is important to distinguish between them. Thus, *an act of resistance* presupposes conscious - albeit not always conspicuous - rejection of the dominant narrative of gender discrimination. On the contrary, *empowerment* does not necessarily acknowledge subordination as an *a priori* problem and therefore does not focus on the wholesale rejection, but tends to oscillate between dismissal and conditional acceptance of submission through the appropriation and 'feminine' usage of the dominant gender ideology in Islam. Therefore, whereas in the first case the focus is explicitly an act of subversion, in the second, the focus is ambiguously somewhere between subversion and accommodation. Deriving from the Foucauldian approach which sees power as productive and therefore not solely constraining but also enabling, the concept of empowerment has been paving the way from the feminism of resistance, where oppositional consciousness and ideology critique holds a central role, to postsecular feminism where agency can be reconceptualised without presupposing autonomy, as discussed in the section below.

2.3 Feminism and its 'Others': postsecular feminism and the 'end of 'oppositional consciousness'

Recent publications such as those of Mahmood in 2005, Butler in 2008 and Braidotti in 2008 have been inviting to the opening of feminism toward new understandings of the constitution of the feminine self and feminist consciousness through the lenses of a particular critical angle: through the repudiation of secularism as cultural and political ethos. The (im)possibility of a cross-cultural feminist ethics, the accommodation of allegiances at odds with the feminist norms, the critique of the unitary subject of Western, First World, liberal or secular feminism, or in different words the status of historical and cultural specificity in feminist accounts of the subject, are themes with a long history within the feminist field. Although earlier critiques of the unitary feminine subject have been discussing the accommodation of allegiances at odds with the feminist precepts, the new element shared by these more recent positions is the shift of feminism to the 'non-rational', the 'non-secular' or the 'religious'. Operating in the intersection of postcolonial and postmodern frameworks, these approaches seem to converge in two points. The first point is the repudiation of secularism which is used as a metaphor of Western categories of sociological knowledge and political organisation. This is done, on the one hand, through a particular understanding of the term's meaning in which secularism becomes a substitute for Eurocentrism, racism and state violence. On the other, the critique of the 'secular' (the expression was coined by Talal Asad in his *Formations of the Secular*, 2005 and is discussed in chapter three) is operated through the re-examination of the relationship between religion and agency in order to demonstrate how the categorisation of religion shapes the practice and conclusions of the feminist engagement with religion and how situating religious agency in its own 'grammar' makes the secular assumptions of feminist critical social theory manifest. Following from this, the second point shared by these approaches is the discussion about degrees of autonomy and self-determination which are not only political, at least in the sense of progressive politics. In this perspective the totalising narratives of resistance or emancipation are replaced by anti-narratives of empowerment and the non-reflective or embodied understanding is prioritised over the intellectualised understanding of self-consciousness.

What is at stake, at least since the poststructuralist turn, is the applicability or the validity of the analysis of Western feminism to non-Western, or otherwise to non-modern traditions. The difference of the postcolonial, Third World or minoritarian 'Other' has been raised in relation to

various contexts and in numerous occasions. However, the intervention of postsecular feminism comes to defend the difference of a new 'Other', the 'religious Other'. In the postsecular feminist accounts, the particular subjectivity of this 'religious Other' must not only be recognised as *de facto* political, but in some ways it must be acknowledged as an example of a more flexible model of subjectivity with an openness to spiritual sensitivities, an ability that the progressive political subject seems not to possess. This 'religious Other' whose subjectivity is thought as being suppressed by the dominant secular culture and the kind of subjectivity it supports is not to be feared or rejected, but in many ways, is thought to be much more open to the possibilities of alternative, happier futures in comparison to the outdated and melancholic secular subject.

I focus here on the recent works of three prominent feminist theorists which can be seen as working within the postsecular paradigm according to the criteria set above, namely Judith Butler, Rosi Braidotti and Saba Mahmood. This selection of authors does not of course claim to be exhaustive of their positions and arguments, which, as it will become apparent through the analysis, point to different conclusions. But I hope that it will demonstrate that their conjoint theoretical moves and break-throughs, have important political and theoretical implications, which do not eventually favour the formulation of a more pluralistic account of agency or political subjectivity, but on the contrary, they lead to its negation, to the abandonment of the notion of autonomy and, finally, to the neutralisation of the very role of critical social theory.

The postsecular turn toward less reflective, less Kantian in a sense, or more 'embodied' forms of knowledge and consciousness, presupposes a certain intellectual climate, that is the radical critique, if not straight-forward rejection of secularism. One of the most prominent examples of the postmodern feminist engagement with the critique of secularism is Butler's 2008 article '*Sexual Politics, Torture and Secular Time*' where the assaults on freedom are viewed as a result of a specific understanding of time, i.e. secular time. In this text Butler frames relatively separate issues, grouped by broad reference to gender and fused together in an attack against secularism, secular times and modernity. Butler brings together the racist immigration laws in Netherlands, the US military interventions in Middle and Central East, the hypocrite laws prohibiting child adoption to homosexual couples in France, the Pope's anti-Islamic comments and the incidents of torture in Abu-Ghraib and Guantanamo and frames them as symptomatic of the domination of secularism as an ideology, as symptomatic of 'certain secular conceptions of history' (Butler 2008:

3). Butler's analysis in terms of empirical underpinning is strikingly similar to the material used by another fierce critique of secularism, Saba Mahmood. Butler's *'j'accuse'* against the secular cultures of today is based partially on the analysis of a particular - clearly neo-Orientalist - text, *'The Arab Mind'*. This work was assigned by US Department of Defence in the 1973 and assumed that there was such a mind and that it could be defined with respect to religious beliefs and specific sexual vulnerabilities of the people of Arab descent, and came to public attention in 2004 when it was linked to the US military officials responsible for the Abu Ghraib scandal who used this document as a source of information. Mahmood's critique (2006) partially relies on the analysis of the Rand Report, *Civil Democratic Islam: Partners, Resources and Analysis*, another neo-Orientalist document released by the conservative research foundation 'National Security Research Division of the Rand Corporation' in which prominent members of the Bush administration were members. The paper claims that the real long term threat for US strategic interests and 'democratic values' comes from traditionalist Islam because of its attitude towards authority and of its modes of reasoning which are causally linked with backwardness and underdevelopment. What is noticeably paradoxical is that these parallel accounts converge in a rather uncomfortable manner: Butler's disapproval of *'The Arab Mind'* as a text subscribing 'to that form of cultural anthropology that treated cultures as self-sufficient and distinctive, which refused the global mixing of cultural and social formations' (Butler 2008: 15) meets Mahmood's endorsement of this precise - isolationist and determining - view of culture, as it will become manifest by the analysis further down.

What is noteworthy in these accounts is their remarkable simultaneous widening and narrowing of the meaning of secularism: on the one hand as noted above, secularism is equated to various forms of state violence or it becomes a substitute for Eurocentrism and all kinds of phobic reactions to difference: torture, war, laws regulating sexual freedoms in Butler's case, and US security and foreign policy concerns in Mahmood's case, are all attributed to an assumed secular ethos, which appears unified and omnipotent, even if these issues belong to categorically different registers and are conditioned by their own specific historicity and politicality. On the other, the empirical material for the construction of such a broad critique which turns secularism into a metaphor of Western categories of sociological knowledge and political organisation is culturally defined either by the US militarist rhetoric and interventions or by the political climate imposed by the weight of this dominant superpower. This way though, our theorists commit a serious

mistake: they take for granted the ideology of ‘secular liberalism’²⁰ – a construct which conflates liberalism with secularism and reduces the one to the other, or considers the one as precondition for the other²¹ – in the form that it was engineered and propagated in recent years. Instead of questioning the uses of terms, ideals and concepts by the ones who manipulate them – as Butler does, for instance, in relation to the term ‘freedom’ – these critical theorists underwrite a specific, considerably limited and instrumentalised version of secularism as formed in the two Bush administration years as the only real or authentic face of secular culture. This becomes even more problematical if one considers the particular form that the ideology of ‘secular liberalism’ acquired in the Bush years owns as much to secularism as to its repudiation and that during those years secular ethics found itself under an unprecedented attack in the modern US history (Kaplan 2004; Linkler 2005). Butler (2008: 14) herself observes that the U.S. ‘civilising mission’, one of the most notable manifestations of the ideology of ‘secular liberalism’ as propagated by the USA, is a ‘cross of secular and non-secular perspectives’.

However, and despite this fierce critique against the ethos of our secular times, Butler’s critique remains animated by the ideas linked to secular-universalist tradition, i.e. freedom, equality, justice (in her own words, ‘my question is not to abandon freedom as a norm, but to ask about its uses’, 2008: 3). Butler’s call for ‘a convergence or alliance’ (2008: 6) between struggles against all forms of discrimination, or ‘solidarity among minorities’ (2008: 21), even if it denies the legitimacy of grand narratives, is undergirded by a certain ‘utopianism’²² and operates within a universalistic account of the subject.²³ Nonetheless it is important to note here that Butler’s engagement with the concept of minority is not the one assumed by multiculturalism, which she thinks as limited because it presupposes ‘the nation-state as exclusive frame of reference, and pluralism as an adequate way of thinking about heterogeneous social subjects’ as well as ‘already constituted communities’ (2009: 31). Butler thinks that the problem we are facing in the post 9/11

²⁰ The term is used by Mahmood (2005) in several occasions throughout the book: 34-35, 73-78, 189-192.

²¹ Connolly (1999: 10) notes that ‘neither is entirely reducible to the other’, whereas Bilgrami (2004: 173) observes that ‘secularism is not dependent on liberalism, since there can be perfectly illiberal forms of secularism’.

²² Hanssen argues that Butler’s position is uncontestably ‘utopian’ in the sense that it is guided by utopian regulative ideas, by ideals – such as universal justice meant as cross-cultural legal and cultural equality of women across the globe – which are yet to be realised. ‘Indeed’ as Hanssen observes ‘to believe in a justice-yet-to-come, as Butler’s poststructuralism does, is not to be adverse to utopianism’ (2000: 251).

²³ In her *Precarious Life* (2004: 20) Butler suggests to ‘start, and to end, with the question of the human’, maybe not in the straight-forward sense of a universal basis of humanity but nonetheless in the more nuanced sense of the ways the human is constituted politically and by way of the vulnerability of our bodies.

era is not simply one of co-existence, but one that concerns the politics of 'differential subject formation within which contemporary maps of power seek (a) to mobilise sexual progressives against new immigrants in the name of a spurious conception of freedom, and (b) to deploy gender and sexual minorities in the rationalisation of recent and current wars' (2009: 32). The point of 'differential subject formation' is where Butler converges with Mahmood, Asad and other postcolonial thinkers who question the universality of the human subject (see chapter three) but also where the conclusions she draws differ as it will be explored in the next section. Having said this however, it is striking that in the body of literature which deals with the question of the Other – feminist, postcolonial, multiculturalist – as examined by this project, it is automatically presupposed that minorities are always oppressed and majorities always oppressive. One would be tempted to ask those critics committed to radical politics or to the imaginary of radical democracy how exactly democracy is to be perceived when majorities (e.g. the historical subject of democratic struggles in modernity par excellence, 'the people' as opposed to the oligarchies of tradition, nobility or transcendental will) are invariably represented as oppressive, hegemonic, anti-egalitarian and so on.

The same goes with another influential text which officially signalled the end of oppositional consciousness and the advent of the affirmative postsecular feminist subject. Braidotti's 2008 article, *In Spite of the Times: The Postsecular Turn in Feminism* is both a cartography of the nascent postsecular movement and a manifesto of its theoretical interventions. For Braidotti, the postsecular trend challenges European feminism because it makes manifest that agency, or political subjectivity, is not antithetical to religious piety or spirituality and that it can be unproblematically conveyed by it. The theoretical argument contests any necessary link between political subjectivity and oppositional consciousness or critique in the negative sense. Therefore, postsecular feminism stands for a 'vision of consciousness that links critique to affirmation instead of negativity' (2008: 2), it 'bears a close link to residual forms of spirituality' (ibid: 15) and it 'casts a new light on the role of spirituality in social and critical theory' (ibid).

Two aspects are significant theoretically as well as politically in Braidotti's manifesto for the analysis attempted here: firstly, the disjunction of political subjectivity and oppositional consciousness and the coupling of political subjectivity with spirituality instead, in order to enable the process of engendering empowering modes of becoming. This is envisioned as a shift of

paradigm which essentially means less emphasis on the dialects of consciousness and more attention on issues of empowerment, positivity and the critique of the negative (ibid: 12). Secondly, a new methodology and role for critical social theory as a series of 'strategies of affirmation', which practically means 'multiple micro-political practices of daily activism or interventions in and on the world we inhabit' (ibid: 16).

From the political point of view, Braidotti remains in a sense still faithful, as Butler does, to radical democratic politics, that is in different words to the enabling of possibility of social change. Braidotti's 'discursive alliance across the different branches of radical critical theory' (Braidotti 2008: 17), also operates within a secular-universalist framework, where issues of freedom, legitimate resistance to inequality, the possibility of collective political action, are the core values. From the epistemological point of view, the grounding of the new postsecular politics in the mainly secular-universalist ideals, seems to suggest that the rupture with secularism is perhaps not as stark as imagined. As McLennan (2010: 11) argues, despite the anti-secularist drive and rhetoric, Braidotti's neo-vitalist version of postsecularism may not be 'nearly as *anti*-secular, nor even as obviously *post*-secular' as desired but most likely, given her allegiance to 'immanent not transcendental theory', 'materialist' version of 'philosophical monism' and the repudiation of secularised versions of theological concepts (Braidotti 2008: 13), as 'an invitation to *better*, more consistent and attractive secular concept - and value-formation' (McLennan 2010: 11). Even more, the category of the postsecular itself is perhaps not as radically open to otherness or anti-Eurocentric as thought by its proponents. Commenting on the ethnocentrism of the postsecular, Leezenberg (2010: 111) argues that 'the postsecular is not a neutral analytical category but a normative notion that has deep secularist and modernist assumptions; besides its empirical and historiographic shortcomings it presupposes a residual secularism and a problematic public-private distinction, and takes the (Western European) liberal nation state as a self-evident framework. It also carries unwarranted, and indeed misleading, assumptions of lineal temporality and a dubious spatial imaginary of societal spheres'. In that sense, both Butler's and Braidotti's critique should be perhaps better viewed as the critique of secularism's tendency to favour the representation of fulfilment of these ideas through institutional means only. Having said this however, it remains the case that Braidotti's sheer dissociation of agency from oppositional

consciousness is a step further from Butler's idea of the nonvoluntaristic subject (1995)²⁴ as she argues that 'political subjectivity or agency need not be aimed solely at the production of radical counter-subjectivities' (Braidotti 2008: 19). The consequences of such theoretical move, when taken to their logical extension, lead potentially to the radical negation of ethical and political autonomy and to the abandonment of the critical role of critical social theory altogether.

2.4 The politics of piety and the docile feminine subject

Year 2005 saw the publication of an important book by S. Mahmood, '*Politics of Piety. The Islamic Revival and the Feminist Subject*', which represents perhaps the most challenging and theoretically sophisticated argument to liberal and to postmodern feminism, including poststructuralist feminism, as it further radicalises the argument about the nature of agency or political subjectivity.²⁵ '*Politics of Piety*' is an analysis of Islamic revivalism through the ethnography of a women's piety movement in the mosques of Cairo, Egypt. The mosque movement had emerged in Egypt in response to what Mahmood's informants described as 'secularisation' or 'westernisation', meant in this context as the marginalisation of religious knowledge as a means of organising daily conduct and its reduction to an abstract system of beliefs (2005: 4). Mahmood's argument departs from an established thesis within the postcolonial literature, i.e. that secular or politically progressive forms of life do not exhaust ways of living meaningfully and richly in the world (Mahmood 2005: xi).

Mahmood challenges the widely-shared feminist assumption that there is something intrinsic to women that should predispose them to resist practices and values such as those conveyed by nonliberal movements like the Islamist ones (2005: 2). Mahmood's thesis is a polemical one as she sets off to challenge the normative liberal assumption that all human beings have an innate desire for freedom, that they all seek autonomy, and that agency is the capacity to realise one's own interests against the constraints of tradition or custom or transcendental will (2005: 8). In a way, she meets Braidotti's 'non-oppositional' agency when she contests the liberal-feminist assumption that agency consists primarily of acts of resisting or subverting social norms and not those that

²⁴ Butler addresses the idea of the 'nonvoluntaristic subject' in her discussion with William Connolly, 'Politics, Power and Ethics: A Discussion between Judith Butler and William Connolly', *Theory and Event*, 24 (2000), http://muse.jhu.edu/journals/theory_and_event/v004/4.2butler.html

²⁵ Mahmood problematised the relationship between resistance and agency and explored the formation of 'pious', ethical subjects in two articles (2001, 2003) which pre-date the publication of *Politics of Piety*.

uphold them (ibid). Mahmood says that she wants to ‘parochialize those assumptions – about the constitutive relationship between action and embodiment, about resistance and agency self and authority - that inform our judgements about nonliberal movements such as the women’s mosque movement’ (2005: 38).

To do so, Mahmood problematises the notion of resistance which is coalescent to the liberal-secular feminist conceptualisation of agency. Resistance to and subversion of norms has been and still is to a great extent the prime trope of feminist analytics of power. She persuasively argues that the feminist literature reproduces resistance as an unproblematic, cross-cultural and in way ‘natural’ predisposition, and in doing so, the feminist analysis fails to capture the agency of those women ‘who may be socially, ethically, or politically indifferent to the goal of opposing hegemonic norms’ (2005: 9). Therefore, Mahmood asks a question with important implications for the conceptualisation of agency: is it at all possible to recognise the existence of a universal category of acts – such as those of resistance – outside of the ethical and political contexts within which such acts obtain their particular meaning and within which their connotations are experienced by the agents? (2005: 9) For Mahmood ‘the category of resistance imposes a teleology of progressive politics on the analytics of power’, and this teleology excludes forms of being in the world that ‘are not necessarily encapsulated by the narrative of subversion and reinscription of norms’ (ibid). Therefore, she questions the binary of subverting-confirming the norms as the site where subjectivity is produced and she proposes to detach the notion of self-realisation of that of autonomous will.

In fact, Mahmood’s theoretical move is a radicalisation of Butler’s poststructuralist critique of the transcendental subject and the repressive models of power.²⁶ She questions Butler’s tendency to conceptualise agency in terms of subversion and resignification of social norms and to locate agency within these operations that resist the dominating and subjectivating modes of power. As Mahmood observes, Butler locates the possibility of agency within the structures of power and suggests that the reiterative structure of norms serves not only to consolidate a particular regime of discourse but also provides the means for its destabilisation. Therefore, there is no possibility of ‘undoing’ social norms that is independent of the ‘doing’ of norms and agency resides within this

²⁶ Indeed the use of Butler’s ‘gender-troubling work to the study of women for whom gender dualism is often remarkably untroubled’, as is the case of the women’s piety movement has been noticed as symptomatic of the effort of feminist critics to adjudicate ‘agency in the midst of rhetorics and practices of religious submission’ (Klassen 2004: 592).

productive reiterability. Although Mahmood recognises that Butler keeps a clear distance from the teleology of emancipatory politics of liberal feminism, by insisting on the contingent and fragile character of the process of resignification/subversion of norms (2005: 20-22) and acknowledges her own debt to the poststructuralist analytics of power, she still thinks that the analysis operates within an agonistic, dualistic framework that norms are either resisted and subverted or consolidated. In different words, Mahmood reproaches the normative subject of poststructuralist feminism for being still a liberatory one, whose agency is conceptualised on the binary model of subordination and subversion. For in doing so, she argues, this approach ignores dimensions of human action whose ethical and political status 'does not map onto the logic of repression and resistance' (2005: 14) and leaves little room for the appreciation of the ways these norms 'are lived and inhabited' by the subjects (2005: 23).

The evidence from Mahmood's ethnographic fieldwork suggests that for the female subjects of the mosque movement in Egypt, acts of subordination have a completely different meaning. According to Mahmood's analysis these subjects cultivate docility, piety and the submission to an external authority as a form of practice of 'positive ethics'²⁷ in order to achieve the self's potentiality. Accounts of piety movements in different locations, however, suggest otherwise: for instance, that piety does not necessarily end with the cultivation of virtuous selves, and that the languages of identity, rights, and equality are not alien to pious Muslims, as argued by Rinaldo (2006) in her ethnography of the pious movement in Indonesia. Or that piety does not always belong to the register of one discursive tradition only, as argued in Deeb's (2006) ethnography of pious Shi'i women in Lebanon which reveals a (clearly gendered) co-dependence of ideas about being pious and about being modern, since it is women who are called to demonstrate their ability to inhabit a moral position related to both states, i.e. piety and modernity. Or that religious spaces, such as the mosque in Britain, allow the women who participate to assert various identities (feminine, political and cosmopolitan) as well as to feel empowered within British society (Bhimji 2009).

²⁷ In her definition of 'positive ethics' Mahmood follows Aristotle via Foucault which allows her to see ethics 'as always local and particular' (2005: 28) and as 'founded upon particular forms of discursive practice, instantiated through specific sets of procedures, techniques and exercises, through which highly specific ethical-moral subjects come to be formed' (2005: 120). In chapter four of *The Politics of Piety* (2005) Mahmood actually maintains that aspects of the Aristotelian tradition have been influential in shaping the pietistic practices of Islam.

Nonetheless for Mahmood, the central distinction in liberal and progressive thought between the subject's real desires and the social conventions is a rather problematical affair as far as Islam is concerned, because in the case of the piety movement, these socially prescribed norms constitute the conditions for the emergence of the self (as a pious subject) and are essential to its realisation (2005: 149). In short, the distinction between desire and social norms is blurred, if not inexistent, in nonliberal cultures, like the Islamic ones. The question for Mahmood then is how is it possible 'to conceive of individual freedom in a context where the distinction between the subject's own desires and socially prescribed performances cannot be easily presumed, and where submission to certain forms of (external) authority is a condition for achieving the subject's potentiality' (2005: 31). To do so, Mahmood moves away from questions formed by the framework of gender to favour questions regarding the embodiment of ethical norms and suggests a three-fold theoretical movement in this direction: firstly, the detachment of agency from progressive politics because the desire of freedom from or subversion of norms is not an innate desire that motivates human beings cross-culturally and independently of their discursive traditions. Secondly, the reformulation of agency in relation to embodied capacities and means of subject formation. Thirdly, to understand self-formation even beyond the effort of granting the Other her epistemological premise and even beyond the attempt of conceiving emancipatory politics outside the narrative of secular history.²⁸ Mahmood goes again a step further from the longstanding feminist line of 'politics of everyday life' to suggest that the transformative project of ethical embodiment is a deeply political practice *per se* since particular conceptions of the self presuppose different kinds of political commitments.

What Mahmood seems to accuse liberal and poststructuralist feminism alike of, is the failure to think historically about the applicability of its norms on the 'Other' in order to understand forms of agency that are not created by the desire of autonomy. For Mahmood, autonomy is not 'an

²⁸ In this line of thought, Hollywood's concerns are indicative of accounts which engage with the tension between emancipation (and its secular lineage) and the rejection of the secular narrative. In her examination of women's agency in religious historiography, for instance, she asks: 'Might there be other emancipatory possibilities in the life worlds rendered visible through alternative histories? Perhaps even more radically, should we assume that agency, as understood within secular historiography, is the only way in which to think about politics (either in the past or in the present)? If it is not, what happens to the very demand to make the other an agent of history that dominates the projects of subaltern and feminist history themselves? And finally, are there ends other than those of emancipation to which we must attend in our desire to understand, explain, and promote the flourishing of women's lives? Might attention to alternative histories help us to see them?' (Hollywood 2004: 527-528).

innate desire that animates all human beings at all times' (2005: 14). She thinks of autonomy as Eurocentric which makes it cross-culturally untranslatable and redefines agency as the way in which one inhabits and practices a culture's norm. This is indeed a bold and truly subverting theoretical move given that all radical or subversive projects – modernist and post-structuralist alike – presume to a greater or lesser degree the moral and political autonomy of the subject. But is it also a profoundly sceptical one which ultimately makes feminist theory, and for that matter, political subjectivity altogether, redundant. Mahmood takes the poststructuralist critique of Western feminism as the site of authentic feminist agency and the concern about culturally specific idioms of subjectivity to the denial of autonomy as a cross-cultural desire and concludes to the non-translatability of ethical experiences and norms. In that sense, Waggoner argues, she risks the introduction of 'a certain kind of cultural and ethical absolutism' (2005: 247). By doing so though, she undermines any possibility of change – a possibility that animates the politics of postsecular feminism – as we all seem trapped into our predetermined and incommensurable subjectivities: in this perspective, the Western female subject is constituted around the expectation of challenging the norms whilst the Muslim female subject is thought as inhabiting the prescribed norms of her own culture. What follows from this logic is not only that cultures shape subjects differently but that there are (pre)determined subjectivities specific to particular cultures, which is a very essentialist, and Orientalist as far as Islam is concerned, view of the Other and the Self.

What seems to stand out as the main difference between poststructuralists like Butler and Braidotti and radical sceptics such as Mahmood is the return to historical specificity, which stands in opposition to Butler's radical contingency as the framework of constitution of the subject. In Mahmood's view, who is following here Talal Asad's work (examined in detail in chapter three), history is re-conceptualised from a sceptical, or even conservative angle, not in order to sustain claims of commonly shared, universal future – as in the case of Marxist and liberal theories of history – but to forge sheer dividing lines between cultures and their futures. The teleology of progress is dismissed in favour of the teleology of insurmountable difference, the teleology of cultural incommensurability, where Islam – or perhaps any other religious difference – is perceived as essentially elusive to any secular epistemology. Even more, the rejection of autonomy as the crucial possibility for reaching the self's potentiality, as the condition for

becoming a subject, seems to lead Mahmood to paradoxical and politically problematic conclusions about the female subject in particular and about historical change in general:

Viewed in this way, what may appear to be a case of deplorable passivity and docility from a progressivist point of view, may very well be a form of agency – one that must be understood in the context of the discourses and structures of subordination that create the conditions of its enactment. In this sense, agentival capacity is entailed not only in those acts that result in (progressive) change but also those that aim toward continuity, stasis and stability (2001: 212).

By denying the ideal of autonomy Mahmood takes postsecular feminism to its logical limits: once the link between oppositional consciousness and agency breaks down, what seems to happen is not the emergence of a new positive and activist political subject and the multiplicity of futures, as Braidotti suggests, but the reduction of subjectivity to the eternally reiterated, unreflective, embodied experience of one's culture and the preservation of the same. What Mahmood seems to suggest is not the merging of modes of appreciation after all, the unity of the cognitive and the intuitive/affective, but their clear attribution to different cultures. This is where Butler's critique of the mentality behind texts like *The Arab Mind*, as 'that form of cultural anthropology that treated cultures as self-sufficient and distinctive, which refused the global mixing of cultural and social formations' mentioned above, meets Mahmood's theoretical enterprise. In a way Mahmood and her radical scepticism - which seems bound to result in deeply conservative political conclusions - departs from the anti-hegemonic position of deconstructing dominant ideologies like secularism or liberalism, to the opposite anti-critical stance, namely to the acceptance of naturalness of social positions and hierarchies of power within a culture. Furthermore, the historicity of practises such as piety and the kind of submission it presupposes are left unexamined - e.g. the modern character of Salafist pietism as well as the particular social and political location of pietist women (Bangstad 2010) – and as an effect of this sociological disengagement important political questions are precluded, for instance questions about the executive power by which divine law is imposed and the role of female piousness movement in upholding and policing moral law (Cooper 2008: 39).

Epistemologically, collapsing the distinction between the social and the individual (rather than contextualising the individual within a particular social structure as an identitarian or communitarian approach would do), between desires and norms, may be informative for explaining, for instance, how this particular pious subject is produced. However, this move is more problematical than assumed given Mahmood's declared anti-humanism and 'double disavowal of the humanist subject', either as recuperating the lost voices of those who are absent from 'hegemonic feminist narratives', or as the recuperation of the members of the mosque movement as 'subaltern feminists' or as the 'fundamentalist Others' of feminism's progressive agenda (2005: 154-155). Mahmood defines her kind of agency not as belonging to the women themselves, but as 'a product of the historically contingent discursive tradition in which they are located' (2005: 32). Following this rationale 'the individual is contingently made possible by the discursive logic of the ethical traditions she enacts' and therefore her activities are 'products of authoritative discursive traditions whose logic and power far exceeds the consciousness of the subjects they enable' (2005: 32). But in this way Mahmood is ironically lead from poststructuralism to the most hard core version of structuralism, almost mirroring Althusser, the difference being that ideology is re-introduced under the positive light of 'discursive tradition'.

Philosophically, the representation of the Other's agency as the incarnation of the normalcy of a given culture is deeply antithetical to the poststructuralist ethics and their radical openness to otherness. As Waggoner observes 'reducing ethics to the embodiment of a culture's norms and by equating it with the status-quo of a culture's traditions, ethical embodiment stands in opposition to an ethics that takes seriously the role of the other. In fact, it entirely excludes consideration of the other' (2005: 258-259). Politically, there are also important implications with Mahmood's radical scepticism and rejection of autonomy as a parochial, Western desire. Indeed, autonomy may not be a universal or natural desire rooted in the human being. One may agree with Mahmood that it is the political tradition of the Enlightenment, or the lived experience of modernity that enables the desire of autonomy, like the experience of the Islamic tradition enables the desire of submission, as indeed all forms of desire (or subjectivity) are discursively organised. From a different angle though, this conclusion, to a certain extent, states the obvious, i.e. that social agents are products of their social environments. The question is, however, what to do – as feminists, as critical social theorists, as engaged academics, or as political beings for whom justice matters – with those social environments which favour or impose conditions of economic,

social, or gender inequality, such as the hierarchical system of gender relations in Islam or anywhere else. Mahmood maintains that this question is impossible to answer and in the end, 'not ours to ask' (2005: 36). And furthermore, she is convinced that the analytical and the political are two modalities of engagement that should not be collapsed into each other (2005: 39, 196). Hence, she does not relate her theoretical insights – that is the location of agency in specific embodied practices that seek to enhance docility and submission – to their political implications.

But even if this is not Mahmood's point, it should be ours, if we wish to maintain a meaningful relationship between social theory, feminist or otherwise, and the social world we investigate. Issues such as the political consequences of the (re)turn to cultural incommensurability or the practical consequences for the lives of those who are judged 'discursively' indifferent to freedom, autonomy or equality are of prime importance for anyone who claims to adopt a critical perspective. In the context of critical social theory where such analyses belong, what seems to be vulnerable is not only the 'Other', which we must be careful not to violently adjust to secular, liberal or Marxist standards, but equally the notion of critique itself and therefore the role of critical social theory. By this I mean to say that if critical social theory needs to be self-critical toward its own assumptions and modes of appreciation, it also needs to be critical in relation to the social world it studies and to the relations of power that underpin its truths. The postsecular move - as 'positive critique' or as the abandonment of radical counter-subjectivities in favour of ethical embodiment - seems both disengaged and disarmed vis-à-vis to questions of inequalities and the ideologies which underpin their alleged 'natural' status.

Chapter Three

Chapter Three

Towards a New Teleology: from Historicism to the Singularity of Cultures

3.1 Introduction: Eurocentrism as a problem

3.2 From postcolonialism to posthistoricism: history in the perspective of the subaltern

3.3 Radical historicism: poststructuralist analytics at cross roads or at a cul-de sac?

3. 1 Introduction: Eurocentrism as a problem

This chapter aims to look deeper into the kind of philosophy of history that underpins the rise of Muslim subjectivity as irreducibly different, and into the theoretical shifts that enabled the conceptualisation of Muslim political agency – either as resisting and constructed around the idea of moral autonomy, or as docile and articulated around the idea of ethical embodiment – as explored through the focus on feminist literature so far. The conclusion reached by the previous chapters suggested that the poststructuralist understanding of Muslim subjectivity indeed points away from the teleology of progressive politics which are thought as imprinting Western characteristics on the Muslim ‘Other’, such as the primacy of intellectualised forms of consciousness over the embodied ones, the constitution of the Self according to the expectation of opposing social norms, the innate desire of autonomy and so on. However, it has also been suggested that this conceptualisation points towards a new kind of radical historicism, which the present chapter scrutinises by looking at its theoretical and ideological underpinnings and by demonstrating its logical impasses and political dilemmas.

In order to understand the origin of ideas around which the Muslim political subject is negotiated and contested between resistance and docility or between consciousness and embodiment it is important to situate them within the larger framework of critique of Eurocentrism, which cuts across the areas of ‘post’ academic knowledge, such as the ones examined by the thesis. For the purposes of our analysis, Eurocentrism here is broadly construed as a set of practices – scientific, cultural, political – which overtly (mostly in the era of colonial imperialism) or tacitly (mostly in the postcolonial era) seek to establish and maintain the primacy of post-Enlightenment European political and epistemic culture at the expense of alternative political systems and epistemologies. As such, the critique of Eurocentrism has encompassed more or less the whole field of humanities and social sciences from the late seventies onwards: sociology, anthropology, feminism,

postcolonialism, decolonial thinking, cultural studies, multiculturalism, race and ethnicity studies, slavery studies, have all been influenced, reconceived, and in some cases entirely articulated, on the basis of the critique of Eurocentrism.²⁹ The critique of Eurocentrism initially developed as a variety of political economy critique with obvious Marxist leanings (such as Amin's prominent book *Eurocentrism*, 1989), and underlines essentially all variants of dependency theory (the seminal example here would be Wallerstein's *The Modern World System*, 1974, 1980, 1989). However, it really gained momentum after its association with the intellectual movement of postmodernism/poststructuralism from which it drew core epistemological dispositions such as the questioning of bedrock assumptions of social science practice, like objectivity or value-free scientific enquiry, the primacy of reason over alternative systems of thought and knowledge (mainly religion), the emancipatory potential of knowledge and the possibility of reaching truth through scientific enquiry.³⁰ Furthermore, anti-Eurocentrism opposed both liberal and Marxist forms of historical explanation which saw modernity and science as inevitably rising within the Western Enlightenment culture and the associated idea that the West/Europe held a unique or exceptional - read superior - position against what has been called 'the Rest', 'the Other', 'the underdeveloped' or 'the premodern'. In that sense, anti-Eurocentrism opposed all forms of historical necessity by insisting on the contingent nature of change and the inevitable hegemonic expediency lurking behind all forms of teleological analysis of human history.

It is well-known that the refutation of the idea of progress - the signature concept of the political ethics and philosophy of social science emanating from the Enlightenment - holds a prominent place in poststructuralist anti-Eurocentric accounts. For the purposes of the present analysis, Progress is defined as the belief in ethical, political, cultural and social improvement, rooted in

²⁹ In this critical reform of disciplines, however, it is often forgotten that 'as a cultural orientation Eurocentrism itself is a hindsight invention of the Europe/Other binary, not the other way around' (Dirlik 1999: 12).

³⁰ To be sure, Turner's (1994: 6) remark that Islamic anti-Eurocentrism and the interest in Islam from a postmodern perspective are symptomatic of postcommunism as an intellectual and political condition should prompt us to consider, along with the demystification of the western metaphysical tradition initiated by the postmodern thinking, the historical and political developments that marked the rise of awareness of the limits of modernity. The layered historical-political disintegration of the West includes historical phenomena and events like the end of the Empire, the anticolonial struggles and the postcolonial realities of today, the end of the Cold War and the collapse of the 'really existing' socialism. And although the legacies of colonialism and anti-colonialism have been consistently debated within the 'reflexive' disciplines and acknowledged for their formative role in the articulation of anti-Eurocentrism as epistemological stance, the significance of the collapse of Eastern Block and of the socialist ideology which underpinned it go often unnoticed. Anti-Eurocentrism, across its disciplinary or local variations, claims to bring about an alternative vision, an opposing force to the hegemonic West. However, up until 1989, socialism constituted the force of opposition which systematically deconstructed the dominant Western liberal political ideology by contesting the necessary link between the economic logic of capitalism and democratic politics as advocated in the liberal tradition and by putting into relation the progress, knowledge and emancipation.

the seventeenth-century scientific revolution, eighteenth-century Enlightenment culture and nineteenth-century positivism (Salvadori 2006: 99). For progressive political thinkers there are two, distinctive, if not contradictory ways of perceiving progress, i.e. as a regulative ideal or aspirational model versus as a necessary process which has become intrinsic to nature and human development (ibid: 8-9), with the second gaining prominence at the end of the course of the Enlightenment movement (ibid: 11). However, poststructuralist thinking has problematised this view by insisting that the one cannot but lead inevitably to the other, i.e. that there is no way of conceiving progress without the hierarchisation of those who are ahead and those who follow and their respective, necessarily unequal, places in all fields of civilisational activity: politics, culture, knowledge, and so on. According to sympathetic accounts of the intellectual trajectory of the concept, it is only when progress becomes dissociated from its humanist foundation, i.e. the rights of individuals and society and their emancipation from oppressive forms of power that it becomes increasingly associated with the idea of historical necessity (ibid: 58). It is the compartmentalisation of progress into components, its decomposition into a single route of improvement, i.e. continual scientific-technological knowledge at the service of political interests and economic growth, that outshined the idea of harmonious functional growth which encompasses science, technology, culture, the techniques of governing and the production and distribution of material goods (ibid: 3). The conviction that the future can henceforth be planned 'scientifically' with the social scientists guiding the leaders of society towards it, stems from this development (ibid: 12-13). The idea of ethical, political, cultural and social improvement gives way to the idea of historical necessity and unstoppable progress: implied in this belief is the conviction that better future requires removing all 'obstacles' from the past blocking the way (2006: 8-9). Hence, the theme of violence as inherent to the idea of progress and to the uniformisation that its mode of reasoning imports and imposes on the rest of the world at the expense of traditional or religious modes of 'being in the world' in the 'post' critical social theory, as we shall see below.

This poststructuralist, anti-foundationalism and anti-progressist variant of anti-Eurocentric critique is the one that underlies the authors and positions addressed by this chapter. Naturally, as explained above, engaging with Eurocentrism and its critics involves potentially the entire area of critical social theory today. One avenue to embark on such task is by looking at the cluster of concepts of history, historicity, historicism and the ways they relate to each other, firstly, because

of their prominence within the field of anti-Eurocentric critique and, secondly, because it is conducive to the main aim of the chapter, i.e. to dissect the philosophies of history undergirding the poststructuralist representation of the Muslim political subject. With this in mind, postcolonial thinking emerges as the most privileged vehicle for such endeavour. Even if the questioning of the progressive and benign-only character of modernity and the stress on the pitfalls of historicist thinking and politics is a recurrent intellectual phenomenon in the twentieth century, postcolonialism pioneered in linking the critique of reason and progress with the anticolonial struggles - and more broadly, with the question of the 'non-West' - on the one hand, and the poststructuralist insights exposing the inextricable relationship between knowledge/science and hegemony/power on the other hand. Therefore, any meaningful understanding of the Muslim political subject emerging through the anti-Eurocentric critique cannot bypass the postcolonial engagement with the nexus of history-historicity-historicism. The chapter proceeds by examining the most elaborate and influential theoretical effort to expose the Eurocentric bias of 'history' itself, i.e. the renowned project of 'provincializing Europe' as articulated by Dipesh Chakrabarty (2000). By doing so, the chapter will be in a position to locate the structural overlaps and tensions between postcolonial thinking and the radical - poststructuralist - historicism represented by Talal Asad, whose anthropology of religion, or 'anthropology of the secular', has been formative in the development of religious pietism and revivalism as a site of critique, or as a locus of agency (e.g. Bracke 2008; Bracke and Fadil 2008; Brown 2006; Hirschkind 2006; Hollywood 2004; Keller 2002; Mahmood 2001, 2002, 2005, 2006).

3.2 From postcolonialism to posthistoricism: history in the perspective of the subaltern

The project of *Provincializing Europe*, initially a historical one, is a significant step in the direction of decentring the West and further deconstructing the dominance of Western epistemologies and values initiated by the poststructuralist/postmodernist movement. Few contributions in the field of critical social theory had the effect of Chakrabarty's volume. Like Said's *Orientalism*, it engages with the question of alterity and its representation in the Western theoretical thinking. But it also marks a step further from the *Orientalism's* critique of the modus operandi of Western intellectual colonialism by offering a new research programme about the way suppressed knowledges and subjectivities can be recovered. *Provincializing Europe* as a

concrete paradigm³¹ in social sciences and humanities is a challenge to Eurocentric thought in the following sense: it puts into question the stadial idea embodied by historicist methodologies, liberal and Marxist alike, that the non-West must develop and catch up with the West. The assumption underpinning the use of this kind of thinking and the categories/values it produced (e.g. development, modernisation, progress) is that societies have evolved from precapitalist to capitalist, or from traditional to modern. They eventually converge on to the global stage – the ‘end of History’ fantasy shared by Hegelian, Marxist and ultra-liberal Fukuyama-style (1992) thought – but until then, non-Western societies must follow the Western model set by those ahead of them in the developmental course of history. Chakrabarty’s argument develops in three levels: firstly, it establishes the problematic by exposing why historicism is a hindrance for any serious consideration of the Other as a real counterpart to the West and not merely as an instance of curiosity, exoticism or charity; secondly, it develops an alternative or corrective to historicism, the concept of ‘subaltern pasts’; and thirdly, it suggests how superseding historicist thought is not only a way of recovering the past in non-hegemonic terms, but also a way of re-imagining the future. Let us look at the development of the argument in some more detail.

Chakrabarty – who follows a quasi Saidian-Foucauldian line of thinking in the sense of linking power to the production of knowledge – claims that historicism enabled the European domination of the world in the nineteenth century by positing historical time as a measure of alleged cultural distance between the West and the non-West (2002: 7). This ideological device worked on two levels of domination: ‘In the colonies, it legitimated the idea of civilisation. In Europe itself, it made possible completely internalist stories of Europe in which Europe was described as the site of the first occurrence of capitalism, modernity, or Enlightenment’ (ibid). For Chakrabarty, therefore, a critique of historicism unavoidably leads to the questioning of political modernity in the non-West, as it is through the recourse to the stagist idea of history – represented by historicist methodologies – that the European political and social thought made room for the political modernity of the subaltern, i.e. the non-European, classes (2000: 9).

³¹ The main source I rely on for the analysis of Chakrabarty’s work is his book *Provincializing Europe. Postcolonial Thought and Colonial Difference* (2000). However, Chakrabarty developed the main argument of *Provincializing Europe* in two earlier articles to which I also refer here: ‘Postcoloniality and the Artifice of History: Who Speaks of the Indian Pasts?’ (1992) and ‘Radical Histories and the Question of Enlightenment Rationalism: Some Recent Critiques of “Subaltern Studies”’ (1995).

By engaging in the critique of historicism, Chakrabarty takes issue with the idea of history itself as being European, and therefore Eurocentric. As he explains in a move that also reminds Said's attack on academic Orientalism, in the academic discipline of history 'Europe' is the sovereign, theoretical subject of all histories in two ways: a) in the sense that all national or civilisational histories are essentially variations of a master narrative which could be called 'the history of Europe' (1992: 1); and b) in the sense that the dominance of 'Europe' is the theoretical condition under which historical knowledge is produced in the third world (1992: 2). Historicism, the methodology of academic history, makes history theoretically knowable for the first time, but with the price of turning all other histories into copies of itself. Or, to put it in Prakash's words, another leading figure of the field of postcolonial history, by appropriating 'the Other as History' (1992: 8). The problem of historicism according to Chakrabarty can be summarised as being a mode of thinking which sees the world as an historical developing entity, as an individual and unique whole that develops over time, hence the narrative and concept of development as well as 'the secular, empty and homogenous time of history' (2000: 23). Accordingly, the critical thrust of his endeavour is supported by challenging a pair of core assumptions of historicist thinking: first, he questions the assumption that 'the human exists in a frame of a single and secular historical time that envelops other kinds of time' and, second, that 'the human is ontologically singular, that gods and spirits are in the end "social facts", that the social somehow exists prior to them' (200: 16). Chakrabarty suggests to work without the assumption of the logical priority of the social and builds his alternative to historicism to the position that 'gods and spirits to be existentially coeval with the human' because 'the question of being human involves the questions of being with gods and spirits' (ibid). For Chakrabarty, the concern underlying the project of *Provincializing Europe* is to document how a kind of cognitive violence – or in different words a kind of 'epistemicide'³² which is itself an effect of Western 'epistemic racism'³³ – is committed against other ways of knowing the world, how reason 'has been made to look "obvious" far beyond the ground where it originated' (1992: 20). The device for the dissection of the convergence of idealism and violence which generated the 'obviousness' of reason, and the narratives of modernity and progress (1992: 22) – both a tool of diagnosis and a remedy in Chakrabarty's account – is the concept of 'subaltern pasts'.

³² According to De Sousa Santos (2002) the 'epistemicide' against non-Western epistemologies was a direct consequence of European colonial expansion.

³³ Mignolo (2000) develops the concept of 'epistemic racism' to describe the process of inferiorisation of non-Western epistemologies and cosmologies in order to legitimise the prioritisation of Western epistemologies ('Reason') as a superior form of knowledge.

To explain Chakrabarty's corrective of 'subaltern pasts' one needs to look a little earlier in the genealogy of thinking in which the project of *Provincializing Europe* belongs. In short, Chakrabarty takes issue with some of the assumptions framing the work of Subaltern Studies Group of which he has himself been an important constituent. The famous collective embarked in the 1980s in the most important attempt of revising Indian history with a clear objective to restore the political agency of those subaltern classes, essentially the peasants in rural India, which were systematically ignored both by the traditional colonial narrative and the so-called orthodox Marxist analysis, in which the revolutionary role of changing history belongs to the working class only. Inspired by Gramsci's (2011 [1975]) insights who took a more positive view of the subaltern classes in order to allow the possibility of a collective class consciousness among workers and peasants, Subaltern Studies, especially during their first phase from which Chakrabarty diverges, sought firstly, to reinstate the subaltern subject as a political agent, secondly, to see the subaltern mobilisation in colonial India (i.e. peasant revolts) as political in contrast to the classical Marxist historiography in which it has been persistently categorised as 'prepolitical' (e.g. Hobsbawm 1983), and thirdly, to represent the subaltern action in its own terms.

It is in relation to this last objective of the Subaltern Studies Group's task, i.e. the representation of the subaltern in his/her *own* terms, that Chakrabarty initiates his critique and builds on his alternative. He thinks that the main move in fully restoring the agency of the subaltern is not simply to acknowledge the political nature of his/her actions but actually to eliminate the 'necessary secularism' (2000: 14) associated with the domain of the political in those accounts. Chakrabarty's vehicle to explore the ways secularism – or the absence of 'gods and spirits' in historicist accounts – erases the real subjectivity of the subaltern is a landmark essay by R. Guha, one of the foundational figures of the Subaltern Studies Group. Guha's 'The Prose of Counter-Insurgency' (1994) deals with the rebellion of Santal, a tribal group in Bengal and Bihar who rebelled against both the British and nonlocal Indians in 1955. In a typical exercise of the Subaltern Studies approach, Guha brings the peasants' political consciousness to the fore and makes it the real engine of the rebellion. The problem for Chakrabarty lies, however, in the way Guha treats the Santal's statement that God was the main instigator of the rebellion: although Guha acknowledges the importance of religiosity to the rebellion and to the peasants' life, he is

actually treating it as a belief. Chakrabarty is uncomfortable with what he sees as 'anthropologizing' the Santal statement, i.e. with the act of converting someone's belief into an object of analysis, as a necessary condition for the 'belief' to find a place in the historian's narrative (2000: 105). In other words, Chakrabarty takes issue with historiography's core tendency to accept religion as a 'means' but not an 'end in itself' (1995: 754).

By Chakrabarty's own admission, the historian's narrative cannot allow 'the divine or the supernatural a direct hand in the affairs of the world' (2000: 104). By the same token, the religious must therefore be reinterpreted as someone's belief, since attributing to it any real agency would be going against the rules of evidence (ibid). The historian therefore, unlike the Santal, cannot involve the supernatural in explaining the event since 'we cannot write history from within what we regard as beliefs' (2000: 16). Hence, we produce 'good' but not *subversive*³⁴ histories which conform to the norms of the discipline (ibid). The detection of this lacuna in the narrativizable and historicizable past, as illustrated by the case of the Santal rebellion, is what Chakrabarty calls 'subaltern pasts' i.e. 'pasts that cannot ever enter academic history as belonging to the historian's own positions' (2000: 105).

But how exactly do subaltern pasts operate and what is their relationship to the historicist historiography? For Chakrabarty, these subordinated relationships to the past, the 'subaltern pasts' are the necessary condition for the possibility of historicisation itself: 'what underlies our capacity to historicize is our capacity not to' (2000: 113). The 'subaltern pasts' give an entry point into the times of gods and spirits, 'times that are seemingly very different from the empty, secular, and homogenous time of history' and which 'are never completely alien; we inhabit them to begin with' (ibid). These pasts that resist historicisation – which are not exclusive to subaltern groups or minority identities alone, but rather refer to the exclusion of these pasts from the 'major' narratives of the dominant institutions³⁵ – demonstrate for Chakrabarty that 'the capacity (of the

³⁴ The idea of subversion is central in the field of postcolonial history: 'writing subaltern history, from this point of view, becomes an activity that is contestatory because of its insurgent readings' as Prakash explains (1990: 400). To be sure, Prakash's 'post-Orientalist historiography', despite the overlapping interest in subversion and in the disclosure of histories excluded by Eurocentric historiography which it shares with the project of *Provincializing Europe*, has a more explicit poststructuralist underpinning and as such it seeks to 'make cultural forms and even historical events contingent, above all, on power relations' (1990: 401), whilst Chakrabarty's attempt still wants to hold on, albeit selectively, on the narrative of the Capital, as we shall a little further down.

³⁵ The emphasis on revising the 'major' narrative of dominant institutions prompted even seemingly unrelated fields of research to inquire into their own 'provinciality' (e.g. the provinciality of America's empire by questioning its alleged exceptional character, Go 2007) or even 'subalternity'. The postcolonisation of Medieval history is a very telling

modern person) to historicize actually depends on his or her ability to participate in nonmodern relationships to the past that are made subordinate in the moment of historicization' (2000: 101). Accordingly, this is what gives a possibility to history to understand the subaltern without historicising or anthropologising his/her agency (2000: 108), to conceive humans from any other period and region as always our contemporaries in some sense and, ultimately, to make visible the plurality of times existing together, the disjuncture of the present itself (2000: 108-109). Finally, for Chakrabarty, the relation between subaltern pasts and the practice of historicising is far from one of mutual exclusion but rather one of interdependency: 'subaltern pasts' act as a supplement

example in that sense. In this strand of thought, the 'Middle Ages' can be thought as a region of history colonised within the history of modernity, 'a typologically empty time recast by the machinery of Modernity as a specific period of history' (Dagenais and Greer 200: 436). In the relevant literature, this colonisation occurs in at least three senses: first, it is experienced as a 'trauma' within the discipline, as an effort to retrace 'the epistemological violence at stake in producing a hard-edged exteriority for medieval studies' (Biddick 1998: 4). Second, the emergence of the discipline, coeval with the time of European imperial expansion, is thought as an attempt to 'establish "The Middle Ages" not as a period in history, but as a vastness of time ripe for colonial exploitation' (Dagenais and Greer 200: 431). In that sense, the argument goes, temporal colonisation is inherent in the colonialist project: 'the colonized other is "primitive", exists in a past state opposed to the European present' (ibid: 435) and therefore, in a move that draws heavily from Chakrabarty's project, 'only Europe, compared to the savagery and barbarity of other continents, has a history. In a way, history is Europe, whereas other continents are only fragments of past and pre-historic stages' (Dainotto 2006: 13). Third, the colonisation of Medieval history is linked more explicitly to the 'task of deconstructing the temporalities of today's Orientalism' (Davis 1998: 629) and more recently, by showing how the 'Middle Ages' become a metonymy for those regions in the world in 'crisis' - i.e. marked by the absence of a sovereign, secular state - and by arguing about the political nature of the historical method of periodisation itself: 'Periodization ... does not refer to a mere back-description that divides history into segments but to a fundamental political technique - a way to moderate, divide and regulate - always rendering its services now. In an important sense, we cannot periodize the past' (Davis 2008: 5). Conversely, in the whole exercise of postcolonisation of Medieval history there are parallel efforts which argue for 'the vital role that medieval studies performed in the emergence and shaping of postcolonial studies as a field of critical inquiry' (Holsinger 2002: 1207). A similar impact can be observed in the field of International Relations: following an analogous trend, the discipline sought to 'provincialize' itself by asking questions about power relations and hierarchies embedded in the constitution of the field itself. This 'provincialization' was expressed as a rejection of the 'Westphalian narrative' (Kayaoglu 2010) and the associated principles of sovereignty and secularism as the dominant normative framework for understanding international history and politics. The discussion about the perspectival and ultimately hegemonic nature of knowledge produced by reason and science and the radical questioning of the foundational premises of IR - revisionist theorists with varying theoretical allegiances have even called the 'Westphalian narrative' a myth (Beaulac 2004; Osiander 2001; Teschke 2003) - generated an identity crisis of the discipline; even its more critical strand was found to be 'subliminally Eurocentric' despite being critical of the West (Hobson 2007). More recently and largely driven by the project of 'provincializing' the discipline a number of scholars reclaimed the 'non-Western' as the domain where the relations of domination sustained by the West could be more effectively challenged and subverted: Inayatullah and Blaney (2004), Pasha and Murphy (2002), Chowdhry and Nair (2002), Tickner and Wæver (2009), Seth (2011), and Shani's explicit call about the necessity to provincialize critical IR theory (2002, 2007, 2008) are amongst the most characteristic attempts which sought to understand the non-Western 'from within their own traditions' (Shani 2007: 422). See Vasilaki (2012) for a critical account of the impact of 'post' theoretical sensitivities in critical IR theory.

to the historian's past in the Derridean sense, i.e. they enable history, the discipline, to be what it is whilst showing its own limits (2000: 112).

The same logic of interdependency between history and the subjective experience of the subaltern underlies Chakrabarty's (2007: 77-78) concept of 'historical wounds' discussed in the context of the historical plights of Aboriginal people and its recognition:

Historical wounds are not the same as historical truths but the later constitute a condition of possibility for the former. Historical truths are broad, synthetic generalisations based on researched collections of individual historical facts. (...) Historical wounds, on the other hand, are a mix of history and memory and hence their truth is not verifiable by historians. Historical wounds cannot come into being, however, without prior existence of historical truths' (2007: 77-78).

What is remarkable in this distinction is the subtle move from the 'subaltern pasts' where the subjectivity (which seems to be considerably overlapping with religiosity *tout court*) of the subaltern must find a place in the narrative of the historian, if we are to supersede the violence exercised by historicism on nonmodern attitudes, to a renewed questioning of the relationship between facts and experiential claims and the necessary degree of consensus that needs to be reached between academic history and the subaltern groups (ibid). It is also interesting that in this case, Chakrabarty does not hesitate to historicise, i.e. to explain the secular, political reasons behind the 'emotional intensity' (ibid) of the language of Aboriginals as a wounded group *cum* historians.

Seen this way Chakrabarty's 'subaltern pasts' introduce a new kind of *history-writing* - opposed to *history-making* of historicism which is thought as prescribing the Eurocentric scenario of progress and the associated stagist account of history to nonmodern civilisations and subjects - an attitude toward history that we could call *posthistoricist*. But what is required for this posthistoricist practice to take root and which assumptions of modern social and human science does it aim to disrupt? Chakrabarty seems to think that the problem of the erasure of the subaltern's real experience lies in the language of social science itself: the closer one gets to it, the higher the risk of obliterating 'the plural ways of being human that are contained in the very different

orientations to the world' (2000: 241). To take this further, he looks at the concept of anachronism and the way it allows for the reification of the past into an object of study (2000: 244) and questions the kind of logic behind the view of the archaic – which in Chakrabarty's case equals the religious more or less - as a remnant of another time instead of something constitutive of the present (2000: 251).

Indeed, few would disagree with the importance of seeing the past as constitutive of the present. The *modus operandi* of the discipline of modern history and especially historicist history - the one that Chakrabarty seeks to 'provincialize' because of its commitment to causality - has always revolved around contextualising its object of research into the web of origins, relationships and manifestations of the past in the present. Therefore, it is far from convincing why history must collapse the distance between the metalanguage of social science and the language of subjective experience of the subaltern, or the distinction between the subject and object of research in order to acknowledge the constitutive role of the past in the present. As Dirlik (1987: 31) observes, the historian's alienation from the historical subject is of a social nature i.e. it is a consequence of participation in a profession, the social price paid for expertise. But even if from the point of view of cultural relativism (incidentally, one that Chakrabarty explicitly rejects, 1992: 20; 2000: 43) such collapse would seem acceptable, there are further problems. McLennan (2010: 18) notices that Chakrabarty's own language is not immune of the denounced 'scientism', since 'despite their subject-friendly and directly-divulgent appearance, terms such as "lifeworld", "cultural diversity", "singular ontology" and so forth are first and foremost theoretical tools of analysis and assessment'.

Likewise, the 'provincialization' of the discipline of history itself, as being 'only one of the ways of remembering the past' (2000: 106) rather confuses than productively problematises the role of history as a human science. In spite of the overlap between history on the one hand, and memory and commemoration on the other, their relationship can only operate in a tangential manner. History as a discipline cannot be reduced in one of the modes of remembering the past, in a tool in the service of politics of recognition or in a way of overcoming historical wounds: it is above all an attempt to explain the past, to make it knowable, intelligible, even tameable, to understand how 'men make their own history (...) under circumstances existing already, given and transmitted from the past' (Marx, 1852). Or in Chakrabarty's own words, to understand how the

past is constitutive of the present, albeit in our case by embracing rather than rejecting the separation of social science from its objects. When this distinction collapses, what is a profoundly regressive move can appear as a liberating act. Take for instance Prakash's enthusiastic response to Nandy's conceptual device of 'mythography of history' (Nandy 1983). In Prakash's eyes, the 'strategy of privileging the "mythic" over the "real" (...) is not only a plea for a recognition of the plurality of critical traditions but a claim for the liberating nature of the victim's discourse, particularly for that of the colonized' (1990: 405). In that sense, posthistoricism seems to have moved from the critical deconstruction of 'myths' (in the sense meant by Barthes 2001 [1957]) all the way back to their uncritical acceptance. What is also revealed in this retreat to 'myth' from the disenchanted world of social science is the peculiar romanticism embedded in the posthistoricalist fantasy that truth is somewhere 'out there', always elusive to secular epistemology and better accessible by intuition or spirituality.

This profound scepticism against the ability of science to produce any substantive understanding without committing an act of violence against the object of research, is constitutive of postcolonial thinking since its formative moments. Spivak's (1988b: 105) observation that 'explaining, we exclude the possibility of the *radically* heterogeneous', summarises perfectly the posthistoricalist suspicion against any attempt to explain the social world in terms of *causality*, i.e. in the last instance, in terms of *relations*,³⁶ as well as the tendency of poststructuralist hermeneutics to view history as the outcome of a discursive antagonism for hegemony.³⁷ The complications stemming from viewing the social world and its history in such *singular logic* are further explored in the next section. Suffice to say for the moment that in an important sense posthistoricism undermines any possibility to critically deconstruct power relations and disrupt

³⁶ Having said this, however, Spivak's interventions work both ways: along with the more prominent and explicit aspect which prioritises 'singularity' instead of 'relationality' as explored further down in the chapter, there is a less pronounced but equally important dimension which allows to think for a mutual transformation, of the 'Western' and the 'non-Western', as explained in more detail in the next chapter.

³⁷ As Žižek (2009a: 22, note 9) comments quoting Frederic Jameson, today's discursive 'anti-essentialist' historicism has a paradoxical ahistorical dimension:

once we fully accept and practice the radical contingency of our identities, all authentic historical tension somehow evaporates in the endless performative games of an eternal present. There is a nice self-referential irony at work here: there is history only insofar as there persist remainders of 'ahistorical' essentialism. This is why radical essentialists have to deploy all their hermeneutic-deconstructive skills to detect hidden traces of "essentialism" in what appears to be a postmodern "risk society" of contingencies – were they to admit that we already live in an "anti-essentialist" society, they would have confront the truly difficult question of the historical character of today's predominant radical historicism itself, i.e. confront the topic of this historicism as the ideological form of "postmodern" global capitalism.

the hegemonies they sustain – a commitment all critical ‘posts’ share – since to do so, one needs to explain how the social world works in the first place.

But there is more that is discarded through the ‘critique historicism in all its varieties’ (2000: 249). If ‘subaltern pasts’ emerge as a compelling objection to the idea ‘that everything can be historicized or that one should always historicize’ (2000: 112) it is precisely because of the blurring of functions between types of knowledge, because of the rejection of inclusions and exclusions that necessarily operate in any meaningful or even broadly efficient scientific pursuit, carried out by Chakrabarty’s account in the first place. Naturally, not everything is historicizable, but by the same token, what cannot be historicizable does not belong to the historian’s narrative: ‘gods and spirits’ are historicizable as a belief and this is their only possible place in history. They can, however, be totally acceptable as reality in myriad other ways of ‘remembering the past’, in collective memory, in rituals of commemoration, in artistic forms of expression. The urgency therefore to bring ‘gods and spirits’ into the practice of modern human and social science is symptomatic of a deeper theme that lies at the heart of Chakrabarty’s posthistoricist project: the modern, historicist understanding of time, i.e. secular time and the critique of the way it ‘colonises’ spaces, cultures and even historical periods. In that sense, McLennan’s observation that

the question of postcolonialism is – and perhaps always has been – nowadays tied up with the question of postsecularism, as long as the perception stands that secularism in thought is a) rationalistically hostile to religious cultures, and b) forms a necessary part of the hegemonic western disparagement of the ‘backward’ non-West (2010: 5)

discloses the *intrinsic* connection between the two fields of critical enquiry (2010: 110). But it also raises the question to what extent the numerous variations of posthistoricist projects are *ultimately* concerned with the subaltern *per se*, rather than with the re-establishment of the religious, supernatural, or antirational, as an acceptable way of making sense of the world within human and social science. In that sense, it is reasonable to ask whether the posthistoricist methodology, despite its best intentions to divulge the richness of the subaltern way of ‘being in the world’, does not reduce the complexity of the subaltern into his/her supernatural beliefs.

Furthermore, the re-organisation of power relations around the binary axis of time – instead of a binary axis of power – creates a paradox at the very heart of the posthistorical problematic. In an early critique of postcolonial studies, McClintock (1992) had noticed that despite its determination to question the ‘imperial idea of linear time’, postcolonial studies are haunted by the idea of linear development. This is not only because whilst challenging the hegemony of western historicism on the imposition of binaries (such as self-other, metropolis-colony, centre-periphery and so on) postcolonialism re-orientates history around a single binary opposition, i.e. colonial/postcolonial (1992: 85-86); but also because political difference between cultures is ‘subordinated to their temporal distance from European colonialism’ (1992: 86). It goes without saying that Chakrabarty’s account is far more sophisticated than the reduction of power relations to the simple opposition of ‘colonial/postcolonial’, as the shift from the problematic of ‘postcolonial’ to that of the ‘subaltern’ demonstrates. However, the predominance of the axis of time over the axis of power is a point that can be extrapolated from McClintock’s critique of postcolonial studies to Chakrabarty’s posthistorical enterprise. Historicist, secular time is endowed with the explanatory ability of a full-fledged metanarrative: like capital, or patriarchy, secular time becomes the overarching causal framework from which all forms of domination and oppression emanate, even if the question of who are the historical agents within the binary opposition of secular/nonsecular is far from been answered.

This question is not of course one of theoretical contemplation only: what is discarded through the metaphor of historicism is also the political ethics of progress, not only in the secondary sense of ‘necessity’ but also in the primary sense of ‘regulative idea or aspirational model’, as explained in the introduction of the chapter. Furthermore, the rejection of modern historical consciousness is inextricable with a certain modern and political way of appropriating the past that cannot be dissociated from the desire of the modern subject to master the present as well as the future. Chakrabarty takes issue with the modern desire ‘both to create the past as amenable to objectification and to be at the same time free of this object called “history”’ (2000: 244) and with historicism’s promise to the human subject of a ‘certain degree of autonomy with respect to history’ (2000: 247). But then, what is exactly the problem with restoring ‘the human subject to history’ as historicism does (Dirlik 1987: 47) and why one needs to seek ‘emancipation not through Reason but from Reason, not through History but from History’ (Ahmad 2008: 360)? As Sternhell (2010: 41) observes, historiography becomes possible with the beginnings of criticism,

which in turn becomes possible through the affirmation of one's autonomy: 'historiography only becomes a form of intellectual activity when one ceases to look for the divine will in history and entrusts oneself to the power of reasoning in order to understand the past and prepare for the future'. It is precisely this anthropocentrism of modern historiography – 'the individual's claim to exercise absolute control of his fate and of human affairs in general through the power of reason' (Sternhell 2010: 181) that Chakrabarty wants to overcome because it seems to preclude 'a radical openness' and 'the capacity to hear that which does not already understand' (1995: 757). The challenge for Chakrabarty is to reconceptualise the present, 'to unlearn to think of history as a developmental process in which that which is possible becomes actual by tending to a future that is singular' (2000: 249). The seductive Heideggerian rhetoric of radical openness and of the futures that already 'are' (2000: 251-251) however, should not make us miss the simultaneous closure of our possibilities to explain the social world. If the modern political subject and social scientist are rejected for their commitment to the future that 'will be', in Chakrabarty's posthistoricist account the subaltern, postsecular practitioner seems to be qualified with a different capacity of 'futurology', one that may not be based on the modern obsession with prediction, but one that takes the explanation of the social world back to the mystical realm of spirituality and myth.

Even so, Chakrabarty is certain that in order to reach the state of 'radical openness' to heterotemporalities one does not need to reject reason, but to recognise it as simply one of the ways of being in the world (2000: 249), in one word, to *provincialize* it. Chakrabarty repeats on several occasions that his project is not one of wholesale rejection of rational argumentation or the legacies of the European thought (1995: 752; 2000: 16, 255), for the European categories of thought are both indispensable and inadequate to account for non-European modes of being in the world (2000: 16, 19). In a non-negligible manner, even if only in terms of rhetoric or wishful thinking, *Provincializing Europe* is thought as a corrective to historicism, since by Chakrabarty's own admission the explanatory power of the universal narrative of Capital is impossible to dismiss if one wishes to produce critical readings of social injustices (2000: 254). Hence the invitation 'to hold together both secularist-historicist and nonsecularist and nonhistoricist tasks on the world by engaging seriously the question of diverse ways of "being-in-the world"' (2002: 21-22). However, what sounds as unlimited pluralism here, may also be the effect of Chakrabarty's intellectual *ambivalence*. As McLennan notices about Chakrabarty's endeavour: 'Ambivalence reigns because, in effect, strict pluralism – thinking about and intellectually accepting "irreducible

plurality” – is impossible to sustain. Once inside the historicist frame, for example, there can be no “multiple temporalities” (2010: 15).

Provincializing Europe's ambivalence may seem more appealing to some than the unambiguous commitment to one epistemological stance. However, what can be safely concluded now is that the effort to bridge the gap ‘between gods and spirits’ and modern politics and science is paralysing as far as the practice of social sciences or humanities are concerned. If religious experience is the locus of the irreducibly subjective, of radical subjectivity which cannot be enunciated in any imaginable cross-cultural or universal terms, then indeed social or human sciences have nothing to say, since the sociology or anthropology of religion are only possible from within a secular epistemology. This observation can be seen in two ways: either it makes social sciences redundant and consequently we are at a deadlock, or it makes the need for a sheer separation between faith and reason within social sciences clearer. In this sense history, and for that matter any other social science discipline, needs secularism no less than it has always been the case. If posthistoricism aspires to be a convincing alternative to secular human and social science, a resolution must be reached. Is then posthistoricism at a cross-roads or at a cul-de-sac? Is it possible to safeguard theoretical cogency without the disconcerting political implications that posthistoricism points to when applied consistently, like in the case of Mahmood’s irreducibly different Muslim subjectivity? Looking at Asad’s work, perhaps the most representative thinker of today’s poststructuralist radical historicism – a radicalised version of posthistoricism itself - will help to illuminate these questions.

3.3 Radical historicism: poststructuralist analytics at cross-roads or at a cul-de sac?

Asad’s work has been formative in the development of arguments which see religious piety as a locus of critique or as a site of political agency. Asad’s ‘anthropology of the secular’ marked a significant break from the familiar perspective of ‘anthropology of religion’, to the point that his approach has been described as ‘religious anthropology’ (Cooper 2008: 43, note 3). Like Said’s *Orientalism* and Chakrabarty’s *Provincializing Europe* which have introduced a new paradigm in the field of humanities and social science, Asad’s *Genealogies of Religion* and *Formations of the Secular* are foundational in the sense of producing a specific genre of studies on the themes of secularism and the constitution of Western nation-state based on the assumption that what made

both of them possible was the exclusion of the non-secular Other. If Chakrabarty's endeavour is structured around the demonstration of the ways historicism excludes the subaltern – that is, the nonsecular subaltern and not, for instance, the gendered one, like in Spivak's (1988a) famous essay - Asad also builds his argument around the disclosure of exclusions which enabled modernity and its logics (humanist, rationalist, secularist) to dominate history and claim universality. Although both perspectives share as their main principle the superseding of progress as the *raison d'être* of history and the (re)consideration of heterotemporalities in the narratives of human and social sciences, these two poststructuralist perspectives draw their insights from rather different sources. Whereas posthistoricism as developed by Chakrabarty leans on Derridean-Heideggerian hermeneutics, hence its inclination in reading subaltern history as a text to be 'decolonised' from the domination of the homogenising historicist time and the enabling of the futures that 'already are', Asad's radical historicism relies heavily on Foucauldian ethics and analytics of power where the embodiment of norms holds a primacy over more intellectualised forms of consciousness. Despite the common engagement in exposing the processes through which historicism or secularism (both metaphors for modernity) acquire their status as hegemonic discourses and operate as epistemological formations, this divergence in theoretical lineage ultimately gives way to different philosophies of history. On the one hand, posthistoricism oscillates between historicism and subaltern pasts, between the contingent character of the historical process and the necessarily totalising narrative of the Capital, therefore potentially allowing space for the re-inscription of secular concepts in the postcolonial context and the possibility of translation and common ground to be recovered from both sides, as it will be explored in the next chapter. On the other hand, radical historicism, more rigorous in following the logical extensions of its theoretical leanings, is lead to a radical cultural relativism, a rigid singular logic which ultimately introduces a new – and politically uncomfortable - teleology of history. But I am running ahead of my argument, so let us see first how the 'anthropology of the secular' engages with the critique of modernity and how this challenge differs from the parallel critical project of *Provincializing Europe*.

Asad's 'anthropology of the secular' is structured around the investigation of the connection between 'the secular' as an epistemic category and 'secularism' as a political doctrine (2003: 1) and has a stated *postsecular intention*: it seeks to break away from 'the coercive constraints of Sociological Truth – the axiom that the social is the ground of being' (2006: 206). It is above all a

historical task since Asad, who is interested in ‘what secularism means historically’ (2006: 217), seeks to understand how we have come to think of the secular in the ways we do, i.e. ‘how certain practices, concepts, and sensibilities have helped to organize, in different places and at different times, political arrangements called secularism’ as well as ‘the structure of political liberties on which this secular democratic state is thought to be built’ (ibid). The important point that Asad’s historical anthropology marks is not simply that the religious and the secular interpenetrate, or that the ‘secular is a mask for religion’ (2003: 26), or even that secularism is defined by its religious origin (2003: 16), all well-known arguments in the debates about secularisation and postsecularism.³⁸ Asad’s conceptual novelty lies in three observations: first, on the view that both religion and the secular are historically constituted; second, that this happens through accidental – contingent – processes that bring together clusters of concepts, practices and sensibilities; and third, that in modern societies the law defines the distinctiveness of social spaces, in particular the legitimate space for religion (Asad 2006: 209).

The main thesis in the ‘anthropology of the secular’ is that both the contemporary view of religion, as well as the anthropological/sociological category of ‘religion’ which is used for the analysis of this view, are modern inventions. In the *Genealogies of Religion* which predate the articulation of the ‘anthropology of the secular’ as a concrete project, Asad argues that that ‘there cannot be a universal definition of religion, not only because its constituent elements and relationships are historically specific, but because that definition is itself the historical product of discursive processes’ (1993: 29). From this premise, Asad deconstructs the process through which the analytical category of religion produces the entity of religion as a transhistorical and transcultural phenomenon, by demonstrating that religion acquires its autonomous essence – as distinct from science and politics – through the process of the historically and culturally specific history of Reformation (1993: 36). By the same token, the transformation of religion from a concrete set of practical rules attached to specific processes of power and knowledge, into a verbalised internal condition, and from there into an abstracted and universalised concept is also a Western-specific phenomenon, which requires the new kind of state, science and legal and moral subject brought by modernity (1993: 42, 47-48).

³⁸ See for instance Taylor’s *A Secular Age* (2007), a seminal example of this trend.

The observation that religion as an autonomous, verbalised realm is a secular invention and that the emergence of autonomous consciousness is coeval with the Western-secular invention of religion, is central to Asad's conceptualisation of secular modernity, defined as a mode of living in the world which vindicates 'the essential freedom and responsibility of the sovereign self in opposition to the constraints of that self by religious discourses' (Asad 2003: 15). Working within the framework of anti-Eurocentric critique, Asad naturally questions the processes through which the modern modes of subjectivation have been imposed on non-European peoples in the name of rationality and progress (1993: 228-229), and like Chakrabarty relates the project of modernity with 'the violence of universalizing reason itself' (2003: 59). In the same logic and with clear Foucauldian leanings, Asad sees the making of the modern 'human' ('endowed with particular capacities for self-awareness, autonomy, and responsibility, that make him/her capable of acting', 2006: 239) and its universalisation as a process of violence inflicted by the West on the non-West through colonisation. Concepts like 'cruelty' are redefined through this process: it is the 'desire to create new human subjects' that underlies the attempt to outlaw customs the European rulers considered cruel: the drive for such actions was not the concern with indigenous suffering but the desire to impose what they considered as civilised standards of justice and humanity on a subject population (2003: 110). In this process of 'learning to be "fully human" only some kinds of suffering were seen as an offence to humanity, and their elimination sought: 'this was distinguished from suffering that was necessary to the process of realising one's humanity – that is, pain that was adequate to its end, not wasteful pain' (2003: 111). Even the modern history of 'torture' itself is not a record of progressive prohibition of cruel, inhuman, and degrading practices: 'it is also a secular story of how one becomes truly human' (2003: 101). Asad's skepticism about the concept of human rights (see for instance Asad and An'Naim 2009) - which he relates to ideas of self-ownership and self-preservation intrinsic to modern governmentality and even neoliberalism itself (2003: 157) – is based on this problematisation of the modern 'human'.

However, there is an important way in which Asad's approach differs in understanding the way the modern, 'secular' violence is exercised and this is where his approach diverges greatly from posthistoricist approaches. The conceptual, epistemic violence which legitimises the political violence of the secular state against the non-secular Other does not only operate by dictating and policing the boundaries of the human, but through the idea of agency, or autonomous will itself: 'The power unleashed in Enlightenment Europe continues to restructure the lives of non-

European peoples, *often through the category of agency of non-European themselves*' (Asad 1993: 229, emphasis added). If posthistoricism seeks to re-establish the real agency of the subaltern, to represent her in her own terms, Asad is taking a step further by actually questioning the extent to which agency, conceptualised as autonomous consciousness, is a western, secular invention, and therefore not only inappropriate to account for the non-Western, but also prone to colonising non-secular modes of subjectivation. Like Mahmood, who has drawn heavily on his own insights in order to argue for the irreducibly different subjectivity enabled by the Muslim tradition, Asad not only delinks agency from subjectivity (2003: 67), but also agency from the notion of resistance and the idea of the autonomous self, and makes a case that agency should be understood not necessarily as resisting, pleasure-seeking and oriented to overcome suffering (2003: 70-79) – at least in the case of the Islamic tradition – because 'forms of suffering are nonetheless intrinsic to the kind of agent a devout Muslim aspires to be' (2003: 90).

The theoretical move that separated agency from autonomy has been explored in detail in the previous chapter, therefore, here I would like to draw attention to the challenge that Asad's work represents for posthistoricism thinking and its commitment to recover the agency of the subaltern, i.e. to the way Asad's radical skepticism aims to expose the 'Eurocentric' bias already embedded in the posthistoricism analytical categories. Asad takes issue with the kind of history that seeks to give to subordinated peoples what Western-formed theoreticians think as 'their own agency' (Asad 2003: 217). Deconstructing the 'making one's own history' project Asad observes that, despite the disavowal of historical narratives of the non-West, the projects that seek to uncover 'suppressed' or 'excluded' histories presuppose 'a concept of history-making that is parasitic on those very narratives' (1993: 17). This observation, of course, does not concern the use of the term 'history' only. Asad's rigorous skepticism points at two core assumptions that posthistoricism shares with historicism itself: first, 'that history is not made unless significant change occurs. It is not sufficient for events to succeed one another; something substantial must be transformed' (1993: 14); and second, that the principle of self-constitution, or else 'consciousness' is central in recovering the subaltern's 'authentic purposes', hence 'an agent cannot make his "own" history unless he is autonomous' (1993: 15). Such postulates are indeed very problematical for a project such as posthistoricism which claims its radical break from Eurocentric epistemologies, since as Asad observes: 'the idea of self-constitution is not merely a historiographical option but a liberal humanistic principle that has far-reaching moral, legal, and political implications in

modern/modernizing states' (ibid). Indeed if we choose to stay a little longer within Asad's sceptical perspective, which profoundly challenges the very core of modern historicity itself, the bedrock assumption of the autonomous moral and political self, it is only consistent to ask 'whose history is been made?', 'what improvised history those agents construct?', 'who is the author, who is its subject?' (1993: 12).

What prompts Asad's interest to ask these questions is the inappropriate – in his view - way that the social science accounts for the non-secular Other, and more specifically for Islamic traditions, by encapsulating them in the 'normalizing' secular-biased concept of religion. Insisting, for instance, that religion and politics, 'two essences modern society tries to keep conceptually and practically apart', are tied together in Islam, presupposes and imposes a view in which religious discourse in the political arena is seen as a disguise for political power (Asad 1993: 28). Not surprisingly for the theorists who work within the poststructuralist paradigm, Asad suggests that we should seek to consider 'each tradition in its own terms' and 'understand ways of reasoning characteristic of given traditions' (1993: 200).³⁹ His own alternative to the Eurocentrism of 'religion' is the concept of 'discursive tradition' which 'connects variously with the formation of moral selves, the manipulation of populations (or resistance to it), and the production of appropriate knowledges' (1986: 7), and 'includes and relates itself to the founding texts of the Qur'an and the Hadith' (1986: 14). In this perspective Islam can be understood neither as a distinctive social structure, nor as a heterogeneous collection of beliefs, artifacts, customs and morals but as an *essential* unity. The 'de-essentialization of Islam' (1993: 169) is for Asad paradigmatic of the kind of thinking revolving around the assimilation of non-European peoples to European civilisation and around the idea that people's historical experience is inessential to them. He thinks that it is precisely this 'de-essentialization' on which Enlightenment's claim to universality is built: 'Muslims, as members of the abstract category "humans", can be assimilated or (as some recent theorists have put it) into global ('European') civilization once they have divested themselves of what many of them regard (mistakenly) as essential to themselves' (ibid).

It is worthwhile delving a little more into the specific meaning of tradition in Asad's work, as it holds a central place in the Islamic-oriented anthropology of Islam he conceives:

³⁹ Hence Asad's suspicion with the concept of cultural translation (1993: chapter 6 passim), an attitude that he shares with Chakrabarty (1995: 755) for whom translation is always 'mistranslation'.

A tradition consists essentially of discourses that seek to instruct practitioners regarding the correct form and purpose of a given practice that, precisely because it is established, has a history. These discourses relate conceptually to a past (when the practice was instituted, and from which the knowledge of its point and proper performance has been transmitted) and a future (how the point of that practice can best be secured in the short or long term, or why it should be modified or abandoned), through a present (how it is linked to other practices, institutions, and social conditions). An Islamic discursive tradition is simply a tradition of Muslim discourse that addresses itself to conceptions of the Islamic past and future, with reference to a particular Islamic practice in the present. (...) My point is not, as some Western anthropologists and Westernized Muslim intellectuals have argued, that 'tradition' is today often a fiction of the present, a reaction to the forces of modernity - that in contemporary conditions of crisis, tradition in the Muslim world is a weapon, a ruse, a defense, designed to confront a threatening world, that it is an old cloak for new aspirations and borrowed styles of behavior. The claim that contemporary ideas and social arrangements are really ancient when they are not is in itself no more significant than the pretense that new ones have been introduced when actually they have not. (...) The important point is simply that all instituted practices are oriented to a conception of the past. (Asad 1986: 14-15)

Sympathetic critics of Asad have noticed an inherent tension in the concept of 'discursive tradition' which draws simultaneously 'from seemingly radically different directions – one in the direction of subversion of status quo, and the other in the direction of a respect for given modes of life' (Scott 2006: 137). For Asad, however, the reconciliation of this tension, between genealogy and tradition is resolved by what these theoretical orientations share, i.e. discipline: 'The later sustains, elaborates, and sometimes argues over disciplinary practices; the former enquires into the contingent formation of their conditions of truthfulness' (2006: 233-235).⁴⁰ In spite of this perfectly valid objection, Asad offers a significant challenge to the modernist conceptualisation of tradition as 'the inheritance of an unchanging cultural substance from the past - as though "past" and "present" were places in linear path down which that object was conveyed to the "future"'

⁴⁰ Incidentally, I would like to submit that there is something more that genealogy and tradition share, namely a certain romanticism about the premodern and a strong anti-modernism which is expressed mostly in the form of anti-statism. In an important way, the understanding of postsecularism cannot be taken further without the consideration of the peculiar anarchist leanings of such approaches, but also without the ways their deep-seated suspicion of the State relates to neoliberal governmentality.

(2003: 222); he challenges the modernist idea that ‘the present is merely a fleeting moment in a historical teleology connecting past to future’ (ibid). For Asad, tradition is traversed by a different sense of temporality, in which the present is always in the centre:

time present is separated from but also included within events and epochs, the way time past authoritatively constitutes present practices, and the way authenticating practices invoke or distance themselves from the past (by reiterating, reinterpreting, and reconnecting textualized memory and memorialised history) (ibid).

Interesting as it is though, the idea of the present and future being conditioned by the ‘discursive tradition’ of Islam, which by Asad’s own admission fuses too closely together ‘eschatology’ and ‘sociology’ (2003: 91) is of a much darker shade, compared with the open-endedness of the contingent, non-predictable futures that ‘already are’ of Chakrabarty’s posthistoricist account. Here, Asad’s radical skepticism borders with straight-forward political conservatism: thinking the making of history as not necessarily oriented to the creation of the future, but ‘as seeking to maintain the “local” status quo, or to follow local models of social life’ (Asad 1993: 19) embodies ‘the disavowal of history itself’ to use Dirlik’s famous phrase (1999: 2). It points to a philosophy of history with its gaze fixed to the back, to the epoch behind, and in an important sense it reduces culture to a space filled by a perpetual reiteration of the same. Asad’s view of Islam as a tradition to be preserved, and the view of history as stasis rather than change, and entirely specific to one location only, leads to puzzling conclusions. As in the case of Mahmood examined in relation to subjectivity, Asad’s declared intention to deconstruct the Eurocentric, Orientalist, ‘positivist’ view of Islam – as static, inimical to change, oriented to the past – leads to the endorsement of the position he had aimed to deconstruct in the first place.

Deep-seated in this view is a *logic of radical singularity* of which Asad is perhaps the purest expression. As Hallward observes, what often passes for specific or particular in ‘post’ approaches of Otherness is, under scrutiny, singular or singularising: the *specific* ‘implies a situation, a past, an intelligibility constrained by inherited conditions (...) [It] is the space of interests in relations of other interests, the space of the historical as such, forever ongoing, forever incomplete’ (2001: 5). On the contrary, the *singular* proceeds in a manner ‘that operates without external criteria to its own operation’ (2001: xii), it is not ‘constrained by any logic outside its own the immanent

criteria' (2001: 3). Indeed, both posthistorical and radical historical approaches which seek to account for the Other in his/her own terms, operate in singularising terms according to which 'each historical moment must be treated as sui generis and as carrying within itself its own explanation' (Ahmad 2008: 373), and as a consequence they define the nonsecular Other in terms of absolute alterity. What are the conclusions that can be drawn from such understanding of poststructuralist analytics of the Other as a singularising logic? Firstly, as it must have been obvious by now, the discourse of cultural singularity and insularity cannot have any intrinsically progressive or emancipatory connotations, and to be sure, the poststructuralist critics do not desire to make claims of progress or even emancipation. Secondly, what can also be firmly established now, is that the discourse of cultural singularity cannot have any genuinely disruptive or subversive implications either. The radical cultural relativism that such views promote as the cornerstone of pluralism and openness is perhaps the strongest version of essentialism: the one that re-affirms stereotypes like Islam as stasis versus Europe as change, Islam as tradition versus Europe as modernity, and ultimately shares the politically conservative view of Islamophobes, i.e. that when cultures mix, a violent act against their essence is taking place. Second, the insularity of cultures across time and space or the lack of continuity in terms of relationality between cultures, eventually neutralises the ability of poststructuralist analytics to account for the Other. Its singularising logic is totally exclusive: 'ultimately, it will act even in the absence of others as such' (Hallward 2001: xii).

Last but not least, the question of political responsibility concomitant with such intellectual insights arises again. Asad's view that 'anthropological inquiry and political commitment should not be confused' (2006: 207) because 'there is always a tension between the need for decisiveness in political commitment and the need for openness in anthropological inquiry' seems to bypass the problem by re-instituting the barrier between the two fields of engagement, the scholarly and the political. Nonetheless, this separation cannot be done without dismissing a crucial feature of Asad's own field of work: i.e. the political nature of poststructuralist, anti-Eurocentric and anti-Orientalist scholarship (Asad's own *Anthropology and The Colonial Encounter*, 1973 was pioneering in that sense) which, in its countless versions and variations, aims to expose and disrupt power relations as well as the making of cultural and intellectual hegemonies of the political present. What is the difference then between the positivist, value-free, Eurocentric

scholarship which refuses to acknowledge its own political nature, from the disavowal of political extensions of one's own intellectual work, like in Asad's case? The impossibility to support such projects or ideas in political terms seems to suggest that the poststructuralist analytics of the Other has come full circle.

Chapter Four

Chapter Four

Postcolonialism versus Islam/ism: Disentangling the Conundrum of a Contested Relationship

- 4.1 Introduction: Islam/ism in the perspective of subjugated knowldges
- 4.2 The historical grounds of the relationship between postcolonialism and Islam/ism
- 4.3 The political potential of postcolonial theory
- 4.4 Postcolonialism meets Islam/ism
- 4.5 The discourse of resistance and the contemporary Left academic and political culture

4.1 Introduction: Islam/ism in the perspective of subjugated knowldges

If feminism is a privileged theoretical terrain for the discussion of questions related to Muslim subjectivity by reference to the constitution of the female and non-Western self - its desires, its expectations, its needs and its politicisation - postcolonialism is the field where the Muslim subject is explored via claims for the decolonisation of history and subjugated knowldges. Naturally, there is no easy way to divide between knowledge and history, between the constitution of (postmodern, postcolonial, subaltern) subjectivity and its inscription in political projects, but for the sake of analytical clarity, this study has been, as much as possible, maintaining a meaningful distinction between the various conceptual categories and vastly overlapping theoretical terrains and disciplines, such as postcolonialism and feminism. As far as such distinction is possible, the understanding of Islam, Islam/ism and Muslim subjectivity through the (poststructuralist) postcolonial perspective remains the object of analysis of the present chapter. Having addressed the epistemological foundations of the philosophy of history undergirding Muslim subjectivity as imagined by threads of postsecularism which converge with postcolonial thinking in the previous chapter, here I seek to further question the intersection between postcolonialism and Islam/ism and bring to the fore those aspects that highlight the ultimate antinomy that animates their respective political orientations. More specifically, this chapter challenges the established assumptions that put postcolonialism and Islam/ism in an explanatory relationship by looking at their divergent theoretical and political agendas and at the contrasting worldviews conveyed by these two projects. By disentangling and juxtaposing postcolonialism and Islam/ism and by exposing their distinctive logics I aim, firstly, to make the conceptual contrast between the two terms tangible and, secondly, to suggest an explanation in

relation to the cultural, political and intellectual conditions, which allow for such relationship to be established.

The inclusion of Islam/ism within the interpreting universe of postcolonialism is taking place against the background of theoretical discussions about the possibility, or better necessity, of decolonising particular indigenous, local, religious or nonsecular knowledges, in an attempt to remedy, or answer back to, the epistemic violence of the West. Obviously, Foucault's thought is a core influence in the articulation of entire fields such as postcolonialism and to the rise of difference as the prevailing category of analysis in critical social theory today. Foucault's work bears a particular interest in marginalised groups whose difference keeps them excluded from the political power and, consequently, in the decentred and decentralised knowledges produced by these groups and suppressed by science, the most emblematic instance of intellectual authority of Western modernity. What is of particular interest in Foucault's critique of modernity and its institutionalised scientific knowledge for the articulation of projects with epistemological claims of the kind postcolonialism or critical Islam/ism make, is the idea of insurrection of subjugated knowledges. For Foucault, subjugated knowledges are those

historical contents that have been buried and disguised in a functionalist or formal systemisation. (...). Subjugated knowledges are thus those blocs of historical knowledge which were present but disguised within the body of functionalist and systematising theory and which criticism – which obviously draws upon scholarship – has been able to reveal. (...) [It is] a particular, local, regional knowledge, a differential knowledge incapable of unanimity and which owes its force only to the harshness with which it is opposed by everything surrounding it – that is through the re-appearance of this knowledge, of these local knowledges, these disqualified knowledges, that criticism performs its work' (1980: 81-82).

In the above passage Foucault not only defines the nature of subjugated knowledges and the process through which they acquire their lesser status of subjugation compared to the superiority of modern science, but he also endows these knowledges and the critics who uncover them with a specific political role, that of resisting science and its objects. Employing archaeology as his methodology of analysis of local discursivities and genealogy as his tactics, Foucault embarks on a project to draw attention to the 'local, discontinuous, disqualified, illegitimate knowledges'

against a hegemonic, not to say totalitarian, unitary theory that would hierarchise and typologise them in the name of 'true knowledge' (ibid). The opposition to the scientific hierarchisation of knowledge becomes the project inscribed within the potential of these distorted and fragmented genealogies. Whether this 'insurrection' is the outcome of insurgency of 'local', 'ethnic' or in any other way culturally specific groups or the effect of the intellectual, academic reinstitution/reactivation of these knowledges on the groups themselves, is a question that runs across the analysis of those who recognise in Islam/ism a potential of critique and radical (i.e. emancipatory) politics, as we shall see in the examination of the question of 'resistance'.

It is exactly this idea of reinstituting culturally specific ways of knowing the world that animates counter-hegemonic epistemic movements such as Islamic, postmodern or postsecular feminism, or postcolonialism as we have seen in the previous chapters and will further explore here. In order to do so, this chapter starts by questioning both the historical and theoretical grounds which sustain the explanatory relationship between postcolonialism and Islam/ism and proceeds to disclose the political potential of postcolonial theory in order to show that it is eventually opposed rather than germane to the ethical and political project imagined by Islamism. Then, the chapter moves on to discuss in detail the most significant effort to draw a theoretical, postcolonial project based on Islam/ism, Bobby Sayyid's *Fundamental Fear*, whilst it looks at other significant efforts which attempt to bring together postcolonialism and Islam/ism by reference to the idea of resistance. Finally, the chapter concludes by offering an explanation as to why Islamism is still thought as 'postcolonial' despite its diverging political orientation.

4.2 The historical grounds of the relationship between postcolonialism and Islam/ism

In the ongoing academic and public debates about the politicisation of religion and the nature of secular political cultures Muslim political activism has been increasingly presented under the banner of 'postcolonialism' and the two terms, Islam/ism and postcolonialism, often appear in tandem in publications (Majeed 2009; Dabashi 2008; Gauch 2006; Majid 2000, 2007; Sayyid 2003), conferences ('Postcolonialism and Islam, NAPS')⁴¹ and postgraduate curricula (for instance the

⁴¹ www.naps-online.org/?cat=17

postgraduate seminars 'Postcolonial Locations Seminar' in Sussex⁴², 'Postcolonialism, Orientalism, Eurocentrism' in Swansea⁴³ and 'Postcolonial Studies' at York⁴⁴ include Islam in their lists of topics to be addressed). What this postcolonial framework seems to imply is that the recent Muslim political activism, whether in its violent, militarist forms or in its softer culturalist versions, needs to be understood as a manifestation of the legacy of colonialism (or of the process of decolonisation), as an understandable reaction to the political and epistemic violence inflicted by the 'West' on the 'Rest'. The link between the two terms, between postcolonialism as a theoretical framework and Islam/ism as a political movement but also as a critical stance in social research is claimed to be two-fold: historical, by reference to the lived experience of colonialism; and theoretical, by reference to the postmodern/poststructuralist turn. It is important to clarify that the use of the term Islam/ism here does not refer to the military or violent action of Islamist activist groups or Islamist states (such as Iran or Saudi Arabia). Instead, consistently with the focus of this study as a whole, this chapter looks at those threads within social theory and literary criticism which have developed a sympathetic stance toward the argument of Muslim groups advocating that the accommodation of religious consciousness-and-practice in the public space is an indispensable component of their identity not only as human beings (for the issue is not limited to questions of consciousness and private beliefs), but as citizens whose life cannot be meaningful and whose freedom cannot be fully enjoyed unless the markers of their Islamic faith are visibly perceptible. In other words, by the term Islam/ism I refer specifically to those positions advocating for the kind of culturalist politics which endorses a view of culture-as-religion and therefore see Islam as the principal and overdetermining instance of social existence.

The relationship between postcolonialism and Islam/ism, as mentioned above, is undergirded by two sets of inter-related assumptions: firstly, historical ones which refer to the common experience of colonialism, the anticolonial struggles and the neocolonial predicament, especially after 09/11.⁴⁵ The second set of assumptions is theoretical/epistemological and can be broadly

⁴²http://209.85.229.132/search?q=cache:qnqIHCIVFekJ:www.sussex.ac.uk/gchums/documents/postcolonial_locations_08.doc+postcolonialism+and+islam&cd=49&hl=en&ct=clnk&gl=uk&client=firefox-a

⁴³ <http://www.swan.ac.uk/politics/PostgraduateStudy/MastersModules/PostcolonialismOrientalismEurocentrism/>

⁴⁴ http://www.york.ac.uk/depts/engl/gsp/taughtma/poco_sem.pdf

⁴⁵ The distinction between anticolonial and postcolonial thinking has been itself a point of friction in scholarly debates, a crucial difference being that anticolonial thinking saw the relationship between coloniser and colonised in clear opposition, whereas postcolonial thinking tends to problematise this relationship. Indeed thinkers who are recognised today as part of the postcolonial canon, such as Fanon, fall – from a strictly theoretical perspective – into the category of anticolonial rather than postcolonial thinking. According to Chakrabarty (2009) there is considerable overlap between

situated within the postmodern/poststructuralist turn. It raises questions about the perspectival - and inextricably entangled with power - nature of scientific ('Eurocentric') knowledge, as well as abandonment of the unified subject of the Enlightenment and the political projects of emancipation engendered by its philosophy. However, we need to take a closer look at the assumptions underpinning the relationship between these two threads of the critique of Eurocentrism, i.e. the postcolonial and the Islamist one. In terms of the evocation of history and experience of the colonialist past, the inclusion of Islam/ism within the explanatory framework of postcolonialism seems indeed an appropriate one as many parts of the Islamic world⁴⁶ have been subordinated to the European powers throughout the era of colonialism. Having said this however, it is important to bear in mind that those who remained sceptical to the merits of postcolonial theoretical enterprise (Ahmad 1995; Moghadam 2006) noticed the historical imprecision located occasionally in the all-encompassing interpretation of Islam through the lenses of the postcolonial trope, such as the case of Turkey, for instance, which was an imperial power itself (though not of the modern sort); or the case of Iran which has never been colonised and on which, incidentally, some of the recent Islamic feminist scholarship focuses by way of postcolonial critique (e.g. Moallem 2005). Indeed postcolonial studies have been justly criticised for sacrificing historical accuracy to the general - even if politically legitimate - aim of 'decolonising' the history and consciousness of subaltern subjects of the postcolonial world. For instance, Bayart, commenting on the ever-expansion⁴⁷ of postcolonialism in field and disciplines of study, notes:

the two currents if one looks at those registers of thinking employed by anticolonial thinkers which revolve around questions of hybridity, difference and anti-essentialism.

⁴⁶ The usage of the term 'Islamic world' here is descriptive, i.e. meant in the historical-geographical sense. It does not intend to imply that Islam should be seen as the engine of history in the cultures and societies in which it is the predominant religious dogma.

⁴⁷ Along with the ever-expansion of postcolonial studies what can also be questioned is the extent to which the overemphasis on the effects of colonialism, or imperialism de-historicises the societies or phenomena studied. In his article *Goodbye to the Tristes Tropes* (1993: 6) the anthropologist Marshall Sahlins comments on the attitude of a 'certain historiography that is quick to take the "great game" of imperialism as the only game in town. It is prepared to assume that history is made by the colonial masters, and that all that needs to be known about the people's own social dispositions, or even their 'subjectivity', is the external disciplines imposed upon them: the colonial policies of classification, enumeration, taxation, education, and sanitation'. What Sahlins criticises with regards to the 'new reflexive anthropology' (1993: 1) is perhaps of interest about postcolonialism too: by prioritising the colonial practices - some of which are inextricably related to the inventions of modern science, the modern State and modern governmentality - the Other is once again devoid of its substance as she seen as an effect of colonialist logic and its practical applications. The 'Other as history' (Prakash 1992: 2) is erased as an effect of Western invention only.

The university prisons will soon be full, as postcolonial studies have now taken all situations of dominance through the ages as their province, without fear of anachronism or absurdity. This includes the Palestinians, of course, those victims of 'colonialism' or even of the Zionist apartheid regime, and the Turkish Gastarbeiter or guest workers in Germany, who are also deemed to be in a 'postcolonial' situation - although the 'coloniality' of Israel is debatable, and Turkey was never colonized. Ditto for the 'nationalities' within the Habsburg Empire, which however did not fall into the category of colonialism and never had possessions of that kind, unlike the German Reich or the Ottoman Empire (Bayart 2010: 17).⁴⁸

According to Bayart the indifference – 'the semantic carelessness' - displayed by the postcolonial perspective *vis-à-vis* the history of colonised societies stems from their general reluctance to offer a precise or restrictive definition of the colonial (2010: 50-51).⁴⁹ Bayart argues that it is precisely this indifference towards historical accuracy (one could even claim towards historicity itself)⁵⁰ that allows for a certain conceptual colonisation on behalf of postcolonial studies of situations 'whose character' as Bayart notices 'is at the very least debatable - as in the case of Zionism' (2010: 51) or in the argument which sees 'a direct line between colonisation and collaboration with Nazism' (2010: 62-63).⁵¹

⁴⁸ Here I use the English translation of Bayart's book by Andrew Brown ('Postcolonial Studies: A Political Invention of Tradition), available on the London Debates 2010, School of Advances Study, University of London webpage, http://www.sas.ac.uk/fileadmin/documents/postgraduate/Papers_London_Debates_2010/Bayart_Post-colonial_studies.pdf (accessed December 2010). All page citations, however, refer to the original book in French.

⁴⁹ This reluctance towards restrictive definition seems indeed constitutive of postcolonialism, if we follow Bhabha and Comaroff's (2002: 30) delineation of the field: 'Postcoloniality, our defining term, became less a name or a topic, and more a way of making connections or articulations across a range of topics and themes, a locus for theoretical and political reflections rather than a label'.

⁵⁰ As we have seen in the previous chapter, postcolonial theory, largely relying on the poststructuralist insights, has an ambiguous attitude towards history, on the one hand claiming to re-write the past of the subaltern on the other rejecting history itself as a 'European construct'. The discussion about the 'crisis of historicity' (Jameson 1991) is central in the dispute between Marxists and poststructuralist/postmodern theorists. Whereas poststructuralists think that their epistemology 're-introduces history' Bennington and Young (1987: 1-2) - whilst rejecting historicism and the associated idea of 'progress' - for Marxists postmodernism is a 'theory of epochal change based on the denial of history' (Meiksins Wood 1997: 7).

⁵¹ This argument has a long pedigree in critical social theory. Hannah Arendt in her *Origins of Totalitarianism* (1973 [1950]) was possibly the first one to explore the genetic affinities between nineteenth century imperialist expansion and Nazism in the sense that they are both examples of totalitarianism. The same idea was taken further by Aimé Cesaire in his *Discourse on Colonialism* (2001) where Nazism is seen as a continuation of colonialism. Cesaire argues that Nazis did to Europeans what Europeans have been doing to the non-Western world for centuries of colonial overseas expansion and, in this perspective Nazism is seen as the 'boomerang effect' of colonial methods coming back to hit Europe. This argument has had an important effect in the recent efforts of 'decolonization of German theory' (Steinmetz 2006) where racism is prioritised as an autonomous causal factor, i.e. as instrumental in the logic of colonial capitalism (Grosfoguel 2009a), in contrast to the Marxist emphasis on economic or political determinants where racism is seen not as an instance of oppression but as a case of exploitation (Ebert 2005). Following this logic then, 'Nazism is also coming to be seen as, among other things, the apotheosis of a series of imperial and colonial expansions, that is to

Bayart argues that the void created by the de-historicisation of colonised societies is refilled by the ‘illusion of cultural identity’ (Bayart 1996). The concept of identity is conferred a ‘quasi-ontological status’ (2010: 45) and subsequently reproduces the identitarian categories produced by the epistemic hegemony of the West which the postcolonial project had set off to dismantle in the first place (2010: 66). Bayart (2010: 45) notices that in France, for instance, the ethnicisation of the social and political issue of the riots in suburbs in 2005 – and for that matter, the greatly debated issues of the ban of veil and more recently of burqa – and their problematisation exclusively in terms of racism silences totally the dimensions of ‘class struggle’ and ‘classism’ (and one could add of gender too)⁵² which are certainly involved here. The discussion about the recent politicisation of Islam in the UK has followed a similar pattern: the public debate about Islam has also been framed either in terms of subjectivity – i.e. in terms of ‘cultural, ‘ethnic’ or ‘religious’ identity – or in terms of Islamophobia, a concept which also subsumes the socio-economic aspects of the issue under a blanket notion of ‘Muslim identity’ as discussed in detail in chapter six.

However, even if one has to agree with Bayart that postcolonial studies overvalue the specificity of colonialism *vis-à-vis* other forms of imperial domination and that this singularisation contributes to the over-simplification of the colonial moment (2010: 46), even if its methodological predilection for discourses and representations can lead to exaggerated generalisations (2010: 44), the postcolonial perspective has much more to offer as a philosophical possibility than critics like Bayart are willing to acknowledge. Especially, as I will attempt to demonstrate below, some of its central theoretical constructs are far from promoting a view of ‘colonialism as one-dimensional, restricting it to an exclusive relationship between the colonized and the colonizer’ (2010: 83). And even more, as the consideration of those iconic concepts of postcolonial theory is conducive not to the uncritical inclusion of Islamism into the postcolonial

say, as a form of empire’ (Steinmetz 2006: 8). Even more recently, the Holocaust has been linked to the project of decolonial thinking and the ‘logic of coloniality’ which located its gestations in the sixteenth century and the rise of modernity itself (Mignolo 2007). See also the summer school in the University of Utrecht on ‘Coloniality, Slavery and the Holocaust: Introducing the Decolonial Option, <http://www.utrechtsummerschool.nl/index.php?type=courses&code=S21> accessed July 2011), which explores the link between the two.

⁵² The issue of the veil bitterly divided feminists in France, precisely along the opposing lines of the identitarian politics of recognition on the one hand and the social politics of equality on the other. Winter (2006) gives an informed account of the fracture within the feminist field in France following ‘l’affaire du foulard’. For a critique of the ‘political hysteria’ over the veil which avoids the slippage to the analytical category of identity, see Terray 2004.

political agenda but to the actual use of postcolonial theory as a critical tool to dissect the nature of Islamism as a political, ethical and epistemological project.

4.3 The political potential of postcolonial theory

The Islamist critique - academic and public - seems to share much with the political culture of dissent and the vocabulary of protest and resistance of postcolonial studies. It also shares the postcolonial suspicion against Eurocentric epistemologies and the fierce critique of secularism. As already mentioned in the previous chapters, secularism in these strands of anti-Eurocentrism is understood both as the normative separation of the public/reason versus private/religion and as the body of secular epistemologies in which religion is the explanandum rather than the explanans. Even more, this critique is indicative of a more generalised turn towards the enunciation of postsecular modes of analysis in social science (McLennan 2007, 2010) and develops either around the violence committed against religious sensitivities, or around the structural limitations of any epistemology based on naturalistic/humanistic understanding to account for nonsecular 'ways of being in the world'. The academic recognition that there is indeed an 'Islamic challenge' to the 'power/knowledge complex of western order' (Sayyid 2006), i.e. the recognition of an Islamic, or Islamist, epistemological rather than solely political challenge, is symptomatic of the rise of a new explicitly antiseccular order in social science. For instance, the fact that Sayyid's article on 'Islam and Knowledge' figures in the prestigious 2006, 23(2-3) *Theory, Culture and Society* special volume on 'Problematizing Global Knowledge', along with other articles on religion, is indicative of the trend which aspires to blur the fundamental divide between faith and reason in secular epistemologies of social science.

However, what needs to be noted here is that not all postcolonial critics are anti-secularists. To take perhaps the most prominent example, Edward Said, the founding father of the field, had repeatedly declared his commitment to the epistemic and political ethos of secularism (1985), associated with 'humanistic critique' (2003 [1978]: xvii) and the 'desire for enlightenment and emancipation' (xxiii). As the scholars who have most engaged with his work notice, Said was not only indifferent to religion but he was antagonistic to it (Hart 2000). For Said, it is vital to 'resist the quasi religious authority of culture', the 'authority of being comfortably at home among one's people, supported by known powers and acceptable values, protected against the outside world'

(1983: 15-16). In that sense, for Said there is not such a thing as religious critique or religious intellectuals. In fact, and to the great disappointment (and often ignorance) of those who seek to ground their enthusiasm of Islamic revivalism - even in the case of Palestine itself - in the Saidian legacy, Said would probably retort that there is no hope for resistance arising from religion *per se*. His references to Hamas, the Palestinian Islamic political party and organisation, are quite telling in that respect. In the *Politics of Dispossession* Said recites that:

In 1992 when I was there, I briefly met a few of the student leaders who represent Hamas: I was impressed by their sense of political commitment but not at all by their ideas. I found them quite moderate when it came to accepting the truths of modern science, for instance...their leaders neither especially visible nor impressive, their writings rehashes of old nationalist tracts, now couched in an 'Islamic' idiom (1995: 403).

Whereas in *Peace and Its Discontents*, he concludes:

I know that the organization is one of the only ones expressing resistance.... Yet for any secular intellectual to make a devil's pact with a religious movement is, I think, to substitute convenience for principle (1996: 111).

Later, Said did not hesitate to qualify the Islamic resistance as 'violent and primitive (...) what Hobsbawm calls precapital, trying to get back to communal forms, to regulate personal conduct with simpler and simpler reductive ideas' (2002: 416). As for his own work often been quoted by Islamists - and nowadays by those who see a critical, emancipatory potential in Islamic revivalism - Said had expressed his concern, if not frustration: 'I find my opinions misinterpreted, especially where they include substantial critiques of Islamic movements. First, I am secular; second, I don't trust religious movements and third I disagree with these movements' methods, means, analyses and values' (ibid: 437). Finally, in his *Humanism and Democratic Criticism*, Said reiterated that 'religious enthusiasm is perhaps the most dangerous of threats to the humanistic enterprise, since it is patently anti-secular and antidemocratic in nature, and in its monotheistic forms as a kind of politics about as intolerably inhumane and downright unarguable as can be' (2004: 51). Incidentally, it is precisely the clarity and tenacity of this secular position throughout his highly inspirational and quoted work that cost Said to be accused himself of Orientalism, in an ironic turn which reminds Bayart's comment on the never-ending invention of postcolonial subjects cited above, and by extension, of Orientalist culprits. Following this rationale Hard argues that

'Said rejects the Orientalists' distinction between Western rationality and Eastern mysticism only to readmit and valorize this distinction under the rubrics of secularism and religion' (2000: 86). I will return to the point of religious resistance at the last section of the chapter in order to examine its problematical use by those authors who argue for the critical and/or emancipatory role of Islamic revivalism.

However, it is not only the initial foundation of the field of postcolonialism on clearly secular premises that poses a problem for the inclusion of Islam/ism in the postcolonial curriculum. I would like to argue that any similarities claimed on theoretical grounds are essentially rhetorical and therefore ostensible to a great extent. The theoretical assumptions of postcolonial theory, its concepts and its analyses (even more the political imaginaries they point to) are diverging rather than converging with the ones associated with Islam/ism, as the general use of the term postcolonial Islam or the frequent inclusion of Islam in the curricula of postgraduate studies or academic publications seems to assume. In fact, I maintain that Islamism as an ideology prioritising purity over amalgamation and which is articulated around the idealisation of tradition could not be farther from postcolonialism's acceptance of the fragility but also fluidity characterising our pasts and presents, our tradition(s) and modernity(ies). By this I mean to say that postcolonialism is a theoretical strand which develops around the problematisation of cultural domination or, better, cultural imperialism. This is not only in the sense of making manifest the convergence of colonial expansion, imperialist cruelty and scientific inquiry which gave rise to the cultural stereotyping of the Orient as advocated by Said in *Orientalism* (1978/2003). Postcolonial theory may be more radical than Said in its critique of the epistemological basis of Western knowledge and often explicitly suspicious of the very central ideas of the Enlightenment project, such as progress (Chakrabarty 1992, 2000; Prakash 1990, 1992) yet, simultaneously, it also engenders the possibility of a two-way transformation of the West *and* the postcolonial.

For the purpose of drawing out this possibility, let us look at some of the most seminal conceptual constructs which have marked the articulation and application of postcolonial theory. The possibility of transformation lies within postcolonial theory, it lies within its very analyses of the ambiguous nature of cultural domination. Bhabha's (1994: 121-131) concept of *mimicry* is

exemplary in capturing this tension,⁵³ in bringing to the fore this, not so obvious yet essential, aspect of the relationship of cultural domination. The act of *mimicry* is a strategy adopted by the colonised subject as a result of the internalisation of the coloniser's system of cultural values, a strategy which threatens and generates anxiety to the coloniser. Therefore *mimicry*, as 'a sign of double articulation', as a strategy of the 'appropriation' of the Other by visualising power, does not only refer to immediate, direct violence but also to the more obscure facet of the relationship of cultural domination, to the way the dominant and the dominated construct their own Other. The understanding of the relationship of cultural domination as a two-way process rather than as a one-dimensional and predictable outcome is also embedded in the concept of *hybridity* which allows for the destabilisation of binaries and the hierarchisations they impose. Thus, opening a space to think of cultures as interacting, transgressing and transforming *each other* beyond the limitations of the traditional binary oppositions of Western thinking/knowledge (1994: 19; 169; 240; 277; 296; 322). Therefore, one could argue that this kind of approach, despite the radical critique of the Western modalities of rationalisation, allows for a two-way transformation, for the re-interpretation of the political and epistemic discourses of modernity. As such, the postcolonial approach is clearly diverging from the monosemantic dystopian representations of modernity as a destructive force which are common place in the Islamist discourse.

The same kind of concern about the possibility, not to say *necessity*, for transformation lies at the heart of Spivak's (1990) strategic move of *catachresis*, essentially, like in Bhabha's case, a move of appropriation of the coloniser's (political) culture. For Spivak, concepts and/or political claims such as nationhood, constitutionality, citizenship or democracy are coded within the legacy of imperialism and as such they are concepts-metaphors with no historically adequate referent in the postcolonial space. However, for Spivak, the fact that the authoritative (the 'correct') narrative was produced in Western Europe does not make the claims less important. *Catachresis* emerges as a strategy, as a process by which the colonised displaces, seizes and re-inscribes the code value of political claims, concepts and epistemologies (1990: 204, 206-207). Spivak's catachrestical move then has important epistemological and political implications as it raises questions concerning matters of authority (who has the authority to speak about concepts or claims), content (what are the prerequisites for the definition of concepts and claims), context (the 'postcolonial' and the

⁵³ Even if one must agree with Bayart (2010: 93) and other critics that mimicry, or otherwise representation, is not the only - or even perhaps a sufficient (Krishnaswamy 2002: 111) - avenue to understand the dynamics of cultural hegemony.

‘Western’) and so on. A wide range of ‘Western’ political claims, or concepts-metaphors, are at stake in the postcolonial and the Western space itself, such as equality, rights, feminism, secularism, or sociological knowledge and their re-definition in relation to the local – postcolonial or otherwise – and the new global context is an open-ended process in which postcolonial theory, as it has been argued (Bhabra 2007), may have a great, even revolutionary, role to play. Whether postcolonialism represents a real ground-breaking possibility to transform the way we understand the social world remains an open debate. However, what can be established now is that *transformation* is a central issue in postcolonial thinking. It is this potential of mutual transformation, the possibility of re-writing the grammar of those important concepts and claims that may allow postcolonial theory to succeed in overcoming the conceptual binaries and political dilemmas of constructs such as the West versus the postcolonial, the West versus Islam, the West versus the Rest and so on.

4.4 Postcolonialism meets Islam/ism

The transformative potential of these concepts, the practical and political implications stemming from the methodology of deconstruction favoured by postcolonialism are very different from the ones suggested by the Islamist critique, which has a different objective altogether and this despite their common radical rhetoric. In order to demonstrate this, let us consider the most consistent attempt to inscribe Islamism in the project of ‘provincializing Europe’, the work of Sayyid and especially his book *A Fundamental Fear. Eurocentrism and the Emergence of Islamism* (2003 [1997]). As this section will demonstrate, even in this elaborate attempt, ‘Islam-as-critique’ fails to engender concepts grasping the complexity of cultural domination as a two-way relationship, or to think productively about transformation. Sayyid’s book represents the most radical and theoretically sophisticated argument advocating a different, i.e. poststructuralist/postcolonial, understanding of the nature of the Islamist project. In Sayyid’s poststructuralist account, Islam is conceptualised as ‘a master-signifier’ (2003: viii), the emergence of Islamism is seen ‘as being a product of the shift in Muslim final vocabularies’ (2003: 138), Islamism itself is defined as ‘a project which attempts to transform Islam from a nodal point in discourses of Muslim communities into a master signifier (...) for the political order’ (2003: 48), and subsequently Islamists are described as ‘those who use Islamic metaphors to narrate their political projects’ (2003: 157). Via the deployment of a poststructuralist framework, Sayyid essentially advocates,

first, the deeply political – ‘subversive’ to be precise (2009: 198) - character of the Islamist movement, and, second, its genuine ability to offer an alternative universal meta-narrative, allegedly free in its conceptualisation and vocabulary from Western influence, as exemplified by the case of Khomeinism.

In fact, few analysts would disagree that Islamism is indeed a political movement - for some it is a revolt against modernity, for others a product of modernity, or postmodernity and their discontents. But what Sayyid hopes to demonstrate with the weaving of a (poststructuralist) conceptual narrative is to grasp what seems to escape modernist, materialist, empirical or factual approaches of the phenomenon: i.e. that Islamism is political not merely in the mundane sense of involvement in the definition of what the ‘good community’ is, but also in the sense that it seeks to produce a different meaning or explanation of the social world, or, in Foucauldian terms, a different ‘regime of truth’. Sayyid argues that what modernist analyses fail to see in Islamic revivalism is its contribution to the articulation of a new ‘post-western’ (2006: 179) order. In this new order of things, ‘Europe’, or the ‘West’, loses the exclusivity of universal metanarrative and its status of adjudicator over all other narratives. To put it in Sayyid’s words ‘the West and the centre are no longer to be synonymous’ (2003: 128-129). In this ‘empty-hearted’ world (2003: 110) created by the decentring of Europe, Islamism emerges as that logic which ‘necessitates the provincialization of the West and its relocation as one centre among many’ (2003: 128).

In that sense Sayyid’s account of Islamism as an instance of ‘difference’ to hegemonic Eurocentrism still qualifies as postcolonial, since it adheres to a signature thesis of postcolonial theory, i.e. that secular or politically progressive forms of life do not and should not have the monopoly of defining ways to lead a meaningful and fulfilling life. But Sayyid’s enterprise also follows the problematical attitude towards historicity within postcolonialism examined above, i.e. the tendency of the field to take under its critical span almost all situations of domination as ‘postcolonial’ or ‘subaltern’ and to uphold a conception of colonialism beyond and above historical and geographical constraints. Hence, ‘coloniality is not to be understood merely in the sense of colonialism, but rather refers to the logic of governmentality that not only supports specific forms of historical colonialism but continues to structure a planetary hierarchy in terms of a distinction between West and the non-West’ (2009: 193).

It is not only 'coloniality' which is conceptualised ideologically rather than pragmatologically in Sayyid's account. 'Europe' as well is treated as an ideological rather than specifically historical and geographical entity, whereas Islam becomes a unitary object, a 'monist abstraction' to use Halliday's (1999: 894) words. It is precisely this choice, an effect of his methodological approach, i.e. poststructuralism and its immanent inflation of linguistic categories, that allows Sayyid to endow Islamism with the power of a metanarrative which can generate 'universal values' (2003: xxii) and contribute to the 'post-western' order of things. Therefore, it comes as little surprise that there is no discussion in Sayyid's account of what Islamists actually maintain, or of those specific elements and assumptions in the Islamist project that qualify as 'postcolonial', 'postmodern' or even 'post-western', politically as well as epistemologically. No doubt there is a great deal of rhetoric, practices and aspirations that would qualify as 'anti-modern' and 'anti-Western' and even 'anti-colonial', but this political attitude of resistance and/or rejection does not automatically guarantee that Islamism offers a conceptual shift in the ways to narrate the social, similar or parallel to the 'posts' that have marked the intellectual history of modernity. Besides, by Sayyid's own admission, the ability of 'Islamicate' society to narrate the West will be limited as long as it relies on residual categories such as the 'West and the Rest' or the 'western' and the 'non-western' (2005: 43). In spite of Sayyid's call to 'radical decolonization' rather than mere 'demonization of the West' (2003: xiii), Islamism is articulated along the lines of opposition between 'Islam versus the West'. Its appeal is not the effect of its conceptual ability to construct a new semantic order of ambiguity, fluidity, hybridity or undecidability by way of postmodern critique of modernity (2003: 120) but the fierce, clear-cut and uncompromising rejection of a monolithic, nonetheless vague 'West'.

To be sure Sayyid does point to the fact that Islamists need to contribute toward the formation of a 'global Islamicate' or 'Ummatic' culture (2003: xiv) and explores the analytical merits of the consideration of the Muslim Ummah as a 'diaspora' (again defined as a 'political' rather than 'geographical' concept, 2000: 41). Various objections can be raised against these abstract and empirically detached terms and definitions, but here I want to draw attention to the fact that the absence of any substantial discussion of Islamist discourse *per se* leads Sayyid to see a rigid, unapologetically universalist and necessarily totalising project as an instance of postmodern, postcolonial politics or as an intellectual exercise in multitude. Naturally, Sayyid is aware of that Islamism has no room for incredulity toward its own metanarrative and little desire to recognise

its own regime of truth as simply one amongst many in the world (2003: 117-118). However, it seems that as long it is anti-western and enunciated 'from another centre outside the orbit of the West' (2003: 120), the Islamist metanarrative still qualifies as postmodern and this despite its 'grand claims and essentialist categories marshalled in an uncompromising absolutist language' (2003: 118).

Indeed under Sayyid's poststructuralist eyes, there is a convergence 'between "internal" critics of the West and the Islamist critique of western hegemony' (2003: 118), even if the only common ground they share is the rhetorical rejection of the vague and all-encompassing 'Western ideology'. However, what allows for this convergence is not the postmodern character of Islamist discourse but the fact that the discourse about Islamism gets increasingly postmodernised. Put differently, it is not the discourse of Islamism, but Sayyid's discourse about Islamism that is postmodern. Sayyid's account is a prime example of a specific trend which conflates the object with the tools and framework of analysis: in that sense it is not the social phenomenon that is postcolonial but the angle from which we look at it. Sayyid, as many others who follow the path of the anti-Orientalist or anti-Eurocentric critique, accuses the non-postmodern accounts of Islam/ism of confusing history with historiography (2000: 45-46; 2005: 33) and of producing hierarchies between the 'civilised West' and the 'barbaric East' by employing genealogical accounts based on this conflation. Undeniably, the intellectual hegemony of the West is based on specific accounts of history. The most valuable knowledge that the postmodern turn brought about was the awareness that history is always historiographical. In that sense Sayyid's account of the history of Islamism (i.e. his account of the trajectory from the fall of - vilified - Kemalism to the rise of - idealised - Khomeinism), his entire critical enterprise is also the outcome, the product of a specific historiography, the kind of historiography enabled by the postmodern turn. This is not claiming that all history is essentially ideological, but simply pointing out that the same meta-theoretical standpoint which allows us to offer a critique (in the sense of determining the limits of a specific approach) of Eurocentric accounts of the world should allow us to see the limitations of the postmodern and postcolonial approaches and adopt the distinct ethical stance for which they have been known: reflexivity vis-à-vis our tools of investigation and the awareness of the ever-constructed character of our objects of analysis.

In terms of the rhetoric of rejection of western hegemony and the focus on the epistemological promise of non-Eurocentric projects, Sayyid's poststructuralist critical Islam/ism appears to share a greater overlap with more recent attempts stemming from broadly postcolonial concerns, such as the decolonial project. The reason for considering the decolonial project here is not only because it is germane to postcolonialism in terms of political motivation and epistemological aspiration, but also because Sayyid's critical Islam/ism and decolonial thinking seem to converge in the intellectual and political initiative of 'Critical Muslim Thought', materialised in a series of summer schools in Granada.⁵⁴ But let us first see what does the decolonial project attempt to achieve, how it differs from postcolonialism, and how it compares with Sayyid's critical Islam/ism. Mignolo, whose work holds together with Quijano's foundational article 'Coloniality and Modernity/Rationality' (2007)⁵⁵ a seminal place in the development of decolonial thinking, defines the decolonial project in his 'Manifesto' as one of 'epistemic disobedience' (2007: 37) or otherwise of 'epistemic shift' which emerged at the very foundation of modernity/coloniality, as its counterpoint, first in the Americas and later in Asia and Africa (2007: 5). Mignolo's argument (2007: 5) stresses the inextricable relationship between the modernity of coloniality by linking the 'salvationist' rhetoric of the first with the 'oppressive' and 'condemnatory' logic of the latter. Therefore, he sees the task of decolonial thinking as above all epistemological and emerging from the necessity to a. de-link thinking from the European categories all together, 'from the tyranny of time as the categorical frame of modernity' (2007: 16) and b. seek a different beginning 'not in Greece but in the responses to the "conquest and colonization" of America and the massive trade of enslaved Africans' (3-4). In that sense, at first glance, Mignolo, like Sayyid, seems to think that the challenge of decolonial thinking is above all epistemic: his project seeks to decentre modernity by depriving it from its status as an ontological point in history, by demonstrating its position as a narrative (albeit dominant) among others. The two projects also converge in their desire to inscribe the genealogy of decolonial and Islam/ist thinking outside the genealogy of European rationality.

The same goes with Grosfoguel (2009a: 11) for whom 'the decolonization of knowledge would require to take seriously the epistemic perspective/cosmologies/insights of critical thinkers from

⁵⁴ This summer school was initially launched in 2010 for the 2011 summer under the name of 'Critical Islamic Thinking' and under the direction of Ramon Grosfoguel (examined in this section) at the time, to change into 'Critical Muslim Thought: Decolonial Struggles, Theology of Liberation and Islamic Revival' in view of the 2012 summer school <http://dialoglobal.com/granada/index.php>

⁵⁵ This article, however, builds on the initial version published earlier in Spanish, see Quijano 1991.

the Global South thinking from and with subalternised racial/ethnic/spiritual/sexual spaces and bodies'. Grosfoguel's (2009a: 26) contribution to decolonialism focuses on the project of 'critical border thinking' which is defined as:

the epistemic response of the subaltern to the Eurocentric project of modernity, which instead of rejecting modernity to retreat into a fundamentalist absolutism, border epistemologies subsume/redefines the emancipatory rhetoric of modernity from the cosmologies and epistemologies of the subaltern, located in the oppressed and exploited side of the colonial difference, towards a decolonial liberation struggle for a world beyond eurocentered modernity.

In that sense, Grosfoguel, following Dussel (2001) situates critical border thinking at the exact opposite of Habermas's unfinished project of modernity, as an unfinished and incomplete project of decolonisation (ibid). Echoing Foucault's subjugated knowldges mentioned above, Grosfoguel – despite his rejection of poststructuralism as we shall see below - sees all knowledges as epistemically located in the dominant or the subaltern side of power relations without, however, collapsing the social location into the epistemic and seeing those on the oppressed side of power relations as necessarily thinking from a subaltern epistemic location, since knowledge produced from below does not automatically qualify as an epistemic subaltern knowledge (2009a: 14). In that sense, his critique is considerably more astute in relation to those authors who automatically read Islam/ism as postcolonial based on its geopolitical location or the status of Muslims as oppressed minorities.

For Grosfoguel, the hegemony of 'Eurocentric fundamentalism' is constructed by assuming a 'zero-point' epistemology from which epistemic knowledge is thought as universal, neutral, value-free and objective (2009b: 98). It is from this point of view, which is 'beyond a point of view', that 'the "rest" of the epistemologies and cosmologies in the world are subalternized as myth, religion and folklore, and that the downgrading of any form of non-Western knowledge occurs' (ibid). In Grosfoguel's view this is how 'epistemic racism' (a term that he borrows from Mignolo) is produced: through the 'sacralization' of the Western tradition of thought and the inferiorisation of non-Western epistemologies and cosmologies (2009b: 99), of which Islam is a prime example. 'Occidentalism' Grosfoguel argues, creates 'the epistemic privilege and hegemonic identity politics of the West from which to judge and produce knowledge about the "Others"'.

Hence 'the subalternization and inferiorization of Islam were not merely a downgrading of Islam as spirituality, but also as an epistemology' (2006: 8). This where Grosfoguel's critical border thinking seems to be mostly attuned with Sayyid's critical Islam/ism regarding the way the West produces Orientalist knowledge about Islam.

However, these similarities collapse as soon as we see that their theoretical resources, the very epistemological essence of these projects is quite different, if not opposed. Both Mignolo and Grosfoguel unequivocally reject postmodernism and poststructuralism because they deem them caught within the Western canon reproducing within its domains of thought and practice a particular form of coloniality of power/knowledge (Grosfoguel 2009a: 11). As Mignolo (2007: 16) maintains, 'post-coloniality (post-colonial theory or critique) was born in the trap of (post) modernity. It is from there that Michel Foucault, Jacques Lacan, and Jacques Derrida have been the points of support for post-colonial critique (Said, Bhabha, Spivak)'. He argues that postcolonial studies and their genealogy are located in French poststructuralism than in the dense history of planetary de-colonial thinking (2007: 5-6). On the contrary, 'de-colonial thinking, upon de-linking itself from the tyranny of time as the categorical frame of modernity, also escapes the traps of post-coloniality' (ibid), it belongs to a different genealogy altogether.⁵⁶ One therefore wonders how Sayyid's explicitly poststructuralist narrative, the edifice upon which critical Islam/ism is build and the vehicle for the decolonisation of Islamic epistemologies, squares with the equally explicitly rejection of this methodology as already entangled in the nexus of coloniality.

Before coming to the closure of this section, it is important to remind that it is not only Sayyid that falls short of fulfilling the promise of postcolonialism. As mentioned above, the terms postcolonialism and postcolonial - both so ensnared that it is impossible to use the one without evoking the other - are used in a historically inaccurate fashion as well as being used purely descriptively or even in a misleading and confusing manner. Let us consider briefly an example of problematical use of these terms in the theorising of Muslim subjectivity. Majid, whose interventions in relation to Islamic feminism were discussed in chapter two, develops his more recent attempts to theorise Muslim subjectivity under the banner of postcolonialism, as the title of

⁵⁶ The extent to which decolonial thinking escapes the Western categories of thought would be a very interesting question to explore by addressing those genealogies which it claims as its forerunners, however, this would exceed the concerns of this chapter.

his 2000 book *Unveiling Traditions. Postcolonial Islam in a Polycentric World* explicitly states. Majid sets off by asserting that postcolonial theory has been particularly inattentive to the question of Islam (2000: 3-4) and that postcolonial critics never seriously examined the place of Islam in debates of multiculturalism (2000: vii). Embracing the familiar stance which rejects the secular/religious divide as adopted by many postcolonial authors, Majid also thinks that ‘the challenge of including Islamic subjectivities and cultural epistemologies into a world of equal differences has been left untheorized, probably because the religious imaginary is dismissed ahead of time as either conservative or unredeemable’ (ibid). Majid’s aim in this book is ‘to challenge secular academics to include the world’s nonsecular expressions as equally worthy of consideration and valid alternatives, and Muslim scholars to rethink their attachments to texts and canons that have obscured the egalitarian and viable legacies of Islam’ (2000: 153). So far indeed his project seems attuned with the general commitment of postcolonial studies in terms of questioning the prevalence of categories of Western thinking and of joining the struggle for a more ‘egalitarian’ epistemological consideration of nonsecular cosmologies.

The problem is, though, that on the other hand, Majid, is quite hostile to postcolonial theory, its concepts and its seminal authors on several accounts: echoing Dirlik’s Marxist uptake of postcolonialism, Majid criticises postcolonialism for its inability to recognise its own status as a possible effect of a new world order situation after colonialism (2000: 23-24), attacks Spivak for being a ‘depoliticized scholar’ and a ‘mediator of an unequal cultural exchange’ echoing Ahmad’s and Appiah’s critique of diasporic Third World intellectuals (2000: 27),⁵⁷ and openly sides with ‘the culturalists who insist that people ought to preserve their own traditions and resist the tempting illusion of melting into an alienating cosmopolitanism’ (2000: 3-4). Furthermore, he engages in a fierce critique of hybridity and syncretism as ‘the cause of so much trauma in the Third World’ (2000: 35-36) and of postmodernism, the epistemological source of the postcolonial theoretical enterprise, for ‘replacing utopian social project with theoretical playfulness’ (2000: 39) and creating those conditions within which ‘progressive definitions of Islam and other Western narratives of emancipation, such as Marxism, become archaically suspect’ (2000: 33). I have

⁵⁷ Here I refer to some of the most well-known signature texts and phrases of Marxist critique of postcolonial theory: “‘When exactly ... does the postcolonial begin?’” (...) When Third World intellectuals have arrived in the First World academe’ (Dirlik 1994: 328-329); ‘Postcoloniality is the condition of what we might ungenerously call a comprador intelligentsia: a relatively small, Western-style, Western-trained group of writers and thinkers, who mediate the trade in cultural commodities of world capitalism at the periphery’ (Appiah 1991: 348); “‘postcoloniality’ is postmodernism’s wedge to colonise literatures outside Europe and its North American offshoots’ (Ahmad 1995: 1).

already commented extensively on Majid's theoretical inconsistencies and on his questionable attempt to bring together Marxism and Islam/ism in chapter one. What I sought to point out here is the problematical and deceptive use of the terms postcolonial by the studies which argue for the critical – postcolonial most notably – nature of academic Islam/ism.

The failure of academic Islamism to engender possibilities of mutual transformation or to re-write the grammar of western concepts is the result of seeing the 'West' or modernity as nothing more than a menacing, one-dimensional hegemonic discourse. In that sense, Islamism fails to capture what postcolonialism engages with in the first place: the appropriation and re-inscription of what has been thought as Western in the postcolonial or in any other political dialect. This failure does not occur only because Islam is a religious dogma rather than a theoretical/epistemological project, but also because Islamist thinkers and theorists fail to acknowledge this basic fact. But even more, because along with the Islamist thinkers, many other theorists conflate radical rhetoric with radical and/or emancipatory social imaginaries and therefore fail to question the identification of Islam/ism as sociological critique or as cognate to the political projects of the radical Left, as explained below. If this explanatory relationship is not sustainable on theoretical grounds, then why Islamic revivalism has been increasingly theorised as 'postcolonial'? Why projects such as postcolonialism or decolonial thinking haste to integrate Islam/ism (and perhaps other versions of culturalist politics) in their theoretical and political universes?

4.5 The discourse of resistance and the contemporary Left academic and political culture

I would like to suggest that part of the answer to the question lies to the view of Islam as a site of resistance, either as a genuine emancipatory force, or as a moral corrective to the both Orientalist and Marxist accounts of Islam as backward or pre-political. This view is shared by both the 'reflexive disciplines' such as postcolonialism or poststructuralist feminism as well as the public discourses situated on the Left of the political spectrum, whether moderate (i.e. seeking the accommodation of Islam in the West) or radical (who see Islam as a metaphor for the toppling of capitalist system). The idea of 'resistance' is a core element in contemporary accounts of the politicisation of Islam and its conceptualisation as inherently critical or dissenting both in Muslim and non-Muslim accounts. The problem is that debating on the basis of inherent characteristics of cultures, civilisations or of the ethical universes of religious dogmas turns out to have little to do

with the anti-foundational, anti-essentialist standpoints that animate such approaches and a lot with the essentialist logic of Orientalism as the examples examined below demonstrate.

Take for instance, Abid-Moghaddam who does not find it 'too far fetched' to claim that it is the very 'presence of God in the Muslim mind that has repeatedly turned into Islam into a vehicle for critiquing the status quo' (2009: 140). Therefore, 'Muslims are one of the sources of global dissent' and 'Islam continues to be (...) a radical 'criticism of hegemony', a line of 'critical thinking' stretching 'from Farabi, Avicenna, al-Kindi and Averroes to German idealist philosophy in the Kantian tradition and Anglo-American Romanticism'. Here we witness a different kind of abstraction from Sayyid's, but one which actually has the same effect: the inscription of Islam/ism into the postmodern universe of 'dissent', 'multitude' and 'counter-hegemony' (2009: 153). It is exactly the idealisation of 'dissent', its abstraction of any real – historically concrete discussion – that allows Abid-Moghaddam to assert that 'while for the "West", at least since the nineteenth century onwards, the great dream of an end of history constitutes the guiding utopia of mankind, Islam continuously transcends history, continues to question the validity of the ontological realities surrounding us' (ibid). From a historical perspective though, the one that Abid-Moghaddam chooses to ignore, because he thinks that 'despite the shift towards a more rigid and totalitarian register since the early twentieth century, Islam remains closely tied to its original utopia' (ibid), it is not Islam that transcends history, but Abid-Moghaddam's ahistorical – idealist – approach. In spite of being aware of abstracting from disparate objects in order to construct an overarching, over-historical continuity of resistance, Abid-Moghaddam still thinks that 'it is fair to say that all of these 'saints', philosophers, poets and thinkers have searched for the ultimate communion of minds beyond confessional boundaries' (2009: 154). What brings them together is the fact that 'they refused to submit' (ibid). Here 'resistance' becomes the linguistic trope which allows Islam to assume the role of the transhistorical subaltern caught in a perennial struggle against a transhistorical 'power'. Ironically enough, such conclusion is not far from the opposite neo-Orientalist logic which animates the 'civilisational mission' of the US, where Christianity, or the 'West' as transhistorical agencies of 'good' are caught in a times immemorial battle against the equally transhistorical 'barbarity of Islam'.

Similarly, the idea of 'resistance' or 'dissent' is central in the articulation of critical projects of broadly Foucauldian inspiration in terms of unveiling subjugated knowldges which locate the

dissenting potential of Islam either in its history of heresy (Majid 2007), or in the very nature and historical role of Shia Islam (Dabashi 2008). Dissent holds a crucial place in Majid's latest book (2007) which builds its argument on the parallel story of history of heresy within the Islamic tradition on the one hand and the heretic traditions within American political thinking on the other. Majid believes that there is a clear analogy - even if many would disagree to what extent a theological, largely traditional, body of scholarship is comparable to a modern tradition of political thinking - between these two entities 'because of the strong universalist drives that Islam and America (or Americanism) generate, both could be treated as rivals in the struggle to shape minds and souls across the globe' (Majid 2007: 5). He, therefore, calls on both Muslims and Americans 'to embrace the heretical thought, or freethinking as the only-saving measure left to avoid an apocalyptic future' (2007: 1) as this constitutes in his eyes the only hope both cultures have to revitalise themselves (2007: 214). The contradiction here, which seems to escape Majid's attention, is again that the much denounced dominant Orientalist rationality which divides the world into 'Islam and the West' underlies the effort of overcoming this binary: the appeal to heresy is made towards these entities, Islam and the West (conveniently collapsed into 'America') precisely.

The rhetoric of resistance and dissent is also central in the edification of Dabashi's *Liberation Theology*. Starting with the premise that 'the most potent dialectical binary that was generated and sustained in the course of the Muslim colonial encounter with European modernity', i.e. 'Islam and the West' collapsed after 09/11, Dabashi tasks himself 'to investigate the emerging modes of Islamic revolutionary mobilization' (2008: 2). In that sense, he believes that 'we are at the threshold of a whole new reconfiguration of power and politics, empire-building, and moral and normative resistances to it' (ibid). The necessity of resistance to that empire 'can no longer be in puritanical Islamic judicial terms, but in emancipatory terms' (2008: 36), which must be 'categorically differentiating them from the sort of militant adventurism and senseless acts of violence identified with the figure of Osama bin Laden' (2008: 9). This new strategy of resistance, Dabashi believes, needs a new ethics which is 'other based, not self-based, Levinasian rather than Husserlian' (2008: 14). But it also requires a new mode of engagement with the Islamic theology – Dabashi's 'Islamic Liberation Theology' – which is based on viewing Islam as a religion of protest, as a paradox, which 'can only morally succeed when it is politically weak and combative, and conversely loses legitimacy when it is in political power' (2008: 61). More precisely, Dabashi

maintains that the source of such Islamic Theology of Liberation is Shi'ism because it is historically the most militant version of Islam. This assumption enables a representation of Shi'ism as a metaphor for dissent, as a condition which enables emancipation:

Shi'ism is Islam in its most combative claim upon the world. Shi'ism began with a negation, a denial, an usurpation. As a result, Shi'ism is ipso facto a religion of protest, a faith avenging itself upon the world for having done wrong. Shi'ism is an incomplete religion, always waiting for its own final delivery, always anticipating its own fulfilment, and the world is the very site of this shortcoming, militantly translated throughout history into an agenda of insurrectionary action. Shi'ism is in perpetual state of expectation, awaiting its own delivery, hoping for its own promise, anticipating to deliver itself (2008: 66-67).

Hence, Dabashi's main theoretical advance which practically turns Shi'ism into the essence of Otherness itself: 'Shi'ism is the Other. Shi'ism is Alterity' (2008: 72). What is of relevance here, like in Abid-Moghaddam's case, is the attribution of an over-historical essence of dissent to Islam. Rather than grounding the possibility of resistance - *if any, if desirable, at what political and intellectual cost*, as discussed above in relation to Said's views on religious resistance - in concrete historical conjunctures (as he could have done, for instance, by properly investigating the obsolete nature of the 'Islam and the West' bipolarity, the observation which is supposed to frame his approach) Dabashi, like Abid-Moghaddam, cannot but fall in a subtle essentialism, a kind of reversed Orientalism which locates the emancipatory potential of Islam in some kind of transcendental essence.

Having said this, Muslims authors are not the only ones who construct their narratives of Muslim subjectivity around the category of resistance or dissent. The idea of religion, and in particular Islam, as a site of resistance or political promise has been central in accounts of gender, as we have seen in the previous chapters, and has been gaining further eminence in the work of critics who have been speaking in the name of the Left in the recent years.⁵⁸ The stated anti-imperialism of Islamism is another reason which partially explains the opening of the Left to religious

⁵⁸ For example, Eagleton whose recent work has been taking an openly 'metaphysical or theological turn' in an effort 'to extend the language of the left as well as challenge that of the right' (2005: vi) in both his accounts of the genealogy of terrorism (2005) and of the relationship between faith and revolution (2009).

movements.⁵⁹ As Sahgal and Yuval-Davis (1992: 6) note, the assumption of the inherently progressive nature of anti-imperialism is ‘one of the unchallenged “truths” of the Left’ and the idea that because a political movement has the ‘right enemy’ brings it automatically on ‘our side’ (ibid) has been increasingly gaining acceptance. This has become especially true in the polarised climate of Bush administration and further exacerbated by the urgency to respond to the rampant demonisation of Muslims after 09/11. In this climate Left critics had recourse to representations of Islam as dissenting, anti-colonial and even liberating in its own way and idealised Islamist resistance sometimes over the actual content and intent of Islamist politics. An exemplary case to the point is critical theorist Buck-Morss who has been recently proposing to examine Islamism as a political discourse together with critical theory as critiques of modernity in the Western-developed form and to identify overlapping concerns (2006: vii). Coming from the perspective of critical theory, Buck-Morss identifies two main avenues where Islamism converges with the ‘global Left’: first, with regards to their shared perception of progress, which is defined ‘in terms of social cohesion rather than individual competition, and evaluates society in civil rather than personal terms’ and second, with regards to their sustained critique of the imposition of the ‘Western’ cultural and political norms as natural (2006: ix). She argues that a new perspective of global Left is open to us if we engage in a political project of ‘translation’ where the treatment of political languages should be mutually open to transformation in order to challenge the unequal arrangements of global power (2006: 7), and it is critical theory and Islamism who can offer the nodal point for such translation to materialise (2006: 8). ‘What if’, Buck-Morss asks,

the “Islamic economy” did not take the easy way of identity politics, defining itself as an economy belonging exclusively to Muslims, but considering its natural constituency to include the anti-globalization movement as the most authentic, contemporary political expression of Islamic principles regarding nature, labor and economic justice? If we are to speak in terms of global Left rather than regime-change within Muslim countries, what may be needed is not less religious reasoning but more’ (2006: 11-12).

This passage encapsulates a familiar attitude by now in this thesis, i.e. the tendency of progressive or radical Left authors to merge Left protesters from a wide spectrum of social movements (typically classified under the banner of ‘minorities’) with Islamic activism of equally varied

⁵⁹ Even if, efforts of simple taxonomy or genuine political inscription of Islamism on the Left – or Right – fail to discuss what Islamic anti-imperialism entails for Muslim humanity, as Bayat (2008) points out.

shades, from radicalised militants who advocate a sheer break from existing forms of society to culturalists who seek accommodation of their beliefs within the Western liberal states. The view of Islamism as 'progressive' because of its reaction to imperialism and its legacy though, tends to obfuscate a paramount aspect of political reality, i.e. that Islamic revivalism is a sign and symptom of the decline of secular Left politics in the Muslim world (Ahmad 2008). The need for greater understanding and genuine tolerance towards the diasporic Muslim communities has often been expanded into a taken-for granted support of the indigenous, authentic, communitarian and into an enthusiasm about 'local victories' and 'local narratives of emancipation'. What goes often unquestioned in these accounts is the assumed 'progressive' or 'Left' character of resistance *per se* which pays no attention to those historical instances when resistance becomes a regressive force, attitude or imaginary. The glorification of 'Islamic resistance', which becomes especially complicated when entangled with the tragedy of the Palestinian people, for instance, is a telling example of the compelling conundrum that the global Left is facing today.

The over-emphasis on the category of 'resistance', and even its trivialisation, as Zizek (2002) observes, needs to be taken into account to comprehend the shift of critical social theory and the political Left to the endorsement, even idealisation of religion from the site for reproduction of hierarchy to a 'sanctuary for doubt' (Gray 2003: 19):

Today's hegemonic attitude is that of 'resistance' – all the poetics of the dispersed marginal sexual, ethnic, lifestyle 'multitudes' (gays, the mentally ill, prisoners ...) 'resisting' the mysterious central (capitalized) Power. Everyone 'resists' – from gays and lesbians to Rightists survivalists – so why not draw the logical conclusion that this discourse of 'resistance' is the norm today, and as such, the main obstacle to the emergence of the discourse which would actually question the dominant relations? (Zizek 2002: 66).

To be sure, even Zizek recognises something special in instances of Islamic revivalism: for example, he sees the explosion of the World Trade Center towers on 09/11 as 'an explosion of lethal jouissance' (2002: 141), whilst he expresses a certain admiration for Muslim radical activism: 'We in the West are the Last Men, immersed in our stupid daily pleasures, while the Muslim radicals are ready to risk everything, engaged in the nihilist struggle up to the point of self-destruction' (2009b: 25). Elsewhere, in a rather incendiary comment against Fukuyama's view of Islamic fundamentalism as 'Islamofascism', Zizek, by defining Fascism as 'the name for

the impossible attempt to have “capitalism without capitalism”, without the excess of individualism, social disintegration, relativisation of values’, argues that Islam holds a real potential to be articulated into a Socialist project: since it ‘harbours the “worst” potentials of the Fascist answer to our present predicament, it could also turn out to be the site for the “best” (2002: 134-135). Therefore, it comes as no surprise that Zizek sees in Islam a ‘great tradition of millenarian “communist” rebellions’ from the Qarmatian Republic and the Zanj revolt⁶⁰ to the Iranian Revolution and the 2009 events that followed the presidential election in Iran (2009: 121-122).

This fascination of critical social theory with a presumed radical energy in Islam - and the subsequent reinstatement of Islamic tradition as a locus of dissent - has a longer history as Foucault’s famous engagement with the Iranian Islamic revolution suggests.⁶¹ Almond traces this postmodern – according to his analysis – interest in Islam’s radical energy in a variety of authors: in Foucault’s ‘irreducible force’, in Baudrillard’s ‘dangerous alterity’, in Derrida’s ‘archaic violence’ (2007: 185), alongside with Nietzsche’s ambivalence between ‘epileptic prophets’ and ‘manly warriors’ (2007: 21). Almond is right to observe that these postmodern engagements with Islam, despite their alterity, say more about postmodernity itself than for Islam (2007: 196). However, the problem is that Almond essentially shares the postmodern anti-essentialist fascination with the Other as the only real depository of knowledge about herself, and almost inevitably slips back into full-fledged essentialism, when he concludes that postmodern Islam ‘remains invariably an Islam-for others, an *Islam-pour-l’Occident*, an *Islam-pour-l’Europe*, and never an *Islam-en-soi*, an Islam for itself (2007: 203). By the same token, this is where Zizek’s crucial difference lies, in comparison with the other authors who speak in the name of Left causes: he sees Islam strategically, instrumentally, unapologetically inscribed in his vision of communist struggle against capitalism and, therefore, he never stops warning against the

⁶⁰ The Qarmatians were a Shi’a Ismaili group eastern Arabia, where they attempted to establish a utopian republic in 899 CE and are mostly known for their revolt against the Abbasid Caliphate. The Zanj Rebellion was the culmination of series of small revolts which took place near the city of Basra (present-day southern Iraq), over a period of fifteen years (869–883 AD). The insurrection have involved enslaved Black Africans (Zanj) that had originally been captured from the African Great Lakes region and areas further south in East Africa and grew to involve over 500.000 slaves who were imported from across the Muslim empire.

⁶¹ As the protests against the Shah in Iran were culminating, Foucault worked as a special correspondent for *Corriere della Serra* and *Le Monde*, travelled to Iran, met with leaders and Khomeini himself and wrote a series of enthusiastic articles about the meaning and potential of Islamic Revolution. For a detailed discussion of this instance of Foucault’s political engagement as well as for the impact of this experience on Foucault’s thought about Enlightenment, homosexuality and political spirituality, see Afary and Anderson (2005).

concrete acts which mobilise reactionary topics by presenting themselves as progressive (2002: 130) and clearly rejects the dangerous motto 'the enemy of my enemy is my friend' which leads to discerning 'progressive' anti-imperialist potential in fundamentalist Islamist movements (2009a: 70).

So where does the de-mystification of the category of resistance leave us in relation to the question posed earlier, i.e. why does postcolonialism and cognate projects and fields haste to embrace Islam/ism despite their theoretical and political discrepancies? I would like to suggest that what needs to be understood as typically 'postcolonial' is not so much the various manifestations of political activism articulated in the name of 'Islam', but rather the recent intellectual developments in Western academia undergirding approaches such as 'postcolonial Islam'. The awareness of the inextricable relationship between Western scientific knowledge and colonial power, the subsequent erosion of the belief in the possibility of disinterested knowledge about the colonised 'Other' and the rise of 'reflexive' fields of studies such as postcolonialism, also need to be understood as part of the legacy of colonialism and as part of the broader process of deconstruction of the 'West'. The existence of 'reflexive' and 'anti-hegemonic' disciplines relies on the continuous discovery of subaltern or marginalised Others which need to be 'postcolonised' in order to be 'decolonised' by the critical enterprise of the experts of reflexivity. By this I do not mean to undervalue the important work of deconstruction of power relations embedded in the ways we study and make sense of the social world or the ways we rewrite our histories and imagine our future as social groups and formations. All I mean to emphasise is what seems to be forgotten in these theoretical exercises of deconstruction: the constructivist, political, and hence potentially -or perhaps inevitably? - hegemonic, character of our accounts of the social and its history, postcolonial included.

Chapter Five

Chapter Five

Religious Multiculturalism and the Politics of Muslim Assertiveness

- 5.1. Introduction: Islam and multiculturalism
- 5.2 The politics of Muslim assertiveness and the logic of multiculturalism
 - The assumption of 'Muslim community'
 - The redefinition of equality
 - A multiculturalism consistent with feminism?
- 5.3. Postsecular multiculturalism: the coming of age or the end of the road?

5.1 Introduction: Islam and multiculturalism

Multiculturalism is one of the fields of theoretical and political engagement that have been most associated with Islam/ism and the discourse of Muslim subjectivity. Although multiculturalism was frequently associated with the 'battleground' of culture wars (Takaki, 1993), i.e. with questions about race and Blackness, with pedagogical debates for the revision of the 'canon' and the expansion of the curriculum so as to reflect better the contributions of minorities in the USA, and questions about the accommodation of indigenous, subnational minorities in Canada, the theory and politics of multiculturalism have been specifically related to Islam in the European and British contexts and to the disputes which brought Muslim political subjectivity to the forefront of political life. In Europe, multiculturalism was largely identified in terms of political theory and policy, initially with the ethnic communities of immigrants, subsequently with the redefinition of 'culture' as ethnicity and, finally, with the conceptualisation of ethnicity as religion.⁶² These slippages in meaning were followed by the latest one, the association of multiculturalism with the specific politics of Muslim communities as well as the policies to deal with this new kind of politics. There seems to be a considerable consensus in academic and political discourses alike that when we speak about multiculturalism in Europe we tend to refer less to immigrants' communities in general, or to the diverse lifestyles as a matter of choice, but more to Islamic communities in the West in particular, to their distinct way of living and to the specific demands they make for their accommodation as a group in Western liberal societies. Some of the major political controversies, if not political crises, related to Islam, such as the veil ban in France, the minaret vote in Switzerland or the Danish cartoons, have been more often than not framed by

⁶² The slippage between culture, religion, race and ethnicity is a common place in the debates about multiculturalism. Hollinger (1995: 13) for instance, notices that culture is often used as a euphemism for ethnicity or race in the USA.

reference to multiculturalism. In many ways multiculturalism has become a metaphor for the presence and accommodation and politics of Muslim communities in Europe, not only for sympathisers of Muslim identity politics but for xenophobes as well, as the case of 2011 Norway attacks, the rhetoric of the English Defence League or of the Front National in France show.

Given the centrality that Islam has acquired in debates about multiculturalism, the present and following chapter focus in the way Muslim subjectivity and its accommodation is discussed within the field of theory and politics of multiculturalism and the kind of political sensibilities enabled by the encounter of multiculturalism and Islam. The present chapter discusses the theoretical foundations on which the emerging political sensibilities about religious citizenship and the redefinition of the public space, its role and its limits are grounded, as examined by the next chapter. The religious, postsecular multiculturalism as advocated by the 'politics of Muslim assertiveness' is often taken for granted as a natural offspring of multiculturalism itself. The chapter aims to challenge this established preconception and demonstrate that the opening of multiculturalism to postsecular ideas comes with the closure of its most progressive potential of 'secular multiculturalism'. To do so the chapter engages with the 'politics of Muslim assertiveness' as advocated by Tariq Modood, whose work represents perhaps the most systematic attempt to open the theory and politics of multiculturalism to religion. The chapter discusses the logic of the politics of Muslim assertiveness as a concrete instance of politico-religious multiculturalism by analysing its conceptual structure, by assessing the cogency of its theoretical claims and by divulging those contradictions and silences which undergird this particular kind of politics. Finally, the chapter addresses the paradox that religious multiculturalism brings to the fore: namely, that on the one hand, the postsecular public order envisioned by religious-oriented multiculturalism is an inherent tendency in multiculturalism *per se* and an effect of the way it conceptualises difference and recognition, whereas on the other, such concession to postsecular logic signals not only the coming of age of but also the end of the road for progressive multiculturalism itself.

5.2 Religious multiculturalism and the politics of Muslim assertiveness

Multiculturalism as a normative, rather than descriptive, term refers to the body of theories, ideologies and policies ranging from promotion of equal respect to the various cultures in a

society, to policies encouraging the preservation of cultural diversity and the recognition of the right of people from ethnic and religious groups to be defined institutionally by the group in which they belong. In a nutshell, the theorists of multiculturalism argue that calling for non-discrimination does not sufficiently address the structural inequalities faced by cultural groups in liberal societies; that people deserve to be recognised as groups and not only as individuals for their special ways of life; that since individuals need basic cultural goods to pursue the good life certain groups should be granted differential rights in order to have the opportunity to pursue a meaningful life; and, finally, that such changes cannot be accommodated within the ostensibly neutral and unfriendly to difference political framework provided by liberalism. Multiculturalism essentially asks what the public and political relevance of citizens' identities as members of ethnic, cultural, or religious groups is and whether these collective identities should impact on the distribution of rights and the recognition of legal claims.⁶³

Besides the overarching framework of culture, one could perhaps identify two main concepts around which all theories of multiculturalism evolve, i.e. minority and community, and which attempt to define both the conditions of group belonging and the accommodation claimed by the group as a result of such belonging. If a schematic attribution of concepts amongst the founding figures of theory of multiculturalism is possible, then Kymlicka is perhaps most associated with the popularisation of the terms minority and accommodation rights, whereas Taylor and Walzer are more known for developing ideas around the concept of community and the politics of recognition. Kymlicka's main concern is to provide a liberal framework for the just treatment of minority groups, which he divides in two categories, national minorities and polyethnic or immigrant groups. From those two, only indigenous national minorities – or in his own terms,

⁶³ Naturally, a wide array of critiques have been produced over the years against multiculturalism's main aims, either from sympathetic perspectives, such as ethical universalism which asks whether political compromise of the demands made by the members of cultural groups should necessarily entail a loss of their distinct identity and if change should necessarily be considered as injustice (Gutmann 1993: 182) and that the recognition of cultural membership as part of human rights should not necessarily entail its conceptualisation as collective rights too (Habermas 1995: 851). Or from unfriendly perspectives, such as 'strong' liberalism for which liberal states exist to accommodate a variety of views and not to pursue collective aims on their own, hence the ethical dilemma of whether respecting human dignity requires the recognition of individual identities or the recognition of group identities is completely out of their concerns (Kukathas 1998: 695, 691). But also, the conceptual pillars of multiculturalism, such as culture and difference, have been under scrutiny from a variety of viewpoints: for instance, multiculturalism's central concept of culture has been criticised for its lurking romanticism (Eller 1997: 252), in particular of non-Western cultures (Bonevac 1994: 170), for the 'reductionist sociology of culture' it produces (Benhabib 2002: 4; Phillips 2007: 8-9, 14), and for its 'monumentalist' tendencies (West 1993: 152). Simultaneously, multiculturalism has been questioned for its propensity to perceive difference as a condition of human existence and not as the effect of its enunciation that constitutes hierarchies and asymmetries of power and for its failure to see that identity groups do not pre-exist discrimination but they are its consequence (Scott 1992: 14-6).

only groups that have a 'societal culture'⁶⁴ - should be granted 'self-government rights' while immigrants should be refused such possibility. Kymlicka identifies three reasons for this distinction: first, because their goal should be their integration within their new home; second, because they are assumed to have made a deliberate choice to live in a specific country and therefore they should be encouraged to forget some of the rights or values of their prior cultural membership; and third, because groups formed by immigration lack the territorial concentration or historical institutions to sustain a vibrant societal culture and therefore a hands-off approach vis-à-vis to their integration would result in further marginalisation, a view that persists in Kymlicka's later work too (2001a). This distinction is justified by the fact that 'this differential treatment reflects differential aspirations, and a different sense of legitimate expectations' (Kymlicka 2010a: 52). However, even in the case of indigenous groups, Kymlicka is willing to grant special rights only to those groups that would be internally liberal. Kymlicka has a view of culture which is instrumental rather than intrinsic (2001a: 62) and hence not lying on the community's character but on a liberal perception which sees culture as 'cultural structure', as a 'context of choice' that would allow the members of the group to make choices from a set of available meaningful options and pursue their own life-styles (O'Neil 1999: 224). Central to Kymlicka's argument is the foundational liberal value of individual autonomy which cannot be overridden for any group-specific rights.

Taylor (1994) and Walzer (1983) have a more communitarian vision of multicultural liberalism, not unrelated to what has been identified as a more general turn 'from contract to community' (Dallmayr 1978). If Kymlicka's centre of interest is the self-government rights for large-scale indigenous minorities with a societal culture, the communitarian debate revolves around the priority of individual freedom. In an important sense, communitarians dispute the conception of the 'autonomous individual' as well as the basic liberal principle that the individual is prior to the community and, therefore, they refute that the interests of communities can be reduced in the interests of their individual members. In the communitarian view the individual is conceptualised

⁶⁴ Kymlicka's definition of 'societal culture' is quite different from the one shared by those who have more communitarian leanings in this debate, and crucially for the analysis here, from the one advocated by postsecular multiculturalism. Kymlicka sees his own definition 'in conflict with the way the term is used in most academic disciplines, where it is defined in a very thick, ethnographic sense, referring to the sharing of specific folk-customs, habits and rituals. Citizens of a modern liberal state do not share a common culture in such a thick, ethnographic sense - indeed, the lack of a common thick ethnographic culture is part of the very definition of a liberal society. But it is equally essential to modern liberal forms of governance that citizens share a common culture in a very different, and thinner, sense, focusing on a common language and societal institutions.' (Kymlicka 2001a: 25, note 18).

as embedded into social roles and relationships and therefore the self is always culturally-specific and citizenship becomes the crux of the matter. Taylor (1994), perhaps the most prominent figure or communitarianism in political philosophy, uses this civic conception of community as the basis of his cultural 'politics of recognition' which initiated a whole era of politics of group differentiation. Taylor argues that liberalism should be grounded on judgments in which the integrity of cultures has an important place and therefore his vision allows space for collective goals. For Taylor (1994: 61) this model of liberalism would 'weigh the importance of certain forms of undifferentiated treatment against the importance of cultural survival and would sometimes finally favour the latter'. It has been noted that the lack of definition of the specific circumstances under which the cultural survival would prevail over uniform treatment begs the question of prioritisation between individual and cultural rights (O'Neil 1999: 240). In the same perspective, Walzer (1994), whereas he entirely endorses Taylor's views, he also agrees with Kymlicka in not granting any rights at all to the immigrant communities as 'immigration involves a serious rejection of the old country' (1980: 784), even if he revised this position later and appeared more willing to consider – under conditions - the demands of recognition of the cultural groups formed by immigration (Walzer 1997). His famous maxim that 'justice is relative to social meanings' (1983: 312) introduces a peculiar cultural relativism that allows, for instance, to conceive of liberal and illiberal societies as systems of meaning equal in relation to each other, but which does not necessarily entail that cultural-religious groups should expect their cultural conceptions of justice to be reproduced within liberal states.

It is within this larger debate about the content, aim and contours of multiculturalism that the rise of a particular politics of recognition of Muslim identity is taking place. Looking retrospectively at the foundational theories of multiculturalism, a second generation of multiculturalist theorists, considered them to be incomplete or inadequate to address what they think that is the greatest challenge for multiculturalist politics in Europe, and most notably in Britain: that is, the conditions of accommodation of cultural groups formed by immigration in general, and of their religious needs in particular. It is important to note that within this debate the term 'immigrants' is essentially a metaphor for ethno-religious communities, whereas the accommodation sought refers almost always to religious needs emanating from this particular – ethno-religious – mode of belonging. Modood is perhaps the most emblematic figure in this debate and his work is the most completed proposition of a multiculturalism open to religion, and

more specifically to Islam. Modood makes the case for a renovation or re-adaptation of multiculturalism on a historical-epochal base, since 'struggles between non-Muslims and Muslims may define our era' (Modood 2006: 53). In this era which is characterised by the end of the ideological hegemony of secularism, religion has come to the fore as a core element for community construction and group mobilisation. The impetus religion has acquired in recent years is attributed to the exclusion of religious associations from the process of resource distribution or to the political marginalisation, demotion or misrecognition of religious identity in favour of allegedly more acceptable identities, such as those of race and gender (Modood and Kastoryano 2006: 172). Modood thinks that the 'Muslim community' is a unique group in the contemporary European and British political arena since 'Muslims have the most extensive and developed discourses of unity, common circumstance and common victimhood among non-EU origin peoples in the EU' (2009: 194). He sees the expression of logic of Muslim claims-making as both contemporary and European, and therefore, as a debate within our society and not amongst societies. That is, it is an internal debate forming part of the liberal democratic tradition, and not a debate on cultural models of societies or civilisations (Modood et al. 2006: 3- 4). As it will be explored in detail below, Modood (2009: 202) sees the new politics of Muslim identity as primarily derived not from Islam or Islamism or by the attacks on Muslims (therefore as 'oppositional', or 'negative' politics as it were) but almost as an instance of 'positive consciousness', to use Braidotti term analysed in chapter two. Hence, for Modood the major source of inspiration for the rise of Muslim subjectivity is the Muslim adaptation and extension of western ideas about equality and the desire to join other equality-seeking movements. In that sense, Modood sees Muslim identity mobilisation as a politics of 'catching up' with racial equality and feminism (Modood 2006: 14, 18; 2009: 196, 198).

While making the case that Muslims are the most significant challenge for the integration of minorities for Europe and one of the criteria for judging Britain as an egalitarian, inclusive, multicultural society (2009: 201), Modood also evaluates that the place of religion in theoretical debates about multiculturalism, is an extremely neglected topic (Modood 2005: 178; Modood and Ahmad 2007: 189). Taking as a basis the stance that multiculturalism is about all minorities regardless of their identity markers, Modood assesses that both in theoretical and political terms, religious assertiveness has been not only overlooked from egalitarians and multiculturalists alike, but also seen as a threat to multiculturalism (Modood and Ahmad 2007: 189). Multiculturalism in

the sense of minority accommodation movement is for Modood the right vehicle to express these demands, however, the existing theoretical constitution of the field is not relevant to the British or more largely European context, as it leaves immigrants' communities, religious demands and most notably Muslim communities out of the picture.

For this reason, Modood asks for the widening of what we could call the 'multiculturalism canon', which is seen as far too narrow to be effectively used as a platform for the recognition of religious groups. Let us follow Modood's argument for the expansion of multiculturalism, as this is where the originality of his critical endeavour lies. Modood argues that the definitions and recognition of suffering from racism in Britain had prioritised a dichotomy between race/ethnicity on the one hand and religion on the other, hence religion was seen as a matter not of mutual respect (and therefore visibility) but as a matter of mutual tolerance whose expression had to be confined in the private sphere (Modood and Ahmad 2007: 189). He (2005: 104) argues that the racial equality discourse and politics that had developed in Britain in the 1980s were dominated by the idea that the major post-immigration issue was 'colour racism' and as a result they suffered from a 'secularist bias', that is, they did not explicitly recognise discrimination and suffering on the basis of religious affiliation. These definitions focus on 'colour', a collective identity marker that Modood deems inadequate for Muslims because they rarely think of themselves in terms of colour. It follows that such view which sees only colour discrimination as a cause of racism and material deprivation cannot account for phenomena of devaluation of people 'not only because of their origins but also because of their membership in a cultural minority' and for cases where the two overlap and 'create a double disadvantage'. For Modood a more extended concept of racism as a basis for a new multiculturalist theory and politics, should help us understand that an oppressed group feels its oppression according to those aspects of its identity that the group - and not the oppressor - values the most and that simultaneously the identification to these aspects precisely is the source of its collective psychological strength. Hence, antiracism for Muslims has an inevitable religious dimension: the new determination of resistance to racial harassment among Muslims owns as much to anti-racist ideologies as to Islamic re-assertion (ibid).

Modood introduces a distinction between a group's 'mode of oppression' and a group's 'mode of being', in order to explain why Muslims mobilise in terms of their religious affiliation rather than identity markers related to ethnicity, colour or class (2005: 159). He (2007: 41) attempts to strike a

balance in order to explain why a minority will respond to certain types of exclusion or inferiorisation between essentialism (the 'sense of being' of the minority group) and historicity ('what identity will emerge as important to a group at a particular time lies in the nature of the minority group in question'). Essentially, he argues that even if 'white British society sees and treats Muslims as a "coloured Other", it doesn't follow that Muslims accept that description of themselves. Excluded groups seek respect for themselves as victims; they resist being defined by their mode of oppression and seek space and dignity for their mode of being' (2005: 159). This collective identification is central to the group's formation and evolution and it is crucial not only to talk about positive self-definition but also about pain, the way the group has been inferiorised (Modood 2007: 41). British Asians (which more or less equate Muslims in Modood's account) are an example of this process as 'they redefine the racism that they experience, from a colour-racism, the experience of not being white in a white society, to a racism which targets Asians in the form of distinctive stereotypes and vilifies aspects of their culture' (ibid).

For this move from race to religion Modood's multiculturalism requires a new definition of equality which is reconceptualised as follows: 'as not having to hide or apologise for one's origins, family or community, but requiring others to show respect for them and adapt public attitudes and arrangements so that the heritage they represent is encouraged rather than ignored or expected to wither away' (Modood and Kastoryano 2006: 171). This new concept of equality draws from two sources: first, from Taylor's famous 'politics of recognition' and specifically the idea that equality appeals to two separate yet interrelated concepts, i.e. equal dignity which focuses on what people have in common (hence it is gender-blind, race-blind and so on) and equal respect which refers to difference as a necessary component in order to conceptualise and institutionalise equal relations between individuals (Modood 2007: 51; Modood 2008: 47). However, the 'individual' here is not the autonomous individual as conceptualised in liberal and Marxist discourses of equality alike, but an individual embedded in communitarian structures; society - and for that matter British society - is not imagined as a liberal association of individuals but as a 'community of communities' (Modood 2005: 20).⁶⁵ This way however, a peculiar dichotomy is introduced not only between different concepts of equality but also between those who see themselves as part of a community and those who do not. Nonetheless, Modood does not

⁶⁵ An expression borrowed from the Parekh report which found that 'Britain is both a community of citizens and a community of communities' (Commission for the Future of Multi-Ethnic Britain 2000: ix).

see the two conceptions of equality as excluding but as complementing each other since: ‘the right to assimilate to the majority/dominant culture in the public sphere, with toleration of “difference” in the private sphere; the right to have one’s “difference” (minority ethnicity etc.) recognised and supported in both the public and the private sphere. While the former represents a liberal response to “difference”, the latter is the “take” of the new identity politics’ (2009: 198). The extent to which this is theoretically consistent as well as practically possible is discussed further below.

The second source for Modood’s redefinition of equality is Young’s shift towards a new paradigm of justice which allows the excluded group to move on from assimilation to the hegemonic cultural norms to affirmation of difference and which sees the positive self-definition of group difference as more liberatory (Young 1990: 157).⁶⁶ For Modood (2009: 197) this is a significant shift which ‘takes us from an understanding of “equality” in terms of individualism and cultural assimilation to a political recognition’; it takes us ‘to “equality” as encompassing public ethnicity’, even if he criticises Young for her omission of religion as a category of difference in her challenge to the dominant paradigm of justice (Modood and Ahmad 2007: 189). In Modood’s perspective this lacuna is a prime example of what he calls ‘the secularist bias’ which he considers emblematic of the initial stages of multiculturalism, although we shall see below to what extent this statement requires itself sociological and historical deconstruction. Nonetheless, Modood is right to point out that the discourse of equality used by multiculturalism met with support from the ‘critical’ or ‘reflexive’ disciplines as it fitted with the wider challenges posed to liberalism, especially by feminists who questioned the male dominance and the ostensible neutrality of the twin domains

⁶⁶ Young’s work aims to displace ‘the distributive paradigm’ of social justice, hence, ‘injustice should be defined primarily in terms of oppression and domination. The scope of justice (...) is not limited to distribution, but includes all social processes that support or undermine oppression, including culture’ (Young 1990: 152). It follows that ‘a better theoretical approach is to pluralise concepts of injustice and oppression so that culture becomes one of several sites of struggle interacting with others’ (Young 1997: 157). Despite the fact that Young shares ‘the communitarian “social thesis” – namely, that individual identity is shaped by and provided through membership of groups, of which cultural groups are perhaps the most important’ (Kelly 2002: 7), her radicalism challenges multiculturalism itself on two fronts: first, by asking that all groups may be accommodated, regardless of their size, importance or type of negative difference (gender, sexuality, disability, age, ethnicity and so on); and second, that citizenship expands into the private realm (i.e. moving beyond the demand of State recognition). Naturally, the prioritisation of cultural over economic justice that such theoretical move entails has been the object of contention. See for instance the exchange between Fraser and Young on what has been called the ‘redistribution–recognition dilemma’ in the *New Left Review* (Fraser 1995, 1997; Young 1997).

of politics and the public space (Modood 2006: 39), even if the association of multiculturalism with feminism can hardly be taken for granted, as we shall see further down.

This new conception of equality is the basis for the formulation of political multiculturalism which is outlined as follows: 'it begins with a concept of negative difference and seeks the goal of positive difference and the means to achieve it, which crucially involve the appreciation of the fact of multiplicity and groupness, the building of group pride amongst those marked by negative difference, and political engagement with the sources of negativity and racism' (Modood 2007: 61). Accordingly, political multiculturalism refers to the struggle and mobilisation but also to policies and institutional outcomes which address the character of 'difference' in order to recognise it and turn its 'negative' definition into a 'positive' one (Modood 2007: 39). This is why emphasising on 'difference' rather than 'culture' is to recognise that groups are not only constituted from the 'inside', i.e. they are not only the effect of belongingness to a minority culture, but also from the 'outside', that is the effect of the group's representation and treatment, which links back to the group's 'mode of oppression' discussed above.

According to Modood (2007: 6-7), these ideas have enough distinctiveness and coherence to grant political multiculturalism the status of a new '-ism' which is defined by the following characteristics: it is contemporary, i.e. it is an idea of political citizenship in contrast to multiculturalism that had developed within the Ottoman Empire;⁶⁷ it is more than a simply outgrowth of liberalism (since it seeks move beyond toleration and state neutrality and the remake of the public sphere in order to fully include marginalised identities, 2007: 64) though it is not a political philosophy or a comprehensive theory of politics either. Finally, Modood's multiculturalism is 'not necessarily dependant on a general theory about the nature of morality or an epistemology and so is not a form of moral or knowledge relativism' (2007: 7). Hence, this new

⁶⁷ The view which sees the Ottoman Empire (meant as an Islamic Empire) as a multicultural paradise with supposedly high levels of religious accommodation and tolerance fails to historicise properly the context within which 'tolerance' was practiced in the pre-Enlightenment, pre-modern sense. As Rotzokos (2006) explains 'tolerance' within the Ottoman context was not meant in terms of rights (central in multiculturalist theory and politics as we have seen so far) because the idea of rights is not part of the political culture of the time. The kind of tolerance that the Ottoman Empire practiced vis-à-vis the *conquered* populations was a concession which was reproducing the *negative distinction* between believers and infidels, between conquerors and conquered. Parekh (2000: 7) is also critical of this view noticing that 'although Turkey under the Ottoman Empire had fairly large amount of Christian and Jewish communities and granted them far greater autonomy than do most contemporary western societies, it was not and never saw itself as a multicultural society'. Kymlicka (1995: 43) concurs that Ottoman-style multiculturalism is totally inconsistent with liberal multiculturalism. According to Delanty (2010: 75), examples such as the Ottoman Empire are best termed as 'ethnopluralism' rather than multiculturalism.

'-ism' is imagined as 'intellectually modest' and 'non-totalistic' political perspective (ibid). As an effect of this position, this new multiculturalism, which 'is not part of a grander theory or political project' (2007: 123), has an anti-theoretical and perhaps anti-intellectual edge (as opposed, for instance, to Parekh's version of multiculturalism who has both normative and philosophical inspirations). As Modood (2007: 18-19) explains his idea of multiculturalism is not a theoretical abstraction nor has an idiosyncratic meaning: it is 'rooted in recent and ongoing policies, politics and other real-world developments. It consists of ideas that influence policy-makers and public debates and are of great controversy'. The merit of this pragmatically conceived multiculturalism is that it can be 'more compatible, with suitable modification where necessary, with a wider variety of intellectual and political viewpoints' (2007: 123-124).

However, these anti-theoretical statements and the denunciation of knowledge relativism are surprisingly coupled to intellectual resources from the tradition of anti-essentialist postmodern thinking that became prominent from the end of 1970s onwards and which are known not only for their relativist stance on knowledge but for their theoreticism too. According to Modood, the politics of difference on which a case for Muslim rights can be built, are drawing

from the very different work of thinkers such as Nietzsche, Heidegger and Wittgenstein, given a certain indeterminate radicalism in the hands of more recent theorists like Foucault and Derrida, anti-essentialism in one form or another has been used to critique hegemonic ideas such as nation-state, community, class and even counter-hegemonic notions such as a woman, black and so on (Modood 2006: 40).

This appreciation of perspectivism

when married to a theory of political equality as participation in a discursive public space (e.g. Arendt; Habermas) can define inclusion in a political community not in terms of (as many European politicians do as regards to Muslims) accepting the rules of the existing polity and its hallowed public-private boundary lines, but the opposite (ibid).

It follows that

public space is defined as essentially contested and indeed created through on-going discursive contestation and political struggles, where the rules of what are appropriate

concerns, and the terms of politics, far from being fixed in advance, are an object of political discourse (e.g. Benhabib; Fraser)' (ibid).

These are surprising claims, since there is a considerable tension between the self-declared anti-foundational pedigree of multiculturalism and the necessary essentialism lurking behind the politics of identity and recognition which are unconceivable without drawing on some irreducible and non-negotiable essence ('mode of being' suffering from a 'mode of oppression' to use Modood's terms). This tension has been a persistent critique against multiculturalism: as McLennan observes, it is not at all given that multiculturalism can easily strike a balance between 'the dispersalism entailed in the emphasis on transgressive hybridities, on the one hand, and the over-essentialist depiction of deep cultures, on the other' (McLennan 2001: 403). The immediate consequence is that within many strong cultures, like the Muslim for which Modood makes the case, have little space for any real accommodation to the fundamental beliefs of their own Other – for instance, liberalism and its adherence on autonomy and free speech, as we shall see in the next chapter. Here we seem to have reached a deadlock: if the stress is on culturalism, indeed the 'multi' can be seen as a threat to any strong community as it requires the relativisation of its values and the hybridisation of its essence. For this reason, McLennan notices that multiculturalism has little chance to become the metacultural ethics of our times (McLennan 2001: 390). Let us follow McLennan's argument on the matter a little further: the analytical unity and political necessity of multiculturalism as a theory collapses whether it is conceived on the basis of a strong or weak culture. For multiculturalism to be able to stand as an '-ism' (one of Modood's claims) one would need to accept that different and often conflicting cultures would need resolving on a higher plane of understanding and political commitment. However, if culture is perceived as 'strong' (the community version), then cultures require preservation and respect and multiculturalism becomes a matter of pragmatic accommodation rather than a theoretical framework. If cultures are perceived as weak (the hybridity version) then identities are thought as inherently multiple, overlapping and unstable, therefore the need to frame them in a unitary and abstracted, even if loose and anti-foundational 'ism', evaporates (McLennan 2001: 391). Modood is aware of the theoretical inconsistencies at the heart of his theory of multiculturalism, however, he thinks that 'multicultural politics, official or otherwise, is not dependent on theoretical clarity; it can proceed, be reformed, qualified, extended and so on without the deconstructivist strictures

of the theorist' (Modood 2007: 98).⁶⁸ The tension between essentialism and anti-essentialism is for Modood a 'misguided search for a discursive coherence' (ibid), a statement which makes any consideration of multiculturalism as a consistent '-ism' self-defeating.

The assumption of 'Muslim community'

One reason for these tensions within Modood's theory of multiculturalism could be the way difference – a core concept for the very articulation of multiculturalism – is perceived. As we have seen so far, Modood's proposition is germane with Young's ideas for whom multiculturalism must encompass all cultural difference and unite oppressed minorities against the hegemonic paradigm of distributive justice. Parekh, the other leading theorist of multiculturalism in Britain, has attempted to give more consistency to the project of multiculturalism by narrowing down its content and scope. Parekh (2000: 3-4) distinguishes three types of diversity (a term which he favours in relation to 'difference'): a. subcultural diversity, such as homosexual and other unconventional lifestyles, which share the dominant system of meaning and values but seek to create spaces for their alternative lifestyles; b. perspectival diversity, as represented for example by feminists or environmentalists, which are not distinct cultural communities living by their own values and views of the world but intellectual perspectives which challenge the foundations of the dominant culture; c. communal diversity, which concerns self-conscious and well-organised communities which preserve and live by their own different systems of beliefs and practices. Naturally, these types of diversity overlap in significant respects, however they differ in political ambition and scope: subcultural diversity is embedded in a shared culture which it wishes to pluralise by opening up new spaces within it rather than replace it altogether; perspectival diversity represents a vision of life which is radical and comprehensive and cannot be easily accommodated within the existing structures. Finally, community diversity, which is the real and only object of multiculturalism for Parekh, is sustained by long-established, distinct communities with their own long histories and ways of life which they wish to preserve and transmit. Parekh argues that the first two usages of the term deprive the terms of focus, since communal diversity is distinct and unique - in the sense that the other two types are found in most societies - and hence, the object of multiculturalism is ethnic communities.

⁶⁸ In a rather fierce and provocative critique of multiculturalism theoretical carelessness, Barry commented that 'multiculturalists tend to be intellectual magpies, picking up attractive ideas and incorporating them into their theories without worrying too much about how they might fit together' (Barry 2001: 252).

However, even if we accept this narrower definition of multiculturalism as a corrective of its scope, there are further problems with the basis of religious-friendly, Muslim-oriented version of multiculturalism advocated by Modood. To start with, the assumption of Muslim community is not only problematical conceptually, but also quite debatable empirically. The consistence and even analytical validity of a construct such as the ‘Muslim community’ has come into question, for instance, by Bechir and Saghieh (2005) who argue that ‘to view immigrants from Algeria and Turkey, Pakistan and Iraq as belonging to a single, homogeneous “Muslim community” reflects an essentialist, neo-colonial view of the “other” which carries negative political consequences’. Bechir and Saghieh take issue with those descriptions in which ‘Muslims are often defined by intellectual-political models of “community identity” and “multiculturalism” advocated by scholars like Tariq Modood’ (ibid). Indeed, by Modood’s own admission, arguing that Muslims deserve recognition and representation, one inevitably prioritises the religious over other social traits and promotes religious Muslims as the representatives of Muslims as a whole (2007: 132). For Bechir and Saghieh however, this is not a minor issue, but the crux of the matter as, in their view, the Muslim community exists ‘above all in the minds of western politicians, “experts” and journalists – and, of course, in the minds of their supposed and self-appointed “spokesmen”’. There is no doubt that the self-identification as a Muslim has been growing fast in Europe and the idea that being a Muslim is not just a matter of faith but a sociological fact too has been gaining prominence (Klausen 2005). Labels, such as ‘Muslim community’, are indeed essential in ‘collective identity-building’ (Spencer 1994) but it is important to remember that these processes of identity-building are triggered by the deployment of the re-ethnicised category of religion. The creation of ‘Muslim community’ is the result of specific policies which *followed* the arrival of immigrant populations in Europe rather than the other way round, whereas the deployment of the term is often used to evade a primary necessity in Europe today, i.e. a common, equal citizenship for all (Bechir and Saghieh 2005; Malik 2007).

Hence, the invocation of ‘Muslim community’ is not a politically innocent move as it adds historical depth to a new social phenomenon. This constructed historicity does not only essentialise Muslims in the way described above, but it also legitimises this particular view of Muslims as ‘community’ in the political imaginary. Commenting on Tony Blair’s speech in December 2006 on multiculturalism suggesting that the way forward for a social cohesion of members of different faith communities was to organise mutual visits and common activities

between classes from the different faiths schools, Yuval-Davis (2011: 138) notes that what is left unchallenged in such views is 'the naturalized boundary of people from different faiths as the only legitimate sub-communities of the British social cohesive national community'. This observation raises the question not only of the validity of multiculturalist arguments, but also of the purpose of their use.

Despite these reservations, the idea of community has met with considerable support from both ends of the political spectrum in recent years. It has become widely accepted that community is something intrinsically good and something to be desired, to the point that the concept of community has come to be thought as self-explanatory, even if few terms have been as malleable and indeterminate as community in recent years. As Hobsbawm (1994: 428) observes, 'never was the world "community" used more indiscriminately and emptily than in the decades when communities in the sociological sense became hard to find in real life'. In some respects, it seems like if traditionalist communitarians and new progressive political movements have bridged their opposing political imaginaries through their fascination about the idea of community. The concept may have assumed centrality within multiculturalist discourses, however, it has not been necessarily welcome among the theorists of multiculturalism. Kymlicka (2001b: 338), for instance, suggested that the association between multiculturalism and communitarianism is proving increasingly unhelpful. If such interest in the idea of community is expected from the right end of the political spectrum, given the association of community with traditional modes of politics and being, it is quite surprising from the left end. The fascination with the idea of community within Left political quarters is not unrelated to the suspicion of collectivism associated with the discredited politics of 'really existing socialism', but equally not unrelated to the false presupposition that minorities are somehow more 'collectivist' than majorities.⁶⁹ But it is also the by-product of the confusion that lies in the origin of the term. Delanty (2010: 3) explains that the defining element in the discourse of community from the seventeenth century onwards was a critique of the state, which at the end of the Enlightenment was absolutist and that in this respect 'community expressed a dream impossible to realise: a vision of a pure or pristine social bond that

⁶⁹ As Kymlicka explains, 'because minority rights are claimed by groups, and tend to be group-specific, they are often described as "collective rights". The fact that the majority seeks only "individual" rights while the minority seeks "collective rights" is then taken as evidence that the minority is somehow more "collectivist" than the majority. The chain of reasoning contains several non sequiturs. Not all-group-specific minority rights are "collective" rights and even those which are "collective" rights in one of other sense of that term are not necessarily evidence of "collectivism"' (Kymlicka 2001a: 20, note 5).

did not need a state. It was, in a sense, a purely utopian concept of community as an emancipatory project' and hence, 'by the nineteenth-century community came to embody the quest for a perfect society'. It is perhaps this anti-statist element embedded in the concept of community that leads progressive and left political thought and activism to endorse the idea of community despite its essentially conservative conceptualisation within multiculturalism.

The redefinition of equality

As we have seen above, one of the strongest claims that Modood is making about the political origin of Muslim-friendly multiculturalism is its relationship with the politics of racial equality and feminism. Central in this opening of multiculturalism to religion is the redefinition of equality on the basis of a collective or communal conception and in contrast with the modern, political grounding which sees individual human beings as the unit of value and which refuses to 'recognize any categories of people having less or more moral weight' (Callinicos 2006: 241). Modood's definition of equality as requiring others to show respect and adapt public attitudes and arrangements to one's origins, family or community, brings culture at the heart of debates about inequality and exclusion⁷⁰ and is located within 'the site of struggle where groups with unequal discursive and non-discursive resources compete to establish as hegemonic their respective interpretations of legitimate social needs' (Fraser 1989: 166). As we have seen, Modood's particular take on equality comes as a corrective to 'conventional' anti-racism which is thought as rigid towards its own understanding of social and cultural difference and its effects. The problem is however, that the history of the concept of equality suggests that emphasis on difference is a characteristic of racist rather than anti-racist reasoning. Malik (1998) argues that the discourse of difference has a pedigree in racist thinking and that the politics of difference 'appropriates many of its themes and reproduces the very assumptions upon which racism has historically been based' (ibid). As Malik explains, the kind of difference advocated by multiculturalism 'has been always at the heart, not of the antiracist, but of the racist agenda' and 'cultural pluralism, far from being a means to liberate the voice of the oppressed, is rooted in the same philosophy that gave rise to the discourse of race' (ibid). Malik argues that the contemporary hostility to universalism mirrors that

⁷⁰ The emphasis on culture as an overarching explanation for and solution to racism lead Appiah to comment that: 'it is not black culture that the racist disdains but blacks. There is no conflict of visions between black and white cultures that is the source of racial discord. No amount of knowledge of the architectural achievements of Nubia or Kush guarantees respect for African-Americans. No African-American is entitled to greater concern because he is descendant from a people who created jazz or produced Toni Morrison. Culture is not the problem, and it is not the solution' (Appiah 1997b: 36). On the same note, Barry (2001: 308) points out that this culturalisation of groups inevitably leads to the conclusion that all disadvantage stems from the misrecognition of a group's culture.

of traditional nineteenth century racial theorists 'who despised what they regarded as the abstract universalism of Enlightenment thinkers which they believed denied, and even undermined, the concrete reality of human differences'. Contrary to the established thesis in some strands of critical social theory that racism is the product of modernity and the culture of Enlightenment itself, Malik reasons that 'racial difference and inequality can only have meaning in a world which has accepted the possibility of social equality and a common humanity' and that 'the discourse of race developed in opposition to the notions of universalism and rationalism' (ibid). Even more, Malik argues that if racial science vanished for good in the postwar world, many of the assumptions of racial thinking found new leases of life in the language of cultural pluralism which advocated that humanity can be divided into discrete groups that should be understood and judged in their own terms and that differences rather than commonalities shaped human interaction (ibid).

Indeed, from the point of view of intellectual history as well as from the point of view of history of ideas, the idea of 'difference' is constitutive of anti-Enlightenment tradition. As Sternhell (2010) shows the main arguments used to counter the concept of equality at the rise of the Enlightenment do not sound very different from ones used today by its modern critics. For instance, Herder's campaign against equality was articulated against the alleged 'uniformity' that liberal equality brings (Sternhell 2010: 218). By the same token, thinkers like Meinecke, who followed the Herderian tradition of 'radical relativism' argued that the equal value of all peoples and all races is close to the French Revolution's idea of equality, thus making a very similar logical lapse with his contemporary counterparts who seek to define equality on the basis of collective or community rights, and who fail to see that for the political and philosophical culture of the Enlightenment 'it was a matter of equality between free individuals, rational beings, possessing natural – that is universal – rights and organized in political communities, not in ethnic groups' (Sternhell 2010: 116-117). It was Herder who introduced the idea – familiar today to defenders of cultural integrity, from cultural relativists to fundamentalist purists - that to be subject to foreign influences is to degenerate (Sternhell 2010: 308-309). The idea that just as every people has to reserve its cultural and ethnic specificity, so it must have a national government and its own religion, is essentially the same principle that drives today the recognition and preservation of communities in the name of their unique, culturally irreducible character.

A multiculturalism consistent with feminism?

Besides racial equality, feminism is also mentioned as a political pillar of the politics of Muslim assertiveness. Without much discussion of their many diverging, if not opposing objectives, Modood takes the relationship between multiculturalism and feminism as given, as if their shared questioning of the assumed neutrality of the political/public sphere puts them automatically and unproblematically on the same side of the fence. The tendency of multiculturalism to disregard that the same relations of power are at work within groups, and that the same discriminatory – for instance, patriarchal or homophobic - elements can be overlooked in the name of supporting a culture or can be ‘concealed under the banner of multiculturalism’ (West 1993: 154) or the fact that well-intended accommodations aiming at mitigating power inequalities between groups often result in reinforcing power hierarchies within them (e.g. Shachar 2001) have been often pointed out by critics. It is, however, important to focus briefly at those discriminatory elements that can be overlooked in favour of the integrity of cultural groups. The issue of gender relations within the group and the discriminatory practices of patriarchy, no doubt common in all cultures, is a privileged avenue to reflect on the practical consequences of attribution of special, ‘collective’ or ‘self-government’, rights to cultural groups. As we have seen it so far in this thesis, the relationship between culture (as religion or as ethnicity) and feminism is a thorny terrain. The effort to avoid cultural imperialism leads often to excessive cultural relativism that is hasty to label any attempt to generalise about gender inequalities as ‘cultural imperialism’. In the same spirit, critique of gender inequalities and patriarchal exercise of power in non-Western cultures is often automatically identified – especially with the rise of right-wing feminism of the post-09/11 years – with the kind of Western supremacism which sees patriarchy as a problem of the ‘Other’.⁷¹

In her famous and controversial article ‘Is Multiculturalism Bad for Women?’ (1999) which was predated by her article ‘Feminism and Multiculturalism: Some Tensions’ (1998), Okin addresses in detail the strains between feminism and multiculturalism. Okin (1998: 664-665) discusses the significant probability of conflict between feminism and group rights for minority cultures, even

⁷¹ This is a recurrent misunderstanding in critiques (for instance Volpp, 2001) pointing out to the persistent orientalist assumptions of the ‘immigrant woman victim of minority culture’ which conflate the popular, public discourses with academic feminism. The fact that the liberal, Marxist or radical strands of feminist criticise the patriarchal structure of ‘non-white’ cultures and call for caution in terms of legal legitimisation of sex-discriminatory practices does not necessarily entail that feminists do not see the patriarchal structure of Western cultures or that they assume that other cultures are static entities.

if those ones are made on liberal grounds, mainly for two reasons: first, because those who argue for group rights fail to consider that cultural groups are, like the societies in which they exist, gendered; and second, because they pay no attention to the private sphere, i.e. they avoid examining the context in which the self and its capacities are formed and in which culture is transmitted. Okin examines the tension between the three main positions expressed with regards to the allowance of special rights of self-government to cultural groups – the ‘strong’ communitarian view, the ‘strong’ liberal position and finally, the position of liberal multiculturalism and proves them all short of defending women’s interest or protecting women against discrimination. Indeed, she concludes that:

in the case of a more patriarchal minority culture in the context of a less patriarchal majority culture, no argument can be made on the basis of self-respect or freedom that the female members of the culture have a clear interest in its preservation. Indeed, they *might* be much better off if the culture into which they were born were either to become extinct (so that its members would become integrated into the less sexist surrounding culture) or, preferably, to be encouraged to alter itself so as to reinforce the equality of women – at least to the degree to which this is upheld in the majority culture (Okin 1999: 22-23).⁷²

According to the communitarian understanding of culture and citizenship, individuals have the right to culture, not just any culture but their own culture and this entails the obligation to support cultures that do not pay respect to the rights of the individual – and for that matter to the rights of women. The case of gender is particularly telling, as one can see a compelling paradox at work: minority cultural groups demanding the right to discriminate in order not to be discriminated by the State and the majority culture. Spinner-Halev’s argument in his article ‘Feminism, Multiculturalism Oppression, and the State’ (2001) is a representative case of this puzzling position. For Spinner-Halev ‘justice ensuring individual rights and equality for all must be balanced against the injustice of a state imposing reform upon the group it oppresses’ (2001: 86). If justice often means protecting individual rights and ensuring gender equality, ‘justice should also mean that the oppressor state allows the oppressed group to maintain or change its

⁷² As expected Okin’s outspoken rejection of multiculturalism and of group rights that undercut women’s autonomy has met with equally fierce critique, most notably about the issue of ‘women’s agency’. A selection of responses to her argument is gathered in the homonymous to her article edited collection (Cohen, Howard and Nussbaum 1999).

long-standing rules concerning its own internal affairs as the group sees fit' (2001: 85-86). He argues that avoiding the injustice of imposing reform on oppressed groups is often more important than avoiding the discrimination against women. For Spinner-Halev the oppressed members within a group have a minimal but important level of autonomy, that of leaving the group. Therefore, he defends the right of these communities to retain these laws if they wish under most circumstances. Let alone the fact that defining what constitutes an 'oppressed' group and of how one could measure and balance the two kinds of oppression and conclude in favour of women's subordination to the discriminatory rules of the group would be a very obscure process, it is difficult to understand how women whose socialisation takes place in sex-discriminatory cultures would even be in position to exercise their 'minimal but important level of autonomy' and walk away from the group. Okin (1998: *ibid*) persuasively argues that the very sense of equal worth of self-respect could never be developed under conditions of sexual discrimination (e.g. sex-discriminatory access to education) and that public support to this kind of illiberal groups is unacceptable for liberal and feminist reasons alike.

What is surprising in this argument, is that Spinner-Halev and others who follow the path of accommodation of religious rights - or 'religious resistance' as we have seen in the case of Islamist feminism for instance - do not seem to ask the question of how women would be enabled to make informed decisions about how to lead their lives, or to make choices amongst various meaningful options, or to freely associate and dissociate from others, aspects that are fundamental to the practice of one's autonomy, in cultures where the problem seems to be precisely the lack of recognition of the individual's autonomy as such. From a feminist perspective the politics of difference and recognition fail to consider intra-group inequalities: either because they assume that identity politics are *ipso-facto* 'left' or 'progressive' due to their opposition to the State, either because they reify culture and therefore consider it as more important than the lives of real people themselves, gender inequalities within the group are overlooked. As Politt (1999: 27) explains, 'in its demand for equality for women, feminism sets off in opposition to virtually every culture on earth. You could say that multiculturalism demands respect for all cultural traditions, while feminism interrogates and challenges all cultural traditions'. Modood's endorsement of feminism as a source of political aspiration of the politics of Muslim assertiveness conveniently bypasses this major tension which traverses the relationship between feminism and traditional modes of belonging, as we have seen it throughout the thesis.

5.3 Postsecular multiculturalism: the coming of age or the end of the road?

If during the rise of anti-Enlightenment tradition the question of pluralism was framed as a battle against the 'uniformity' brought about by the abolition of privileges (Sternhell 2010: 218), today the battle of pluralism is given against the alleged 'uniformity' imposed on non-secular forms of life and flourishing by the dominant secular culture. The critique of secularism is perhaps the aspect which breaks more strikingly from mainstream multiculturalism in Modood's postsecular version who argues that any programme of racial and multicultural equality is not possible without a discussion of the merits and limits of secularism (2007: 71-72), even if 'the emergence of Muslim political agency has thrown multiculturalism into theoretical and practical disarray' (2007: 85). Indeed the particular demands that have been associated with the politics of Muslims assertiveness have met with the essentially negative reaction of the founding figures of the field, especially when the practical consequences of religious multiculturalism became the epicentre of one of the most important political crises of liberalism in recent years, i.e. the *Satanic Verses* controversy, which brought this split within the field of theory of multiculturalism to the fore. Kymlicka saw the controversy as an attempt from British Muslims to seek laws 'primarily to control apostasy within the Muslim community, rather than to control the expression of non-Muslims' (Kymlicka 1992: 43) and to gain the legal power to 'restrict the liberty of its own members, so as to preserve its traditional religious practices' (1992: 39). Taylor, although admitting that there is something problematical about telling Muslims, as members of a different culture, that 'this is how we do things here', he eventually concludes that 'this reply must be made in cases like the Rushdie controversy, where "how we do things" covers such issues as the right to life and to freedom of speech' (Taylor 1994: 62-63). Finally, Walzer argues banning the *Satanic Verses* would mean to 'suggest that pluralism and equality require a rhetorical non-aggression pact. No one should insult, disdain, mock, scorn, or express contempt for anyone else's person or beliefs. As in the pious adage about the dead, so now with the living, we must speak nicely about one another or say nothing at all. This is public life on tiptoe and it is hard to imagine a free society accepting such constraints (Walzer 1989: 14). The *Satanic Verses* controversy highlights the inherent difficulty of multiculturalism to find a politically defensible, yet theoretically consistent, position between recognition or accommodation rights, especially when the secular basis of discussion for the settlement of public affairs is removed.

In spite of the reservations if not hostility to the politicisation of religion as a facet of multiculturalism expressed from these leading figures, Modood persistently argues that the most important problem against a redefinition of equality sensitive to difference is secularism, which he distinguishes into a 'soft' desirable version ('secularism-as-is', 2008: 51) and a dangerous 'missionary' (ibid) version. In arguing that the inclusion of Islam as an organised religion and of Muslim identity as a public identity is necessary to pursue religious equality, Modood and Kastoryano (2006: 176) maintain that 'while this inclusion runs against certain interpretations of secularism, it is not inconsistent with what secularism means in Europe. We should let the latter and the spirit of compromise that it represents to be our guide and not an ideological secularism that is unfortunately generating European domestic versions of "the clash of civilizations" thesis and the conflicts that entails for European societies'. Not only that, but secularism seems also to be the main obstacle between 'coalitional possibilities between sexual politics and religious multiculturalism' (Modood 2008: 47).

The crux of the matter in the critique of secularism from a multiculturalist perspective is the public versus private identities and spheres and 'the view that certain activities, discourses, identities, organisations, authority etc., namely those and only those that can be categorised as "religious", are not appropriate in the public sphere' (Modood 2008: 50). Building on the familiar critique about the assumed morally and religiously neutral nature of the public domain Modood (2005: 113) argues that 'this way of structuring space and of deciding what is public and what is private can be an enormous source of power and inequality' because the subordinate, oppressed or marginal groups also have values norms and voice which should be part of the structuring of the public space (Modood 2007: 54). In this sense it comes as no surprise that he also rejects the secular proposal of further eliminating the traces of religious bias in the public sphere (for instance, by withdrawing public funding for all religious schools) because this is a 'form of equality in which the privileged lose something but the underprivileged gain nothing' (Modood 2006: 44).

This postsecular stance, a shared conceptual and moral locus across the varieties of 'post' social theories that engage with Muslim subjectivity, shifts the focus from the practical questions of accommodation of minority and oppressed groups, i.e. from questions of 'merely civil rights' (Young 1990: 16) to the issue of recognition and the kind of reform of social consciousness it

requires. Modood's take on multiculturalism seems to presuppose that such a reform is necessary in order to properly understand the different kind of commitment that religion represents. For Modood, it is a matter of recognising the special status of religion is a necessary step towards addressing religious inequalities. In his critique of Spinner Halev's (2000) proposition that the rights allocated of religious groups should be made available to everyone as a pragmatic and fair solution of the way conservative religious minorities can be accommodated in liberal societies, Modood argues that this solution 'fails to show that religious people are not being treated specially' (2005: 181) because religion has a normative force overriding ordinary desire. This is, however, a reasoning that does not stand up to scrutiny, not only because it fails to consider other forms of normative force, such as urban and youth subcultures for whom their special attire is integral to their identity, or political dissenters and activists (e.g. refusal to military service) whose political commitments may also have extraordinary normative force; but also because it is self-defeating as it claims that differential treatment based on religious grounds because religion is a special case does not entail that the beneficiaries of those rights are treated specially.

Such view which implies a kind of reform of social consciousness if recognition is to be accomplished is also shared by Parekh, one of the leading figures in philosophical multiculturalism. For Parekh (2000: 110) the failure of recognition and appreciation of other ways of life stems from the fact that liberals focus on 'tolerating and rarely respecting or cherishing them'. Nothing less than a 'cultural revolution', to use Barry's (2001: 275, 277) words, would be required for such appreciation as one cannot cherish something one does not believe in, but, naturally, one must tolerate it because the law says so. Such move requires almost a kind of conversion which is perhaps not that far from 'the totalist logic of integration' which Parekh (2000: 187) criticises:

There is therefore a relentless pressure to bring the private realm into harmony with the values of the public realm, *so that public values are internalized and become part of every citizen's moral identity and understanding*. This is how the Lang Commission on Nationality in France defined integration, and justified state intervention in immigrant ways of life and thought. In Germany *it is not considered enough if immigrants observe the country's public values*; they must make an '*inner affirmation*' of them. Muslim parents who send their children to religious classes and warn them against the influence of some Western values are said to 'act against integration'. Integration not only goes all the way down but also keeps

extending sideways. It is not enough if immigrants integrate economically and politically but prefer to marry among themselves or lead culturally self-contained lives (emphasis added, *ibid*).

Despite the deployment of the soft language of diversity, this reform of social consciousness requires nothing less than a change in what people *think* rather than in what people *do*, a move which is perhaps more oppressing and authoritarian than the clear cut categories and the logic of equidistance of the secular political culture. The other problem, of course, with approaches which over-emphasise the language of sentiments at the expense of normativity of rights is that if equal rights 'are disparaged as worthless in the absence of a "cultural revolution"' as Barry (2001: 277) notices, 'they are liable to be swept away by a counter-revolution'. The sad example of all revolutions proclaimed in the name of moral values and on the grounds of consciousness reform alerts of the potential dangers of this kind of a-political politics which appeals to moral sentiments rather than the logic of equality and individual rights, including the right to remain indifferent or unappreciative of other ways of life, as long as everyone tolerates each other. But there are further problems with the way this reform of social consciousness and cultural change are understood within Parekh's work. Barry notes that the kind of change envisioned by Parekh's work is inconsistent, if not contradictory to its own political philosophy (the same goes for Modood as he also insists that cultural – meant as ethnicity and/or religion - difference, above all other forms, should be regarded as sovereign). Commenting on the Parekh Report (2000), Barry (2001b: 68) points to the deep influence of conservative philosopher Michael Oakeshott and his views on the crucial role of traditional ways of doing things as a political resource and on the uselessness of general principles as guides to action. 'Changes of the kind that the Report proposes have not come about in the past by reflecting on "intimations" but by appeal to abstract universal principles of the most crassly rationalistic kind' Barry observes (*ibid*), by listing the examples of the abolition of slavery and the transformation of the legal status of women. Or in other words, these changes which encompass the entirety of social institutions require a radical break with 'common values' and the established, traditional ways of thinking, as well as their coding in the vocabulary of universal rights. As Barry (2001b: 69) concludes, the kind of change – for instance anti-discriminatory measures - imagined by Parekh cannot be justified on the basis of its own political theory, but on the contrary it can be implemented on the universal validity of non-discrimination, regardless of whether it is part of the 'local repertoire'.

The logic of recognition and primacy of the 'community' stems from a more fundamental questioning of liberalism, by which what is often meant is secularism, or in which the two terms and the respective political cultures they represent are thought as identical and interchangeable. According to this line of critique secularism and liberal justice – individual rights, political and moral autonomy, freedom of choice – are only one of the many cultural norms and ways of being in the world, of which none should be prioritised and all should be politicised and contested. In this logic, secular and liberal values alone cannot provide the basis of justice for ethno-cultural or ethno-religious groups or for their relations with the dominant Other, namely the Western societies in which usually the problem of multicultural coexistence arises. Modood's and Parekh's work are premised on the larger critique of the West in the sense of 'provincializing' the universalism of its political culture, i.e. liberalism and secularism.

One of the challenging critiques of the idea that ethno-cultural or ethno-religious groups do not share liberal – and for that matter, secular – values and that the content of their demands has philosophical and political implications, such as the rejection of Western political values comes from within the field of multiculturalism itself. In his response to Parekh's (1997) reluctance to forge a theory of multicultural citizenship based on what he deems as the heritage of just one cultural tradition, i.e. liberalism, Kymlicka (2001a: 60-61) argues that the disagreement between minority groups and the liberal state is not about the legitimacy of liberal-democratic principles but about 'the implications of these principles for concrete questions about the distribution of power between federal and regional governments, or about the legitimacy of affirmative action or about naturalization rules, or about the designation of public holidays, or about the scope of minority language rights'. For Kymlicka, despite the fact that for philosophers like Parekh are tempted to represent multiculturalism as a 'clash of civilizations' 'in which the majority seeks to impose its Western liberal democratic traditions on minorities who resist in the name of some other world-historic culture with its distinctive political traditions', such representation is wrong because 'the heart of multiculturalism in the West is about how to interpret liberal democratic principles, not about whether those principles are legitimate' (ibid).⁷³

⁷³As Glazer (1997) had famously stated that 'we' - advocates and sceptics alike - 'are all multiculturalists now' (the title of his book). Kymlicka (2001a: 35) also states elsewhere that multiculturalism had won the battle and that 'the question we face is not whether to adopt multiculturalism, but rather what kind of multiculturalism to adopt'.

To be sure both Modood and Parekh oscillate in the way they represent Muslim demands: on the one hand, the Muslim community is represented as motivated by the Western liberal values and hence their demands can be framed in the language of rights and accommodated within soft versions of liberalism and secularism; on the other hand, this same community is also presented as subjectified by values that are different and incomprehensible without a reform of the current social consciousness and political culture, hence, they need to be framed in a language of recognition. If we follow Kymlicka (2001a: 47) again, the reason for such oscillation partially lies on the fact that existing multiculturalist theorists conflate normative and explanatory statements, i.e. that the fact that certain group-specific demands are consistent in theory with liberal-democratic values does not necessarily mean that the groups are demanding these rights in practice motivated by liberal-democratic values. By the same token, the fact that the Muslim demands may be in theory consistent with anti-racism and feminism does not entail that these demands are motivated by the political values of such discourses and that the politics of Muslim assertiveness is 'a politics of "catching up" with racial equality and feminism' (Modood 2006: 14, 18; 2009: 196, 198). The fact that a broad coalition between minorities, between, for example, religious multiculturalism and feminists or gay activists, remains on the level of wishful thinking and is confined within the academic sphere with little resonance in the way the members of minority groups frame their claims, is quite telling of the kind of conflation overriding the debate, and it becomes even more questionable politically for those intellectuals who are viewed as spokespersons of a given community.⁷⁴

The explanation for such oscillation, even inconsistency, could also lie within the absence of any foundational basis or within the relativist stance that such approaches adopt in the last instance. Kymlicka argues that the emphasis on the 'sacred' rather than instrumental value of culture which undergirds the shift towards religious-friendly multiculturalism conflates the fact that individuals are free to decide how sacred they view the particular traditions and practices of their culture and to try to persuade others to do so, and even if within the liberal framework this is a permissible attitude, it is not an obligation of the State: 'If we accepted the idea that the state should view cultural practices as sacred, then liberalism would never have arisen. In every

⁷⁴ The question of creation of alliances between various minority, oppressed and dissenting groups has been a declared objective of the multiculturalist political project since its inception, even if it has occasionally been recognised that alliance does not come automatically through common stories of marginalisation and that intellectual work cannot be exported from the one context to another (CCGS, 1992: 536).

society where liberalism has emerged, it has emerged precisely by defeating the claims of cultural conservatives that existing practices and traditions are sacrosanct' (2001a: 62). Like liberalism which cannot stand without a foundational basis, multiculturalism cannot stand as a viable alternative without ceding to conservative ideas of sacredness and cherished traditions which have little to do with modern forms of democratic government and modern political claims (feminist, anti-racist and so on) about moral autonomy and emancipation. The problem with postsecular multiculturalism seems to be the same that Leo Strauss had identified in his critique of Isaiah Berlin's pluralism: the fact that postsecular multiculturalism cannot live without an 'absolutist' basis and cannot live with an 'absolutist' basis (Strauss 1961).

Kymlicka's internal critique of the revised, religious version of multiculturalism is right in the sense of correctly identifying the shortcomings of retreating to forms of governing modern states and their minorities by prioritising recognition and questions of consciousness instead of accommodation and practical questions of redistribution of power and resources. However, it misses out the fact that the religious turn of multiculturalism, as advocated by Modood and Parekh, is simply the logical extension of the internal dynamics of multiculturalism itself. The prioritisation of indigeneity – as an instance of unique difference - on which his own foundational work is based and the general emphasis of culture as the overdetermining instance of existence, the conceptualisation of difference as an innate and self-evident source of social good, cannot but lead logically to further relativisation of political values and fragmentation of difference. Indeed no conceivable multiculturalism can sufficiently explain why certain differences require recognition of special status and others not. In that sense the religious or postsecular turn of multiculturalism is nothing more than its natural development.

But what also emerges now is a contradiction which the postsecular turn of multiculturalism brings to the fore: namely, that the endorsement of religious difference is not only a sign of a more mature and inclusive multiculturalism but also the closure of the possibility of articulation of progressive 'secular multicultural', to use Pathak's (2008) term. In his internal critique of multiculturalism Pathak takes issue with the conceptualisation of culture as 'something we inherit, not something that we make' (2008: 131) and with the idea that 'historical communities' – essentially a metonymy for ethno-religious communities – are a 'qualitatively different experience from voluntary forms of association' (2008: 132) in Parekh's work (incidentally, ideas that

undergird to a large extent Modood's work as well). Pathak observes that this heavy preference of 'historical communities' and of inherited over secular relations in Parekh's thinking comes at the expense of a worldly sense of community as experiential and evolving and that such prioritisation has two major consequences. Firstly, in line with observations made by Malik (2007, 2009) and Sivanandan (1990), such prioritisation finds itself in 'agreement with the patronage of inherited culture' and legitimises the state multiculturalist policy which 'in the British context at least, has financially rewarded the pursuit of cultural recognition', and which fostered 'the formation of ethnically defined fiefdoms managed by a class of community ambassadors who arrogate representative authority to themselves' (2008: 132). Secondly, and even more importantly for the kind of questions pursued here, Pathak associates the prioritisation of historical ethno-religious communities with a clear anti-secular orientation: 'the inherited cultures which draw most protection from anti-secularists are overwhelmingly religious (as they are in Parekh's multiculturalism)' (2008: 133) - and for that matter in Modood's version of politico-religious version of multiculturalism too. Pathak argues that anti-secularism and multiculturalism converge in many levels but the most paradoxical one is their shared unequivocal articulation of culture, 'especially when set in relief against the resurgence of cultural nationalism across the world' (ibid). The immediate political implication of such convergence can be seen in the example of Indian politics where anti-secularists have turned not only against the condemnation of nationalism but simultaneously towards the dismantlement of secular opposition to it: 'this surrender to religious culture has been fateful and partly responsible for the Indian Left's capitulation to Hindutva's assault on Indian secularity' (2008: 134). By doing so, both anti-secularists and multiculturalists find themselves on the wrong side of the political fault lines, even if they do not recognise it themselves Pathak argues (ibid), and we shall examine the consequences of such culturalisation of politics in the case of Islam in the next chapter.

Naturally, in the case of both Parekh and Modood it would be more precise to talk about postsecularism rather than clear-cut anti-secularism, even if a common concern between these two trends is 'the preservation of religious communities' cultural autonomy from conformity to secular values' (Pathak 2008: 134) and which in the case of Islam is manifested as a fascination with religious subjectivity as authentic, special, oppressed and in need of recognition and public accommodation. Pathak challenges those projects which see cultural recognition and religious prioritisation as 'the end of the rainbow' and asks 'why we shouldn't take multiculturalism's

attentiveness to identity and build something more ambitious with it' (2008: 136). His suggestion towards constructing possibilities of 'secular multicultural' draws on Vergès's (2001) 'creole cosmopolitanism' which he describes as motivated by a longing for 'access to the universal', by the disapproval of assumptions that inhabitations of 'cultural' minority produce exclusively parochial political values and by the possibility to defend secular principles from the particularities of local positions without strain or contradiction (ibid). Such a move towards the abandonment of cultural difference and the quest of a universal to be constructed, meets Phillips's re-imagination of a 'multiculturalism without culture'. Arguing from a feminist perspective, Phillips (2007: 8) defines this theoretical move as follows: 'a multiculturalism that dispenses with the reified notions of culture that feed those stereotypes to which so many feminists have objected, yet retains enough robustness to address inequalities between cultural groups; a multiculturalism in which the language of cultural difference no longer gives hostages to fortune or sustenance to racists, but also no longer paralyses normative judgment'. While she finds it important to recognise that people have cultural needs, Phillips argues that time has come to dispense with particular notions of culture that have proven unhelpful and to find a middle ground (Phillips 2007: 52).⁷⁵

What is implicitly suggested here, by both Pathak and Phillips, is that if multiculturalism is to make a politically progressive contribution it needs to shed its overdetermining culturalism. Whether multiculturalism can be re-articulated by rejection of difference and as a quest of a new universalism is a question that is beyond the scope of the questions I sought to address here. But what can be safely established is that religious, postsecular multiculturalism, of which the politics of Muslim assertiveness is a prime example, cannot be constitutive of any kind of progressive and inclusive political thinking as its overdetermining culturalism and prioritisation of traditional ethno-religious communities precludes any access to the universal (in the sense of the possibility to articulate secular principles from the particularities of local positions, as mentioned above) unless by assimilation of its 'Other' to its own logic and truth. The next question then is what kind of political culture and reasoning are fostered through the logic of culturalism. Significant controversies of our times have been framed by multiculturalist sensibilities and their appeal, most notably by reference to Muslim subjectivity. This is what the next chapter aims to explore by focusing on the discourse of Islamophobia and its political uses and rhetorical tropes.

⁷⁵ In this attempt, Phillips seems not far from Appiah's (1997a, 2006) cosmopolitan manifesto despite her suspicion towards what she sees as a 'problematic transnational cosmopolitanism' (Phillips 2007: 15).

Chapter Six

Chapter Six

Shaping Political Reasoning: Muslim Subjectivity and the Culturalisation of Politics

- 6.1 Introduction: Muslim subjectivity between competing political frameworks
- 6.2 Debating Islamophobia: from concept to discourse
- 6.3 Political assertion as ethical battle: oppression, offence and injury
- 6.4 Culturalism and its discontents

6.1 Introduction: Muslim subjectivity between competing political frameworks

As seen in the previous chapter, culture has come to play a very important role in the way social difference is explained, most emblematically in the case of Islam. This analytical turn to culture, supports a more generalised tendency in academic and public debates, known as culturalism, which often reduces sociological phenomena, especially when Others are concerned, to the culture of a group, minority, nation, civilisation, 'race' and so on, and popularises the idea that societies are composed by groups who all have a clear, stable homogeneous and over-determining set of cultural values and standards. This chapter focuses on the way the logic of culturalism has given shape to specific, religious and culture-friendly forms of political reasoning, and how it has given form to a political landscape which favours the understanding of Islam as a matter of an oppressed, identity-oriented and recognition-seeking public subjectivity. Some of the most important political controversies in recent years were defined by their relationship to Islam and the demands expressed for the accommodation of religious rights of Muslim community: the *Satanic Verses*, the veil, the burqa, the Danish cartoons, the minaret vote in Switzerland, Monica Ali's novel *Brick Lane*, Dutch politician's Pim Fortuyn death, Ayaan Hirsi Ali's and Theo Van Gogh's documentary *Submission* and the subsequent assassination of the former, are well-known cases which brought to the fore of political agendas the discussion about Muslim subjectivity as well as about the type of compromise that can be reached to accommodate religious subjects and communities in modern Western societies. The tensions that are stemming from the expectedly strained relationship between the mostly secular and liberalised nature of today's Western societies and the demands for accommodation of the mostly conservative (in both the ethical and political sense of the term) religious minorities have been overwhelmingly presented within rigid binary schemes: either under the rubric of the alarmist 'clash of civilizations' scheme, or as an

instance of collision of power between the neo-imperialist, neo-colonial or neo-Orientalist Western states against the oppressed and resisting religious Muslim minorities. However, such polarised approach of the issue – which must be recognised as an issue without giving in to the exaggerated and untruthful representation of Islam as a threat, but also without presupposing Islam’s politically resisting or subversive character – reproduces the dilemma identified at the introduction and attested throughout the thesis: the ‘us’ against ‘them’ (us, as the ‘civilised West’ against the ‘backward Islam’, or ‘us’ as the ‘anti-hegemonic Left’ against the ‘dominant West’) which, despite its political effectiveness is not necessarily suitable for analytical and interpretative purposes. This is not to deny that depending on which political framework controls the semantic field, the phenomenon – i.e. the meaning of Muslim public subjectivity – turns out to be a different thing. However, at closer inspection, the real issue seems to be at the crossroads of these competing political frameworks rather than within them, since despite their opposing purposes, they tend to reproduce the same timeless but obviously not yet tired scheme of ‘clash’. Therefore, the point is not to pick up the ‘right’ moral stance but to explain how and why the dilemma arises in the first place, and what forms of public reasoning and political sensibilities it enables and sustains.

In order to look at the way public and political sensibilities have been formed in relation to religious and more precisely Muslim subjectivity and analyse their significance, the chapter will look, first, at the concept of Islamophobia. This term in which the controversies mentioned above were framed, is used both to describe anti-Muslim sentiments and the discrimination - real or experienced as such – suffered by Muslims as a result of such attitudes, as well as to provide a language for denouncing situations that are qualified as Islamophobic. The section focuses in the transformation of Islamophobia from a diagnostic of discrimination into a discourse of victimhood. Second, the chapter will look at the uses of pivotal rhetorical tropes and analytical categories of the politics of Muslim subjectivity, namely oppression, offence and injury in order to show how political and moral sensibilities about religious identities have been enabled in academic and public debates about Islam. Finally, the chapter will reflect on the political effects of the language of culture on which such sensibilities rely and it will argue that the kind of culturalism prevailing in contemporary discussions about difference is not conducive to a political culture in which the tensions that arise naturally in the public sphere can be appreciated and productively debated. On the contrary, once coated with the language of victimhood, these

tensions turn almost inevitably into collisions. The chapter will conclude by arguing that the prominence of culture brought to the fore by the logic of culturalism is, in the last instance, the mirror-image of the Orientalist rationality that anti-Orientalism seeks to analytically deconstruct and politically counter, and that the generalised culturalisation of politics ultimately gives rise to new insidious ways of excluding the Other in the name of culture.

6.2 Debating Islamophobia: from concept to discourse

The concept of Islamophobia, which is coeval with the emergence of Muslim subjectivity - aims to account for a social condition in which Muslims emerge as an object of aversion, fear and hostility in Western societies, as well as to provide an analytical tool for dissecting the phenomenon and a lexicon for its moral and political denouncement. It enters the public arena following the well-known report 'Islamophobia: A Challenge for Us All' produced by the Runnymede Trust in 1997, a British research foundation specialising in ethnic and racial issues. In this often cited report, Islamophobia is defined as 'an unfounded hostility towards Islam', as well as 'the practical consequences of such hostility in unfair discrimination against Muslim individuals and communities, and the exclusion of Muslims from mainstream political and social affairs' (Commission on British Muslims and Islamophobia 1997: 4). Even if the term was in use since the beginning of the twentieth century (Bravo-Lopez 2011), it really acquired popularity, as well analytical value and political significance, after the publication of the Runnymede report and especially after the 09/11 events. Since then, each one of international political crises related to Islam - especially the 'wars of terror' - and each one of the controversies in relation to the moral fabric of Western societies mentioned above, further established the term as perhaps the most central in the analysis and critique of such events.

Despite its popularity, and the insertion of an 'escape clause' in the Runnymede report i.e. *unfounded* hostility as Shryock (2010: 4) observes, the concept was not spared from criticism. Malik (2005) for instance disputed the very existence of the widespread Islamophobia on the basis of empirical evidence, which he separated from the aversion against Muslims, whereas Halliday (1999: 898) had argued that the term has misleading associations as the attack is not against not Islam as a faith but Muslims and that a more appropriate term would be 'anti-Muslimism'. Bleich (2011: 1583) notices that little, except the assumption that 'Islamophobia is a social evil', unites

the divergent definitions and the lack of precision and coherence among academic and lay users of the term. He (2011: 1588) argues that one of the difficulties in pinning down the term is that debates about Islamophobia are taking place across several levels, such as its definition, key components, intensity causes and effects and identifies three problematical areas of usage of the term: the over-reliance of authors on the historical roots of Islamophobia; the identification of current socioeconomic disadvantages suffered by Muslim communities and the anecdotal or symbolic character of the examples of violence directed against Muslims; and, finally, the conflation of attitudes toward overlapping ethnic, national-origin, or immigrant-status groups.⁷⁶ As a corrective, Bleich (2011: 1585) suggested that Islamophobia is best defined as ‘indiscriminate negative attitudes or emotions directed at Islam or Muslims. ‘Indiscriminate’ here does not refer to differentiated attitudes or emotions, hence Islamophobia is not merely the act of questioning or even criticising aspects of Islamic doctrine or Muslim practices but the reasoning which deducts the condemnation of Islam or Muslims as a whole because of the rejection of certain practices. Bravo-Lopez’s definition concurs to the rejection of facile attribution of the term for cases that consist of ‘a merely critical or negative attitude towards Islam’ (2011: 563). In his critical engagement with the term, he insists that what constitutes Islamophobia is not ‘degrading or humiliating representations of Islam and the Prophet constitute Islamophobia per se’ but the motivation underpinning the misrepresentation of Islam or its symbols and holy figures (2011: 561). Hence, for Bravo-Lopez, the ideology of Islamophobia carries within it an image of Islam as the enemy, ‘as a threat to “our” well-being and even to “our” survival’ (2011: 569) and of Muslims insofar as they are perceived as the incarnation of Islam (2011: 568). This particular angle of ‘enemy image’ in deciphering ‘Islamophobia’ is a very important element to understand how the ideology of culturalism works, as we shall see in the last section of the chapter.

The discussion about the scope and content of the concept of Islamophobia here is not for the sake of scholarly preoccupation only. Conceptual clarity in this case is a matter of the way intellectual sensibilities are mobilised and political motives attributed. Firstly, because the very etymology of the term tends to pathologise responses, some legitimate, to Islam as a set of ideas or an ideology, as well as to the kind of Muslim subjectivity that has emerged since the theoretical cum political turn to culture. Naturally, Islamophobia is not a clinical psychological term, hence

⁷⁶ This point is also shared by Laitin (2010: 437) who points to the general difficulty in ‘isolating the Muslim component’ from debates about immigration.

the component 'phobia' does not refer to irrational fear, and in that sense it is indeed equivalent (but not an alternate) to racism, sexism and so on. However, like in the case of xenophobia or homophobia, the term does make appeal to the same continuum of normality/pathology used by those who see Islam, foreignness or homosexuality as an 'illness'. Secondly, because the automatic labelling of negative reactions to Islam as racism or cultural racism – or in different terms the redefinition of Islam as race - puts progressive and secularist critics of Islam, and of any other religion for that matter, at an extremely difficult position where they risk to be labelled as racists. It eventually risks putting discussion about religion, and more specifically about Islam, off limits as legitimate scepticism can be easily extrapolated as Islamophobia and subsequently as racism (Balakrishnan 2001). Take for instance the way Okin's famous essay 'Is Multiculturalism Bad for Women' (1999), discussed in the previous chapter. Okin was accused of racism for arguing that, from a (liberal) feminist point of view, certain minority patriarchal practices and traditions which harm women do not deserve to be preserved and that women may be better off if such traditions were to become extinct or alter themselves to reinforce the equality of women. Fekete (2006: 12) reproaches Okin for advancing a thesis that is 'tendentious, elevating multiculturalism as it does into a philosophical doctrine and investing it with meanings which are not there, in order to show that special privileges afforded to immigrants threaten the fragile human rights of western women'. However, Fekete's critique becomes equally tendentious when it conflates Okin's liberal feminism with the defence of national culture and when it compares Okin's reservations in relation to multiculturalism's tolerance of gender discriminatory practices with Huntington's 'clash of civilizations'. What this discussion reveals is that the slippage, from the criticism of specific practices related to religion as being problematical within a liberal feminist perspective to the accusation of holding an explicitly confrontational Islamophobic understanding of politics, is only one step away once categories and tools of analysis become interchangeable.

The tendency to collapse criticism of religious doctrine with the aversion of the people who practice it is already present in the emerging moment of the contemporary form of the concept of Islamophobia: the Runnymede report defines Islamophobia as 'a useful shorthand way of referring to dread or hatred of Islam - and, therefore, to fear or dislike of all or most Muslims' (Commission on British Muslims and Islamophobia 1997, p. 1), an important description as it introduces the idea that the dread or hatred of Islam can be unproblematically extrapolated into the fear or dislike of all Muslims. Even if this definition is nuanced by clarifying that 'it is not intrinsically

phobic or prejudiced, of course, to disagree with or to disapprove of Muslim beliefs, laws or practices' and that 'legitimate criticism and disagreement' is different from 'unfounded hostility and prejudice' (Commission on British Muslims and Islamophobia 1997: 4), the questionable assumption that criticism of the dogma leads to the racist hate of its believers or practitioners seems to be congenital to the contemporary upsurge of Islamophobia as a concept.

This slippage between different forms and purposes of rejection – suspicion, criticism, indifference, discrimination, hate, racism – is prominent in the way supporters of Muslim religious sensibilities and defenders of the right to criticism get entangled in an antagonism for victimhood and alarmism. The public statement titled 'Manifesto: Together Facing the New Totalitarianism', is representative of the tone characterising the debate. The intellectual figures who sign this controversial proclamation, state that: 'We refuse to renounce our critical spirit out of fear of being accused of "Islamophobia", a wretched concept that confuses criticism of Islam as a religion and stigmatization of those who believe in it'.⁷⁷ On the one hand the Manifesto criticises the political use of the concept Islamophobia for conflating religious scepticism with religious hatred. Despite the polemical temper, it does raise the issue of whether legitimate religious scepticism, in serious or satirical form, should necessarily entail the rejection, discrimination or actual hatred of the entire population which shares these specific religious beliefs, an issue explored in more detail in the next section. On the other hand, however, it makes a sensational appeal by comparing different forms of totalitarianism: 'After having overcome fascism, Nazism, and Stalinism, the world now faces a new global totalitarian threat: Islamism'. Naturally, no comparison is politically or intellectually neutral, especially with regards heavily loaded ethical matters. In this case it is obvious to what kind of moral sensibilities such parallel hints, namely anti-Semitism and the Holocaust and its haunting legacy for Europe's traditions of tolerance and diversity. But what is even more interesting to note is the fact that those who support the right of Muslim subjectivity to be expressed and accommodated even in ways that clash with established liberal traditions within Western societies, have recourse to the same symbolically powerful terms such as anti-Semitism.

⁷⁷ The 'Manifesto: Together Facing the New Totalitarianism' is a political statement made in response to the violence surrounding the *Jyllands-Posten* Muhammad cartoons controversy. The letter was published in the French weekly newspaper Charlie Hebdo. The statement signatories were Ayaan Hirsi Ali, Chahla Chafiq, Caroline Fourest, Bernard Henri Lévy, Irshad Manji, Mehdi Mozaffari, Maryam Namazie, Taslima Nasreen, Salman Rushdie, Antoine Sfeir, Philippe Val, Ibn Warraq. The full statement can be viewed in <http://news.bbc.co.uk/1/hi/world/europe/4764730.stm>

Drawing a parallel with anti-Semitism is a fundamental aspect in the construction of the discourse about Islamophobia. In making the case that a new term is necessary to describe the emerging phenomenon of anti-Muslim prejudice, the Runnymede report states that 'In a similar way there was a time in European history when a new word was needed and coined to highlight the growing dangers of anti-Jewish hostility. The coining of a new word, and with it the identification of a growing danger, did not in that instance avert eventual tragedy. By the same token the mere use of the new word "Islamophobia" will not in itself prevent tragic conflict and waste' (Commission on British Muslims and Islamophobia 1997: 4). This analogy runs deep in the contemporary discussion of Islamophobia as a phenomenon of discrimination and as a term that accounts for it, and the case is made more often than not on the basis of recognising Islamophobia as a form of racism. Meer and Noorani, for instance, argue that since Jews and Muslims define themselves and are defined by others through reference to race and religion, it is reasonable to consider whether they have shared any similarities in their representation as constitutional religious minorities in the State (2008: 196) and to challenge 'crude politico-legal distinctions between anti-Semitism and anti-Muslim sentiment' (2008: 214). In a similar vein, Modood claimed that 'while some people dispute whether contemporary anti-Muslim prejudice can properly be called racism as opposed to intolerance, no one, as far as I know, asks if anti-Semitism is racism' (2005: 10)⁷⁸ and pointed to the politically selective ways in the terms 'racism' and 'racist' and their dependence on biology, favouring, for instance Jews, and discriminating against Muslims (ibid). Fekete (2006: 10) argued that the archetypical Muslim as inimical to Europe stands for what the archetypical Jew once used to be. The analogy is also popular beyond academia and among Muslim spokespersons: during the Rushdie affair Muslim philosopher Shabbir Akhtar wrote that 'the next time there are gas chambers in Europe, there is no doubt concerning who will be inside them'; Massoud Shadjareh, chair of the Islamic Human Rights Commission stated in 2000 that 'Muslims in Britain face the same fate this century as Jews in Europe in the last'; whilst Salma Yaqoob, Respect party councillor in Birmingham, estimated in

⁷⁸ Indeed few would refute the racist nature of anti-Semitism, nonetheless, it should be noted that such views are not unheard of, and they do not necessarily take place within racist milieus only: Bravo López (2011: 558), following Katz (1983), Levy (1991), Langmuir (1996), Lindemann (1997) Pulzer (2005) and Volkov (2006) notes that 'it is doubtful that anti-Semitism can be considered as a form of racism or cultural racism. Indeed, the relationship between anti-Semitism and racism has been and still is the subject of a longstanding debate in literature on anti-Semitism. Within this debate, there is a strong tendency to deny that anti-Semitism is a form of racism without denying that there is a union between the two in certain contexts'.

2006 that Muslims in Britain ‘are subject to attacks reminiscent of the gathering of anti-Semitism in the first decades of the last century’ (cited in Malik 2009: 131-132).

Nonetheless the idea that Muslims are in a similar position to the one historically experienced by Jews as victims of anti-Semitism was also met with considerable scepticism. Schiffer and Wagner argue that equating ‘anti-Semitism and Islamophobia would not only be a moral problem, but an analytical one as well’ (2011: 78) since the two phenomena are located in different historical continuums (2011: 81). They point out that ‘it is inappropriate to play Jews and Muslims off against each other as objects of racist discourses’ (2011: 78) and conclude that ‘it is obviously absurd to claim that Muslims today are in the same situation as Jews were “back then”’ (2011: 83). In a similar vein Bunzl also advised against the common impulse to analogise anti-Semitism and Islamophobia and qualifies as alarmist any suggestion implying that ‘Muslims are about to be targeted for something like a second Holocaust’ which does not of course exclude the fact that ‘Muslims are the victims of extraordinary discrimination’ (Bangstad and Bunzl 2010: 215). Bunzl argues that whereas anti-Semitism was invented in the late nineteenth century to police the ethnically pure nation-state, Islamophobia, is a formation of the present, marshaled to safeguard a supranational Europe (2005: 502; see also Boyer 2005). Therefore, obscuring the distinctions between different forms of hostility and arguing for the fundamental analogy of anti-Semitism and Islamophobia is misleading, not only historically but also in terms of their contemporary articulations (ibid).

The question that arises at this point then is why, despite the reservations expressed by critics in terms of the historicity and politicality of the comparison between Islamophobia and anti-Semitism, the parallel has taken a deep root in Muslim claim-making. I would like to suggest that the answer lies into the transformation of Islamophobia from a concept, from a diagnostic of discrimination, into a *discourse* that aims not merely to identify incidents of discrimination but to make the case that Muslims collectively are the victims of modern Western ideology which constitutes itself and sustains its domination by opposition to Islam. In a sense Islamophobia as a discourse makes almost an epochal claim: it becomes the symbol of postsecular times, in which secularism – as a dominant, oppressing state ideology and as a modern mode of governance and the cluster of ethical sensibilities – comes under question by religious revivalism and by the more generalised cultural turn to religiosity, of which Muslim public subjectivity is perhaps the most

prominent example. This is the turning point when Islamophobia turns from a measuring and monitoring device of anti-Muslim and anti-Islamic expressions, attitudes and hostilities and of the tendency of those to become generally more accepted, into a discourse which defines Islamophobia as

an ideological phenomenon, one that includes systems of thought and meaning, manifested in signifiers and symbols that influence, impact on and inform the social consensus about the Other. From this perspective, Islamophobia is not necessarily restricted to any specific action, practice, discrimination or prejudice but instead shapes that which is widely accepted as natural and normative with regard to Muslims, Islam or both (Allen 2011: 290).

6.3 Political assertion as ethical battle: oppression, offence and injury

The discourse of Islamophobia is a major vehicle through which forms of public reasoning are enabled such as the increasingly popular idea that religious subjectivities are oppressed or injured - beyond evident cases of discrimination - because of the way modern secular societies and their institutions are articulated. The appeal to victimhood and suffering of the Muslim community as a result of Islamophobia is central both for claims-making as well as for enabling political and moral sensibilities in support of these claims: as Birt (2009: 217) states, 'the common experience of Islamophobia creates a unique community of suffering, which conflates ethnically disparate communities as Muslims and creates an assertive Muslim identity politics'. In this context victimhood and suffering should be understood, primarily, as the result of ideological victimisation, i.e. relating to ideas and values that victimise individuals or groups, and secondly, to the material consequences for those who are victimised. Within this particular understanding of victimhood, political assertion is redefined as a matter of ethical battle where identitarian categories related to the understanding and vulnerability of the oppressed self, like injury or offence prevail over the ones of class position. Similarly, the struggle for social justice is about recognition of social identities and the symbolic injustice of cultural domination, nonrecognition or disrespect that they suffer, rather than the identification of social power axis, i.e. structural inequalities in opportunities and institutionalised power asymmetries. This is why the ethical matters arising from cases such as the *Satanic Verses* affair, the Danish cartoons, and the lesser in

magnitude, nonetheless similar in form and content furore over the *Brick Lane* novel – all of them art products and not factual accounts - caused more, or at least as much, reaction as matters of life and death, like the wars in Afghanistan and Iraq, cases of torture and human rights violations, such as the Guantanamo Bay outrage, or the veil ban and Swiss minaret vote which, despite their symbolic character, are practically involved in the actual practice of Islamic faith.

This shift of politics towards questions of ethics is by no means limited to the case of Islam alone but it is symptomatic of the identitarian ideology engendered by the nexus of suffering, recognition and reparation. This political attitude which affirms difference by emphasising suffering and which necessarily leads to antagonism between narratives of victimhood and claims of reparation by way of comparison between minorities, was, for instance, at the heart of ‘culture wars’ revolving around the revision of schools’ and colleges’ curricula in the US. Commenting on the politics of victimhood, Schlesinger (1991:1) noted on the dynamics of this peculiar antagonism between narratives of wounded identities:

At issue were textbooks responsive to the new curriculum. Polish-Americans demanded that any reference to Hitler's Holocaust must be accompanied by accounts of equivalent genocide suffered by Polish Christians. Armenian-Americans sought coverage of Turkish massacres; Turkish-Americans objected. Though Black historians testified that the treatment of Black history was exemplary, Afrocentrists said the textbooks would lead to “textbook genocide”. Moslems complained that an illustration of an Islamic warrior with a raised scimitar stereotyped Moslems as “terrorists”. One group after another (...) insisted that its forebears had suffered more than anyone else in history.

This generalised turn to the affirmation of moral vulnerability and victimhood is central in the idea that Muslim subjectivity gets insurmountably hurt when its symbolic universe is offended. The idea that such offence is unquestionably an act of Islamophobia has become an increasingly accepted explanation for political disputes related to questions of moral values, such as blasphemy and free speech. Oppression, offence and injury are perhaps the most identifiable categories of analysis cum rhetorical tropes through which the events related to the expression of Muslim public subjectivity are debated. There is no doubt that Muslims are today – i.e. in the post-09/11 era, because of its particular weight in international politics and the contemporary configurations

of world order – the targets of relentless stigmatisation,⁷⁹ the victims of this particular historical conjuncture (rather than, it needs to be noted again, the victims of an alleged perennial hostility between ‘the West’ and Islam, as it is discussed further down). But they are also the central figures in a moral drama involving the oppressed and the oppressor, in which the oppressed demand recognition of their suffering, which is claimed in terms of the offence and injury against their collective Muslim identity.

In the logic of this moral drama, victimhood is attested on the basis of drawing analogies between major tragic historical experiences or experiences on the one hand and the injury Muslims suffer as a result of disrespect towards holy figures and symbols of the faith on the other hand. Take for instance Parekh, who has recourse at the kind of impression that a parallel with the Holocaust, as perhaps the most tragic and iconic event of victimhood of modernity, can generate. In arguing against the idea that literary work should enjoy unlimited freedom beyond moral and social responsibility and norms of decency with regards to the *Satanic Verses* controversy, Parekh (2002: 318) experiments with the following hypothetical example:

Imagine a writer writing about the tragic victims of Auschwitz. He mocks and ridicules them, trivializes their suffering, and presents them as a despicable lot thoroughly deserving the mindless brutality inflicted upon them. He creates scenes of collective debauchery, wife-swapping, incest cannibalism and Jewish women offering themselves and their young sons and daughters to Nazi guards in return for a few more days of life or a few more crumbs of bread.

Parekh of course, recognises that ‘this is not at all to say that Rushdie’s discussion of Islam is anything like this’ (ibid) but the effect that the sacrilege of the historical memory of the Holocaust is so powerful that what goes unnoticed is the fact that the analogy between the collective trauma and collective memory of an atrocious historical experience is not of the same order as the injury felt by the offence of religious, and for that matter any other, beliefs or set of ideas. The same goes with the analogy between the ban on works which glorify self-immolation and the ban of *Satanic Verses* by the Indian government, used as an example for the same purpose

⁷⁹ As reported widely in the press, see for instance Abdul Bari 2012a; Abdul Bari 2012b; ‘American Terror: A Renewed Wave of Islamophobia Sweeps the United States’ 2012; Dabashi 2012; Hasan 2012; Kahn 2012; Walker and Taylor 2011.

by Parekh (2002: 320). Nonetheless, inciting self-harm, especially in situations entangled with deep-rooted traditions of gender inequalities, is not ethically of the same order as a book which satirises a holy figure.

Parekh is not alone in allowing for such slippage between experiences and phenomena of a different historical and political order to determine judgment as to what kind of recognition is owed to matters of injury of symbolic order and what kind of toleration is expected by religious groups, namely Muslims in this case, against irreverent views in liberalised societies. Modood, for instance, uses similar analogies to make the case of group defamation suffered by the Muslim community as a result of publishing the *Satanic Verses* novel by inviting to consider propositions, such as 'Six million Jews did not die in Nazi gas chambers' or 'American blacks have a lower IQ than American whites' (Modood 2005: 119). Modood reasons that each of these statements is regarded as false or highly misleading, and grossly disrespectful to a minority who have the right to be angry, 'because the statements belong to an ideology of domination and exploitation' (ibid). Modood (2005: 121) explains, that besides what he calls beliefs of primary identification (such as skin colour or sex) there are other beliefs which have historical and sociological significance for a group because they are involved in its oppression and hence, 'that piece of history, that piece of oppression, can become so central to the psyche, to the life and continuing vulnerability of that group, that it can become part of its mode of being' (ibid). The Holocaust to modern Jewry and of slavery to the African diaspora are such cases according to Modood and this is why the liberal state 'must uphold the truth of and commitment to certain beliefs and protect them, if not from critical inquiry that promises to be respectful, at least from gratuitous and blatantly offensive attack' (ibid). By extension, according to Modood's argument, Muslims must be protected by equivalent harm, such as the publication of the *Satanic Verses*, because the honour of the Prophet is 'as central to the Muslim psyche as the Holocaust and racial slavery to others' (ibid).

The premise of such reasoning, however, is questionable, not only because it compares situations that belong to different registers but also because it conflates beliefs with truth claims. The indignation or anger that such statements arouse not only to cultural groups but to the general public and the reason such statements lead to legal persecution in France or Germany, is not simply because they belong to an ideology of domination and exploitation, but because such statements either deny historical facts, in the case of Holocaust, or produce pseudo-scientific data

in the case of white and black IQs, i.e. *they falsify truth*. In the case of the Holocaust what is denied - and is punishable by law in countries like Germany or France which were among the central political stages for the unfolding of the tragedy of anti-Semitism which led to the gas chambers – are the collective memory and trauma of one of the most monstrous episodes of recent European history. In the case of American blacks, the falsification alludes to another atrocious phenomenon, namely slavery, and the ideology which sustained it, that is racism and its pervasive legacy in the social stratification of America until today. The persecution of the denial of truthfulness and factuality of such tragedies in France or Germany is based on the premise of denying or falsifying truth claims about the historical suffering of the relevant cultural or racial groups and not on the harm done on their beliefs about their collective identity. The fact that religious belief – or any other belief - may be constitutive of or central to a group's or a person's identity cannot bear the same weight as historical facts or claims about truth in decisions regarding what kind of protection specific groups, but also historical memory at large, are entitled to. This is not to repudiate *a priori* that religious beliefs, or perhaps other forms of beliefs, deserve protection and respect under specific circumstances, but that this protection cannot be grounded on grounds of truth and false claims since belief is not conditioned by the same relationship to reality as facts.

As noted above, comparisons are not politically or academically neutral and what is particularly problematical in the case of comparisons with the Holocaust or slavery is that such comparisons imply that the experience of reading the *Satanic Verses*, or *Brick Lane*, or looking at the Danish cartoons – all works that, it needs to be repeated do not belong to the realm of the factual but to that of the imagined, artistic or satirical – has a similar impact as the collective trauma of concentration camps or slavery and its deep-rooted legacy in the way social and racial hierarchies are sustained. Or that the stigmatisation of Muslims today has impacted in the same way that anti-Semitism had in the interwar years. Misused analogies as the ones analysed above collapse belief and fact, and in a sense they trivialise historical victimhood too. But they also contribute to a political culture of outrage and moral panic. Tyrer and Sayyid (2012: 355) are perhaps right to observe that there is a tendency to see the affirmation of Muslim subjectivities as a scandal, but what they fail to notice is the counter-tendency to turn scepticism or legitimate criticism against

the accommodation of claims related to the expression of Muslim subjectivity into an equivalent scandal.⁸⁰

The case of Danish cartoons is a telling example of the way Muslim political subjectivity has become a scandal both by Islamophobes who rhetorically exploited central values of Western liberalised and secularised societies, such as free speech and the separation of the public from the private sphere, or the separation of the State from Church, and by supporters of religious-friendly multiculturalism who had recourse to accusations of racism and of the oppressing tactics of secular modern state against marginalised religious groups. From both sides, publishing or banning the contentious work was framed as a scandal, either a scandal against free speech and unacceptable advances of Muslim religiosity in the core of European values, or a scandal of European racism and discrimination against oppressed and fragile minorities. If the case of *Satanic Verses* is a landmark of the rise of Muslim subjectivity, the Danish cartoons controversy is significant for comparing how much gravity identity politics has acquired in domestic and international political arenas, but also how much the idea that religions identities are in fact oppressed in modern secularised societies and that offence of religious identities constitutes discrimination and racism, took root in public and academic debates. Critics and sympathisers of Muslim identity politics converge in their observations about the transformation of the moral landscape of public sphere since the Rushdie controversy. Sympathisers, like Meer and Mouritsen (2009: 334) note when comparing the different take between Denmark and the UK press in the controversy that ‘the explanation for (...) differences rests not only on Britain’s more “multicultural” traditions, but also the experiences of the Rushdie affair and the subsequent debate that had already taken place in Britain’. On the other side of the fence, Malik (2009: 149) observes ‘there had been much equivocation by politicians and intellectuals over the Rushdie affair, but no one seriously doubted Rushdie’s right to publish the novel. There was little equivocation over the Danish cartoons, just widespread acceptance that it has been wrong to publish, and even more wrong to republish. Writers and artists, political leaders insisted, had a responsibility to desist from giving offence and upsetting religious sensibilities’. In this transformation of political reasoning which brought religion to the fore of the political arena, the politics of Muslim subjectivity – and not Islam as a religious dogma - has played perhaps the most

⁸⁰ For example, Talal Asad (2009b: 137), the founding father of the anthropology of the secular, described the Danish cartoons controversy as ‘the Danish cartoons scandal’.

central role. Islamophobes and Muslim identity politics sympathisers alike promoted from both sides the idea that religion is indeed a different kind of identity and, hence, religious subjectivity became the locus of otherness, either for the politics of exclusion supported by the xenophobic right, or for the politics of rights of recognition and accommodation advocated by multiculturalists.

The Danish cartoons controversy began when the right-wing Danish newspaper *Jyllands-Posten* published twelve editorial cartoons depicting the Prophet Muhammad in September 2005, among which the most controversial being the one which depicted Mohammad with a bomb in his turban and the Islamic creed written on the bomb. In a statement that provoked much discussion about its intentions the newspaper announced that the publication of the cartoons was aiming to contribute to the debate regarding self-imposed censorship in relation to the criticism of Islam. Perhaps the most ironic aspect of the case is that the creation of the cartoons was triggered by exactly the opposite reasons for which it was accused (i.e. a blasphemous attack to Muslim faith and to the Muslim Danish minority): in 2005 Kare Bluitgen, a writer of children's book, was writing a book on Islam hoping that it would contribute to its better understanding by a new generation of Danish citizens. However, it turned out to be almost impossible to find an illustrator out of fear of insulting religious sensibilities. The left-wing newspaper *Politiken* ran a story about the case (entitled 'Profound Anxiety about Criticism of Islam') to which the rival right-wing *Jyllands Posten* responded with the publication of the Prophet Mohammad cartoons (Malik 2009: 143). In a sense, the publication was both the result and the target of the ways religious subjectivities had shaped forms of political reasoning, despite the fact that it was exploiting this problematic for the benefit of conservative and largely xenophobic politics. The publication was followed by protests organised by Danish Muslim organisations. The cartoons were further republished in more than fifty countries, which exacerbated the controversy, further dissolving the political categories of Left and Right and their traditional stances within the European press.⁸¹ Four months later, Muslims organised protests across the Islamic world, some of which escalated

⁸¹ See for instance Miera and Sala Pala's (2009) discussion about the stance of left-wing and right-wing press in Germany and France during the Danish cartoons crisis.

into violence with a total of more than a hundred reported deaths and attacks against the Danish embassies, which turned the controversy into an international crisis.⁸²

The prevailing tendency during and at the aftermath of the events was to see the reactions against the cartoons as the immediate effect of the offence that Muslims felt as a result of the insult to the Prophet's honour. This explanation was convenient both for the proponents of politics Muslim subjectivity as it took the extent and intensity of reactions as a sign of the offence suffered by Muslims world-wide, and for the Islamophobes for whom it provided an excellent opportunity to illustrate the alleged Muslim rage against 'the West' and the danger it represents to Western societies. However, it seems that the political mobilisation was less motivated by the cartoons themselves, but by the lack of political dialogue and discussion in the immediate aftermath of the cartoons' publication (Müller and Özcan 2007: 290). As Lægaard (2007: 490) observes, 'if offence was reasonably taken, it was because of contextual factors, not just, and not primarily, offence to religious sensibilities caused by the cartoons as such'. Even more, it also seems that there were several motivations and meanings invested within the protests themselves; for instance, Larsson and Lindekilde (2009: 366) note that the second wave of Muslim mobilisation was fuelled by 'misrepresentation' felt by many Danish Muslims, who disapproved of the actions and arguments of the imams driving the initial protests: 'it was, thus, primarily a reaction to grievances imposed by other Danish Muslims, and not the Muhammad cartoons as such'.

Among multiculturalist scholars there is considerable consensus to read the Danish cartoons as an instance of racism or cultural racism, in line with the logic underpinning the discourse of Islamophobia, as explained above. For Levey and Modood (2009: 428) the controversy of the cartoons contains three problematic aspects: first, that representing the Prophet is a breach of a well-known Islamic injunction; second, that the cartoons suggest that Islam is violent and dangerous; and third, that this representation targets all Muslims as violent and dangerous, and hence it constitutes a form of racism. In the line of reasoning explained in the previous section, Levey and Modood (2009: 443) argue that 'once we break with the idea that (contemporary) racism is only about biology, then we should be able to see that cultural and religious groups also can be racialized' and that the stereotypical targeting of Muslims in cartoons qualifies as a part of

⁸² For a different reading of the internationalization of the crisis, see Olesen (2007) who analyses the crisis in terms of the porous public and transnational public sphere, in particular about the role of transnational satellite television channels, such as Al-Jazeera and Al-Arabiya in the diffusion of the conflict.

it (see also Lindekilde et al., 2009: 303). The reading of cartoons as racist is a particularly interesting aspect of the case not only because, as noted above the direct identification of Islamophobia with racism, or cultural racism tends to compromise dialogue as to what kind of allowances are (or should be) given to religious sensibilities in today's liberalised and secularised societies, but also because it is very difficult to conclude on the racism of the cartoons precisely because of the nature of object of controversy, i.e. humoristic cartoons. As Weaver (2010: 675) explains, the reading of the cartoons as Islamophobic and racist is only one, *amongst others*, since they could be also seen as a criticism of Islamic fundamentalism, as blasphemous images and as satire and a defence of freedom of speech. Weaver (2010: 678) points out that 'certain cultural signs can contain the ability to produce simultaneous and ambiguous racist and non-racist readings' and that 'the structural ambiguity of satire complicates a comparison with hate speech' (2010: 682). Humour, he explains, differs from serious communication and hence 'it is difficult to convincingly argue that it could be censored on the grounds of it being intended to generate specific serious reactions' (ibid). Weaver (2010: 683) notes that the idea of reading the cartoons as racist emerges in the academia and that racism does not appear to be the issue at the outset of the Muslim complaints. That, of course, does not exclude the possibility of the cartoons being motivated and generating anti-Muslim racism but it does highlight the 'ambiguous form' of the cartoons (2010: 689) and suggests that 'there is no one true or correct reading of them' (ibid).

The claim that the Danish cartoons are unambiguously racist may be unsustainable in close inspection, it is, however, politically powerful. It is also linked to the idea of oppression, to the argument which reasons that because Muslims identity is oppressed, it is somehow morally and politically legitimised to take offence when aspects of the Islamic faith are criticised or satirised, or treated with a lack of respect. However, there is little clarification whether Muslim subjectivity is oppressed as a religious identity *per se* or because is it entangled in a web of other types of exclusions, as we shall see below, and little discussion about how exactly a given publication is connected to the assumed oppression in a way which makes the publication morally problematic, and whether this constitutes enough of a reason for restrictions on freedom of expression. Racism (or cultural racism) becomes the larger sematic field that associates oppression to offence and to the claim that Muslim subjectivity *qua religious* and not linked to other social identities and inequalities, is oppressed and discriminated and must be protected as such. Ziauddin Sardar, for example, squarely located the cartoons as an issue of oppression: 'This is not an issue of freedom of

expression; it is very much an issue of power. In Britain, Muslims are in a good position and are capable of representing themselves, but in Europe they are marginalised and do not have the means to reply. If you use your freedom of expression to denigrate and abuse, knowing they have no way of responding, then it is an act of oppression' (quoted in Meer and Mouritsen 2009: 346).

This line of reasoning – the line of oppressed, offended and injured religious identities – has also been followed in the case of another controversy, of lesser magnitude but similar substance, i.e. the publication and filming of Monica Ali's novel *Brick Lane*. The novel, named after Brick Lane, a street at the heart of London's Bangladeshi community, follows the life of a Bangladeshi woman who moves to Tower Hamlets in London at the age of eighteen to marry an older man and portrays the dilemmas faced by women in a patriarchal culture. The novel attracted criticism because it was perceived as negative portrayal of Bangladeshi community in Britain and small-scale protests were organised. In commenting on those protests and their meaning, Ahmed (2010: 25) argues that 'in a context of racial and religious inequality, where access to the public sphere is unevenly distributed, the protests are better understood as symptomatic of a subordinate social position'. She invites to a 'materialist reading of the protest as symptomatic of social inequalities' (2010: 37), not with the aim 'to eclipse faith within class or to dismiss the significance of the sacred but rather to point to the impossibility of extricating religion from structures of class and race' (2010: 27). Ahmed convincingly argues that the public sphere is not religiously blind but shaped by hierarchies of religion - as well as race, class, gender and sexuality – and that religion, like race, contributes to the definition of one's social position (2010: 25). Indeed this is a sociologically interesting take as it situates religious identity within the context of contemporary social inequalities.

In this materialist perspective, Ahmed reads the protest 'as a struggle for self-representation and against the structures of inequality which obstruct its protagonists' path to these rights' (2010: 28) and criticises Ali because she fails, in her view, to situate the community, including its patriarchal practices, within its wider social and historical context (2010: 38). For Ahmed, Ali's novel does not acknowledge 'the history and the vulnerabilities' of the offended and that offence and the protest that can ensue is to a degree symptomatic of social disenfranchisement, or in different terms, that 'the unevenness of the discursive arena which grants some voices more "freedom" to speak than others and means that some people are more likely to take offence than others' (ibid).

However, these conclusions are difficult to be sustained from the materialist perspective. Like in the case of Modood whose work Ahmed follows and the logic of oppression of a ‘non-European religious and cultural minorit[y] in the context of a secular hegemony’ (Ahmed 2010: 28), if religious identities are recognised as entangled with inequalities of class and gender, and if oppression is part and parcel of such formation of power, then perhaps religion is not the main reason for exclusion or the main motivation for protest. If the protest is one of ‘predominantly working-class South Asian Muslims’ (Ahmed 2010: 28), then from a materialist point of view, religion is a proxy for the oppression of other more socially significant exclusions, and most notably, class.⁸³ But then the argument about the special nature of Muslim subjectivity and the particular oppression it suffers as a result of the ‘secular hegemony’ which cannot be either captured or subsumed to other categories such as race or class – examined in detail in the previous chapter – evaporates. From a multiculturalist point of view, these conclusions are also problematic as they recognise, first, that the structure of the Muslim community is indeed patriarchal, which is something that Islamic and religious-friendly feminists have gone to great lengths to defy. And second, that this patriarchal structure is the result of wider historical and social conditions, which means that these conditions of exclusion can be altered, with economic and social integration for instance, and which subsequently entails that religion would have to take the back-seat in terms of social identification to allow primacy for other forms of identity in order to change the conditions of exclusion.

What is also particularly problematical in these accounts is the way offence is transformed, from a reasonable explanation to an almost expected and naturalised expression of oppressed identities, to a moral justification and to a legal argument. As Malik (2009: 189) observes, in certain cases, the idea of the giving of offence becomes indistinguishable from the creation of hatred and the same goes with the fomenting of hatred from the inciting to violence. Ali Mazrui’s take on the *Satanic Verses* controversy is characteristic of such slippages: in the aftermath of the Rushdie affair he had stated that ‘a book can be a lethal weapon’ and had argued that ‘a pen writing three provocative paragraphs in London could let loose a flood of dangerous consequences a world away’, and asked provocingly ‘when is a writer guilty of manslaughter?’ and whether this could ‘conceivably be at the moment of writing itself?’ (ibid). Such reasoning, however, which moral

⁸³ Or to put in Halliday’s (1999: 899) terms in his critical examination of the concept of Islamophobia, ‘much of what is presented as the Islamic critique of the West has little or nothing to do with religion. (...) It has little to do with belief, and a lot to do with political power in the contemporary world’.

sentiments are given primacy over political arguments transforms the idea of hate speech to ‘a means of rebranding obnoxious political arguments as immoral ones’, as Malik notes, and forecloses political debate by having recourse of criminal sanctions (ibid).

The normative question then that arises in situations where offence on religious sensitivities is discussed in relation to legal restrictions, like the publication or banning irreverent works, is whether Muslims are required to tolerate the offence caused by the publication of such works and as such it must be assessed within the dialectic of toleration. Framing the question as an issue of toleration is especially relevant here as reparations to the offence are sought within the liberal legal framework and not, for example, on the level of civic responsibilities and political wisdom.⁸⁴ Within the perspective of toleration Lægaard (2007: 487-488) argues that offence to religious sensitivities does not provide a *prima facie* moral reason against expressions having this effect, because this is not a strong enough reason to justify legal restrictions on freedom of expression in such cases. Even if morally relevant, the kind of harm involved is not significant enough to ground restrictions on freedom of expression. This is because the strength of feeling cannot plausibly determine the moral assessment of utterances. An alternative, Lægaard continues, would be to see offence to religious sensitivities as a different kind of offence – which is the case argued by the sympathisers of Muslim identity politics – but in this case, in order to establish a distinction, one needs to go beyond the mere feeling of offence to the idea that the taking of offence is closely connected to ‘the holding of beliefs about wrongfulness’. However, from the point of view of toleration this presents problems too, since limiting freedom of expression with specific reference to religious sensitivities does not take into account that people have different and conflicting religious beliefs and hence views about wrongfulness. Therefore, to introduce limits on freedom of expression in order to avoid offence to religious sensitivities would be a radical departure from toleration – a principle conceived with the purpose of accommodating the variation in religious beliefs and where ‘the difference and the resulting disapproval are circumstances of toleration, not something to be removed’. But then would that not entail that religious norms are imposed on those who do not share them? In that sense, reasoning politically

⁸⁴ See for instance, Ramadan’s take on the issue which avoids argumentation on the basis of oppression, offence and injury and prioritises the idea of civic rather than legal limitations: ‘There are no legal limits to free speech, but there are civic limits. (...) It is a matter of civic responsibility and wisdom, not a question of legality or rights. In that context, I think it was unwise to publish these cartoons’ (Ramadan 2006: 17).

with offence as a compass is almost unsustainable inside the framework of liberalism within which the claims about offence and its reparation are made.

The other main avenue that reactions following the publication of controversial works have been discussed revolves around the idea of injury suffered by religious sensibilities. The argument about injury is naturally germane to the ones of oppression and offence, and used interchangeably in the relevant debates. However, even if loosely used, it is significantly different on the conceptual level: if the oppression and offence felt by religious minorities are argued on the basis of the existing political and legal culture, the issue of injury is debated on an extra-liberal and extra-secular level altogether, and in that sense it constitutes a more radical argument. In her reading of the Danish cartoons controversy, Mahmood (2009: 66) attempts to break with the prevailing idea that the case represents an impasse between the liberal value of freedom of speech and a religious taboo and with their associated logics i.e. that to accommodate religion would be to compromise free speech on the one hand, and that an accommodation of both is necessary for the preservation of a multicultural and multireligious Europe, on the other hand. Both logics, Mahmood argues, fail 'to understand the sense of injury expressed by so many Muslims' (2009: 68). What Mahmood (2009: 70) finds striking in the way Muslim mobilisation against the cartoons was explained, is that it was 'so easily assimilated to the language of identity politics, religious fanaticism, and cultural/civilizational difference' and how 'little attention has been paid to how one might reflect on the kind of offence the cartoons caused and what ethical, communicative, and political practices are necessary to make this kind of injury intelligible'. To make this injury legible then Mahmood (2009: 78) suggests that

the offence of the cartoons committed was not against a moral interdiction ("Thou shall not make images of Muhammad") but against a structure of affect, a habitus, that feels wounded. This wound requires moral actions, but its language is neither juridical nor that of street protests, because it does not belong to an economy of blame, accountability, and reparations. The action that it requires is internal to the structure of affect, relations, and virtues that predispose one to experience an act as a violation in the first place.

This is indeed an interesting shift of focus, as it defies what many Muslims and non-Muslim commentators have taken as the crux of the matter, i.e. the fact that a religious prohibition has

been transgressed. But most importantly, it also defies those who see the offence felt by Muslims and the protests which ensued as a result of oppression. In that sense, reading the protests through the prism of injury takes away the political edge – by and large expressed as a debate for and against legal changes that would require the alteration of the shape of public sphere – off the picture, since for Mahmood (2009: 89) the future of the Muslim minority in Europe depends not so much ‘on how secular-liberal protocols might be expanded to accommodate its concerns’ but it depends on ‘a larger transformation on the cultural and ethical sensibilities of the Judeo-Christian population that undergird the cultural practices of secular-liberal law’.⁸⁵ Hence, the battle for Muslim subjectivity is not to be given within the liberal, or even larger political framework, but it becomes entirely a question of the ethical realm, of esoteric transformation, which requires the restructuring of the secular collective consciousness of modern societies.

Obviously an approach which looks at changes regulating the public sphere – the essence of the politics of Muslim assertiveness as we have seen in the previous chapter – with skepticism, if not rejection, is politically paralysing. Yet, conceptually, it is a natural consequence of the idea that there is something special about religious subjectivity, and even more about Muslim subjectivity, which cannot be accommodated or even understood within the ‘secular hegemony’. However, is this claim sustainable, is Muslim subjectivity so irreducibly different and therefore so elusive to secular understandings shaped as they are by the Judeo-Christian legacy? Mahmood makes the argument for the distinct texture of the injury Muslims feel on the basis of the tradition of Muslim piety, in which a Muslim’s relationship to the Prophet is predicated not so much upon a communicative or representational model as on an assimilative one (Mahmood 2009: 76); or in different words following Mahmood’s argument analysed in chapter two, based on an understanding and experience of faith that is embodied rather than intellectualised. From within the perspective of ethics this emphasis on injury and on a structure of affect that feels wounded makes sense and may indeed be read as an extra-secular and peculiarly Islamic. From a sociological perspective though, these conclusions are questionable: Roy (2002: 131), for instance, observes that, what he famously called ‘religiosity’, i.e. the visible, experiential and expressive

⁸⁵ Butler (2009: 123), Mahmood’s interlocutor in a volume discussing the concept of blasphemy, injury and free speech, is highly critical of Mahmood’s legal scepticism, both because ‘this turn to the cultural and ethical domain is conditioned by an argument that the law is so pervasively secular that any effort to seek redress for injury through the law would strengthen the very instrument through which secularism asserts its hegemony and define as the proper domain of religion’, but also because law cannot be understood as radically different from questions of sensibility since it functioned in different historical occasions to change sensibilities.

form of faith – ‘embodied’ in the poststructuralist lexicon – is a common characteristic of all religious revival movements of the twentieth century which are distinguished by an ‘anti-intellectualism that favours a more emotional religiosity’ where ‘feelings are more important than knowledge’. Not only that, but he also notes that revivalist religious movements, Christian as well as Muslim, are no longer fighting along political lines, but in order to defend moral standards and values, and that ‘this is why abortion, gay marriage and creationism are the new battlefields, not secularism in itself; these religious movements are no longer interested in politics as such. And it is precisely this front line, based on values, that devout Muslims (...) are joining. Paradoxically, the visibility of Islam is aligning it with other religions’ (Roy 2011: 94). If this is the case, then the emphasis on injury of Muslim sensibilities says something about the culture of today, about the ‘secular condition we all inhabit’ (Asad 2009: 21) and its *contemporary* shift to emotions,; it suggests something that needs to be understood within the context of modernity and secularity, rather than as a structure of affect or as a cluster of moral sensibilities that are suppressed and excluded by the modern, secular governmentality.

6.4 Culturalism and its discontents

As mentioned in the introduction the logic which drives the way claims about Muslim subjectivity are made and debated within the public space emanates from the ideology of culturalism. Culturalism is the idea that individuals are determined by their culture, a culture that is mainly inherited and not made, mostly self-sufficient and absolutely vital in the realization of the Self. As a consequence cultures appear to have a claim to special rights and protections - even if at the same time they have a questionable or even inimical stance to individual rights, or equality of sexes. Culturalism has been the ideological vehicle for the expression of claims for the recognition of suppressed cultural minorities and most notably of the politics of Muslim subjectivity. However, culturalism - and especially its variant which religion becomes the determinant of culture – is a double-edged strategy, one which cannot only be used to culturally define and promote the accommodation of oppressed cultural-religious groups, but also one which can be used for exactly the opposite purpose, to culturally define, on that same basis, and then exclude these groups.

One of the most characteristic examples of the way culturalism works in the reversed way, i.e. to exclude rather than include, is the ideology which sees Islam as a cultural and civilisational threat as encapsulated by the political neologism of 'Eurabia'. The term, which was first coined as a name for a newsletter of the Euro-Arab friendship committee in the 1970s, was revived by the British-Swiss historian Bat Ye'or in her book *Eurabia: The Euro-Arab Axis* (2005) to describe what she identified as a secret project between European politicians and the Arab world for the 'Islamicisation' of Europe. As Carr (2006: 1) notes, what began as an fringe conspiracy theory 'has become a dangerous Islamophobic fantasy that has moved ever closer towards mainstream respectability, as conservative historians and newspaper columnists, right-wing Zionists and European neofascists find common cause in the threat to "Judeo-Christian" civilisation from Muslim immigrants with supposedly incompatible cultural values'. The premise to such theories is that Europe is a doomed continent – often with its own consent – which is 'on the brink of cultural extinction' because of a coordinated attempt of Islamicisation or Arabisation (ibid). Central to such views, is a particular version of Islam, which 'blurs or ignores the distinctions between Islam and Islamism, between violent and non-violent forms of Islamism, between Muslim as an ethnic category and Muslim as a statement of faith, between immigrant, terrorist and refugee' (Carr 2006: 14).

The view which legitimised the scheme of separate, fundamental incompatible civilisations and popularised the idea of imminent threat had already taken root since the end of 1990s, most notably in Huntington's *Clash of Civilizations and the Remaking of the World Order* (2002 [1997]), as well as in an antecedent article by Lewis entitled 'The Roots of Muslim Rage' (1990), where the catchphrase 'Clash of Civilizations' figures as a subheading. However, what is interesting here is that neo-conservatives, neo-Orientalist or Islamophobic scholars are not the only ones who resort to the idea of describing civilizations as separate, opposing entities and who promote a time-less, place-less and a-historical logic. The idea that Islamophobia is a newer version or a continuation of Orientalism, as a project of European domination, is common place among critical scholars in the field. Gingrich (2005: 514), for instance, argues that one does not have to embrace each and every aspect of Said's *Orientalism* to understand that, as a variant of Orientalism, Islamophobia is a product of the colonial era. Afshar (2008: 411, 413) claimed that a modern day form of Orientalism remains at the core of the current history of race and gender in the West and current wars in the Middle East. Levey and Modood (2009: 441) suggest that the

way Muslims are perceived today 'is both connected to how they have been perceived and treated by European empires and their racial hierarchies, as well as by Christian Islamophobia and the Crusades in earlier centuries'. Kumar (2012) argues that Islamophobic myths did not arise spontaneously after the end of the Cold War but are rooted in centuries of conquest and colonialism, from the Crusades to the War on Terror.

There are several problems in explanations that attempt to argue for a linear development of 'Western' animosity against Islam: as Halliday (1999: 895) comments, 'it is tempting, but misleading, to link contemporary hostility to Muslims to the long history of conflict between "Islam" and the West' and he adds that the past provides a reserve of reference and symbol for the present, it does not explain it. But what is perhaps the most problematical aspect is the tendency to explain developments in domestic and international politics in terms of civilizations, and their 'perennial' essence from which aversion and 'clash' is perhaps unavoidable: in the same way it is not politics that produces Islam in history but 'Islam' which produces politics – as Said's *Orientalism* has shown - it is not politics that produce the American and European interventions in Muslim-majority countries, or the socio-economic structural inequalities that produce the exclusion of Muslims immigrants, but the 'Western' time immemorial hate of Islam. Such culturalization – and almost inevitably de-historicization – of the explanatory frameworks of contemporary phenomena comes inevitably with a political price. Whether Islamophobia is an entirely new phenomenon, a version of Orientalism or the old Christian enmity against Islam cloaked in the new attires of secularism, the most important ramification of this turn to culturalism is the emergence of new ways of demarcating the Other in a negative light. The new differentialist categories moved from questions of 'race' to questions of culture: 'mainstream political discourse began to substitute cultural and other markers of difference in place of historically established biological - pseudo or otherwise - or physical markers' (Allen 2011: 291) and during this process a generalised suspicion of Muslims as holders of an alien culture threatening the European values prevails (Fekete 2006: 2).

In this context, culture acquires 'a putative explanatory power in addressing (global) socio-political antagonisms because it accommodates the evasion of the politics of the emergence of the Muslim Other' (Semati 2010: 257). What is crucial to this process, as Semati (2010: 266-267) argues, is a 'culturalist' or 'differentialist' racism in which the Other/self dichotomy is not

explained in an inferior/superior framework but instead the 'Other' is believed to be 'different' and this 'difference' is systematically presented as insurmountable. This emphasis on difference enables the popularization of a cultural-ideological view which seeks to explain the ills of the social order by attributing them to Islam by conflating histories, politics, societies and cultures of the Middle East into a single unified and negative conception of Islam (ibid). But most importantly, it is a way of conceptualising politics that explains political acts not in terms of geopolitical calculations, motives, and actors, but in terms of religion (ibid). This is an interesting point as it shows how culturalism and the stress on difference have permeated political reasoning on all levels. If the revival and autonomization of culture-as-religion as an explanatory framework produced sinister results in international politics, giving birth to the narrative of 'civilizational clash' and 'civilizational mission' to mask the cynical violence of military interventions in the Muslim-majority countries, it produced equally sinister results in domestic politics. The 're-codifying of immigrants as Muslims in the West' (Zemni 2011; Roy 2011; Miera and Sala Pala 2009; Allievi 2006) – where the discourse of difference and Muslim identity politics emerged – is perhaps the most ironic backfiring of the ideology of culturalism. In this re-codification of immigration socio-economic problems are reframed as cultural problems, whereas 'political problems are diluted in a culturalist explanation that targets Muslims' unsuitable cultural and religious background as the reason for economic exclusion and marginalisation' (Zemni 2011: 29). Yilmaz (2012: 369) argues that in the new discourse of culture, 'the ontology of the social has become culturalized', since culture has become central in questions of belonging and alterity. This cultural paradigm, within which 'social identities can be understood as interpellated by culture' (2012: 373), naturalises social distinctions and explains social problems by reference to the incommensurable nature of different cultures, but also it creates the conditions for far-right politics to bring immigration to the centre of political discourse by establishing Muslims an incompatible ontological category predicated on culture (2012: 368).

The appropriation of cultural schemes of explanation by the far-right is a common line in xenophobic and ultra-conservative thought, as we have seen in the previous chapter in the discussion of the conceptual lineage of the concept of difference (Sternhell 2010). However, the recent upsurge of culture and/or civilization in the discourse of far-right is not only a matter of conceptual affiliation. It is also the effect of perhaps the most significant political development of post-1989 times, i.e. the repositioning of Left and Right within the political spectrum. In the mid-

1990s Gitlin (1995: 84) had commented on the phenomenon as a reversal of positions between Left and Right by pointing out that ‘Throughout the nineteenth and twentieth centuries, the Left believed in a common human condition, the Right in fundamental differences among classes, nations and races. The Left wanted collective acts of renewal, the Right endorsed primordial ties of tradition and community against all disruptions. Today it is the Right that speaks a language of commonalities. Its rhetoric of global markets and global freedoms has something of the old universalist ring’. However, this initial reversal looks more like a convergence today. The eminence of the ideology of culturalism has changed the political fronts in a way that the Left and the Right share essentially the same political logic, i.e. the defence of particularism with the Left claiming respect for minority cultures - and often tolerating controversial and sometimes downright unacceptable practices in the name of the struggle against cultural imperialism - and the Right realigning around the defence of national identity. Eriksen and Stjernfelt (2010) observe that both these stances are the effects of culturalism and of its ideology of protection of these identities under various guises, ethnic for the Left, national for the Right: ‘Leftwing culturalists claim that various distinct cultures should be able to co-exist on the same territory or in the same state, where, formally or informally, different jurisdictions for individuals are applied, according to the cultural group into which they were born. Rightwing culturalists maintain the same attitude towards preserving cultural identity, but each culture in its own territory, each culture in its own country’. The premise is essentially the same ‘each select their chosen people – and not all people can be equally chosen’ (ibid). This is why Eriksen and Stjernfelt argue that the culturalism of the Left and the Right do not constitute the main antithesis in modern politics but the two sides of the same coin, which shows ‘how little the Left actually knows about its political opponents in the battle that has developed over the last few decades, during which the question of culture has appeared on the agenda and gradually replaced prior debate on divergent political utopias’ (ibid).

It is exactly this ideology that has paralysed the Left from articulating credible and effective alternatives to the symbolic slippage from immigration to Islam and opened the way for the far-right discourse to become hegemonic. As Yilmaz argues (2012: 369, 372, 373) this hegemony is enabled by the fact that both far-right positions and those who argue against it share *the same* epistemology of the social. By this Yilmaz means that the new antagonistic identity categories – the ‘people’ or ‘nation’ which excludes the ‘cosmopolitan elites’ who are supposed to have

destroyed the nation through lax immigration policies toward Muslim immigrants - became the common sense of the social structure. Naturally, in such accounts, social divisions such as class, gender, sexual orientation and so forth, are omitted from the construction of the 'people'. What this shared epistemology of the social means is that a new continuum is invented in which the 'us' against 'them' is reconfigured around a line of cultural threat against 'our' achievements. Such discourse gives the false impression of homogeneity across the political spectrum and reconfigures the traditional political and social hegemonic struggles in Europe: 'what used to be the traditional divide between capital and labor that once formed the contours of left and right in Europe is now a cultural divide between national citizens on the one side and cosmopolitan cultural elite and Muslim immigrants on the other' (2012: 373-374). This culturalization of political discourse leaves the Left essentially ideologically disarmed as its progressive foundation of anti-capitalist, anti-imperialist, anti-sexist and anti-homophobic arguments has been detached from its historical relationship to left-wing politics and subsequently appropriated by the populist right to re-define national identity and demarcate the new scapegoats.

Indeed, the collapse of the Left-Right political divide and the culturalisation of politics have created one of the most striking paradoxes of our times: the entanglement of sexual politics with anti-Muslim discourse. The debate has been particularly relevant in the Netherlands, with the case of Pim Fortuyn as a prime example of the naissance of a discourse which brings together the politics of sexual liberation and public homosexuality with blatantly Islamophobic and xenophobic views.⁸⁶ What is implicated in the articulation of such discourses is the use of sexual liberation to represent Europe as the cradle of freedom and modernity and as the 'natural opposite' to Muslim's alleged backwardness and homophobia. However, 'this instrumentalization of gay rights', as Mepschen et al. observe (2010: 965) 'puts progressives, anti-racists, feminists, and lesbian and gay activists in an impossible position: taking up the defence of lesbian and gay rights and public gayness comes to be associated with Islamophobia, while solidarity with Muslims against Islamophobia is represented, especially by the populist right, as trivialising or even supporting "Muslim" homophobia'. The phenomenon is not unknown in Britain where the English Defence League, an Islamophobic socio-political formation with a lesbian, gay, bisexual and transsexual (LGBT) division, which has adopted a similar paradoxical, yet highly effective,

⁸⁶ This attitude forms part of the broader phenomenon of 'homonormativity' (Duggan 2002), i.e. the articulation of lesbian and gay identities that do not any more subvert but reproduce heteronormative assumptions and structures.

attitude of integrating elements of contemporary multiculturalist discourse about diversity in relation to sexual identity with an aggressive Islamophobic rhetoric (Allen 2011). As anti-Islamic far-right rises across Europe (Walker and Taylor 2011), depicting Muslims as the ultimate threat to sexual freedoms, especially by those who traditionally have opposed them, is a growing tendency which has spread from the fringes of the political spectrum to the centre of political campaigns and State policies. Under these circumstances, Butler suggests (2009: 130), sexual progressives must make the State their object of critique even if it appears to support sexual freedom, because freedom in this case becomes instrumental to the reproduction to national identity through restrictive and coercive immigration politics. As she convincingly argues, 'it is one thing for the state to value freedom of expression and to protect expression, but it is quite another to be the agent who decides whose freedom of expression will be protected and whose will not' (ibid).

Butler's call to question the instrumentalisation of hard-won social rights by the politics of exclusion is an extremely important one, in an era, where Left and Right seem to converge over what they used to fight for, i.e. over questions of gender, sexual and other types of social equality. Refusing to sacrifice one minority for another is indeed extremely important in order to counter discourses that play minorities against each other for the benefit of populist and xenophobic political ends. But there seems to be another equally important point that has been elided by those debates which focus on the culturalisation of politics. The fact that the culturalisation of political discourse is inextricably tied with the rise of culturalism in social and human sciences and the general shift to the analytical category of difference through which further slippage to culture, ethnicity and religion occurs. If monolithic conceptions of culture and religion are prevailing, especially in the case of Islam, it is because Islamophobes and their critiques alike, as this chapter has shown, share a common recourse to Islam – or the 'Muslim community' – which has become again, after decades of materialist, sociological explanations of social divisions, inequalities and international politics, a holistic, a-historical and in the end a-political category, the one that Said's *Orientalism* had sought to question and deconstruct. Through this re-turn to culture, which cuts across disciplines, fields and modes of engagement, analysis falls back to the kind of essentialism which reasons that from Islam comes everything and to Islam goes everything. It is the detachment of identity politics and social movements from their egalitarian, universalist philosophical underpinning, the general disregard of the narrative of the Capital and

the profound representational crisis of working class interests in the political system - as noted from Marxist and neo-Marxist critics in numerous occasions - that slowly culturalised political discourse. The well-intentioned pragmatism of multiculturalists and liberals of various convictions, i.e. that the 'Muslim problem' - must be resolved because of the sheer number of Muslim immigrants in the West, shares the problematical assumption that we are dealing indeed with a problem of 'cultures', i.e. 'the oppressed Muslim culture against the oppressing secularist culture', which is, in the last instance, the mirror image of 'the threatening Islam against the weakened Western civilisation'. The point is not that Europe or the West are now more culturally diverse, because of immigration or because of globalization, but that culture has become a primary way of describing social and political divisions. 'The alternative to the clash of civilizations' as Halliday (1999: 901) had suggested, and to xenophobia by the same token, 'need not be the mutual indulgence of communities'. Indeed, does culturalism need to be our preferred way of approaching the Other, does religious, ethnic or cultural isolationism need to be our best answer to the hegemony of the West? As this chapter and the thesis as a whole has argued, far from it. On the contrary, a better alternative could be a step towards re-establishing the link between equality and its universalist underpinning on the political and the conceptual level and the re-imagination of commonalities not as the property of the 'West', but as globally constituted and shared, as it is proposed in the conclusion.

Conclusion

Conclusion: Towards a New Universalism?

Where does the deconstruction of poststructuralist and postsecular analytics of the Other leave critical social theory? Pursuing three areas of investigation, i.e. feminism, postcolonialism and multiculturalism as vehicles to explore respectively, the conceptualisation of Muslim subjectivity, the philosophy of history and epistemology of social science undergirding such view of subjectivity, and its effects on political and public culture, the thesis arrived in three main conclusions.

First, via a consideration of recent postmodern feminist literature engaging with the question of Muslim subjectivity, chapters one and two showed that the conceptualisation of the subject as detached from its humanist underpinning - and most notably from autonomy, which is recoded as a 'European', parochial desire - leads culturally-specific and postsecular feminisms to logical and political impasses. We have seen that once the link between oppositional consciousness and agency breaks down, what emerges is not a new 'positive' political subject but the reduction of subjectivity to the eternally reiterated, unreflective, embodied experience of one's culture. The reconceptualisation of agency from the profoundly sceptical angle of ethical embodiment, makes feminist theory, and for that matter political subjectivity altogether, redundant: the poststructuralist critique of Western feminism as the site of authentic feminist agency and the concern about culturally specific idioms of subjectivity is taken to the denial of autonomy as a cross-cultural desire and ethical experiences and norms are thought as essentially non-translatable. This way, however, any possibility of change - and utterly cross-cultural communication and understanding - is undermined, as we all seem trapped into our incommensurable subjectivities. What follows from this logic is not only that cultures shape subjects differently but that there are predetermined subjectivities specific to particular cultures, which is an essentialist, but also deeply conservative, understanding of the subject and ultimately of history itself.

Second, through a focus on postcolonial analytics chapters three and four investigated the philosophy of history underpinning this particular conceptualisation of the Muslim subject and inquired after the epistemology of social science presupposed by such theoretical moves. As we have seen the effort to converge religion and social theory has been proven a compelling

conundrum for the practice of social sciences or humanities. If religious experience is the locus of the irreducibly subjective, as it has been explained in the thesis, if it is by nature ever elusive to secular epistemologies, then human or social sciences have indeed nothing to say about this particular experience and the kind of subjectivities it enables. This observation could be seen in two ways: either it makes sociological analysis redundant by positioning its object of inquiry out of its analytical reach, or it re-asserts the need for a sheer separation between faith and reason, as two different registers of the richness of being human and in that sense, critical social theory needs secularism no less than it has always been the case. Even more, the examination showed that conceding to postsecularism *qua* cultural relativism as a way of considering the non-Western Other has unwelcome implications for the practice of critical social theory. The way cultural relativism operates philosophically – on the basis of insularity, and as a consequence, of exclusion rather than inclusion of the Other – cannot but leave outside its scope questions of ethics, responsibility, reflexivity, and *ultimately critique*. This is because deep-seated in the view that considers the Other as understood primarily in his/her (assumed) own terms, only from ‘within his/her own tradition’, there is a logic of radical singularity. The kind of scepticism that emanates from the strands of postsecular thinking examined by the thesis undermines the ability of social science to produce any substantive understanding of the Other without committing an act of violence and it reduces all efforts to narrate the Other in terms of a shared language into an act of cultural or epistemic imperialism. The language of singularity that cultural relativism speaks is in the last instance the language of isolationism and exclusion. It has also been established that politically, the discourse of cultural singularity cannot have any intrinsically subversive implications: in an important sense the cultural relativist stance undermines any possibility to critically deconstruct power relations and disrupt the hegemonies they sustain, since it re-introduces forms of arbitrary (traditional, religious) authority in the name of struggle against domination. The important degree of *autonomy* in respect to tradition or religion and the relations of domination and subordination they enable brought about by the anthropocentrism of modern, humanist, secular epistemology is rejected by the postsecular philosophies examined by the thesis. It has been demonstrated that the anti-foundationalism endorsed by the politics of Muslim subjectivity is often led back to the strongest version of essentialism: i.e. the one that re-affirms stereotypes like the West as change and the Rest as stasis, Europe as modernity and Islam as tradition, the Westerner as secular and the ‘Other’ as religious and so on, and eventually shares the profoundly conservative view that cultural interaction is a form of degeneration.

Third, by way of focusing on the theory of multiculturalism and the forms of public reasoning and political sensibilities it makes possible, chapters five and six attempted to shed light to the effects of such understanding of Muslim subjectivity has had on the political culture in our days. It has been shown that the prevailing culturalism in the ways 'difference', and in particular 'religious difference', are debated is not conducive to a political culture where the tensions that arise naturally in the public sphere can be productively appreciated and resolved. On the contrary, by speaking the language of victimhood and moral outrage, these tensions turn into clashes and anti-hegemonic politics inevitably fall back into reproducing a mirror-image of the logic of exclusion which animates the discourses that they seek to counter in the first place. It has been established that culturalism, and especially its variant in which religion becomes the determinant of culture, cannot only be used to define and promote the recognition of oppressed cultural-religious groups, but it can also be used for exactly the opposite purpose, i.e. to promote new differentialist categories constructed around the idea of culture and, hence, new ways of excluding the Other in the name of culture. As it has been demonstrated, the re-codifying of immigrants as Muslims in the West - where the discourse of difference and Muslim identity politics emerged - is perhaps the most ironic backfiring of the ideology of culturalism.

As such, the general contribution of the thesis was to demonstrate - using as its vehicle the analysis of Muslim subjectivity - that the direction critical social theory has taken after the poststructuralist/postmodern turn has not been conducive to the emergence of ideas and politics that have the potential to subvert the current relations of domination or to re-organise knowledge in new, non-hegemonic ways. Imagining the Muslim subject as heteronomous and as irreducibly different, conceptualising history as a process of self-containment and stasis rather than transformation and progress, leads critical social theory and the anti-hegemonic politics to paradoxical conclusions. What the thesis aspired to make tangible is that the prioritisation of postsecular and posthistoricist epistemologies is not necessarily the cornerstone of pluralism and openness but it can also be the closure of possibilities of explanation, deconstruction and, hence, subversion. The analysis of Muslim subjectivity and the way it is debated and reclaimed within the three areas of investigation showed that despite their anti-Orientalist, anti-essentialist aspirations, such epistemologies often operate by following the same logic of exclusion located within essentialist and Orientalist frameworks. Even more, the thesis showed that the logic of

difference cannot but fall back into the same ‘modernist’, ‘anthropocentric’, ‘humanistic’ or ‘progressive’ assumptions if it wants to avoid unwelcome political implications. Indeed the way the politics of Muslim subjectivity are analysed within the strands of critical social theory engaged by the thesis, offer a serious challenge to established ideas about what constitutes knowledge, what the aims of social research are, as well as the normative political assumptions about how the world should be. If ideas and values, such as equality, progress, moral and political autonomy or emancipation are not thought as having universal validity, as the postsecular and posthistoricist analytics examined by the thesis argue, then we are left with two possibilities. Either critical social theory identifies itself with the ‘post’ epistemologies and politics and sees political values as relative and dependant on context and therefore perceives the universality of such ideas as simply imperialist tools that sustain the hegemony of the West over the Rest. But this, as we have seen comes often with the price of puzzling political ramifications and of the paralysis of social science itself. Or, and this is the stance that the thesis ultimately adopts, these values must be reconceptualised as universal but not Western, as ideals to be enunciated and realised from a plurality of positions and locations in the globe.

The possibility of a new world order, and even more for critical social theory, of a new knowledge order, depends on our ability to understand the nature of challenges associated with the politics of difference. By this I mean that the real *political* question that the politics of Muslim subjectivity – as all politics of difference - leaves outside its scope is not whether social theory has been shaped by Eurocentrism. Of course it has. The fact that all alternative theoretical approaches come in the format of ‘post’, ‘anti’ or ‘de’ (like post-colonial, post-Western, anti-Western, or the most recent de-colonial or de-Westernisation) says a great deal about the way the West still defines the terms of the debate. The challenge for critical social theory of our times is where to go after the provincialisation of Europe, after the realisation that power and knowledge are mutually constitutive and after ‘objectivity’ has been proven both false and undesirable. I would like to suggest that, in these circumstances, the real question, and if we follow Badiou (2001: 25), ‘an extraordinarily difficult one’, is not one of benign recognition of difference but ‘that of recognizing the Same’. That is in other words, how to work towards a new kind of genuine universalism which can address the existing unequal power relations beyond the framework of liberal capitalism favoured by the Western elites, but also beyond the return to the hierarchies of religion or tradition, as suggested by the post-Western epistemologies examined by the thesis. By

genuine universalism I do not mean the kind of Westernism to which new imperialists have had recourse in the recent years, like in the case of ‘war on terror’. Such attempts, widely discussed and denounced across disciplines, are nothing more than another strategy of Western neo-imperialism. By universalism I do not mean the false ‘neutrality’ of liberalism either, since, if we follow Žižek (1997: 50), ‘accepting the radically antagonistic - that is, political - character of social life, accepting the necessity of “taking sides”, is the only way to be effectively universal’. In this perspective, we must both accept the antagonistic character of society, because there is no neutral position since struggle is constitutive, and remain universalists, i.e. speak on the behalf of universal emancipation (ibid).

In that sense, the ‘universal’ is not to be understood as something fixed or timeless, but as an open-ended project to be built according to the given historical circumstances by all those who share a commitment to the subversion of relations of domination. Hence, the essential step to take towards this direction would be to dissociate universalism from Westernism and to reclaim it in terms of shared commonalities and shared futures. What such move would entail? First, a humanist conceptualisation of the subject for whom autonomy, resistance and emancipation matters, since when these values are dismissed as European desires only, forms of heteronomy – and hence arbitrary authority – find their way back to the centre-stage of politics. To do so, however, it is important to subvert the association of progress with market economy and to re-think the humanist-secular subject as a progressive and emancipatory one rather than as the agent of contemporary capitalism. Second, a consideration of the material along with the symbolic in our accounts of inequality and violence done against the vulnerable ‘Others’, which has been often underscored since the poststructuralist turn. Although symbolic violence/domination has offered invaluable insights in the ways power operates, what has been considerably neglected is the materiality of violence or exclusion. Re-emphasising this kind of materiality would help us see, for instance that vulnerable Muslim communities are not excluded on the grounds of ‘being Muslim’, i.e. because of Islamophobia, but on the grounds of their position in social stratification and the kind of symbolic formations that this material hierarchy enables. Or, that vulnerable Muslim countries are not attacked because of their religious affiliations but because of their unequal position in the international political order. Third, a certain recovery of the concept of ideology, if critical social theory wishes to maintain a substantial relationship between the social world and the regimes that underpins its truths. By this I do not wish to advocate a retreat to

crude notions of 'false consciousness' even if, despite its patronising character, this concept has something interesting to say about the way the dominant narrative of our modern times, i.e. capitalism, subjectifies us all. What I mean by ideology critique is a critical examination of needs and the ability to resist the absolute relativisation of systems and regimes of truth; but also not to foreclose the possibility of progressive social change, which cannot be achieved by focusing only on realising one's position in the nexus of power, as well to maintain the hope that 'another world is possible'.

Nothing has made more clear the need to re-imagine the universal than the current economic crisis which made obvious the precariousness of social rights, those rights so easily taken for granted or discarded as 'Western inventions', and which showed how people from different locations are essentially subjugated to the same structural inequalities. What we are witnessing at this moment of crisis is the engineering of the accelerated death of the twentieth century and its promise of a better, i.e. more equal, society. The dismantlement of the Welfare State, the depreciation of public education, the commodification of health, the systematic devaluation of the public sector, the demonisation of poverty as a personal failure rather than a social problem, are all typical symptoms of the global neoliberal appropriation of political (State) power (Vasilaki 2011). What does critical social theory have to offer to the analysis of the current predicament and in support to the resistance against the de-humanisation of life itself? Very little, I would argue, if it does not reclaim the universal as an ability to translate the commonality of experiences of subjugation and to create – from a multiplicity of equal positions - shared desires of autonomy and emancipation. Such move would not take universalism for granted – like Westernism – but it would set universalism as its aim, as a project to be realised, and would imply the crafting of histories, futures and methodologies which connect rather than separate. The critical question and real hope for social theory and subversive, radical democratic politics for our times is the pursuit of such theoretical moves: openly political, uncompromisingly egalitarian and therefore universal.

Bibliography

- Abaza, M.** (2002) *Debates on Islam and Knowledge in Malaysia and Egypt. Shifting Worlds*, London and New York : RoutledgeCurzon.
- Abdul Bari, M.** (2012a) 'It Is Time for Inclusive Politics', *Al Jazeera*, 21 March 2012, <http://www.aljazeera.com/indepth/opinion/2012/03/2012319132050458647.html>
- Abdul Bari, M.** (2012b) 'Islamophobia: Europe's new Political Disease', *Al Jazeera*, 06 May 2012, <http://www.aljazeera.com/indepth/opinion/2012/05/201255112042394786.html>
- Abid-Moghaddam, A.** (2009) 'Islamutopia, (Post)Modernity and the Multitude' in Hayden, P. and el-Ojeli, C. *Globalization and Utopia. Critical Essays*, Houndmills: Palgrave Macmillan, 137-155.
- Abu Odeh, L.** (1993) 'Post-Colonial Feminism and the Veil: Thinking the Difference', *Feminist Review*, 43, 26-37.
- Abu-Lughod, L.** (1990) 'The Romance of Resistance: Tracing Transformations of Power through Bedouin Women', *American Ethnologist*, 17(1), 41-55.
- Abu-Lughod, L.** (1998) (ed.) 'Introduction: Feminist Longings and Postcolonial Conditions' in Abu-Lughod, L. (ed.) *Remaking Women. Feminism and Modernity in the Middle East*, Princeton: Princeton University Press: 3-31.
- Abu-Lughod, L.** (2002) 'Do Muslim Women Really Need Saving? Anthropological Reflections on Cultural Relativism and Its Others', *American Anthropologist*, 104(3): 783-90.
- Afary, J. and Anderson, B.** (2005) *Foucault and the Iranian Revolution. Gender and the Seductions of Islamism*, Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Afshar, H.** (1996a) (ed.) *Women and Politics in the Third World*, Routledge: London and New York.
- Afshar, H.** (1996b) 'Women and the Politics of Fundamentalism in Iran' in Afshar, H. (ed.) *Women and Politics in the Third World*, Routledge: London and New York, pp. 121-141.
- Afshar, H.** (1998) *Islam and Feminisms: An Iranian Case-Study*, Houndmills Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Afshar, H.** (2007) 'Muslim Women and Feminisms: Illustrations from the Iranian Experience', *Social Compass*, 54(3): 419-434.
- Afshar, H.** (2008) 'Can I see Your Hair? Choice, Agency and Attitudes: The Dilemma of Faith and Feminism for Muslim Women Who Cover', *Ethnic and Racial Studies*, 31:2, 411-427.
- Agathangelou, A. M. and Ling, L. H. M.** (2004) 'Power, Borders, Security, Wealth. Lessons of Violence and Desire from September 11', *International Studies Quarterly*, 48(3): 517-538.

- Ahmad, A.** (1995) 'The Politics of Literary Postcoloniality', *Race and Class*, 36(3): 1-20.
- Ahmad, A.** (1997) 'Postcolonial Theory and the 'Post' Condition', *The Socialist Register 1997*, 353-381.
- Ahmad, A.** (2008) 'Islam, Islamisms and the West', *Socialist Register*, 1-37.
- Ahmadi, F.** (2006) 'Islamic Feminism in Iran: Feminism in a New Context', *Journal of Feminist Studies in Religion*, 22(2): 33-53.
- Ahmed, A. S. and Donnan, H.** (eds.) (1994) *Islam, Globalization and Postmodernity*, London and New York: Routledge.
- Ahmed, L.** (1992) *Women and Gender in Islam. Historical Roots of a Modern Debate*, New Haven and London: Yale University Press.
- Ahmed, L.** (2000) 'The Women of Islam', *Transition*, 9(3), 78-96.
- Ahmed, R.** (2010) 'Brick Lane: A Materialist Reading of the Novel and its Reception', *Race & Class*, 52(2): 25-42.
- Al-Azmeh, A.** (1993) *Islams and Modernities*, London: Verso.
- An-Na'im, A. A.** (2008) *Islam and the Secular State*, Cambridge Massachusetts and London: Harvard University Press.
- Al-Hassan Golley, N.** (2004) 'Is Feminism Relevant to Arab Women?' *Third World Quarterly*, 25(3), 521-536.
- Allen, C.** (2011) 'Opposing Islamification or Promoting Islamophobia? Understanding the English Defence League', *Patterns of Prejudice*, 45(4): 279-294.
- Allievi, S.** (2006) 'How & Why "Immigrants" became "Muslims"', *ISIM Review*, 18: 18-20.
- Almond, I.** (2007) *The New Orientalists. Postmodern Representations of Islam from Foucault to Baudrillard*, London: I. B. Tauris.
- 'American Terror: A Renewed Wave of Islamophobia Sweeps the United States' (2012), Programmes, *Al Jazeera*, <http://stream.aljazeera.com/story/american-terror-0022320>
- Amin, S.** (1989) *Eurocentrism*, London: Zed.
- Anderson, P.** (1979) *Lineages of the Absolutist State*, London: Verso Editions.
- Antonio, R.** (1981) 'Immanent Critique as the Core of Critical Theory: Its Origins and Developments in Hegel, Marx and Contemporary Thought', *British Journal of Sociology*, 32(3): 330-345.
- Appiah, A. K.** (1997a) 'Cosmopolitan Patriots', *Critical Inquiry* 23: 617-634.

- Appiah, A. K.** (1997b) 'The Multicultural Misunderstanding', *New York Review of Books*, 44 (October 1997): 30-36.
- Appiah, K. A.** (1991) 'Is the Post- in Postmodern the Post- in Postcolonial?', *Critical Inquiry*, 17(2), pp. 336-357.
- Appiah, K. A.** (2006) *Cosmopolitanism. Ethics in a World of Strangers*, New York: Penguin Books Ltd.
- Arendt, H.** (1973 [1950]) *The Origins of Totalitarianism*, New York: Harcourt Brace Jovanovich.
- Arkoun, M.** (2007) 'The Answers of Applied Islamology', *Theory, Culture and Society*, 24(2): 21-38.
- Arnason, J. P.** (1989) 'The Imaginary Constitution of Modernity' (1989) *Revue européenne des sciences sociales* 86: 323-337.
- Asad, T.** (1986) 'The Idea of an Anthropology of Islam', *Occasional Paper Series*, Center for Contemporary Studies, Georgetown University.
- Asad, T.** (1993) *Genealogies of Religion. Discipline and Reasons of Power in Christianity and Islam*, Baltimore and London: The Johns Hopkins University Press.
- Asad, T.** (1998 [1973]) *Anthropology and the Colonial Encounter*, Amherst New York: Humanity Books.
- Asad, T.** (2003) *Formations of the Secular. Christianity, Islam, Modernity*, Stanford: Stanford University Press.
- Asad, T.** (2006) 'Responses' in Scott, D. and Hirschkind C. (eds.) *Powers of the Secular Modern. Talal Asad and His Interlocutors*, Stanford CA: Stanford University Press: 206-303.
- Asad, T.** (2009a) 'Free Speech, Blasphemy and Secular Criticism' in Asad, T., Brown, W., Butler, J. and Mahmood, S. (eds.) *Is Critique Secular? Blasphemy, Injury and Free Speech*, Berkeley: University of California Press: 20-63.
- Asad, T.** (2009b) 'Reply to Judith Butler' in Asad, T., Brown, W., Butler, J. and Mahmood, S. (eds.) *Is Critique Secular? Blasphemy, Injury and Free Speech*, Berkeley: University of California Press: 137-145.
- Asad, T. and An-Na'im, A.** (2009) 'Religion, Law, and the Politics of Human Rights. Talal Asad and Abdullahi An-Na'im in Conversation', *Berkley Center for Religion, Peace and World Affairs*, Georgetown University, Social Science Research Council, available on <http://blogs.ssrc.org/tif/wp-content/uploads/2009/11/Talal-Asad-and-Abdullahi-An-Naim-in-conversation.pdf> (accessed August 2011).

- Badiou, A.** (2001) *Ethics. An Essay on the Understanding of Evil*, London and New York: Verso.
- Badran, M.** (1995) *Feminists, Islam, and Nation: Gender and the Making of Modern Egypt*, Princeton N.J.: Princeton University Press.
- Badran, M.** (2001) 'Understanding Islamism and Islamic Feminism', *Journal of Women's History*, 13(1): 47-52.
- Badran, M.** (2002) 'Islamic Feminism: What's in a name?' in <http://weekly.ahram.org.eg/2002/569/cu1.htm>
- Badran, M.** (2005) 'Between Secular and Islamic Feminisms: Reflections on the Middle East and Beyond', *Journal of Middle Eastern Women's Studies* 1: 6–28.
- Badran, M.** (2006) 'Islamic Feminism Revisited' in <http://www.countercurrents.org/gen-badran100206.htm>
- Balakrishnan, G.** (2001) 'The Politics of Piety', *New Left Review* 7, January-February: 156-160.
- Bangstad, S.** (2010) 'Saba Mahmood and Anthropological Criticism after Virtue', *Theory, Culture and Society*, 28(3): 28-54.
- Bangstada, S. and Bunzl, M.** (2010) "'Anthropologists Are Talking" About Islamophobia and Anti-Semitism in the New Europe', *Ethnos*, 75(2): 213-228.
- Barlas, A.** (2002) *Believing Women in Islam: Unreading Patriarchal Interpretations of the Qur'an*, Austin: University of Texas Press.
- Barry, B.** (2001) *Culture and Equality. An Egalitarian Critique of Multiculturalism*, Cambridge and Oxford: Polity.
- Barry, B.** (2001b) 'The Muddles of Multiculturalism', *New Left Review* 8, March-April: 49-71.
- Barthes, R.** (2001 [1957]) *Mythologies*, New York: Hill and Wang.
- Bauer, J.** (1985) 'Sexuality and the Moral Construction of Women in an Islamic Society', *Anthropological Quarterly*, 58(3), 120-129.
- Baum, B.** (2004) 'The Feminist Politics of Recognition', *Signs*, 29(4), 1073-1102.
- Bayart, J-F.** (1996) *The Illusion of Cultural Identity*, London: Hurst & Company.
- Bayart, J-F.** (2010) *Les études postcoloniales. Un carnaval académique*, Paris: Karthala.
- Bayat, A.** (2008) 'Islamism and Empire: The Incongruous Nature of Islamist Anti-Imperialism', *Socialist Register*, 38-54.
- Beaulac, S.** (2004) 'The Westphalian Model in Defining International Law: Challenging the Myth', *Australian Journal of Legal History* 7(2) 2: 181–213;

- Bechir, S. and Saghie, H.** (2005), 'The "Muslim community": a European invention', openDemocracy, http://www.opendemocracy.net/conflict-terrorism/community_2928.jsp
- Beckingham, C. F.** (1979) 'Reviews: Orientalism', *Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies, University of London* 42(3): 562-564.
- Benhabib, S.** (2002) *The Claims of Culture: Equality and Diversity in the Global Era*, Princeton NJ: Princeton University Press.
- Bennington, G. and Young, R.** (1987) (eds.) *Post-structuralism and the Question of History*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Benzine, R.** (2004) *Les nouveaux penseurs de l'islam*, Paris : Albin Michel.
- Bhabha, H. and Comaroff, J.** (2002) 'Speaking of Postcoloniality in a Continuous Present' in Goldberg, T. D., Quayson, A. and Comaroff, J. (eds.) *Relocating Postcolonialism*, Oxford: Blackwell Publishing: 15-46.
- Bhabha, H. K.** (1994) *The Location of Culture*, London and New York: Routledge.
- Bhambra, G.** (2007) 'Sociology and Postcolonialism: Another 'Missing' Revolution?', *Sociology*, 41: 871-884.
- Bhimji, F.** (2009) 'Identities and Agency in Religious Spheres: A Study of British Muslim Women's Experience', *Gender, Place and Culture*, 16(4): 365-380.
- Biddick, K.** (1998) *The Shock of Medievalism*, Durham and London: Duke University Press.
- Bilgrami, A.** (2004) 'Secularism and Relativism', *boundary 2*, 31(2): 173-196.
- Birt, J.** (2009) 'Islamophobia in the Construction of British Muslim Identity Politics', in Hopkins, P. and Gale, R. (eds.) *Muslims in Britain. Race, Place and Identities*, Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press: 210-227.
- Bleich, E.** (2011) 'What Is Islamophobia and How Much Is There? Theorizing and Measuring an Emerging Comparative Concept', *American Behavioral Scientist*, 55(12) 1581-1600.
- Blencowe, C.** (2012) *Biopolitical Experience. Foucault, Power and Positive Critique*, Houndmills Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Boddy, J.** (1982) 'Womb as Oasis. The Symbolic Context of Pharaonic Circumcision in Rural Northern Sudan' *American Ethnologist*, 9: 682-698.
- Bonevac, D.** (1994) 'What Multiculturalism Should Not Be', *College Literature*, 21(3): 157-172.
- Boroujerdi, A.** (1996) *Iranian Intellectuals and the West. The Tormented Triumph of Nativism*, Syracuse NY: Syracuse University Press.
- Boyer, D.** (2005) 'Welcome to the New Europe', *American Ethnologist*, 32(4): 521-523.

- Bracke, S.** (2008) 'Conjugating the Modern/Religious, Conceptualizing Female Religious Agency. Contours of a 'Post-secular' Conjuncture', *Theory, Culture and Society*, 25(6): 51-67.
- Bracke, S.** (2008) 'Conjugating the Modern/Religious, Conceptualizing Female Religious Agency. Contours of a 'Post-secular' Conjuncture', *Theory, Culture and Society*, 25(6): 51-67.
- Bracke, S. and Fadil, N.** (2008) 'Islam and Secular Modernity under Western Eyes. A Genealogy of a Constitutive Relationship', EUI Working Papers, *Robert Schuman Centre for Advanced Studies 2008/05, Mediterranean Programme Series*, European University Institute.
- Bravo López, F.** (2011) 'Towards a Definition of Islamophobia: Approximations of the Early Twentieth Century', *Ethnic and Racial Studies*, 34(4): 556-573.
- Brown, W.** (2006) *Regulating Aversion. Tolerance and the Age of Identity*, Princeton NJ: Princeton University Press.
- Bruck, G. vom** (2008) 'Naturalising Women's Bodies: The "Headscarf Affair" and the Politics of Representation', *Identities*, 15(1): 51-79.
- Buck-Morss, S.** (2003/2006) *Thinking Past Terror. Islamism and Critical Theory on the Left*, London and NY: Verso.
- Bunzl, M.** (2005) 'Between Anti-Semitism and Islamophobia: Some Thoughts on the New Europe', *American Ethnologist*, 32(4): 499-508.
- Burgat, F.** (2005) *Face to Face with Political Islam*, London and New York: I. B. Tauris.
- Butler, J.** (1995) 'For a Careful Reading' in Benhabib, S., Butler, J. Cornell, D. and Fraser N. (eds.) *Feminists Contentions*, New York: Routledge: 127-44.
- Butler, J.** (2004) *Prearious Life. The Powers of Mourning and Violence*, London and New York: Verso.
- Butler, J.** (2008) 'Sexual Politics, Torture and Secular Time', *The British Journal of Sociology*, 59(1), 1-23.
- Butler, J.** (2009) 'The Sensibility of Critique: Response to Asad and Mahmood' in in Asad, T., Brown, W., Butler, J. and Mahmood, S. (eds.) *Is Critique Secular? Blasphemy, Injury and Free Speech*, Berkeley: University of California Press: 101-136.
- Butler, J.** (2009) *Frames of War. When Life is Grievable?*, London and New York: Verso.
- Callinicos, A.** (2006) *The Resources of Critique*, Cambridge and Malden: Polity.
- Carr, M.** (2006) 'You Are now Entering Eurabia', *Race & Class*, 48(1): 1-22.
- Cesaire, A.** (2001) *Discourse on Colonialism*, New York: Monthly European Review.

- Chakrabarty, D.** (1992) 'Postcoloniality and the Artifice of History: Who Speaks of the Indian Pasts?' in *Representations*, 37: 1-26.
- Chakrabarty, D.** (1992) 'Postcoloniality and the Artifice of History: Who Speaks of the Indian Pasts?', *Representations*, 37: 1-26.
- Chakrabarty, D.** (1994) 'Categorical Theory; A Response to Aijaz Ahmad', *Middle East Report*, 187/188: 54-55.
- Chakrabarty, D.** (1995) 'Radical Histories and the Question of Enlightenment Rationalism: Some Recent Critiques of "Subaltern Studies"', *Economic and Political Weekly*, 30(14): 751-759.
- Chakrabarty, D.** (2000) *Provincializing Europe. Postcolonial Thought and Historical Difference*, Princeton and Oxford: Princeton University Press.
- Chakrabarty, D.** (2007) 'Manifestos for History' in Morgan, S., Jenkins, K. and Munslow, A. (eds.), *History and the Politics of Recognition*, London: Routledge: 77-86.
- Chakrabarty, D.** (2009) 'Anti-colonial History of the Postcolonial Turn: Essays in Memory of Greg Denning', *Melbourne Historical Journal*, 37: 1-23.
- Chicago Cultural Studies Group (CCSG)**, (1992) 'Critical Multiculturalism', *Critical Inquiry*, vol. 18(3): 530-555.
- Chowdhry, G. and Nair, S.** (2002) (eds.) *Power, Postcolonialism and International Relations. Reading Race, Gender and Class*, London and New York: Routledge.
- Cindoglu, D. and Zencirci, G.** (2008) 'The Headscarf in Turkey in the Public and State Spheres', *Middle Eastern Studies*, 44(5): 791-806.
- Clifford, J.** (1980) 'Review Essays: Orientalism', *History and Theory* 19(2): 201-223.
- Cliteur, P.** (2011) 'Female Critics of Islamism: Liberal or Secular Islam?', *Feminist Theology*, 19(2): 154-167.
- Cohen, J., Howard, M. and Nussbaum, M. C.** (1999) (eds.) *Is Multiculturalism Bad for Women?*, Princeton NJ: Princeton University Press.
- Commission of the Future of Multi-Ethnic Britain** (2000) *The Future of Multi-Ethnic Britain. The Parekh Report*, London: Profile Books Ltd.
- Commission on British Muslims and Islamophobia** (1997) *Islamophobia. A Challenge for Us All*, London: The Runnymede Trust.
- Connolly, W. E.** (1999) *Why I Am Not A Secularist*, Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press.
- Cooke, M.** (2001) *Women Claim Islam: Creating Islamic Feminism through Literature*, New York: Routledge.

- Cooper, J.** (2000) 'The Limits of the Sacred: The Epistemology of Abd al-Karim Soroush' in Cooper, J., Nettler, R. and Mahmood, M. (eds.) *Islam and Modernity. Muslim Intellectuals Respond*, London and New York: I. B. Tauris, 138-56.
- Cooper, M.** (2008) 'Orientalism in the Mirror. The Sexual Politics of Anti-Westernism', *Theory, Culture and Society*, 25(6): 25-49.
- Dabashi, H.** (2008) *Islamic Liberation Theology. Resisting the Empire*, London and New York: Routledge.
- Dabashi, H.** (2012) 'Merci, Monsieur Badiou', *Al Jazeera*, 22 May 2012, <http://www.aljazeera.com/indepth/opinion/2012/05/2012521133112754351.html>
- Dagenais, J. and Greer, M. R.** (2000) 'Decolonising the Middle-Ages. Introduction', *Journal of Medieval and Early Modern Studies*, 30(3): 431-448.
- Dainotto, R. M.** (2006) 'The Discreet Charm of the Arabist Theory: Juan Andrés Historicism, and the De-Centering of Montesquieu's Europe', *European History Quarterly*, 36(1); 7-29.
- Dallmayr, F.** (1978) (ed.) *From Contract to Community: Political Theory at Cross Roads*, New York: Marcel Dekker.
- Davis, K.** (1998) 'National Writing in the Ninth Century. A Reminder for Postcolonial Thinking about the Nation', *Journal of Medieval and Early Modern Studies*, 28(3): 611-637.
- Davis, K.** (2008) *Periodization and Sovereignty. How Ideas About Feudalism and Secularization Govern the Politics of Time*, Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press.
- Dawn, E.** (1979) 'Reviews of Books: Orientalism', *The American Historical Review* 84(5): 1334.
- De Sousa Santos, B.** (2002) 'Toward a Multicultural Perception of Human Rights', in Berta Hernandez-Truyol, ed., *Moral Imperialism. A Critical Anthology*, New York: New York University Press: 39-60.
- Deeb, L.** (2006) *An Enchanted Modern. Gender and Public Piety in Shi'i Lebanon*, Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Deeb, L.** (2010) 'Gendering Islamophobia and Islamophilia: The Case of Shi'i Muslim Women in Lebanon' in Shryock, A. (ed.) *Beyond the Politics of Enemy and Friend*, Bloomington and Indianapolis: Indiana University Press, pp. 94-110.
- Delanty, G.** (2010 [2003]) *Community. Second Edition*, London and New York: Routledge.
- Dirlik, A.** (1987) 'Culturalism as Hegemonic Ideology and Liberating Practice', *Cultural Critique*, 6: 13-50.

- Dirlik, A.** (1994) 'The Postcolonial Aura: Third World Criticism at the Age of Global Capitalism'. *Critical Inquiry*, 20(2), pp. 328-356.
- Dirlik, A.** (1999) 'Is There History After Eurocentrism? Globalism, Postcolonialism, and the Disavowal of History', *Cultural Critique*, 42: 1-34.
- Doumato, E.** (1992) 'Gender, Monarchy, and National Identity in Saudi Arabia', *British Journal of Middle-Eastern Studies*, 19(1), 31-47.
- Duggan, L.** (2002) 'The New Homonormativity. The Sexual Politics of Neoliberalism', in R. Castronova, R. and Nelson D.D. (eds) *Materializing Democracy. Towards a Revitalized Cultural Politics*, Durham, NC: Duke University Press: 175-194.
- Dussel, E.** (2001) *Hacia una Filosofía Política Crítica*, Bilbao: Desclée de Brouwer.
- Duval, S.** (1998) 'New Veils and New Voices: Islamist Women's Groups in Egypt' in Ask, K. and Tjomsland, M. (eds.) *Women and Islamization: Contemporary Dimensions of Discourse on Gender Relations*, Oxford: Berg, 45-72.
- Dwyer, C.** (1999) 'Veiled Meanings: Yond British Muslim Women and the Negotiation of Differences', *Gender, Place and Culture*, 6(1): 5-26.
- Eagleton, T.** (2005) *Holy Terror*, Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Eagleton, T.** (2009) *Reason, Faith and Revolution. Reflections on the God Debate*, New Haven and London: Yale University Press.
- Ebert, T.** (1991) 'The "Difference" of Postmodern Feminism', *College English*, 53(8), 886-904.
- Ebert, T.** (2005) 'Rematerializing Feminism', *Science and Society*, 69(1): 33-55.
- Eickelman, D. and Anderson, J.** (1999) (eds.) *New Media in the Muslim World. The Emerging Public Sphere*, Bloomington: Indiana University Press.
- Eisenstein, Z.** (2002) 'Feminisms in the Aftermath of September 11', *Social Text* 72, 20(3), 79-99.
- El-Fadl, K.** (2001) 'Islam and the Theology of Power', *Middle East Report*, 221: 28-33.
- El Guidi, F.** (1999) *Veil. Modesty, Privacy and Resistance*, Berg: Oxford and New York.
- Eller, J. D.** (1997), 'Anti-Anti-Multiculturalism', *American Anthropologist*, vol. 99(2): 249-256.
- Eriksen, J-M. and Stjernfelt, F.** (2010) 'Culturalism: Culture as Political Ideology', 29 July 2010, openDemocracy, <http://www.opendemocracy.net/page/jens-martin-eriksen/culturalism-culture-as-political-ideology>
- Esack, F.** (1997) *Quran, Liberation and Pluralism. An Islamic Perspective of Interreligious Solidarity against Oppression*, Oxford: Oneworld.

- Esposito, J.** (1999) *The Islamic Threat. Myth or Reality?*, Oxford and New York: Oxford University Press.
- Fadil, N.** (2009) 'Managing Affects and Sensibilities. The Case of Not-handshaking and Not-fasting', *Social Anthropology/Anthropologie Sociale*, 17(4): 439-454.
- Fekete, L.** (2006) 'Enlightened Fundamentalism? Immigration, Feminism and the Right', *Race & Class*, 48(2): 1-22.
- Fernea, E. W.** (1998) *In Search of Islamic Feminism: One Woman's Global Journey*, New York: Anchor.
- Filali-Ansary, A.** (2003) *Reformer l'islam?*, Paris: La Découverte.
- Foucault, M.** (1980) *Power/Knowledge. Selected Interviews and Other Writings 1972-1977*, New York: Pantheon, 78-108.
- Fraser, N.** (1985) 'What's Critical about Critical Theory? The Case of Habermas and Gender', *New German Critique*, 35: 97-131.
- Fraser, N.** (1989) *Unruly Practices. Power, Discourse and Gender in Contemporary Social Theory*, Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press.
- Fraser, N.** (1995) 'From Redistribution to Recognition? Dilemmas of Justice in a "Post-Socialist" Age', *New Left Review* 1/212, July-August: 68-93.
- Fraser, N.** (1997) 'A Rejoinder to Iris Young', *New Left Review* 1/223, May-June: 126-129.
- Fukuyama, F.** (1992) *The End of History and the Last Man*, London and New York: Penguin Books.
- Gauch, S.** (2006) *Liberating Shahrzad. Feminism, Postcolonialism and Islam*, Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press.
- Gingrich, A.** (2005) 'Anthropological Analyses of Islamophobia and anti-Semitism in Europe', *American Ethnologist*, 32(4): 513-515.
- Gitlin, T.** (1995) *The Twilight of Common Dreams: Why America is Wracked by Culture Wars*, New York: Henry Holt.
- Glazer, N.** (1997) *We Are All Multiculturalists Now*, Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Go, J.** (2007) 'The Provinciality of American Empire: "Liberal Exceptionalism" and U.S. Colonial Rule, 1898-1912', *Comparative Studies in Society and History*, 49(1): 74-108.
- Gole, N.** (1996) *The Forbidden Modern. Civilization and Veiling*, Michigan: Ann Arbor, The University of Michigan Press.
- Gole, N.** (2000) 'Snapshots of Islamic Modernities', *Daedalus*, 129(1): 91-117.

- Gole, N.** (2003) 'The Voluntary Adoption of Islamic Stigma Symbols', *Social Research*, 70(3): 809-828.
- Gole, N.** (2004) 'Islam in Europe', *Index on Censorship*, 4: 110-116.
- Gole, N.** (2010) 'European Self-Presentations and Narratives Challenged by Islam: Secular Modernity in Question' in Rodriguez, E. G., Boatca, M. and Costa S. (eds.) *Decolonizing European Sociology. Transdisciplinary Approaches*, Farnham and Burlington: Ashgate.
- Goodenough, W.H.** (1976) 'Multiculturalism as the Normal Human Experience', *Anthropology and Education Quarterly*, 7(4): 4-6.
- Gramsci, A.** (2011 [1975]) *Prison Notebooks, volume I, II, III*, New York: Columbia University Press.
- Gray, J.** (2003) *Straw Dogs*, London: Granta.
- Grosfoguel, R.** (2009a) 'A Decolonial Approach to Political-Economy: Transmodernity, Border Thinking and Global Coloniality', *Kult*, 6: 10-38.
- Grosfoguel, R.** (2009b) 'Human Rights and Anti-Semitism after Gaza', *Human Architecture: Journal of Sociology of Self-Knowledge*, VII, 2: 89-102.
- Grosfoguel, R. and Mielants, E.** (2006) 'The Long-Durée Entanglement between Islamophobia and Racism in the Modern/Colonial Capitalist/Patriarchal World-System. An Introduction', *Human Architecture: Journal of Sociology of Self-Knowledge*, V, 1: 1-12.
- Guha, R.** (1994) 'The Prose of Counter-Insurgency' in Dirks, N. et. al., *Culture/Power/History: A Reader in Contemporary Social Theory*, Princeton: Princeton University Press: 336-371.
- Gutmann, A.** (1993), 'The Challenge of Multiculturalism in Political Ethics', *Philosophy and Public Affairs*, vol. 22(3): 171-206.
- Habermas, J.** (1995) 'Address: Multiculturalism and the Liberal State', *Stanford Law Review*, vol. 47(5): 849-853.
- Halley, J. and Ticineto Clough, P.** (2007) (eds.) *The Affective Turn: Theorizing the Social*, Durham: Duke University Press.
- Halliday, F.** (1993) 'Orientalism and Its Critics', *British Journal of Middle East Studies* 20(2): 145-163.
- Halliday, F.** (1999) "'Islamophobia' Reconsidered', *Ethnic and Racial Studies*, 22(5): 892-902.
- Halliday, F.** (2003) *Islam and the Myth of Confrontation. Religion and Politics in the Middle East*, London and New York: I.B. Tauris.

- Hallward, P.** (2001) *Absolutely Postcolonial. Writing between the Singular and the Specific*, Manchester and New York: Manchester University Press.
- Halpern, M.** (1963) *The Politics of Social Change in the Middle East and North Africa*, Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Halverson, J. R. and Way, A. K.** (2011) 'Islamist Feminism: Constructing Gender Identities in Postcolonial Muslim Societies', *Politics and Religion*, 4: 503-525.
- Hanson, A.** (1989) 'The Making of the Maori: Culture Invention and Its Logic', *American Anthropologist*, 91(4): 890-902.
- Hanssen, B.** (2000) *Critique of Violence. Between Poststructuralism and Critical Theory*, London and New York: Routledge.
- Hart, W. D.** (2000) *Edward Said and the Religious Effects of Culture*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Harvey, D.** (1981) 'Introduction', *Sociological Perspectives*, 33(1): 1-10.
- Hasan, M.** (2012) 'We Mustn't Allow Muslims in Public Life to Be Silenced', *The Guardian*, 8 July 2012, <http://www.guardian.co.uk/commentisfree/2012/jul/08/muslims-public-life-abuse>
- Hashim, I.** (1999) 'Reconciling Islam and Feminism', *Gender and Development*, 7(1), 7-14.
- Hassan, R.** (1996) 'Feminist Theology: The Challenges for Muslim Women', *Middle East Critique*, 5(9): 53-65.
- Hassan, R.** (1999) 'Feminism in Islam' in Sharma, A. and Young, K. K. (eds.) *Feminism and World Religions*, Albany: State University of New York Press.
- Hirschkind, C.** (2006) *The Ethical Soundscape. Cassette Sermons and Islamic Counter Publics*, New York and Chichester: Columbia University Press.
- Hirschkind, C. and Mahmood, S.** (2002) 'Feminism, Taliban and the Politics of Counter-Insurgency', *Anthropological Quarterly*, 75(2): 339-354.
- Hobsbawm, E.** (1983) *Elementary Aspects of Peasant Insurgency in Colonial India*, Delhi: Oxford University Press.
- Hobsbawm, E.** (1994) *The Age of Extremes. The Short Twentieth Century, 1914-1991*, London: Michael Joseph.
- Hobson, J. M.** (2007) 'Is Critical Theory Always for the White West and for Western Imperialism? Beyond Westphalian towards a post-Racist Critical IR', *Review of International Studies* 33: 91-116.

- Hodgson, M. G. S.** (1974) *The Venture of Islam (vol. 1-3)*, Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press.
- Hollinger, D.** (1995) *Postethnic America: Beyond Multiculturalism*, New York: Basic Books.
- Hollywood, A.** (2004) 'Gender, Agency and the Divine in Religious Historiography', *The Journal of Religion*, 84(4): 514-528.
- Holsinger, B. W.** 'Medieval Studies, Postcolonial Studies, and the Genealogies of Critique', *Speculum*, 77(4): 1195-1227.
- Holt, M.** (1996) 'Palestinian Women and the Intifada: An Exploration of Images and Realities' in Afshar, H. (ed.) *Women and Politics in the Third World*, Routledge: London and New York, pp. 186-203.
- Hourani, A.** (1983/1962) *Arabic Thought in the Liberal Age*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Hourani, A.** (2001/1991) *Islam in European Thought*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Huntington, S.** (2002 [1997]) *The Clash of Civilizations and the Remaking of World Order*, London: Free Press.
- Inayatullah, N. and Blaney, D. L.** (2004) *International Relations and the Problem of Difference*, London and New York: Taylor and Francis Books.
- Irwin, R.** (2006) *For Lust of Knowing. Orientalists and Their Enemies*, London: Allen, Lane, Penguin Book.
- Jameson, F.** (1991) *Postmodernism or the Cultural Logic of Late Capitalism*, London: Verso.
- Joseph, S.** (1998) 'Comment on Majid's "The Politics of Feminism in Islam": Critique of Politics and the Politics of Critique', *Signs*, 23(2), 363-369.
- Kabbani, R.** (1986) *Europe's Myth of Orient*, Bloomington, IN: Indiana University Press.
- Kandiyoti, D.** (1988) 'Bargaining with Patriarchy', *Gender and Society*, 2(3), 274-290.
- Kandiyoti, D.** (1991a) 'Islam and Patriarchy: A Comparative Perspective' in Keddie, N. and Baron, B. (eds.) *Women in Middle Eastern History: Shifting Boundaries in Sex and Gender*, New Haven: Yale University Press.
- Kandiyoti, D.** (1991b) (ed.) *Women, Islam and the State*, Philadelphia: Temple University Press.
- Kaplan, E.** (2004) *With God on Our Side: George W. Bush and the Christian Right*, New York: The New Press.
- Katz, J.** (1983) 'Misreadings of anti-Semitism', *Commentary*, 76(1): 39-44.
- Kaya, I.** (2000) 'Modernity and Veiled Women', *European Journal of Social Theory*, 3(2), 195-214.

- Keller, M.** (2002) *The Hammer and the Flute. Women, Power and Spirit Possession*, Baltimore: John Hopkins University Press.
- Kelly, P.** (2002) (ed.) *Multiculturalism reconsidered*, Cambridge and Oxford: Polity Press.
- Kepel, G.** (2002) *Jihad. The Trail of Political Islam*, London: I. B. Tauris.
- Kepel, G.** (2004) *The War for Muslim Minds. Islam and the West*, Cambridge Massachusetts and London: The Belknap Press of Harvard University Press.
- Kerr, M. H.** (1980) 'Reviews: Orientalism', *International Journal of Middle East Studies*, 12(4): 544-547.
- Khan, D.** (2012), 'Islamophobia is America's Real Enemy', *The Guardian*, 9 February 2012, <http://www.guardian.co.uk/commentisfree/2012/feb/09/islamophobes-us-muslims-enemy>
- Kipnis, L.** 'Feminism: The Political Consciousness of Postmodernism?', *Social Text*, 21, 149-166.
- Klassen, P.** (2004) 'Agency, Embodiment and Scrupulous Women' (review article), *Journal of Religion*, 84: 592-603.
- Klausen, Y.** (2005) *The Islamic Challenge: Politics and Religion in Western Europe*, Oxford and New York: Oxford University Press.
- Khosrokhavar, F.** (2004) 'The New Intellectuals in Iran', *Social Compass*, 51(2): 191-202.
- Krishnaswamy, R.** (2002) 'The Criticism of Culture and the Culture of Criticism: At the Intersection of Postcolonialism and Globalization Theory', *Diacritics* 32(2): 106-126.
- Kukathas, C.** (1992) 'Are There Any Cultural Rights?', *Political Theory*, 20(1): 105-139.
- Kukathas, C.** (1998) 'Liberalism and Multiculturalism: The Politics of Indifference', 26(5): 686-699.
- Kumar, D.** (2012) *Islamophobia and the Politics of Empire: Empire Abroad and at Home*, Chicago IL: Haymarket Books.
- Kymlicka, W. (1992) 'Two Models of Pluralism and Tolerance', *Analyse and Kritik*, 13: 33-56.
- Kymlicka, W.** (1995), *Multicultural Citizenship: A Liberal Theory of Minority Rights*, Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Kymlicka, W.** (2001a) *Politics in the Vernacular: Nationalism, Multiculturalism and Citizenship*, Oxford and New York: Oxford University Press.
- Kymlicka, W.** (2001b) *Contemporary Political Philosophy*, Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Lapidus, I.** (1997) 'Islamic Revivalism and Modernity. The Contemporary Movements and the Historical Paradigms', *Journal of the Economic and Social History of the Orient*, 40(4): 444-460.

- Lægaard, S.** (2007) 'The Cartoon Controversy: Offence, Identity, Oppression?', *Political Studies*, 55: 481-498.
- Laitin, D.** (2010) 'Rational Islamophobia in Europe', *Archives of European Sociology*, LI, 3: 429–447.
- Langmuir, G. I.** (1996) *Toward a Definition of anti-Semitism*, Berkeley, Los Angeles and Oxford: University of California Press.
- Laroui, A.** (1976) *The Crisis of the Arab Intellectual: Traditionalism or Historicism?*, Berkeley: University of California Press.
- Larsson, G. and Lindekilde, L.** (2009) 'Muslim Claims-making in Context: Comparing the Danish and the Swedish Muhammad Cartoons Controversies', *Ethnicities*, 9(3): 361–382.
- Lazreg, M.** (1988) 'Feminism and Difference. The Perils of Writing as a Woman in Algeria', *Feminist Studies*, 14(1): 81-107.
- Lazreg, M.** (1994) *The Eloquence of Silence. Algerian Women in Question*, New York: Routledge.
- Leezenberg, M.** (2010) 'How Ethnocentric is the Concept of the Postsecular?' in Molendijk, A. L., Beaumont, J. and Jedan, C. (eds.) *The Religious, the Political and the Urban*, Leiden and Boston: Brill, 91-112.
- Levey, B. G. and Modood T.** (2009) 'The Muhammad Cartoons and Multicultural Democracies', *Ethnicities*, 9(3): 427–447.
- Lewis, B.** (1990) 'The Roots of Muslim Rage', *The Atlantic*, September issue (available online on <http://www.theatlantic.com/magazine/archive/1990/09/the-roots-of-muslim-rage/4643/>)
- Lindekilde, L., Mouritsen, P. and Zapata-Barrero** (2009) 'The Muhammad Cartoons Controversy in Comparative Perspective', *Ethnicities*, 9(3): 291–313.
- Lindemann, A. S.** (1997) *Esau's Tears: Modern Anti-Semitism and the Rise of the Jews*, Cambridge and New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Linkler, D.** (2005) *The Theocons: Secular America under Siege*, New York: Anchor Books.
- Lorasdagi, B. K.** (2009a) 'The Headscarf and 'Resistance Identity-Building': A Case Study on Headscarf-Wearing in Amsterdam', *Women's Studies International Forum*, 32: 453-462.
- Lorasdagi, B. K.** (2009b) 'The Headscarf and Emancipation in the Netherlands', *Feminism and Psychology*, 19(3): 328-334.
- Lutz, H.** (1991) 'Migrant women of "Islamic background": Images and self images', Occasional Paper No 11. MERA, Amsterdam.

- MacKinnon, C.** (2006) 'Women's September 11th: Rethinking the International Law of Conflict', *Harvard International Law Journal*, 47(1): 1-31.
- MacLeod, A. E.** (1993) *Accommodating Protest: Working Women, the New Veiling and Change in Cairo*, New York: Columbia University Press.
- Mahmood, S.** (2001) 'Feminist Theory, Embodiment, and the Docile Agent: Some Reflections on the Egyptian Islamic Revival', *Cultural Anthropology*, 16(2), 202-236.
- Mahmood, S.** (2003) 'Ethical Formation and the Politics of Individual Autonomy in Contemporary Egypt', *Social Research*, 70(3): 1501-1530.
- Mahmood, S.** (2005) *The Politics of Piety. The Islamic Revival and the Feminist Subject*, Princeton and Oxford: Princeton University Press.
- Mahmood, S.** (2006) 'Secularism, Hermeneutics, and Empire: The Politics of Islamic Reformation', *Public Culture*, 18(2): 323-347.
- Mahmood, S.** (2009) 'Religious Reason and Secular Affect: An Incommensurable Divide?' in Asad, T., Brown, W., Butler, J. and Mahmood, S. (eds.) *Is Critique Secular? Blasphemy, Injury and Free Speech*, Berkeley: University of California Press: 64-100.
- Majeed, J.** (2009) *Muhammad Iqbal. Islam, Aesthetics, Postcolonialism*, New Delhi: Routledge India.
- Majid, A.** (1998a) 'The Politics of Feminism in Islam', *Signs*, 23(2), 321-361.
- Majid, A.** (1998b) 'Reply to Joseph and Mayer: Critique as a Dehegemonizing Practice', *Sings*, 23(2), 377-389.
- Majid, A.** (2000) *Unveiling Traditions. Postcolonial Islam in a Polycentric World*, Durham: Duke University Press.
- Majid, A.** (2007) *A Call for Heresy. Why Dissent is Vital to Islam and America*, Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press.
- Malik, K.** (1998) 'Race, Pluralism and the Meaning of Difference', *New Formations*, no 33 http://www.kenanmalik.com/papers/new_formation.html
- Malik, K.** (2005) 'The Islamophobia Myth', *Prospect*, available on http://www.kenanmalik.com/essays/prospect_islamophobia.html
- Malik, M.** (2007) 'The Failures of Multiculturalism in the Secular State and Islam in Europe (ax:son johnson foundation, 2007)', http://www.kenanmalik.com/papers/engelsberg_mc.html
- Malik, K.** (2009) *From Fatwa to Jihad. The Rushdie Affair and Its Legacy*, London: Atlantic Books.

- Mandaville, P.** (2001) *Transnational Muslim Politics. Reimagining the Ummah*, London: Routledge.
- Marx, K.** (1852) *The Eighteenth Brumaire of Louis Bonaparte*, available on <http://www.marxists.org/archive/marx/works/1852/18th-brumaire/ch01.htm> (accessed August 2011).
- Mayer, A. E.** (1998) 'Comment on 'Comment on Majid's "The Politics of Feminism in Islam"', *Signs*, 23(2), 369-377.
- McClintock, A.** (1992) 'The Angel of Progress. Pitfalls of the Term "Post-Colonialism"', *Social Text*, 31/32: 84-98.
- McLennan, G.** (2001) 'Can There Be a "Critical" Multiculturalism?', *Ethnicities*, 1: 389-408.
- McLennan, G.** (2007) 'Toward Postsecular Sociology?', *Sociology*, 41(5): 857-870.
- McLennan, G.** (2010) 'Eurocentrism, Sociology, Secularity' in Costa, S., Rodriguez, E.G. and Boatca, M. (eds.) *Decolonizing European Sociology*, Furnham and Burlington: Ashgate, 119-133.
- McLennan, G.** (2010) 'The Postsecular Turn', *Theory, Culture and Society*, 27(4): 3-20.
- Meer, N. and Mouritsen, P.** (2009) 'Political Cultures Compared', *Ethnicities*, 9(3): 334-360.
- Meer, N. and Noorani, T.** (2008) 'A Sociological Comparison of anti-Semitism and anti-Muslim Sentiment in Britain', *The Sociological Review*, 56(2): 195-219.
- Mepschen, P., Duyvendak, J. W. and Tonkens, E. H.** (2010) 'Sexual Politics, Orientalism and Multicultural Citizenship in the Netherlands', *Sociology*, 44(5): 962-979.
- Mernissi, F.** (1991) *The Veil and the Male Elite. A Feminist Interpretation of Women's Rights in Islam*, Cambridge MA: Perseus.
- Mernissi, F.** (1992) *Islam and Democracy. Fear of the Modern World*, Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley.
- Mernissi, F.** (1993) *The Forgotten Queens of Islam*, Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Miera, F. and Sala Pala, V.** (2009) 'The Construction of Islam as a Public Issue in Western European Countries through the Prism of the Muhammad Cartoons Controversy', *Ethnicities*, 9(3): 383-408.
- Mignolo, W.** (2000) *Local Histories/Global Design: Coloniality, Border Thinking and Subaltern Knowledge*, Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Mignolo, W.** (2007) 'Epistemic Disobedience and the Decolonial Option. A Manifesto', <http://waltermignolo.com/publications/> (accessed July 2011).

- Mir-Hosseini, Z.** (1996a) 'Women and Politics in post-Khomeini Iran. Divorce, Veiling and Emerging Feminist Voices' in Afshar, H. (ed.) *Women and Politics in the Third World*, Routledge: London and New York, pp. 142-170.
- Mir-Hosseini, Z.** (1996b) 'Stretching the Limits: A Feminist Reading of the Shari'a in Post-Khomeini Iran' in Yamani, M. (ed.) *Feminism and Islam: Legal and Literary Perspectives*, London: Garnet.
- Mir-Hosseini, Z.** (2000) *Islam and Gender. The Religious Debate in Contemporary Iran*, London and New York: I. B. Tauris Publishers.
- Mir-Hosseini, Z.** (2002) 'Islamic Law and Feminism: The Story of a Relationship', *Yearbook of Islamic and Middle Eastern Law* 9: 34-42.
- Mir-Hosseini, Z.** (2006) 'Muslim Women's Quest for Equality: Between Islamic Law and Feminism', *Critical Inquiry*, 32(4): 629-645.
- Moaddel, M.** (1998) 'Religion and Women: Islamic Modernism versus Fundamentalism', *Journal for the Scientific Study of Religion*, 37(1), 108-130.
- Moallem, M.** (2005) *Between Warrior Brother and Veiled Sister. Islamic Fundamentalism and the Politics of Patriarchy in Iran*, Berkeley: Berkeley University Press.
- Moallem, M.** (2005) *Between Warrior Brother and Veiled Sister: Islamic Fundamentalism and the Politics of Patriarchy in Iran*, Berkeley: University of California Press.
- Modood, T.** (2005) *Multicultural Politics. Race, Ethnicity and Muslims in Britain*, Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press.
- Modood, T.** (2006) 'British Muslims and the Politics of Multiculturalism', in Modood, T., Triandafyllidou, A. and Zapata-Barrero, R. (eds.) *Multiculturalism, Muslims and Citizenship. A European Approach*, London and New York: Routledge, 37-56.
- Modood, T.** (2007) *Multiculturalism. A Civic Idea*, Cambridge: Polity.
- Modood, T.** (2008) 'A Basis for and Two Obstacles in the Way of A Multicultural Coalition', *The British Journal of Sociology*, 59(1): 47-52.
- Modood, T.** (2009) 'Muslims and the Politics of Difference' in Hopkins, P. and Gale, R. (eds.) *Muslims in Britain. Race, Place and Identities*, Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 193-209.
- Modood, T. and Ahmad, F.** (2007) 'British Muslim Perspectives on Multiculturalism', *Theory, Culture and Society*, 24(2): 187-213.

- Modood, T. and Kastoryano, R.** (2006) 'Secularism and the Accommodation of Muslims' in Modood, T., Triandafyllidou, A. and Zapata-Barrero, R. (eds.) *Multiculturalism, Muslims and Citizenship. A European Approach*, London and New York: Routledge, 162-178.
- Modood, T., Triandafyllidou, A. and Zapata-Barrero, R.** (2006) 'European Challenges to Multicultural Citizenship: Muslims, Secularism and Beyond' in Modood, T., Triandafyllidou, A. and Zapata-Barrero, R. (eds.) *Multiculturalism, Muslims and Citizenship. A European Approach*, London and New York: Routledge, 1-22.
- Moghadam, V.** (2006) 'Book Reviews: *Between Warrior Brother and Veiled Sister: Islamic Fundamentalism and the Politics of Patriarchy in Iran*, by Minoo Moallem, Berkeley: University of California Press, 2005. *Politics of Piety: The Islamic Revival and the Feminist Subject*, by Saba Mahmood, Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press, 2005', *Signs*, 32(1): 275-278.
- Moghadam, V. M.** (1993a) *Modernizing Women: Gender and Social Change in the Middle East*, Boulder, Colorado: Lynne Rienner.
- Moghadam, V. M.** (1993b) 'Rhetorics and Rights of Identity in Islamist Movements', *Journal of World History* 4(2): 243-66.
- Moghadam, V. M.** (2001) 'Feminism and Islamic Fundamentalism: A Secularist Approach', *Journal of Women's History*, 13(1): 42-45.
- Moghadam, V. M.** (2002) 'Islamic Feminism and Its Discontents: Toward a resolution of the Debate', *Signs*, 27(4), 1135-1171.
- Moghadam, V. M.** (2006) 'Between Warrior Brother and Veiled Sister: Islamic Fundamentalism and the Politics of Patriarchy in Iran; Politics of Piety: The Islamic Revival and the Feminist Subject, Book Reviews', *Signs*, 32(1): 275-278.
- Moghissi, H.** (2002) *Feminism and Islamic Fundamentalism. The Limits of Postmodern Analysis*, London and New York: Zed Books Ltd.
- Mohanty, C. T.** (1984) 'Under Western Eyes: Feminist Scholarship and Colonial Discourses', *boundary*, 2(12), 333-358.
- Mohanty, C. T.** (2002) "'Under Western Eyes" Revisited: Feminist Solidarity through Anticapitalist Struggles', *Signs*, 28(2), 499-535.
- Mojab, S.** (2001) 'Theorizing the Politics of "Islamic Feminism"', *Feminist Review*, 69, 124-146.
- Moruzzi, N.** (1994) 'A Problem with Headscarves. Contemporary Complexities of Political and Social Identity', *Political Theory*, 22: 653-672.

- Müller, M. G. and Özcan, E.** (2007) 'The Political Iconography of Muhammad Cartoons: Understanding Cultural Conflict and Political Action', *PSOnline* www.apsanet.org, 287-291.
- Mussallam, B.** (1979) 'Power and Knowledge', *MERIP Reports* 79: 19-26.
- Nandy, A.** (1983) *The Intimate Enemy: Loss and Recovery of Self under Colonialism*, Delhi: Oxford University Press.
- Narayan, U.** (2000) 'Undoing the "Package Picture" of Cultures', *Sings* 25(4): 1083-1086.
- Noor, F.** (2002) *New Voices of Islam*, Leiden, ISIM (International Institute for the Study of Islam).
- O'Neil, D.** (1999) 'Multicultural Liberals and the Rushdie Affair: A Critique of Kymlicka, Taylor, and Walzer', *The Review of Politics*, 61(2): 219-250.
- Okin, S. M.** (1998) 'Feminism and Multiculturalism: Some Tensions', *Ethics*, 108(4): 661-684.
- Okin, S. M.** (1999) 'Is Multiculturalism Bad for Women?' in Cohen, J., Howard, M. and Nussbaum, M. C. (eds.) *Is Multiculturalism Bad for Women?*, Princeton NJ: Princeton University Press, 7-25.
- Olesen, T.** (2007) 'The Porous Public and the Transnational Dialectic: The Muhammed Cartoons Conflict', *Acta Sociologica*, 50(3): 295-308.
- Osiander, A.** (2001) 'Sovereignty, International Relations, and the Westphalian Myth', *International Organization* 55(2): 251-288.
- Parekh, B.** (1997) 'Dilemmas of a Multicultural Theory of Citizenship', *Constellations* 4(1): 54-62.
- Parekh, B.** (2000) *Rethinking Multiculturalism. Cultural Diversity and Political Theory*, Basingstoke: Palgrave MacMillan.
- Parekh, B.** (2006) 'Europe, Liberalism and the 'Muslim Question' in Triantafyllidou, A., Modood, T. and Zapata-Barrero, R. (eds.) *Multiculturalism, Muslims and Citizenship. A European Approach*, London and New York: Routledge, 179-203.
- Parekh, B.** (2008) *A New Politics of Identity. Political Principles for an Independent World*, New York: Palgrave MacMillan.
- Pasha, M. K. and Murphy, C. N.** (2002) (eds.), *International Relations and the New Inequality*, Malden MA and Oxford: Blackwell Publishing Inc.
- Pateman, C.** (1989) *The Disorder of Women: Democracy, Feminism and Political Theory*, Cambridge: Polity.
- Pathak, P.** (2008) 'Making a Case for Multiculture. From the 'Politics of Piety' to the Politics of the Secular?', *Theory, Culture and Society*, 25(5): 123-141.
- Phillips, A.** (2007) *Multiculturalism without Culture*, Princeton: Princeton University Press.

- ‘Politics, Power and Ethics: A Discussion between Judith Butler and William Connolly’, *Theory and Event*, 24 (2000), http://muse.jhu.edu/journals/theory_and_event/v004/4.2butler.html
- Politt, K.** (1999) ‘Whose Culture?’ in Cohen, J., Howard, M. and Nussbaum, M. C. (eds.) *Is Multiculturalism Bad for Women?*, Princeton NJ: Princeton University Press, 27-30.
- Prakash, G.** (1990) ‘Writing Post-Orientalist Histories of the Third World: Perspectives from the Indian Historiography’ in *Comparative Studies in Society and History*, 32, pp. 383-408.
- Prakash, G.** (1992) ‘Postcolonial Criticism and Indian Historiography’, *Social Text*, 31-32: 8-19.
- Pulzer, P.** (2005) ‘Third thoughts on German and Austrian Antisemitism’, *Journal of Modern Jewish Studies*, 4(2): 137-178.
- Quijano, A.** (2007) ‘Coloniality and Modernity/Rationality’, *Cultural Studies*, 21(2-3): 168-178.
- Roald, A. S.** (1998) ‘Feminist Reinterpretation of Islamic Sources: Muslim Feminist Theology in Light of the Christian Tradition of Feminist Thought’ Ask, K. and Tjomsland, M. (eds.) *Women and Islamization: Contemporary Dimensions of Discourse on Gender Relations*, Oxford: Berg Publishers: 17-44.
- Rahman, F.** (2000) *Revival and Reform in Islam. A Study of Islamic Fundamentalism*, Oxford: Oneworld.
- Ramadan, T.** (2003) ‘Les musulmans et la mondialisation’, *Pouvoirs*, 104 : 1-13.
- Ramadan, T.** (2004a), *Ce que je crois*, Lausanne: Favre.
- Ramadan, T.** (2004b) *Western Muslims and the Future of Islam*, Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Ramadan, T.** (2006) ‘The Danish Cartoons, Free Speech and Civic Responsibility’, *NPQ*, 17-18.
- Ramadan, T.** (2009) *Radical Reform. Islamic Ethics and Liberation*, Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- ‘Religion, Law and the Politics of Human Rights. Talal Asad and Abdullahi An’Naim’ September 29, 2009, Berkeley Centre for Religion, Peace and World Affairs, Georgetown University, available on <http://blogs.ssrc.org/tif/wp-content/uploads/2009/11/Talal-Asad-and-Abdullahi-An-Naim-in-conversation.pdf>
- Rinaldo, R.** (2006) “Feminism in Uncertain Times: Islam, Democratization, and Women Activists in Indonesia.” Paper presented at the 8th Annual Conference on Globalization held at the University of Chicago on April 11, 2006, available on the conference website as a PDF <http://cas.uchicago.edu/workshops/scg/conference/2006/index.html>
- Rodinson, M.** (2007/1973) *Islam and Capitalism*, London, San Francisco and Beirut: Saqi

- Roseneil, S.** (1995) 'The Coming of Age of Feminist Sociology. Some Issues of Practice and Theory for the Next Twenty Years', *The British Journal of Sociology*, 46(2): 191-205.
- Rotzokos, N.** (2006) 'Multiculturalist Interpretations of the Ottoman Past: Towards a Postmodern Romanticism', *O Politis*, 144: 25-28 [in Greek Ροτζώκος, Ν. «Πολυπολιτισμικές αναγνώσεις του οθωμανικού παρελθόντος: προς ένα μεταμοντέρνο ρομαντισμό», *Ο Πολίτης*].
- Roussillon, A.** (2005) *La pensée islamique contemporaine. Acteurs et enjeux*, Paris: Téraèdre.
- Roy, O.** (1994) *The Failure of Political Islam*, London: I.B. Tauris.
- Roy, O.** (1999) 'Le post-islamisme?', *Revue du monde musulman et de la Méditerranée*, 85(1): 11-30.
- Roy, O.** (2002) *Globalised Islam: The Search of a New Ummah*, London: Hurst.
- Roy, O.** (2011) 'Afterword. Islam in Europe: An Ordinary Religion like Any Other' in Haenni, P. and Lathion, S., (eds.) *The Swiss Minaret Ban: Islam in Question*, Religioscope: 90-95 (available on <http://www.minaret.li/resources/ReligioscopeSwissMinaretBan.pdf>)
- Safi, O.** (2003) (ed.) *Progressive Muslims. On Justice, Gender and Pluralism*, Oxford: Oneworld.
- Sahgal, G. and Yuval-Davis, N.** (1992) 'Introduction: Fundamentalism, Multiculturalism and Women in Britain' in Sahgal, G. and Yuval-Davis, N. (eds.) *Refusing Holy Orders. Women and Fundamentalism in Britain*, London: Virago Press.
- Sahlins, M.** (1993) 'Goodbye to the Tristes Tropes: Ethnography in the Context of Modern World History', *Journal of Modern History*, 65(1): 1-25.
- Said, E.** (1983) *The World, The Text and The Critic*, Cambridge, Massachusetts: Harvard University Press.
- Said, E.** (1985) 'Orientalism Reconsidered', *Cultural Critique*, 1: 89-107.
- Said, E.** (1995) *The Politics of Dispossession. The Struggle for Palestinian Self-Determination 1969-1994*, New York: Vintage.
- Said, E.** (1996) *Peace and Its Discontents. Essays on Palestine in the Middle East Peace Process*, New York: Vintage.
- Said, E.** (2002) *Power, Politics and Culture: Interviews with Edward Said* (ed. Gauri Viswanathan), New York: Vintage.
- Said, E.** (2003 [1978]) *Orientalism*, London and New York: Penguin Books.
- Said, E.** (2004) *Humanism and Democratic Criticism*, New York: Columbia University Press.
- Saliba, T.** (2002) 'Introduction' in Saliba, T., Allen. C. and Howard, J. (eds.) *Gender, Politics, Islam*, Chicago: University of Chicago Press: 1-14.

- Salvadori, M. L.** (2008) *Progress. Can We Do Without it?*, London and New York: Zed Books.
- Sayyid, S.** (2000) 'Beyond Westphalia: Nations and Diasporas – The Case of the Muslim *Umma*' in Hesse, B. (ed.) *Un/Settled Multiculturalisms: Diasporas, Entanglements, 'Transruptions'*, London and New York: Zed Books, 34-50.
- Sayyid, B. S.** (2003 [1997]) *A Fundamental Fear. Eurocentrism and the Emergence of Islamism*, London: Zed Books Ltd.
- Sayyid, S.** (2005) 'Mirror, Mirror: Western Democrats, Oriental Despots?', *Ethnicities*, 5(1): 30-50.
- Sayyid, S.** (2006) 'Islam and Knowledge', *Theory, Culture and Society*, 23 (2-3): 177-179.
- Sayyid, S.** (2009) 'Contemporary Politics of Secularism' in Brahm Levey, G. and Modood, T. (eds.) *Secularism, Religion and Multicultural Citizenship*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Schiffer, S. and Wagner C.** (2011) 'Anti-Semitism and Islamophobia – new enemies, old patterns', *Race & Class*, 52(3): 77–84.
- Schlesinger, A. M.** (1991) *The Disuniting of America: Reflection on a Multicultural Society*, USA: Whittle Direct Books.
- Schor, N.** (1995) 'French Feminism is a Universalism' in Schor, N. *Bad Objects. Essays Popular and Unpopular*, Durham: Duke University Press: 3-27.
- Scott, D.** (2006) 'The Tragic Sensibility of Talal Asad' in Scott, D. and Hirschkind C. (eds.) *Powers of the Secular Modern. Talal Asad and His Interlocutors*, Stanford CA: Stanford University Press: 134-153.
- Scott, J. W.** (1992) 'Multiculturalism and the Politics of Identity', *October*, 61: 12-19.
- Scott, J. W.** (2005) 'Symptomatic Politics. The Banning of Islamic Head Scarves in French Public Schools', *French Politics, Culture and Society*, 23(3): 106-127.
- Semati, M.** (2010) 'Islamophobia, Culture and Race in the Age of Empire', *Cultural Studies*, 24(2): 256-275.
- Seth, S.** (2011) 'Postcolonial Theory and the Critique of Postcolonial Relations', *Millennium-Journal of International Studies* 40(1): 167-183.
- Shachar, A.** (2001) *Multicultural Jurisdictions: Cultural Differences and Women's Rights*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Shaikh, S.** (1997) 'Exegetical Violence: Nushuz in Qur'anic Gender Ideology', *Journal for Islamic Studies*, 17: 49-73.
- Sharabi, H.** (1970) *Arab Intellectuals and the West. The Formative Years: 1875-1914*, Baltimore and London: The John Hopkins University Press.

- Shani, G.** (2002) 'A Revolt against the West': Politicized Religion and the International Order-A Comparison of the Islamic Umma and the Sikh Qaum' *Ritsumeikan Annual Review of International Studies*, The International Studies Association of Ritsumeikan University, vol. 1: 15-31.
- Shani, G.** (2007) "Provincializing" Critical Theory: Islam, Sikhism and International Relations Theory', *Cambridge Review of International Affairs* 20(3): 417-433.
- Shani, G.** (2008) 'Toward a Post-Western IR: The *Umma*, *Khalsa Panth*, and Critical International Relations Theory', *International Studies Review* 10: 722-734.
- Shilliam, R.** (2011) (ed.) *International Relations and Non-Western Thought: Imperialism, Colonialism and Investigations of Global Modernity*, Oxon and New York: Routledge.
- Simmons, G. Z.** (2003) 'Are We up to the Challenge? The Need for a Radical Re-ordering of the Islamic Discourse on Women' Safi, O. (ed.) *Progressive Muslims: On Justice, Gender, and Pluralism*, Oxford: Oneworld: 235-148.
- Shaheed, F.** (1995) 'Networking for Change: The Role of Women's Groups in Initiating Dialogue on Women's Issues' in Afkhami, M. (ed.) *Faith and Freedom: Women's Human Rights in the Muslim World*, London and New York: I.B. Tauris.
- Shryock, A.** (2010) (ed.) *Islamophobia/Islamophilia. Beyond the Politics of Enemy and Friend, Bloomington and Indianapolis: Indiana University Press.*
- Shryock, A.** (2010) 'Islam as an Object of Fear and Affection' in Shryock, A. (ed.) *Islamophobia/Islamophilia. Beyond the Politics of Enemy and Friend*, Bloomington: Indiana University Press: 1-25.
- Sivanandan, A.** (1990) *Communities of Resistance: Writings on Black Struggles for Socialism, London: Verso.*
- Smith, J.** (1979) 'Women in Islam: Equity, Equality and the Search for the Natural Order', *Journal of the American Academy of Religion*, 47(4), 517-537.
- Soroush, A.** (2000) *Reason, Freedom and Democracy in Islam. The Essential Writings of Abdolkarim Soroush*, Oxford and New York: Oxford University Press.
- Spencer, M.** (1994) 'Multiculturalism, "Political Correctness" and the Politics of Identity', *Sociological Forum*, 9(4): 447-567.
- Spinner-Halev, J.** (2000) *Surviving Diversity: Religion and Democratic Citizenship*, Baltimore: The John Hopkins University Press.

- Spinner-Halev, J.** (2001) 'Feminism, Multiculturalism Oppression, and the State', *Ethics*, 112(1): 84-113.
- Spivak, G. C.** (1988) 'Can the Subaltern Speak?' in Nelson, C. and Grossberg, L. (eds.) *Marxism and the Interpretation of Culture*, Urbana: University of Illinois Press, 66-111.
- Spivak, G. C.** (1988b) *In Other Worlds. Essays in Cultural Politics*, New York and London: Routledge.
- Spivak, G. C.** (1990) 'Poststructuralism, Marginality, Postcoloniality and Value' in Collier, P. and Geyer-Ryan, H. (eds.) *Literary Theory Today*, New York: Cornell University Press, 198-222.
- Steinmetz, G.** (2006) 'Decolonizing German Theory: An Introduction', *Postcolonial Studies*, 9(1): 3-13.
- Sternhell, Z.** (2010) *The Anti-Enlightenment Tradition*, New Haven and London: Harvard University Press.
- Strauss, L.** (1961) 'Relativism', in Schoeck, H. and Wiggins, J. W. (eds.) *Relativism and the Study of Man*, Princeton: D. Van Nostrand, 135-157.
- Tadjbakhsh, S.** (1998) 'Between Lenin and Allah: Women and Ideology in Tajikistan' in Herbert L. Bodman, H. L. and Tohidi, N. (eds.) *Women in Muslim societies: Diversity within Unity*, Boulder, Colorado: Lynne Rienner Publishers, 163-185.
- Takaki, R.** (1993) 'Multiculturalism: Battleground or Meeting Ground?', *Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 530: 109-121.
- Tapper, R.** (1995) 'Islamic Anthropology and the "Anthropology of Islam"', *Anthropological Quarterly*, 68(3), 185-193.
- Taylor, C.** (1994) 'The Politics of Recognition' in Gutmann, A. (ed.), *Multiculturalism and 'The Politics of Recognition'*, Princeton: Princeton University Press, 25-73.
- Taylor, C.** (2007) *A Secular Age*, Cambridge MA and London: Belknap Press of Harvard University Press.
- Terray, E.** (2004) 'La question du voile: une hystérie politique' in Nordmann, C. (dir.) *Le foulard islamique en questions*, Paris: éditions Amsterdam, 103-117.
- Terray, E.** (2004) 'La question du voile: une hystérie politique' in Nordmann, C. (dir.) *Le foulard islamique en questions*, Paris: éditions Amsterdam, 103-117.
- Teschke, B.** (2003) *The Myth of 1648: Class, Geopolitics, and the Making of Modern International Relations*, London: Verso.

- Tickner, A. B. and Wæver, O.** (2009) (eds.) *International Relations Scholarship around the World*, Oxon and New York: Routledge.
- Turner, B.** (1974b) *Weber and Islam. A Critical Study*, London and Boston: Routledge and Kegan Paul.
- Turner, B.** (1978) *Marx and the End of Orientalism*, London, Boston and Sydney: George Allen and Unwin.
- Turner, B.** (1994) *Orientalism, Postmodernism and Globalism*, Routledge: London and New York.
- Tyrer, D. and Sayyid, S.** (2012) 'Governing Ghosts: Race, Incorporeality and Difference in post-Political Times', *Current Sociology*, 60(3) 353–367.
- Vasilaki, E. R.** (2003) 'Entre tradition et modernité: Idéologie, femmes, féminité sous le régime de Métaxas en Grèce (1936-1941)', unpublished PhD thesis, Ecole des Hautes Etudes en Sciences Sociales, Paris.
- Vasilaki, E. R.** (2008) 'Gender, Memory and Politics: Women in the Fascist Years', *Historica*, 26(48): 79-102 [in Greek].
- Vasilaki, R.** (2011) 'Seeing like a PIG: the Crisis in Greece from a Different Perspective', *Greek Left Review*, <http://greekleftreview.wordpress.com/2011/08/12/london-calling-riots-and-the-politics-of-deprivation/>
- Vasilaki, R.** (2012) 'Provincialising IR? Deadlocks and Prospects in Post-Western IR Theory', *Millennium-Journal of International Studies*, 41(1): 3-22.
- Vergès, F.** (2001) 'Vertigo and Emancipation, Creole Cosmopolitanism and Cultural Policies', *Theory, Culture and Society* 18(2–3): 169–83.
- Volkov, S.** (2006) *Germans, Jews, and Antisemites: Trials in Emancipation*, Cambridge and New York: Cambridge University Press
- Volpp, L.** (2001) 'Feminism versus Multiculturalism', *Columbia Law Review*, 101: 1181-1218.
- Wadud, A.** (1999) *Qur'an and Woman: Rereading the Sacred Text from a Woman's Perspective*, New York, NY: Oxford University Press.
- Wadud, A.** (2004) 'Quran, Gender and Interpretive Possibilities', *Hawwa*, 2(3): 316-336.
- Waggoner, M.** (2005) 'Irony, Embodiment, and the "Critical Attitude": Engaging Saba Mahmood's Critique of Secular Morality', *Culture and Religion*, 6(2): 237-261.
- Walker, P. and Taylor, M.** (2011), 'Far-Right on the Rise in Europe, Says Report', *The Guardian*, 6 November 2011, <http://www.guardian.co.uk/world/2011/nov/06/far-right-rise-europe-report>

- Wallerstein I.** (1980) *The Modern World System II. Mercantilism and the Consolidation of the European World-Economy, 1600-1750*, Burlington, California and London: Academic Press.
- Wallerstein, I.** (1981/1974) *The Modern World System I. Capitalist Agriculture and the Origins of the European World-Economy in the Sixteenth Century*, Burlington, California and London: Academic Press.
- Wallerstein, I.** (1989) *The Modern World System II. The second era of great expansion of the capitalist world-economy, 1730-1840s*, Burlington, California and London: Academic Press.
- Walzer, M.** (1980) 'Pluralism: A Political Perspective' in Thernstorm, S. (ed.) *Encyclopaedia of American Ethnic Groups*, Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 781-787.
- Walzer, M.** (1983) *Spheres of Justice. A Defence of Pluralism and Equality*, Oxford: Martin Robinson.
- Walzer, M.** (1989) 'The Sins of Salman', *The New Republic*, 10 April 1989: 13-15.
- Walzer, M.** (1994) 'Comment' in Gutmann, A. (ed.), *Multiculturalism and 'The Politics of Recognition'*, Princeton: Princeton University Press, 99-103.
- Walzer, M.** (1997) *On Toleration*, New Haven: Yale University Press.
- Wax, M. L.** (1993) 'How Culture Misreads Multiculturalism', *Anthropology and Education Quarterly*, 24(2): 99-115.
- Waylen, G.** (1996) 'Analysing Women in the Politics of the Third World' in Afshar, H. (ed.) *Women and Politics in the Third World*, Routledge: London and New York, pp. 7-24.
- Weaver, S.** (2010) 'Liquid Racism and the Danish Prophet Muhammad Cartoons', *Current Sociology*, 58(5): 675-692.
- West, C.** (1991) *Ethical Dimensions of Marxist Thought*, MA: Monthly Review Press.
- West, C. and Brown, B.** (1993) 'Beyond Eurocentrism and Multiculturalism', *Modern Philology*, 90: S142-S166.
- Winder, B.** (1981) 'Books Reviews: Orientalism', *Middle East Journal*, 35(4): 615-619.
- Winter, B.** (2001) 'Fundamental Misunderstandings: Issues in Feminist Approaches to Islamism', *Journal of Women's History*, 13(1): 9-41.
- Winter, B.** (2006) 'Feminists aboard the Titanic: Feminists and the Debate over the Hijab in France', *Feminist Studies*, 32(2): 279-298.
- Ye'or, B.** (2005) *Eurabia: The Euro-Arab Axis*, Madison, Teaneck: Fairleigh Dickinson University Press.

- Yilmaz, F.** (2012) 'Right-wing Hegemony and Immigration: How the Populist Far-right Achieved Hegemony through the Immigration Debate in Europe', *Current Sociology*, 60(3) 368-381.
- Young, I. M.** (1990) *Justice and the Politics of Difference*, Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Young, I. M.** (1997) 'Unruly Categories: A Critique of Nancy Fraser's Dual Systems Theory', *New Left Review* 1/222, March-April: 147-160.
- Yuval-Davis, N.** (1997) *Gender and Nation*, London: Sage.
- Yuval-Davis, N.** (2011) *The politics of Belonging. Intersectional Contestations*, London: Sage.
- Zeghal, M.** (2008) 'Réformismes, Islamismes et Libéralismes religieux', *Revue du monde musulman et de la Méditerranée*, 123: 17-34.
- Zemni, S.** (2011) 'The Shaping of Islam and Islamophobia in Belgium', *Race & Class*, 53(1): 28-44.
- Zizek, S.** (1997) 'Multiculturalism, Or the Cultural Logic of Multinational Capitalism', *New Left Review* 1/225 (September-October 1997): 28-51.
- Zizek, S.** (2002) *Welcome to the Desert of the Real*, London and New York: Verso.
- Zizek, S.** (2009a) *First as a Tragedy Then as a Farce*, London and New York: Verso.
- Zizek, S.** (2009b) *Violence*, London: Profile Books.